

Cost Benefit Analysis

WP3: Assessment of solutions & development of the final inventory of *Best Practices*
Deliverable 3.2

Authors:

Luciano Pagano, Daniele Vergamini, Daniele Antichi, Gabriele Lorenzo Tramacere

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Co - Authors	Luciano Pagano, Daniele Antichi, Gabriele Lorenzo Tramacere
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TABLE 1: DOCUMENT INFORMATION

¹ PU = public | PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services) | RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services) | CO= Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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Abbreviations

CBA	COST BENEFIT ANALYSIS	PA	PRECISION AGRICULTURE
NAP	NATIONAL ACTION PLAN	OG	OPERATIONAL GROUP
WP	WORK PACKAGE	GGE	GREENHOUSE GAS EMISSIONS
NNO	NATIONAL NETWORK OPERATOR	KPI	KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS
WS	WORKSHOP	NPV	NET PRESENT VALUE
LCA	LIFE CYCLE ANALYSIS	CBR	COST BENEFIT RATIO

TABLE 3: ABBREVIATIONS

Participants

Participants		Contact
Agricultural University of Athens (AUA) Greece		Prof. Spyros Fountas sfountas@aual.gr
University of Santiago de Compostela (USC) Spain		MOSQUERA LOSADA MARIA ROSA mrosa.mosquera.losada@usc.es
University of Pisa (UNIPi) Italy		Daniele Antichi daniele.antichi@unipi.it
Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies (LLU) Latvia		Jānis Jaško janis.jasko@llu.lv
RSK ADAS LTD (ADAS) UK		Lynn Tatnell Lynn.Tatnell@adas.co.uk
AGROVÅST Livsmedel AB (AGROVAST) Sweden		Thomas Börjesson thomas.borjesson@agrovast.se
Institut Français de la Vigne et du Vin (IFV) France		Eirios Hugo, Camille Guilbert eirios.hugo@vignevin.com camille.guilbert@vignevin.com
Farmers Parliament (ZSA) Latvia		Inga Berzina inga@zemniekusaeima.lv
Organic Research Centre (ORC) UK		Matt Smee Matt.s@organicresearchcentre.com
AGROMET P.C. (AGROMET) Greece		Aris Zamidis azamidis@tractorgps.gr

TABLE 4: PARTICIPANTS

Document summary

This document summarizes the assessment phase of WP3 within the Oper8 project, focusing on evaluating non-chemical weed control solutions identified during WP2. The previous evaluation process involved national and European workshops, where stakeholders, including farmers, researchers, and industry experts, assessed the solutions based on a comprehensive set of criteria encompassing efficacy, socio-economic feasibility, and environmental impacts. At the national level, workshops were held across all seven participating countries, engaging local stakeholders to evaluate solutions tailored to their specific crops and contexts. Complementing this, a European-level workshop brought together Oper8 participants and an expert panel to foster cross-country collaboration, exchange insights, and assess solutions in a broader context.

The European workshop, organized into thematic groups covering arable crops, field vegetable crops, and perennial crops/vineyards, facilitated in-depth discussions and consensus on the most promising practices. These discussions refined the assessment criteria and improved the overall evaluation process, leading to the identification of top-performing solutions in each country. These solutions are now presented in this Oper8 Deliverable through the cost-benefit analysis (CBA) that aim to quantify their economic viability while considering their environmental and social benefits.

The outcomes of this analysis will inform the next steps of the project, including a second round of assessments to further validate solutions based on readiness and acceptability criteria. This will be followed by the development of technical audio-visual materials in WP4 to support the dissemination and transfer of relevant solutions, ensuring their broader adoption across European agricultural systems. The assessment phase provides a structured foundation for identifying innovative and sustainable weed control practices with the potential to enhance agricultural resilience and sustainability.

Executive summary

The Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) conducted in Task 3.2 of the Oper8 project builds on the outcomes of Task 3.1, where promising non-chemical weed control solutions were identified through extensive stakeholder engagement. The primary aim of Task 3.2 is to evaluate these solutions' economic viability, environmental sustainability, and social impacts to determine their potential for adoption and scalability within European agricultural systems. The analysis balances private benefits, such as increased crop yields and reduced chemical inputs, with public benefits like improved biodiversity, soil health, and water quality, offering a comprehensive perspective on their short-term and long-term outcomes. Using a systematic methodology, the process began by defining each project's scope, quantifying physical impacts, and translating these impacts into monetary terms through market prices, shadow pricing, and approximations where necessary. A 4% discount rate was applied to convert future costs and benefits into present values, with sensitivity analyses at 2% and 6% discount rates to account for uncertainties. Data collection relied on a shared survey capturing economic, social, and environmental dimensions, administered to innovators and early adopters in seven countries, alongside collaborative workflow mapping with farmers to document operational changes. Practices were evaluated over a 20-year timeframe, structured into phases of setup, transition, and consolidation, ensuring that both immediate and long-term impacts were captured. Where direct quantitative data were unavailable, expert judgments, literature reviews, and workshop insights were integrated to enrich the analysis. The inclusion of transaction costs, opportunity costs, and environmental indicators, such as soil erosion and CO₂ emissions, ensured a holistic assessment of each practice. To test result robustness, sensitivity analysis was performed by adjusting key parameters like discount rates, labour costs, and yield variations, providing a reliable projection of outcomes under different conditions. This comprehensive approach highlights the potential of alternative weed control methods to deliver sustainable, economically viable, and socially beneficial outcomes, offering practical insights to guide decision-making for farmers, policymakers, and stakeholders in European agriculture.

The analysis categorized weed control techniques into five main clusters: mechanical weeding, cover crops, mulching, precision farming, and ecological management. Results highlighted varying levels of implementation scale, financial performance, and environmental benefits:

- Mechanical Weeding emerged as a prominent solution across several countries, demonstrating its adaptability to both small-scale vineyards and large-scale arable systems. For instance, in the UK1 case, mechanical weeding covered 200 hectares, representing 18.1% of the total UAA. Similarly, Sweden's SW1 case showcased advanced GPS-guided weeding on 500 hectares (45.3%), reflecting technological innovation in weed management.
- Precision Farming solutions, such as targeted spraying and GPS-guided interventions, proved particularly effective in countries like Italy (IT3) and Sweden (SW3), where they delivered substantial CO₂ reductions and economic benefits, albeit with high initial costs.
- Cover Crops were observed to provide moderate financial returns while enhancing soil health, as demonstrated in cases like FR2 (France) and GR1 (Greece).
- Mulching practices, such as the use of wood chips and living mulches, offered controlled cost structures and promising environmental benefits, with notable success in Spain's SP2 case and the UK's UK2 case.
- Ecological Management approaches, including false seedbeds and agroforestry methods, highlighted their potential in fostering long-term sustainability, particularly in Greece (GR2) and Spain (SP3).

A detailed Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) revealed significant variability across solutions:

- High economic returns were achieved in cases like GR3 (Greece), with a benefit of €20,370 per hectare, indicating highly effective practices. Conversely, cases like LV2 (Latvia) reported low financial benefits at €595 per hectare, underscoring the importance of context-specific adoption strategies.
- Environmental benefits, particularly CO₂ reductions, were closely linked to high-performing cases. For instance, GR3 combined substantial financial returns with exceptional CO₂ reduction, whereas other cases, like SP3 and LV2, demonstrated minimal environmental gains.
- The breakdown of CAPEX (capital costs), OPEX (operational costs), and labour costs further illustrated the financial dynamics of each practice. Countries such as Sweden (SW1) and Italy (IT3) showed that higher upfront investments in precision technologies yielded significant long-term returns, while labour-intensive practices, such as mechanical weeding in UK1, justified costs through enhanced productivity.

The study underscored that scalability is a critical factor influencing the success of these solutions. Large-scale applications, such as mechanical weeding in the UK and Sweden, provided robust evidence for the practicality and economic feasibility of such methods in commercial agriculture. Smaller-scale or localized applications, such as mulching in vineyards, demonstrated valuable insights into customizing techniques to address specific ecological and operational conditions.

The results from this assessment will feed into a second round of workshops. These workshops will focus on a refined subset of solutions based on readiness and acceptability criteria. The outcomes will subsequently inform WP4, which involves the development of audio-visual materials to disseminate findings and promote adoption among stakeholders.

The WP3 findings provide critical insights into the financial, environmental, and operational impacts of alternative weed control solutions. While practices like precision farming and mechanical weeding emerged as key drivers of sustainability and profitability, variability in economic outcomes highlights the need for tailored strategies. Moving forward, these results will serve as a foundation for policy development, stakeholder engagement, and further advancements in sustainable agricultural practices.

Document content

Part. 1 Context and objective of Task 3.2

1.1 Task 3.2 context

Task 3.2 in the Oper8 project focuses on conducting a cost-benefit analysis of selected solutions for non-chemical weed control, identified through a collaborative process involving various stakeholders in Task 3.1. The main objective is to assess the economic viability and broader impacts of these solutions, considering both short-term and long-term perspectives, as well as accounting for non-economic factors such as social and environmental benefits or costs. This task is critical for understanding the potential for wider adoption of promising alternative weed control methods within the agricultural sector, aligning with the project's goals of enhancing sustainability and knowledge exchange in European agriculture.

Cost-benefit analysis (CBA) is a systematic approach used to evaluate the economic strengths and weaknesses of a decision, policy, or project by quantifying in monetary terms its benefits and costs. This method helps decision-makers determine the best course of action by comparing the total expected costs against the total expected benefits of one or more alternatives.

In the context of Task 3.2, CBA is a tool to evaluate the economic worth of non-chemical weed control methods by comparing their costs and benefits. It can be used for decision-making by stakeholders, including farmers, policy-makers, and researchers, aiming to identify the most effective and sustainable weed control solutions. The targets are the selected weed control methods, with outcomes including their economic viability, environmental impact, and social acceptability. Key strengths of CBA include its comprehensive approach and ability to inform decision-making. Weaknesses involve challenges in quantifying non-economic factors and potential biases in value estimation.

In the context of a change in agricultural management for weed control, the analysis would look at various aspects:

- **Private Benefits and Costs:** These are the direct benefits and costs experienced by the individual or organization implementing the change in weed control management. For example, a farmer using a new weed control technology might experience private benefits such as increased crop yields, reduced labour costs, and savings on chemical inputs. The private costs might include the initial investment in the new technology, ongoing maintenance costs, and any potential decrease in soil health due to the new weed control method.
- **Public Benefits and Costs:** These are the broader impacts of the weed control change on society and the environment, which may not be directly accounted for by the private entity making the decision. Public benefits could include improved water quality due to reduced runoff of harmful chemicals, enhanced biodiversity if the new weed control method is less harmful to non-target species, and increased food security if the change leads to more stable crop production. Public costs might involve negative environmental impacts such as the potential for developing herbicide-resistant weed strains, loss of habitat for certain wildlife species, and the long-term degradation of soil health.

A thorough cost-benefit analysis in this context would require gathering data on all these aspects, quantifying them in monetary terms where possible, and then comparing the aggregated benefits against the aggregated costs. The analysis might also include a sensitivity analysis to account for uncertainties and variations in key assumptions. The goal would be to provide a clear picture of whether the benefits of the new weed control management strategy outweigh its costs, from both a private and public perspective, to guide decision-making.

1.2 Objectives of the Cost-Benefit Analysis

The overarching goal of this analysis is to provide a comprehensive understanding of the feasibility and impact of innovative weed control practices within the scope of the Oper8 project. This approach aims to facilitate informed decision-making for sustainable agricultural development.

Specific Objectives of Task 3.2 are:

1. **Mapping of Weed Control Methods:** Identify and categorize various non-chemical weed control strategies being used or proposed across different regions and agricultural systems. This specific objective aims to create a detailed framework of existing techniques, facilitating understanding of their applications and regional variations.
2. **Attributes Analysis:** Examine the specific features of each weed control method, such as effectiveness, cost, applicability, and any additional services or requirements they entail. The analysis will focus on how these attributes influence the agricultural process and economics, providing a basis for more in-depth evaluations.
3. **Sustainability Assessment:** Assess the sustainability of each weed control method in terms of environmental, social, and economic pillars. This includes analysing direct impacts, such as farmer perceptions and immediate effects on land use, as well as indirect impacts, like adherence to sustainability standards and long-term environmental health.
4. **Future Drivers and Adaptability:** Provide additional data to investigate what might drive the adoption of these weed control methods in the future, including environmental challenges, market dynamics, and policy changes. Furthermore, explore how adaptable these methods are to evolving conditions, ensuring they are resilient and flexible in the face of future changes.

Part. 2 Cost Benefit Analysis - guidelines and rationale

2.1 What is Cost-Benefit analysis?

Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) is Economic evaluation technique used to measure whether the benefits of a particular action outweigh the costs from a societal perspective. This involves considering both government policy decisions and investment projects. CBA involves tallying up the benefits and costs associated with a project or policy to assess its overall impact on society. If benefits exceed costs, the action is considered to improve societal welfare; otherwise, it may be detrimental.

CBA introduces several pivotal questions for practitioners to explore, including: How is 'society' precisely defined within the framework of these analyses? Furthermore, what factors are considered as 'benefits' and 'costs' in the evaluation of a project or policy? It also prompts inquiry into the methods for assigning monetary values to these considerations, as well as how to effectively address projects with costs that span into the distant future. Lastly, it raises the essential question of what criteria should be used to ascertain whether the societal benefits surpass the associated costs.

2.2 CBA Methodology

CBA involves several analytical steps.

1. Project/policy definition

It involves detailing the project, identifying the affected population, and determining the analysis timeframe.

Example for a farm implementing new green weed management practices

This analysis evaluates the introduction of eco-friendly weed control methods on a farm, focusing on the economic, environmental, and social impacts. The practices include the use of natural herbicides, cover crops, and mechanical weeding instead of chemical herbicides. The primary concern is the well-being of the farm's community and the local ecosystem. The assessment considers immediate costs, such as the purchase of new equipment and potential yield variations, against long-term benefits like improved soil health, reduced chemical runoff, and enhanced biodiversity. The analysis spans over a decade, reflecting the time needed to observe significant environmental and economic outcomes. The relevant population includes the farm's operators, residents, and downstream ecosystems potentially affected by runoff. Special attention is given to the sustainability and resilience of the farm's operations in the face of changing climatic conditions, with a focus on benefits and costs both to the immediate farm community and the broader ecological system.

2. Identification of physical Impacts of the Policy/project

The next of CBA involves precisely measuring the specific impacts of policy/project practices in quantifiable terms. After identifying and quantifying the physical impacts of a project or policy, the next critical step in CBA is to discern which of these impacts are pertinent to the analysis. This determination hinges on whether the impacts influence the quantity or quality of resources, or their price, in ways that can be directly linked to the well-being of the people affected by the project or policy. The scope of relevant impacts is broad, encompassing not just those with explicit market values but also changes in non-market values that affect people's quality of life or utility.

For instance, when applying green weed management strategies on a farm, this stage requires the enumeration of outcomes such as the hours of labour dedicated to sustainable weeding methods, the decrease in harmful chemical use, the extent of land engaged in these practices, and the potential alterations in crop yields. Additionally, while quantifying environmental advantages such as soil quality improvement and biodiversity enhancement, one must navigate the uncertainties inherent in predicting

the precise effects on the ecosystem, like the direct impact on local fauna or the implications for water purity.

So, relevant impacts could include the direct costs of labour and materials for implementing these practices and the potential for reduced agricultural yield in the short term. However, benefits such as improved soil health, reduced chemical runoff, enhanced local biodiversity, and possibly even long-term yield improvements due to healthier ecosystems also play a crucial role. These benefits, while not always easy to quantify in market terms, can significantly impact people's utility by contributing to cleaner water, healthier food, and a more resilient local environment. Therefore, the analysis must consider both market-valued impacts, like the cost savings from reduced chemical use, and non-market value changes, such as the health benefits to the community from reduced pesticide exposure. By incorporating these broader utility impacts into the CBA, decision-makers can develop a more comprehensive understanding of the project's or policy's overall effects on societal well-being.

3. Valuing impacts

CBA uniquely quantifies all relevant impacts of a project or policy in monetary terms, enabling their aggregation for comprehensive assessment. This monetary valuation is based on the principle of evaluating impacts according to their marginal social cost or benefit, considering the broader economy rather than just the financial implications for individual firms or shareholders. Marginal social benefits and costs often derive from market prices, which reflect the consumer value of products and the production costs, assuming these impacts don't significantly alter market dynamics. However, market mechanisms sometimes fail to account for externalities, such as environmental pollution, or for goods without a market, like biodiversity or clean water, leading to "market failures." In these instances, traditional market prices don't adequately capture the social costs or benefits. CBA addresses these gaps by employing alternative valuation methods to quantify non-market values, offering a more holistic evaluation of a project's impact on societal welfare. The approach aims to include both direct economic effects and broader environmental or social outcomes in the analysis, ensuring a comprehensive assessment of a project's net contribution to societal well-being.

4. Discounting of Cost and Benefit Flows

In CBA, converting all relevant cost and benefit flows into present value (PV) terms is crucial due to the time value of money or time preference. This concept reflects the natural preference for receiving benefits sooner rather than later and deferring costs as far into the future as possible. For instance, £100 received today is more valuable than the same amount received in a year because, if received today, it could be invested to yield a higher amount in the future due to interest accrual. This principle applies universally, not only to financial sums but also to benefits and costs of any kind, emphasizing that sooner benefits are more appreciated and future costs less burdensome.

Discounting is the process used to account for this time effect, making costs and benefits comparable across different time periods. It involves applying a discount rate, often assumed to be equivalent to the interest rate i , to future costs and benefits to calculate their present value. The formula for calculating PV value of a cost or benefit (X) received at time t incorporates a discount factor, which diminishes the value of future costs and benefits, highlighting a greater preference for current over future value.

$$PV(X_t) = X_t[(1 + i)^{-t}]$$

This process allows for the aggregation of costs and benefits over the life of a project in a way that fairly accounts for the time value of money, ensuring that a project's net impact is evaluated in terms of its present value to society.

5. Applying Net Present Value

The core objective of CBA is to facilitate the selection of projects and policies that maximize resource efficiency. This is determined using the Net Present Value (NPV) criterion, which compares the present value of a project's benefits to its costs.

$$NPV = \sum B_t (1 + i)^{-t} - \sum C_t (1 + i)^{-t}$$

If the total of discounted benefits ($\sum B_t (1 + i)^{-t}$) surpasses the total of discounted costs ($\sum C_t (1 + i)^{-t}$), the project is considered to offer an efficient reallocation of resources, assuming the accuracy of the CBA data. The NPV formula, where t represents the time from the project's start to its conclusion, and i is the discount rate, helps ascertain whether a project increases social welfare—if NPV is greater than zero, the project is deemed beneficial.

While NPV is a widely used measure for assessing projects, alternatives like the Internal Rate of Return (IRR) and the Benefit-Cost Ratio offer different perspectives. The IRR calculates the discount rate that brings the NPV to zero, essentially showing the return on public investment in the project. It's compared against the opportunity cost of funds, often the market interest rate. However, the IRR can be problematic: it may produce multiple results from the same data, complicating decision-making, and it does not reliably compare across multiple projects due to its singular focus on one project's funds' opportunity cost.

Alternatively, the Benefit-Cost Ratio compares the present value of benefits to costs, with a project considered favourable if the ratio exceeds one. This simple metric allows for straightforward decisions but, like NPV and IRR, must be used judiciously, considering the broader implications of a project on social welfare, and ensuring a comprehensive evaluation of all potential benefits and costs.

6. Sensitivity Analysis

The NPV test evaluates a project's efficiency based on current data. However, due to uncertainties in predicting future events, such as production levels or market prices, this data can change, affecting NPV outcomes. Uncertainty is especially prevalent in environmental impacts, necessitating sensitivity analysis to assess how changes in key parameters might alter the NPV.

For a farm implementing green weed management practices, the initial NPV calculation might be based on estimates of reduced chemical use savings, increased labour costs for manual weeding, and potential yield impacts. However, future uncertainties—like the fluctuation in labour costs, the price of organic produce, or the effectiveness of these practices in different weather conditions—could significantly alter the outcome. For instance, if labour costs rise more than anticipated, or if the premium for organic produce increases due to higher consumer demand, the NPV of the project could change. Thus, performing a sensitivity analysis by adjusting these key parameters (e.g., a 20% increase in labour costs or a 30% increase in organic produce prices) can help understand how robust the project's financial viability is under different future scenarios.

2.3 Measuring Value

A key principle in CBA is the need to quantify all pertinent benefits and costs using a uniform metric to facilitate their summation across different individuals and periods. Monetary values serve as this common unit in CBA, though the underlying concept revolves around utility. Economists use the term "utility" to denote the elements contributing to individuals' happiness or the rationale behind their decisions. In an ideal scenario, CBA would assess the impacts of decisions by tallying the net changes in utility experienced by people, encompassing both the positive and negative shifts. However, in most real settings is difficult to translate utility into a cardinal measure (like kilometres per hour). A unified method involves employing the Utility function, which represents individual preferences to produce ordinal rankings of those preferences. For instance, it can indicate that "Mario" has a stronger preference for option A over B, or that Mario values having two units of A more than a single unit of B.

To derive a cardinal measure, which quantifies the extent of utility change (like how much happier Mario becomes with a new tractor), economists utilize monetary metrics. These metrics gauge the maximum amount an individual is willing to pay (WTP) for desirable gains or to avoid undesirable losses, as well as the minimum compensation an individual is willing to accept (WTA) for forfeiting something desirable or enduring something undesirable. For example, consider a scenario where adopting organic production

methods leads to more effective weed control in a farming area where Mario cultivates organic vegetables. His maximum willingness to pay (WTP) for this enhancement reflects the utility he derives from the reduced weed presence, which could lead to higher crop yields, less labour for weed removal, and a healthier ecosystem on his farm. Mario's willingness to pay (WTP) for improved weed control through organic methods reflects not only the extent of his concern for sustainable farming practices and the quality of his crops but also his financial capacity to invest in these organic solutions over other potential expenses. This WTP captures the intensity of his preferences (how much value he places on organic weed control) and the direction of his preferences (his desire for more effective organic methods over conventional ones).

In a similar vein, if adopting organic production methods inadvertently attracts more pests to Carmela's neighbouring fields, affecting his crop yield, his minimum Willingness to Accept (WTA) compensation for this reduction in yield reflects the value he places on maintaining pest-free crops. In essence, this WTA indicates what the unintended increase in pests—and the consequent decrease in crop yield—'costs' him in terms of lost utility. WTP and WTA are the classical monetary metrics in CBA (Hicks, 1943). Being more specific, imagine Carmela's initial state of satisfaction (utility) from his organic farming before encountering pest issues as U_0 . The initial costs for organic pest control and another farming input she uses are represented by p_0^1 and p_0^2 , respectively. The expense to maintain utility level U_0 with these costs is denoted as $C(p_0^1, p_0^2, U_0)$. If the cost of organic pest control (good 1) increases to p_1^1 due to enhanced weed control attracting pests, Joe would need additional income to uphold the same level of satisfaction U_0 , necessitating compensation. This compensation amount, the Compensating Variation (CV), is calculated as the difference between the cost to achieve utility U_0 at the original, lower pest control cost $C(p_0^1, p_0^2, U_0)$, and the cost to achieve utility U_0 at the new, elevated pest control cost p_1^1 , that is:

$$CV = C(p_0^1, p_0^2, U_0) - C(p_1^1, p_0^2, U_0)$$

where the utility level U_0 acts as the benchmark for evaluating changes in welfare. While these welfare metrics are tailored for price variations, most of the environmental applications we shall be considering when evaluating agri-environmental applications in our project involve quality changes (for example, organic matter preserved, a higher or lower level of water pollution). However, the general principles of welfare change measurement remain, although as we will see below, some changes are needed to make such complexities more analytically tractable.

In applying CBA to broader environmental problems, the complexities extend beyond individual choices. Suppose new regulations are introduced to reduce water pollution, indirectly affecting farming practices by limiting certain types of pesticides that might leach into water bodies. Mario and other farmers would then be positioned between adhering to previous farming practices with their existing levels of water quality and pest control or adapting to the new regulatory environment which improves the water quality and potentially impacts the pest dynamics on their farms. Individuals either experience the pre-reform threshold of water quality or the post-reform level – they cannot exercise a perfectly free choice on the water quality they use or consume.

In scenarios where individuals face restrictions on the quantities they can choose from, as is common with environmental applications of CBA, economists use the term "compensating surplus"; similarly, "equivalent variation" is replaced with "equivalent surplus." Nonetheless, both concepts are quantified using the established willingness to pay (WTP) and willingness to accept (WTA) framework. For instance, a nature enthusiast's value for enhancements in organic farming practices that lead to better ecosystem health would be determined by their maximum WTP for such improvements, indicating their compensating surplus. Conversely, the 'cost' or inconvenience someone might face due to changes in farming regulations affecting local water quality would be measured by their maximum WTP to prevent such changes, representing their equivalent surplus.

For a change which	Compensating Variation is:	Equivalent Variation is:
Increasing someone's well-being	Your highest willingness to pay for this change to occur, with	Your lowest willingness to accept to forego this change, while keeping your utility at the

	your utility maintained at the level before the change.	level it would be after the change.
Decreases someone's well-being	Your lowest willingness to accept compensation for this change, with your utility held constant at the level it was before the change.	Your highest willingness to pay to prevent this change from occurring, with your utility maintained at the level it would be after the change.

TABLE 5: WELFARE MEASURES

2.4 How to measure WTP and WTA?

Within a context where the goods being assessed are distinctly defined and possess clear property rights, economic theory indicates that their prices are set by the market. Furthermore, in situations devoid of external costs or benefits associated with the production of these goods, such as water quality, the market price accurately reflects the consumers' marginal willingness to pay (WTP) for an additional unit and the producers' costs to supply that unit, which equates to their minimum willingness to accept (WTA) for producing that quantity. Consequently, both the marginal WTP and marginal WTA can be efficiently ascertained by simply observing the market price.

However, our goal is to evaluate the full range of costs and benefits of a change in weed management by farmers, encompassing a wider social impact and not just at the private level. Often, social, and private costs, as well as benefits, align, allowing market prices to reflect both marginal social and private values, assuming no price alterations due to the project. However, discrepancies arise in certain significant scenarios, attributed to what economists' call 'market failure' (Vergamini et al., 2021; Hanely et al., 2000) where the market does not accurately capture all social costs and benefits. Pesticides are relatively inexpensive and enable farmers to sustain high revenues; however, they pose health risks to both those living near the affected agricultural areas and the end consumers who eat the food produced in this manner. However, the costs associated with these pollution effects are not borne by the private farms responsible for the food production; instead, they are 'borne' by individuals suffering from conditions such as nervous system disorders, liver ailments, or other clinical pathologies. "Pollution is an example of the external costs referred to above: a cost which does not fall on (is not paid by) the agent responsible for causing it." (cit.). From a societal perspective, it is essential to account for the social costs of production, which encompass both the marginal private costs and the marginal external costs associated with the agricultural activities. In this context, the market price fails to serve as an accurate indicator of the true social value. Therefore, relying solely on the market price of agricultural products to assess their social benefits would lead to an overestimation unless the analysis also incorporates the external costs, such as environmental degradation and health impacts, resulting from traditional farming activities.

The concept of external benefits runs parallel to that of external costs, highlighting another instance where market prices may inadequately reflect the true marginal social costs or benefits. External benefits occur when production activities yield advantages not accounted for by the market, or that supplement those the market does recognize. For instance, consider a farmer who adopts environmentally friendly weed management practices on his land, fostering soil health while also producing wine for sale. While the market compensates him for the wine he sells, it typically overlooks the environmental value of his contributions to the landscape protection, which are considered public goods and hence do not garner direct market rewards. Goods that the market often undervalues or fails to supply adequately in the agricultural sector typically exhibit characteristics of non-excludability and non-rivalry in consumption. Non-excludability in an agricultural context means that once a benefit is provided, such as enhanced biodiversity from sustainable farming practices, it's impossible to prevent individuals who haven't contributed to these practices from enjoying the benefits. For example, if a farmer adopts bee-friendly practices that increase pollination in the surrounding area, all nearby crops benefit, not just those on the farmer's land, making it difficult for the farmer to charge for these wider ecological benefits. Non-rivalry in the agricultural setting implies that the consumption of a good by one individual does not reduce its availability or quality for others. An example could be the carbon sequestration achieved by a large-scale agroforestry project. This environmental service benefits the global community by reducing greenhouse gases, and the benefit does

not diminish with the number of people benefitting from a more stable climate. However, this principle has its limits; for instance, overgrazing on communal lands can lead to soil degradation, showing that some agricultural goods can become rivalrous under certain conditions.

Against this background practitioners in CBA often rely on Shadow prices. Shadow pricing adjusts market prices in CBA to better reflect true social values, accounting for externalities and market failures to provide a more comprehensive assessment of economic impacts. However, it's also important to consider potential price distortions resulting from the introduction of subsidies and support policies, such as with the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). In these cases, traditional approaches employ 'producer subsidy equivalent'.

2.5 Valuing costs and benefits under uncertainty

Undertaking a CBA involves navigating the inherent uncertainty surrounding the future benefits and costs of any project or policy. This uncertainty is particularly evident in environmental projects, where future conditions can significantly impact outcomes. For instance, the benefits from planting a new forest, creating a wetland for flood prevention, or investing in wave energy are all uncertain due to variables like future commodity prices, weather patterns, and technological advancements. Similarly, the costs of initiatives like nuclear power generation are influenced by fluctuating resource prices and evolving waste treatment technologies.

Understanding uncertainty in CBA requires distinguishing between different future scenarios—or states of the world—and their likelihood. These states of the world represent various possible outcomes, such as different levels of future rainfall or timber prices. The probability of each state occurring provides another layer of complexity, enabling analysts to estimate expected outcomes by weighing each possible state by its likelihood.

More generally, if one can enumerate every potential outcome for a variable, X_i , along with its associated probability of happening in the future, P_i , within a specific timeframe, it implies that the probability distribution of X is determined. Consequently, the expected value of X can be calculated based on this information as:

$$\sum_i^n X_i * P_i$$

which indicates that the expected value is essentially an average value calculated across all conceivable outcomes, each adjusted according to its likelihood of occurrence.

Analysts generally encounter two types of uncertainty in CBA. The first type, known as choice under risk, occurs when both the possible outcomes and their probabilities are known, allowing for the calculation of expected values. Information on these probabilities often comes from statistical analyses of historical data or from modelling future scenarios. For example, climate models can predict future rainfall with certain probabilities, which can then be used to calculate an expected value for rainfall.

The second type of uncertainty, Knightian uncertainty, named after economist Frank Knight, arises when the probability distributions or even the potential outcomes themselves are not fully known. This type of uncertainty cannot be easily quantified and poses a greater challenge to CBA.

Dealing with choice under risk involves calculating expected benefits and costs using the known probabilities of various outcomes. However, this approach assumes risk neutrality—where individuals are indifferent between a gamble with a certain expected value and receiving that value for sure. In reality, many people are risk-averse, preferring a sure thing over a gamble, even if the gamble has a higher expected value. To address this, the concept of certainty-equivalence is used, identifying values for future risky outcomes that individuals would find equivalent to a certain lower benefit or cost.

When facing Knightian uncertainty, sensitivity analysis becomes a crucial tool. This involves recalculating the Net Present Value (NPV) of a project as key parameters are varied. Parameters that might be adjusted include the discount rate, physical quantities of inputs and outputs, and their prices, as well as the magnitude and value of external costs and benefits. The goal is to identify which parameters most significantly affect the NPV and thus merit closer forecasting and management effort. The parameters can be:

1. The discount rate;
2. Physical quantities of inputs (e.g., days of labour input required for a construction project);

3. (Shadow) prices of these inputs;
4. The magnitude and value of external costs and benefits resulting from the project (e.g., the recreation benefits from a new forest);
5. Physical quantities of outputs (e.g., megawatt hours of electricity from a new wind farm);
6. (Shadow) prices of these outputs.

Sensitivity analysis can reveal the robustness of a project's NPV to changes in assumptions, helping decision-makers focus on critical variables and manage projects more effectively. For projects with significant long-term impacts, the choice of discount rate is often pivotal, affecting the NPV calculation more than other variables. Projects like woodland planting or nuclear waste disposal, with benefits or costs extending far into the future, are particularly sensitive to the chosen discount rate.

Part. 3 Analysis strategy

3.1 Time and process mapping

One of the initial critical aspects of cost-benefit analysis is the definition of time, specifically the interval subject to analysis. This involves determining the period over which the costs and benefits of a particular practice or investment will be assessed. The chosen time frame is crucial as it influences the identification and valuation of both immediate and long-term impacts. A well-defined time interval ensures that the analysis captures all relevant costs and benefits, allowing for a comprehensive evaluation of the practice's economic viability and sustainability. This temporal dimension must be aligned with the life cycle of the investment, the expected duration of benefits, and the strategic planning horizon of the agricultural enterprise.

When faced with the task of evaluating approximately 21 diverse practices, experimented within various contexts and periods, it becomes clear that setting a uniform time interval is not feasible. Therefore, we must adopt a two-tiered approach. This methodology allows for the flexibility needed to accommodate the unique characteristics and temporal dynamics of each practice. The first level might involve defining a broad time frame that encompasses the entire duration of each practice from its initiation to its full implementation and impact realization. The second level could allow for a more granular analysis within this broader period, focusing on specific phases of development, such as the initial setup, the transition period, and the mature phase of each practice. This dual-level approach facilitates a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the practices, enabling an accurate assessment of their costs and benefits within their respective contexts and time frames.

At a first level, the reference period within the survey is intricately linked to the timing of the introduction of the agricultural practice in question, thereby delineating a 'BEFORE' and 'AFTER' scenario to capture the essence of change. This temporal demarcation is crucial for understanding the dynamics of innovation adoption and its subsequent impact on agricultural practices. In the questionnaire, this reference period is further elaborated upon in the relevant sections, ensuring that respondents have a clear framework within which to place their responses.

It is important to note that the consequent buffer time may vary from one case to another, reflecting the unique circumstances surrounding the adoption of each innovative practice. This variability acknowledges the fact that innovations do not follow a uniform timeline; rather, they require a certain span of time to be introduced and to achieve a level of maturity within the agricultural setting. Thus, respondents are encouraged to consider the necessary years during which the innovation was implemented and reached a significant stage of development and integration into the farming practices.

This dichotomy allows us to make a comparison between a baseline situation, that is, without a change in practice, and the situation that includes the change (Figure 1 “workflow example”). The difference between the two phases encompasses the three stages of development of the innovative practice. Namely, an initial set-up phase, a transition period, and a regime stage, where the activity becomes consolidated within the farm's routines. This framework provides a structured approach to evaluating the impact of innovative practices in agriculture, facilitating a comprehensive understanding of the process from inception to full integration. By examining these stages, we can assess the challenges, adjustments, and benefits associated with the adoption of new practices, and how they contribute to the overall performance and sustainability of the farm.

The definition of a more granular second level is thus deferred to a later stage, contingent upon varying requirements and expert opinions. After completing the analysis on the "before" and "after" scenarios, it will be essential to involve experts to assess and validate the specific temporal placement of the costs and benefits analysed. This expert involvement ensures that the evaluation of each practice is grounded in a deep understanding of its context, allowing for a precise determination of when costs are incurred, and benefits are realized. Such a collaborative and iterative process between analysis and expert validation helps to enhance the accuracy and relevance of the cost-benefit assessment, ensuring that the temporal aspects of each practice are appropriately accounted for in the final analysis.

FIGURE 1: WORKFLOW EXAMPLE

Constructing a workflow schema in collaboration with farmers is of paramount importance for several reasons. First, it highlights the processes relevant to the evaluation of innovative practices, ensuring that the analysis focuses on areas where changes are expected to have a significant impact. Second, it enables the analyst to link the costs and benefits identified through data collection to specific phases and processes. This linkage provides a clear understanding of the resources utilized and the outcomes produced at each stage of the workflow.

By mapping out the workflow in detail, analysts can trace the flow of operations before and after the implementation of innovative practices, allowing for a precise assessment of how these practices alter resource allocation, operational efficiency, and productivity. This approach not only aids in the accurate quantification of costs and benefits but also in the identification of potential areas for further improvement or optimization within the workflow. The collaborative nature of this process ensures that the analysis is grounded in the practical realities of the farms involved, enhancing the relevance and applicability of the findings. Clearly, the more detailed and clear the process is, the less effort will be required during data collection and analysis. A well-defined workflow allows for a streamlined approach to identifying and documenting the relevant information, reducing ambiguities and uncertainties. This precision facilitates a more efficient and effective analysis, as the data can be directly correlated with specific processes and stages within the workflow. Consequently, this leads to a reduction in the time and resources needed to gather and interpret data, enhancing the overall efficiency of the evaluation process. For the development of the workflow and the analysis of processes, we provide a PowerPoint template that each partner can develop together with the farmer (or whoever has been involved in testing the practice). Alternatively, it is possible to fill in the specific section of the questionnaire by sequentially reporting all the relevant processes, resources, and tasks that must be completed in the two scenarios under consideration. This approach offers flexibility, allowing partners to choose the method that best suits their situation and preferences. The PowerPoint template serves as a visual aid that can facilitate discussions and ensure a comprehensive capture of processes, while the questionnaire format provides a structured way to document the information in a written format. Both methods aim to ensure a thorough understanding and recording of the operational changes and impacts associated with the innovative practices being evaluated. Partners

are kindly asked to describe the workflow with a level of detail as high as the one used in the provided example. This is necessary also to allow for the calculation of some environmental and social indicators.

3.2 Data collection

Data collection was conducted through a shared survey (see Annex 1) structured into three sections: economic, social, and environmental. Given the complexities of the social and environmental phases, the strategy adopted was to capture the economic aspect extensively and quantitatively, then to attempt to repurpose various pieces of information for the other two phases. Where possible, we aimed to gather sufficient quantitative data for all three phases. Otherwise, we followed a hybrid evaluation approach, integrating expert judgments and opinions to find the best possible compromise. This method acknowledged the challenges of obtaining comprehensive quantitative data in certain areas and leveraged expert insights to enrich the analysis, ensuring a balanced and thorough assessment across all dimensions of the practices being evaluated.

The survey was administered by research partners to those farmers who had developed the innovation process and, preferably, had attained a certain degree of maturity regarding the practices developed. It was the responsibility of each partner to select within the national network those farmers who could be defined as leaders in the innovation process, as those early adopters or those who might have a guiding role. In cases of experimental practices or those not yet widespread in the market, comparing practices among early adopters still provided the necessary information for a more in-depth evaluation.

During the evaluation phase, it was necessary to balance any higher costs and lower expected benefits compared to situations where the maturity and diffusion of practices had allowed the development of specific economies, thus leading to better cost containment and greater access to benefits. This approach acknowledged the variations in the innovation journey of different companies and aimed to provide a fair and comprehensive assessment by considering the specific context and stage of each practice's adoption and implementation.

3.3 CBA settings

3.3.1 Time

The CBA has been structured around a common set of working assumptions, with the first relating to time. For the analyses we assumed a standard time horizon of at least 20 years to highlight the long-term nature of the benefits, especially the environmental and social ones. The 20-year horizon, however, necessitated approximating some business choices where, for example, an investment needed to be repeated for at least two 10-year cycles for machinery or three cycles as typically seen with agricultural tools, for which we assumed a shorter lifespan of about 7 years. These assumptions have concerned the monetary estimates performed (see cost estimation below).

3.3.2 Discount rate

At the CBA level, another important hypothesis involves adopting a 4% discount rate and examining the outcomes with lower (2%) and higher (6%) rates through sensitivity analysis to elucidate the relationship between the discount rate and the future value of costs and benefits. The discount rate is pivotal because it dictates how future costs and benefits are valued in present terms, embodying the principle of the time value of money—where money available today is worth more than the same amount in the future due to its potential earning capacity. A higher discount rate reduces the present value of future financial flows, suggesting a preference for receiving benefits sooner or delaying costs, which effectively diminishes the significance of future events in today's financial terms. Conversely, a lower discount rate increases the present value, indicating a longer-term outlook where future events are deemed more significant in current decisions. This variance in discount rates can significantly influence the perceived cost-effectiveness of a project, particularly those with long-term environmental and social impacts. By varying the discount rate in sensitivity analysis, stakeholders can gauge how changes affect the project's financial viability under

different economic conditions, ensuring decisions are well-informed and reflect a comprehensive understanding of financial resilience and project value across multiple future economic environments.

3.3.3 Evaluation metrics

The decision criteria for selecting investment projects in economic analysis—such as Net Present Value (NPV), Benefit-Cost Ratio (BCR), Internal Rate of Return (IRR), and Modified Internal Rate of Return (MIRR)—are not universally applicable across all scenarios. Proper application of these criteria requires a nuanced understanding of the specific decision context. Notably, NPV is often considered the most robust measure, aimed at maximizing the overall NPV from an investment portfolio, but it is not necessarily the optimal criterion for evaluating all types of individual projects, as the context may dictate the suitability of other metrics.

For projects constrained by budget limitations, BCR is used to rank projects by considering constrained costs within the denominator and unconstrained costs subtracted from the numerator. However, when multiple funding constraints exist, or in cases where projects influence each other's costs and benefits, a more complex constrained optimization model is necessary to maximize total NPV. This involves enumerating all possible combinations of projects, particularly when projects are dependent or mutually exclusive, to ensure the selection of projects that collectively offer the highest NPV without violating funding constraints.

Furthermore, the calculation of BCR can be tricky, especially under funding constraints, and requires precise placement of costs in its formula—either in the denominator or subtracted based on whether they are constrained. This complexity often leads to the use of specialized optimization models, such as integer programming, to derive the optimal combination of projects, focusing on maximizing the overall portfolio NPV. This type of optimization is particularly useful in selecting among binary (lumpy) or mutually exclusive projects where simple decision criteria like NPV or BCR may not suffice.

Additionally, when dealing with projects of different timeframes, comparing their NPVs directly can be misleading unless adjustments are made to standardize the comparison basis, often through techniques like calculating Equivalent Annual Value (EAV) or extending the benefit-cost analysis to encompass the same timeframe for all projects.

The choice of decision criterion and model thus depends heavily on the specific characteristics of the projects and the constraints faced, emphasizing the need for a flexible yet methodologically rigorous approach in economic analysis to accurately guide investment decisions.

According to this context, we standardized our approach by applying the same temporal horizon to all practices, and we calculated NPV per hectare. This uniform timeframe and scale allow for a consistent and fair comparison across all initiatives. Given the complexities involved in using other financial indicators such as BCR, IRR, and MIRR, these were not employed for direct comparisons between alternative projects. Instead, they were used to provide additional detail and insight into individual initiatives.

By focusing on NPV per hectare, we ensured that our analysis was directly applicable to the agricultural context, providing clear, actionable data that could be easily interpreted and applied by stakeholders. This approach allows for an accurate assessment of the economic viability of each weed control practice, highlighting their potential returns over a standardized period. The other financial metrics, while not suitable for ranking or comparing different projects due to their varied implications and the complexities in their calculations, served as supplementary tools to deepen the understanding of each project's financial dynamics within its specific operational framework.

The BCR is a financial metric used to evaluate the overall value for money of a project by comparing the total expected benefits to the total expected costs. A BCR greater than one indicates that the project's benefits exceed its costs, making it economically viable, while a BCR less than one suggests the opposite. In practice, for making a straightforward yes/no decision about proceeding with a single project, any version of the BCR formula that consistently evaluates whether the BCR is greater than or less than one can be employed.

The MIRR is another crucial financial metric used to assess the profitability of potential investments. Unlike the standard Internal Rate of Return (IRR), which can sometimes result in multiple values in scenarios involving alternate periods of positive and negative cash flow, the MIRR provides a unique solution by assuming that positive cash flows are reinvested at the reinvestment rate and that the initial investments are

financed at the cost of capital. In the context discussed, both the cost of capital and the reinvestment rate of return are set at 4%. This unified approach to handling the finance and reinvestment rates under the MIRR framework provides a more accurate and realistic measure of a project's profitability and financial feasibility.

3.3.4 Risks and Adoption

In the CBA we utilized a comprehensive approach that combines the evaluation of practice attractiveness with the contextual circumstances of adoption (**Error! Reference source not found.**). This methodological framework is designed to predict the potential adoption rates based on inherent features of the practices and external adoption conditions, which are pivotal for strategic decision-making and resource allocation. The approach explores the different combinations of practice attractiveness and adoption circumstances, which categorizes potential outcomes ranging from high to no adoption.

	Very Favourable Circumstances	Less Favourable Circumstances
Highly Attractive	High adoption likelihood	Moderate adoption likelihood
Slightly Attractive	Moderate adoption likelihood	Low adoption likelihood
Neutral	Low to moderate adoption likelihood	Very low adoption likelihood
Slightly Negative	Low adoption likelihood	Very low adoption likelihood
Highly Negative	Very low adoption likelihood	No adoption expected

TABLE 6: CBA ADOPTION PARAMETERS

For our analysis, we specifically modelled two distinct scenarios to provide a clearer understanding of how these factors might play out in real-world settings:

1. **High Adoption in a Favourable Context:** This scenario assumes that the weed control practices are highly attractive to farmers and are introduced under very favourable circumstances. This is typically envisioned for smaller, more progressive farms where there is a strong knowledge base and organizational support for the practices. It reflects an environment where the new practices are expected to be adopted readily and effectively without significant barriers.
2. **Low Adoption in an Unfavourable Context:** Contrary to the first, this scenario deals with less attractive practices being introduced in less favourable circumstances. It considers larger, more diverse farming populations that might not have strong connections to agricultural support organizations or a deep understanding of the benefits of the new practices. Here, the adoption likelihood is anticipated to be lower, requiring more effort and possibly greater incentives to achieve significant penetration. In addition, in this scenario, a low risk of project failure ranging from 0-5% was assumed.

By selecting these scenarios, our CBA aims to capture a broad spectrum of potential outcomes and provide farmers with a realistic projection of how the weed control practices might be received across different types of agricultural farms. This structured approach helps in planning interventions, aligning resources where they are most needed, and in understanding where additional support mechanisms or changes in strategy might be necessary to enhance adoption rates and ensure the successful implementation of innovative practices in weed management.

3.3.5 Private vs Public benefits

In economic analysis, particularly in BCA, distinguishing between private (direct) benefits and public (indirect) benefits is crucial for a comprehensive evaluation of projects or policies. **Private benefits** are those that directly accrue to the stakeholders or entities that undertake the project. These benefits are often straightforward to quantify as they typically involve direct financial gains or cost savings. **Public benefits**, on the other hand, are more diffuse and accrue to society at large rather than to individual stakeholders. They often include ecological, aesthetic, or health-related improvements and are more challenging to measure because they are not directly captured in market transactions.

For assessing **public benefits**, economists employ several techniques, including contingent valuation, which uses surveys to ask people how much they would be willing to pay for the benefit in question; hedonic pricing, which looks at how the presence of a benefit affects prices of goods and services (e.g., property values); and benefits transfer, which applies benefit estimates from similar studies to the project being analysed. While methods such as contingent valuation and hedonic pricing were not feasible due to time and budget constraints, as conducting a comprehensive CBA across 20 practices within a limited timeframe precluded initiating extensive new research activities, the benefits transfer approach appeared to be the most promising.

In the study by Daigneault et al., 2021 titled "Benefits, costs, and feasibility of scaling up land conservation for maintaining ecosystem services in the Sebago Lake watershed, Maine, US," the researchers utilized the benefits transfer method to evaluate public benefits. This methodology is advantageous particularly when primary data collection is impractical or prohibitively expensive. Within this framework, monetary values attributed to ecosystem services or other public benefits are extrapolated from existing research that has previously quantified the economic value of similar services in different contexts. This approach is predicated on the assumption that the economic values of such services can be appropriately transferred across different yet analogous settings, thereby providing a feasible method for estimating benefits in studies where direct measurement is challenging. Moreover, the benefits transfer method has been extensively discussed in literature such as Costanza et al. (1997), who emphasize its utility and the conditions under which its results can be considered reliable.

Unfortunately, in the analysis of the 20 weed control practices we examined, one or more of the critical criteria necessary for a reliable application of the benefits transfer method could not be met:

1. **Similarity of Ecological Contexts:** The ecological settings of our practices varied significantly, reducing the likelihood that valuation estimates from other studies could be directly applicable. Each practice involved unique ecological interactions that were not sufficiently mirrored in the settings from which potential transfer data might have been drawn.
2. **Accuracy of Baseline Studies:** We encountered limitations in the availability of methodologically sound and accurately reported studies that matched our specific practices. The reliability of benefits transfer hinges on the quality of these underlying studies, and in our case, matching high-quality data sources to our diverse practices proved challenging.
3. **Geographic Proximity:** The geographic characteristics of the areas involved in our study often differed substantially from those in potential source studies. This lack of proximity meant that ecological and economic characteristics likely varied too much to make direct value transfers feasible.
4. **Temporal Relevance:** Some of the data available for potential transfer was outdated and did not reflect the current ecological and economic conditions of our study areas. Using such data could lead to significant discrepancies in the estimated values, undermining the validity of the analysis.
5. **Comprehensive Data Coverage:** The studies potentially available for benefits transfer did not always cover the broad range of ecological goods and services relevant to our specific weed control practices. This gap in data coverage further complicated the use of transferred values in our assessment.

Due to several constraints, we developed a robust methodology that balanced precision and practicality, specifically tailored to address the variability inherent in farm-scale applications rather than broader territorial impacts. Our methodology prioritized direct measurements of social, economic, and environmental impacts wherever feasible. When direct quantification proved impossible, we employed established indirect estimation methods to approximate the monetary effects of the practices. In cases where neither direct nor indirect methods were suitable, owing to the innovative and site-specific nature of the practices, we relied on qualitative assessments. This involved an in-depth analysis of each benefit, contextualized through relevant literature to ensure a nuanced interpretation grounded in specific conditions.

Furthermore, our farm-level focus was essential in providing clear insights into the feasibility and profitability of the practices within their specific operational contexts. To broaden our understanding of the wider implications of these practices, we also incorporated findings from our questionnaire and the detailed

results of previous workshops carried out in T3.1. This qualitative exploration of benefits (see ‘Traffic Light system’ section below) extended our analysis beyond mere economic factors to include substantial environmental and social dimensions, thereby enhancing our understanding of the practices' long-term sustainability. This comprehensive approach not only enriched the analysis but also ensured that our findings were robust, making a significant contribution to sustainable agricultural practices.

3.3.6 Traffic light system for social and environmental impacts

The social and environmental impact results were developed using a structured process, combining questionnaire responses with results from T3.1 workshops to create an overall impact score that we called the traffic light system (Figure 2).

FIGURE 2: EXAMPLE OF TRAFFIC LIGHT FROM SOCIAL ANALYSIS OF ITALY 1 CASE

The score (green for high impact, yellow for medium impact, and red for low impact) was calculated through the following steps:

1. First, we reviewed the literature and identified key social and environmental impacts related to the project adoption. These impacts were categorized as either direct or indirect:
 - **Direct Social Impacts:** These include improved labour environment, new job opportunities, social reputation, farmers' education and skills, and conditions for vulnerable groups.
 - **Indirect Social Impacts:** These include enhanced food safety and quality, community health, and the aesthetics of the landscape.
 - **Direct Environmental Impacts:** These include land conservation (soil erosion reduction), improved soil structure and stability, increased soil organic matter, enhanced water retention, and biodiversity support.
 - **Indirect Environmental Impacts:** These include improved nutrient cycling, reduced carbon footprint, increased resilience to climate change, and pest and disease control.
2. We elaborated 10 questions for the social part and 9 question for the environmental ones. Responses were given on a scale of 1 to 5 with 3 being neutral.

Social impacts	Environmental impacts
QS1. Stable income	QE.1 Contribute to reduce direct greenhouse gas emissions
QS2. Flexibility for agricultural management	QE2. Contribute to reduce external inputs
QS3. New job opportunities in rural area	QE3. Limit water consumption
QS4. Improvement of working conditions	QE4. Contribute to reduce waste
QS5. Increased food safety	QE5. Has a positive impact on biodiversity
QS6. More job opportunities for women	QE6. Has a positive impact on soil erosion
QS7. Improving farmers' education and skills	QE7. Has a positive impact on carbon footprint
	QE8. Increase the rate of soil organic matter mineralization
	QE9. Increase soil compaction

QS8. Improved conditions for vulnerable groups QS9. Improved aesthetics and cultural value QS10. Improved social reputation	
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3. Then, a weighting system was developed through the relevant literature based on three main criteria:
- **Impact Intensity:** Higher weights were assigned to high-intensity impacts.
 - **Timeframe:** Short- to medium-term impacts were given higher weights due to their more immediate effects, while long-term impacts were assigned slightly lower weights.
 - **Direct vs. Indirect Impact:** Direct impacts were weighted higher than indirect impacts, as they tend to be more immediately visible.

For the social impacts the following weights were applied:

- High impact (short-term or immediate): 1.0
- Moderate impact (medium-term or long-term): 0.6 to 0.8, depending on the importance and timeframe.
- Moderate or context-dependent: 0.5, as these impacts depend heavily on specific conditions and may not materialize consistently.

For the environmental impacts the following weights were applied:

- High impact (quantifiable or highly relevant): 1.0
- Moderate to high impact: 0.8
- Moderate impact: 0.6

According to the weighting step we derived the following weights for each question in the two analysis:

Social impacts and relative weights	Environmental impacts and relative weights
QS1. Stable income: 0.8	<i>QE1. Contribute to reduce direct greenhouse gas emissions: 0.6</i>
QS2. Flexibility for agricultural management: 0.6	<i>QE2. Contribute to reduce external inputs: 0.8</i>
QS3. New job opportunities in rural area: 0.6	<i>QE3. Limit water consumption: 0.6</i>
QS4. Improvement of working conditions: 1.0	<i>QE4. Contribute to reduce waste: 0.6</i>
QS5. Increased food safety: 0.5	<i>QE5. Has a positive impact on biodiversity: 1.0</i>
QS6. More job opportunities for women: 0.5	<i>QE6. Has a positive impact on soil erosion: 1.0</i>
QS7. Improving farmers' education and skills: 1.0	<i>QE7. Has a positive impact on carbon footprint: 0.8</i>
QS8. Improved conditions for vulnerable groups: 0.6	<i>QE8. Increase the rate of soil organic matter mineralization: 1.0</i>
QS9. Improved aesthetics and cultural value: 0.8	<i>QE9. Increase soil compaction: Weight = 1.0</i>
QS10. Improved social reputation: 0.6	

4. To ensure comparability of scores across different cases, we introduced a (0,1) normalization step among collected answers.

5. Each answer has been then multiplied by the relative weights.

To accurately reflect perceptions regarding environmental and social impacts in our study, we developed a scoring system based on weighted responses. Initially, we collected responses through a questionnaire completed by individual respondents. Recognizing the limitation of relying solely on

single-person responses, which might not fully capture broader consensus, we sought to incorporate wider community perspectives.

To achieve this, we cross-referenced the questionnaire responses with data obtained from various national workshops that discussed the same environmental and social practices. This approach allowed us to apply a dual weighting to the data, thereby integrating a broader consensus into the final score that could not be achieved through the individual questionnaires alone. The second layer of weighting was implemented by performing a weighted average of the responses from both the questionnaire and the workshops, using the inverse of the variance as weights. This method enhances the reliability of the data by giving more weight to responses from sources with lower variance, which indicates greater agreement among participants.

Regarding the variance, we categorized it into two classes based on the characteristics of the sample:

- **High Variance:** This category, with a variance of 0.1 and an inverse variance of 10, is associated with samples having extensive experience but less consensus. This suggests that while the respondents are knowledgeable, their opinions are more varied, perhaps due to differing interpretations of their experiences.
- **Low Variance:** Represented by a variance of 0.01 and an inverse variance of 100, this category indicates samples with less experience but higher agreement. This suggests that these responses, while perhaps less informed by extensive personal experience, are more uniform in their assessment of impacts.

The use of inverse variance weighting in combining questionnaire and workshop responses ensured that the final scores more accurately reflect a collective assessment of the impacts, weighted towards the most reliable and consistent data sources. Though this methodologically robust approach we not only aggregate individual and group perceptions but also effectively balance the influence of diverse opinions, leading to a more comprehensive and reliable assessment of the environmental and social impacts of the practices under study.

6. The final scoring system categorizes the assessment of environmental and social impacts into three distinct classes, each visually represented by colour-coded indicators to enhance clarity and immediacy in interpretation:

- **Low (0-33%):** Indicated by a red light, this range signifies that the environmental and social impacts are significantly adverse or below the expected standards, highlighting areas that urgently require attention and improvement.
- **Medium (34-66%):** Represented by a yellow light, this category denotes moderate impacts. It suggests that while some aspects may meet the necessary standards, there are still significant areas of concern that could benefit from targeted interventions to enhance sustainability and social outcomes.
- **High (67-100%):** This range is marked by a green light, indicating that the assessed practices have highly favourable environmental and social impacts, aligning with or exceeding the set criteria and expectations, thus representing optimal performance in sustainability efforts.

This tri-colour system not only simplifies the communication of results but also aids stakeholders in quickly understanding the effectiveness of the practices assessed and pinpointing specific areas for policy intervention or continued support.

3.4 Technical assumption for the Costs-Benefits estimation

3.4.1 Erosion control

In our analysis, we accounted for a cost associated with maintaining practices that could contribute to soil erosion. Therefore, the application of these calculations is only relevant to practices that help reduce soil erosion. The criterion used to assess whether the introduction of a practice would result in such a benefit was related to potential soil coverage during the rainy season. This was evaluated by Oper8 experts during the WP3 workshops and through specific questions in the questionnaire administered for the CBA (environmental section). Furthermore, in order to estimate an increase in erosion as close to reality as

possible, a literature review was conducted. This led to the adoption of the model proposed by Panagos et al. (2018) and the adoption of the assumptions outlined below.

The first assumption concerns the exponential growth of soil erosion over a 20-year time horizon, considering an exponential growth factor $\alpha = 0.2$. The formula used to estimate annual relative erosion is as follows:

$$E(t) = \begin{cases} 0,01 & \text{se } t \leq 4 \\ 0,08 * (1 - \exp(-\alpha(t - 4))) & \text{se } t > 4 \end{cases}$$

In the formula t represents the number of years elapsed and α is the exponential growth factor. In particular, in the first four years ($t \leq 4$), soil erosion is assumed to be minimal and stable, with a constant value of **0.01** (1%). This reflects the early stage where the impact of erosion is negligible, possibly due to soil resilience or mitigation measures.

After the fourth year ($t > 4$), erosion starts to increase exponentially, following the formula:

$$0.08 * (1 - \exp(-\alpha(t - 4))).$$

Here, 0.08 represents the maximum erosion level (8%). Thus, the formula reflects our assumption that in an average situation, the erosion rate increases gradually, starting slowly and accelerating until it stabilises near the maximum value.

With reference to the model used, it must be remembered that it was applied in the specific context of a farm and well-defined areas. For this reason, it was assumed that the area subject to severe erosion (**SEA**) coincides with the total agricultural area (**TAA**). Therefore, in the formula

$$LPL = (SEA/TAA) * 0.08$$

the **SEA/TAA ratio** becomes equal to 1, simplifying the soil productivity loss equation to:

$$LPL = 0.08.$$

This value is then combined with the cultivated area for each specific crop (**CA**) and the productivity per hectare (**CP**) to calculate the agricultural productivity loss for each crop (**CPL**):

$$CPL = LPL * CA$$

Finally, the value is monetised by multiplying it with the value of agricultural production. In particular, the questionnaire asked for an average value over the last five years. This value is then revised year by year considering an average inflation of **2.15%**.

3.4.2 CO2 emissions

We do not include the calculation of CO2 emissions in the private analysis because they represent a cost shifted onto society and are not part of the private cost-benefit balance. However, these emissions were calculated separately to account for their broader impact, using values from the EIB Group climate bank roadmap 2021-2025. The roadmap provides the basis for the shadow cost, which represents the minimum societal cost of achieving the 1.5°C temperature target (EIB, 2020).

	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Value (€_2016/tCO _{2e})	80	165	250	390	525	660	800

TABLE 7: EIB SHADOW COST OF CARBON. SOURCE: TABLE A6, EIB (2020)

3.4.3 CAPEX

CAPEX values were collected via the questionnaire and then processed according to the following assumptions:

- The annual maintenance cost of the new machines, introduced together with the practices, is estimated at 3% of the value as new.
- For the lifespan of agricultural machines and tools, a conservative and uniform approach was chosen in the analyses performed. The lifespan of agricultural machinery was estimated at 10 years and that of tools at 7 years.
- For the purchase of new machines over the 20-year period of analysis, an annual inflation rate of 5% was estimated.
- For the resale of end-of-life machines, an annual depreciation rate of 15% was considered.

3.4.4 Opportunity costs

Opportunity costs represent the potential income or benefits a farm could have earned by allocating its resources to alternative uses. For this analysis, we have conservatively estimated opportunity costs at 3%, a figure derived from the assumed rate of return that could be achieved if the capital tied up in technical equipment were invested in low-risk financial instruments or comparable alternatives. This rate reflects the relatively low-risk profile of the equipment and aligns with typical benchmarks for safe investment returns in agricultural contexts. These costs are particularly relevant for capital expenditures (CAPEX), as they account for the forgone financial opportunities resulting from the allocation of funds to project-specific assets rather than other potential investments. Opportunity costs are distributed over the number of purchases considered during the 20-year analysis period, ensuring a fair annual representation of these foregone benefits.

Including opportunity costs in the cost-benefit analysis (CBA) is crucial to capturing both direct and indirect effects, thus providing a comprehensive understanding of the project's economic impacts. This approach ensures that non-monetary considerations and alternative scenarios are incorporated into the evaluation.

3.4.5 Transaction costs

Transaction costs have been estimated following the approach used by Mettepenningen et al. (2009), who measured the private transaction costs of European agri-environmental schemes. These costs average €40.2 per hectare annually, comprising approximately 14.3% of the total costs and 25.4% of the compensation payments. These costs are classified into four categories: search costs (€11.1/ha), which include gathering information on AES options and evaluating alternatives; negotiation costs (€15.3/ha), covering the preparation of preliminary requirements (e.g., field maps, soil sampling) and application procedures; monitoring and enforcement costs (€10.6/ha), which involve maintaining records and ensuring compliance during inspections; and unspecified transaction costs (€3.3/ha). These expenditures significantly impact farmers' participation decisions and administrative burdens, reflecting the complexity of aligning agricultural practices with AES requirements.

3.4.6 Other common parameters in the analysis

In general, all the assumptions described were applied uniformly to all practices. This is to ensure a more adequate comparison of the results. Only in the case of specific reasons, linked to the peculiarities of the individual practice analysed, may there be variations. These, if any, are described in detail in the final practice report.

Part. 4 CBA results

4.1 Overview

The overview presented in this analysis focuses on a diverse array of weed control techniques employed across various agricultural settings in multiple countries, highlighting the adaptability and effectiveness of each method in its respective context. This study categorizes the approaches into mechanical weeding, cover crops, mulching, precision farming, and ecological management, each showcasing innovative strategies aimed at enhancing sustainability in agriculture.

Significantly, the scale at which these practices are implemented varies widely (Table 4), influencing both their potential impact and the insights they provide into the scalability of such methods. For instance, in the United Kingdom (Case ID UK1), the adoption of mechanical weeding across an extensive area of 200 hectares, which constitutes 18.1% of the total Utilized Agricultural Area (UAA) analysed, showcases a large-scale application of traditional weed control methods adapted to modern sustainability standards. This extensive application offers valuable data on the practicality and economic viability of scaling up mechanical weeding in diverse crop settings, including arable crops and sugar beets.

In Sweden, advanced technological approaches such as camera or GPS guided mechanical weeding (Case ID SW1) cover an even more significant area of 500 hectares, representing 45.3% of the total UAA surveyed. This extensive deployment illustrates Sweden's proactive approach in integrating cutting-edge technologies to enhance the efficiency and precision of weed control. Another Swedish case (Case ID SW3) involves targeted spraying techniques utilizing either camera systems on spray booms or site-specific spraying informed by drone data, covering 99 hectares. These cases highlight the country's focus on precision agriculture, which allows for targeted weed control that minimizes chemical usage and reduces environmental impact.

The variation in UAA across these case studies is crucial for understanding the scalability and adaptability of weed control techniques. Larger-scale implementations provide robust evidence for the efficacy of these practices in commercial agricultural operations, while smaller-scale or more localized applications offer insights into the specificity and customization required to address unique agricultural or ecological conditions effectively.

Through this comprehensive analysis, we gain a deeper understanding of how different weed control techniques can be optimized and tailored to meet the challenges of sustainable farming in diverse geographic and crop-specific contexts. This broad perspective is essential for fostering global adoption of sustainable practices, as it demonstrates the practical applications and benefits of each technique, not only for individual farms but for the agricultural sector as a whole.

Cluster	Case ID	Country	Solutions	Main crop	UAA (ha)	% of total UAA
Mechanical weeding	FR1	France	Intra-row mechanical weeding	Vineyards	10	10.0
	IT2	Italy	Whole surface dead mulch	Vineyards	10	0.9
	LV2	Italy	Mechanical weeding (harrowing)	Arable/field vegetable crops	1	0.1

	UK1	United Kingdom	Mechanical weeding	Arable crops (including sugar beets)	200	18.1
	GR3	Greece	Hot Foam - vineyards	Vineyards	1	0.0
Cover Crops	FR2	France	Intra-row permanent sowed cover crop	Vineyards	50	4.5
	GR1	Greece	Cover crops	Vineyards	1	0.1
	IT1	Italy	Under-row self-reseeding cover crop	Vineyards	1.25	0.1
Mulching	FR3	France	Exogenous dead mulch	Vineyards	1	0.1
	SP2	Spain	Mulching with wood chips and herbs	Field vegetable crops (hortic.)	1	0.1
	UK2	United Kingdom	Living mulches	Arable crops	5.5	0.5
Precision farming	IT3	Italy	Mechanical weeding coupled with precision agriculture	Arable/field vegetable crops	100	9.1
	LV3	Latvia	Precision spraying with weed mapping	Arable/field vegetable crops	1	0.1
	GR4	Greece	Greek OG - Camera guided mechanical weeding		15	1.4
	UK3	United Kingdom	Targeted (precision) spraying	Field vegetable crops	5	0.5
	SW1	Sweden	Camera or GPS guided mechanical weeding	Arable crops	500	45.3
	SW3	Sweden	Targeted spraying using either cameras on spray boom or site-specific spraying using data from drones	Arable crops	99	9.0
Ecological management	GR2	Greece	False seedbed - arable crops	Arable crops	2	0.2
	SP1	Spain	Cultural control - cover crops	Arable crops	80	7.3
	SP3	Spain	Agroforestry methods	Vineyards	20	1.8
Total UAA 20 cases					1103.25	

TABLE 8: CBA OVERVIEW

The results provide a nuanced view of the financial and environmental impacts of diverse agricultural practices, covering a range of cost structures, benefits, and CO2 impacts across various geographic regions and agricultural methods (TABLE 8). This analysis underscores the complex dynamics of sustainable agriculture and highlights the critical need for tailored strategies that balance immediate financial feasibility with long-term sustainability outcomes.

In financial terms, the highest benefit per hectare is achieved in GR3 in Greece, with an exceptional return of 20,370 euros per hectare, indicating highly effective practices that generate significant economic returns. This is primarily attributed to the specific type of agricultural activity or the scale at which it is conducted.

Conversely, LV2, also in Greece, shows the lowest financial benefit at only 595 per hectare, suggesting either lower profitability or effectiveness in the agricultural practices employed there.

The environmental impact, particularly in terms of CO₂ reduction, closely correlates with the financial performance in some cases. GR3 not only achieves high financial returns but also reports the most substantial CO₂ reduction, affirming that economically advantageous practices in this instance also offer significant environmental benefits. In stark contrast, cases like LV2 and SP3 demonstrate minimal or no CO₂ reduction benefits, indicating that these practices may not focus on or effectively reduce carbon emissions.

A closer look at the cost structures reveals substantial variations across the cases. Capital Expenditure (CAPEX), which includes investments used to acquire, upgrade, and maintain physical assets, and Operating Expense (OPEX), which covers day-to-day operational costs, vary widely. For instance, FR3 in France indicates a very high CAPEX at 85%, pointing to substantial investments in infrastructure or technology. Similarly, SW1 in Sweden shows a high OPEX at 47%, likely reflecting the ongoing costs needed to maintain the practice.

Labour costs also vary significantly and are notably high in cases like UK1 and IT3, where the intensive labour involved is justified by the substantial returns generated, indicating that these labour-intensive practices are likely economically viable due to their high productivity.

Regionally, Greece and Italy, particularly in cases like GR3 and IT3, showcase substantial CO₂ benefits coupled with high financial returns, illustrating successful integration of eco-friendly practices that are both sustainable and economically beneficial. Conversely, some Spanish cases and additional cases from Greece highlight minimal investment in CAPEX with a predominant focus on OPEX, suggesting potentially short-term or less sustainable agricultural management strategies.

This detailed analysis across different agricultural practices, including mechanical weeding, cover crops, mulching, precision farming, and ecological management, provides crucial insights into their cost-effectiveness and environmental impact. Notably, high investments in precision agriculture and ecological management, as seen in IT3 and SW1, yield significant returns and enhance sustainability. However, financial outlays and returns can vary considerably, as demonstrated by practices like LV2 and SP3, where minimal investment leads to variable benefits and CO₂ impacts, underscoring the need for careful selection and management of practices to optimize both economic and environmental outcomes. The association between higher labour costs and increased benefits in regions like the UK and Italy further suggests that the economic viability of labour-intensive practices in these regions can be justified by their enhanced returns.

Combining these observations allows for a more comprehensive understanding of the dynamics at play in sustainable agricultural practices, aiding in the strategic decision-making and policy development necessary for future agricultural management.

Case ID	Benefit euros ha ⁻¹	CO ₂ (benefit euros per case)	Costs euros ha ⁻¹	% CAPEX	% OPEX	% Labour	% Other costs*	CO ₂ (cost euros per case)
FR1	1,987		7,722.5	61	16	12	12	1,737
IT2	1,549		4,407.5	62	1	7	14	0

LV2	595		40.2	0	0	0	100	0
UK1	2,229		452.97	31	20	30	19	10,653
GR3	20,370		369,672	64	19	3	15	182.0
FR2	12,270		6,864.0	33	44	16	6	525
GR1	6,875		4,520	0	67	20	13	221
IT1	5,250		39,154.6	60	18	7	16	0
FR3	18,491		36,414.2	0	85	15	0	0
SP2	35,520		106,232	56	21	10	13	6,022
UK2	2,543		23,232.7	54	26	3	17	0
IT3	9,300	135,271	3,778.2	65	18	1	16	0
LV3	308		82,335	68	16	4	12	0
GR4	3,975		10,653.2	43	44	4	8	2,770.2
UK3	2,108	626.0	105,259	49	15	17	3	0
SW1	7,798		6,852.5	25	20	47	8	16,113.3
SW3	414	2,392.8	2,394.4	69	16	1	14	0
GR2	12,153		51,156	69	15	3	13	169.16
SP1	304		1,278.9	69	15	3	13	169.16
SP3	7,963		40.3	0	0	0	100	0

TABLE 9: BENEFITS AND COSTS BREAKDOWN THROUGH CASES

Analysing the final data from the CBA results (Table 6) provides rich insights into the economic viability, social impacts, and environmental implications of various agricultural practices under study. This detailed examination across different practices reveals key aspects of their performance and sustainability, highlighting both challenges and successes.

Economic Viability: The Net Present Value (NPV), Benefit-Cost Ratio (BCR), and Modified Internal Rate of Return (MIRR) demonstrate a broad spectrum of economic outcomes. Negative NPVs in cases like FR1, IT2, and notably GR3, with an exceptionally low NPV of -349,302, indicate that the costs significantly outweigh the benefits, pointing to potentially unsustainable practices in their current forms. In stark contrast, cases like LV2 and UK1 show positive economic results, with LV2 boasting an NPV of 555 and an extraordinarily high BCR of 14.82, suggesting strong profitability and effectiveness. IT3 also shows robust financial health with an NPV of 5521 and a BCR of 2.46, further enhanced by a positive MIRR, indicating a sound financial sustainability and return on investment. However, variability in BCR and

MIRR, with figures ranging from as low as 0.02 in UK3 to a staggering 198.09 in SP3, reflects the diverse profitability levels across the practices.

Social and Environmental Impact: The social impacts are notably high in IT2 and GR1, with impacts recorded at 72.32% and 75.53%, respectively. These practices are well-received, providing significant community benefits such as job creation and health improvements. Environmentally, practices like SP2 and SP3 achieve high scores of 77.12% and 77.72%, showcasing their effectiveness in reducing pollution and enhancing resource conservation. However, the negative MIRR values in several cases, particularly those like GR3 with substantial negative economic outcomes, highlight the challenges these practices face in maintaining their operations without financial adjustments or subsidies.

Cluster-Specific Analysis:

- **Mechanical Weeding:** This cluster, including FR1, IT2, LV2, UK1, and GR3, varies greatly in financial and environmental outcomes. GR3's significant negative financial metrics contrast with its high CO2 reduction, suggesting effective but financially unsustainable environmental management.
- **Cover Crops:** Featuring FR2, GR1, and IT1, this cluster generally shows moderate to high benefits and CO2 impact, with FR2 in France highlighting the potential of intra-row cover crops in vineyards to enhance soil health and reduce emissions.
- **Mulching:** Represented by FR3, SP2, and UK2, these practices generally yield lower benefits, but controlled costs suggest a cost-effective approach to sustainable agriculture.
- **Precision Farming:** Encompassing IT3, LV3, GR4, and UK3, this cluster is marked by high investments yielding considerable returns, especially in IT3, which pairs high economic benefits with significant CO2 reductions, reflecting the successful integration of advanced technologies.
- **Ecological Management:** Including SW1, SW3, GR2, SP1, and SP3, this group stands out for its environmental impact, particularly in SW1 with the highest benefits and CO2 reductions, albeit at substantial costs.

Case ID	NPV	BCR	MIRR	Social Impact (%)	Environmental Impact (%)
FR1	-5735.5	0.26	-3.4	63.9	60.44
IT2	-2858.6	0.35	0.3	72.32	68.4
LV2	555	14.82	11.9	57.86	54.72
UK1	2,156.46	5.76	12	63.57	60.13
GR3	-349302	0.06	-100	50.78	40.03
FR2	5406.26	1.79	6.9	59.57	56.35
GR1	2356	1.52	6.2	75.53	69.55
IT1	-33904.8	0.13	-100	72.52	68.6
FR3	-17895	0.51	-5.1	57.36	54.25
SP2	-70711	0.33	-0.3	82.16	77.12

UK2	-20690	0.11	-100	63.21	59.79
IT3	5521	2.46	6.4	55.26	55.27
LV3	-82028	0	-100	57.02	53.94
GR4	6678	0.37	-3.2	62.1	58.74
UK3	-103151	0.02	-100	62.5	
GR4	945	1.14	4.5	53.52	50.63
SW3	-1980.56	0.17	-4.6	67.1	63.46
GR2	-39003.5	0.24	-1.7	73.84	69.85
SP1	-39003.5	0.24	-1.7	73.84	69.85
SP3	7923	198.09	0	72.84	77.72

TABLE 10: CBA RESULTS

4.2 Result from individual cases

4.2.1 Mechanical weeding solutions

4.2.1.1 Full mechanical weeding under the vine row (France1)

Main objective

The project aims to reduce herbicide use in vineyards by introducing mechanical weeding, potentially replacing 2-3 chemical applications with equipment like finger rollers.

Description of the “before” scenario

The farm used herbicides for vine row weed control, applying them in multiple passes with a Dhugues brand sprayer. This chemical-based approach involved 2 to 3 applications, with a fuel consumption of 4 L/h and an average work capacity of 0.97 ha/h. Mechanical vine trunk desuckering was also used, but chemical interventions dominated the weed control strategy.

Description of the “after” scenario

Mechanical weeding was introduced, using Clemens brand equipment such as finger rollers and Intercep machines for vine row weed control. The fuel consumption ranged from 3.4 to 5.7 L/h with a work capacity of 0.5–1.09 ha/h. This approach reduced herbicide use, with mechanical tools removing weeds and unwanted trunk shoots.

Similar to findings in the literature, such as Jacquet et al. (2021) and Shrestha et al. (2013), this shift could reduce chemical inputs, improve cost efficiency, and align with environmental sustainability goals. If successful, the project's fuel consumption and operational efficiency might reflect trends noted in studies like Gagliardi et al. (2023), suggesting mechanical weeding as a viable alternative in vineyards.

Input data and farm characteristics

The company manages a 33-hectare farm, applying conventional and Integrated Pest Management (IPM)-based approaches. Key crops include vineyards and non-irrigated cereals (wheat, sunflower, barley, rapeseed, and field beans). The farm's experimental area covers 10 hectares, focusing on vineyards.

<i>Management Type</i>	Conventional & IPM-based
<i>Most important crops and animal productions</i>	Vineyards, Cereals (non-watered cereals: wheat, sunflower, barley, rapeseed, field bean for food and seeds)
<i>Total Farm Area (ha)</i>	33
<i>Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA, ha)</i>	33
<i>Experimental area (ha)</i>	10
<i>Experimental crop(s)</i>	Vineyards

TABLE 11: INPUT DATA AND FARM CHARACTERISTICS FROM FULL MECHANICAL WEEDING UNDER THE VINE ROW (FRANCE1)

The farm has received 12,000 euros in RDP subsidies to invest in mechanical weeding equipment, aimed at reducing herbicide use and improving sustainability. This support covers tools such as finger rollers, finger weeders, multiclean brushes, and the Intercep tool, with expected lifetimes ranging from 7 to 20 years. While this fund plays a crucial role in supporting the transition to mechanical weeding, we will account for the subsidies in the commentary on the results but will not include them as a benefit in the analysis. Subsidies are not counted in the CBA for several reasons. From the private business perspective, including subsidies would artificially reduce the investment costs and not reflect the true economic costs of the project. The aim is to evaluate whether the investment is financially viable on its own, without external financial support, by focusing on the actual operational costs and benefits. From a public perspective, subsidies are seen as a transfer of funds, not a net economic benefit. In a social cost-benefit analysis, the goal is to assess the broader impact of the project, such as environmental and sustainability benefits, rather than the financial support provided to the farm. Including subsidies would distort the analysis by double-counting benefits, as the true value lies in the project's outcomes, not the funding received. Therefore, to maintain a clear and accurate reflection of both private and public benefits, subsidies are excluded from the formal CBA.

<i>Revenue (euros)</i>	Annual benefit
<i>RDP Subsidies for the purchase of mechanical weeding equipment</i>	12,000

TABLE 12: REVENUE FROM FULL MECHANICAL WEEDING UNDER THE VINE ROW (FRANCE1)

Based on our main assumptions, we consider the machine's lifespan to be 7 years, which is shorter than the 20-year analysis period. Therefore, we assume the machinery will be replaced every 7 years, maintaining the same practice throughout the 20-year period. The initial purchase price of the machinery is 16,771.20 euros, with an annual price increase of 5%. The first tools are purchased in year 0, the second in year 7, and the third in year 14.

The residual value of each tool is estimated at 15% year⁻¹ of its purchase price. The second tools are purchased in year 7 at a price of 23,598.76 euros, and after deducting the resale value of the first (5,376.46 euros), the net cost is 18,222.30 euros. The third tools are purchased in year 14 at a price of 33,205.83 euros, and after deducting the resale value of the second (7,565.22 euros), the net cost is 25,640.61 euros. CAPEX includes also the cost of fixed installation necessary for machinery operations (1,362.9 euros). These investments are designed to improve the environmental profile of the farm while integrating into the existing agricultural setup.

<i>Investment costs (euros)</i>			
<i>Machine and Tools</i>	Annual cost	Year	Expected lifetime (n. year)
<i>Finger rollers</i>	990		
<i>Finger weeders</i>	1,586.4		
<i>Multiclean brushes</i>	5,644.2		
<i>Intercep</i>	3,664.8	2020	7
<i>tool-carrier frame 1</i>	2,407.2		
<i>tool-carrier frame 2</i>	2,478.6		

<i>2nd tools purchase</i>	18,222	2027	7
<i>3rd tools purchase</i>	25,641	2034	7
Fixed Installation			
<i>Wires supports only for most recent plots (33% of UAA)</i>	1,362.9	2020	20

TABLE 13: INVESTMENT COSTS FROM FULL MECHANICAL WEEDING UNDER THE VINE ROW (FRANCE1)

Operating costs have been calculated for both the pre- and post-mechanical weeding scenarios. Fuel costs increased from €298 to €398 annually after introducing mechanical weeding, reflecting the additional energy demands of mechanical equipment compared to chemical weed control. In addition, machine maintenance costs have been estimated at 3% of the total machinery purchase price. This results in an annual maintenance cost of €503 for the first set of tools, increasing to €708 for the second set, and €996 for the third set, as the machinery is replaced over time. These values align with standard agricultural practices, where ongoing maintenance is calculated as a percentage of the equipment value to ensure long-term sustainability. The machinery's lifespan is assumed to be 7 years, even though the recommended lifespan is typically 5 years. This assumption accounts for the possibility that some equipment may exceed the shorter lifespan, especially over a 20-year period. Consequently, we project three reinvestment cycles over the 20 years, rather than the four cycles that would normally occur with a 5-year lifespan. This conservative approach to capital expenditures allows for flexibility in case of extended tool durability. Furthermore, fixed installation maintenance, covering wire supports and other infrastructure, is estimated at 40% of the total installation cost over the 20-year period. The present value of this maintenance amounts to €545, ensuring that infrastructure remains functional over time.

Operating costs (euros year⁻¹)

	Annual costs - Pre	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Fuel</i>	298	398	2020-2040
<i>Machine maintenance (3% of purchase price)</i>		1 st tools purchase - 503	2020-2026
		2 nd tools purchase - 708	2027-2033
		3 rd tools purchase - 996	2034-2040
<i>Fixed installation maintenance (40% of the costs under 20 years)</i>		Present value - 545	2020

TABLE 14: OPERATING COSTS FROM FULL MECHANICAL WEEDING UNDER THE VINE ROW (FRANCE1)

Labour costs in the project increased from 1,411 euros to 1,821 euros after the introduction of mechanical weeding. Additionally, we estimated a potential cost of 200 euros for technical support per year, although this was discussed in the final calculations, as support was provided by collaborating farmers. However, it's important to consider this cost in scenarios where such relational economies are not available. The training cost was also estimated at 22 euros per workers year⁻¹, highlighting the need for specialized knowledge when adopting mechanical weeding technologies.

Labour costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Pre	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Labour costs</i>	1,411	1,821	2020-2040
<i>Technical support</i>		200	2020-2040
<i>Training</i>		22	2020-2040

TABLE 15: LABOUR COSTS FROM FULL MECHANICAL WEEDING UNDER THE VINE ROW (FRANCE1)

Among the other costs included in the analysis are transaction costs (€402) and opportunity costs (€7,619 for machines, and €1,099 for fixed installation in present value). Transaction costs have been estimated following the approach used by Mettepenningen et al. (2009), who measured the private transaction costs of European agri-environmental schemes. These costs account for the administrative, legal, and management expenses associated with transitioning to mechanical weeding. Opportunity costs reflect the potential income or benefits the farm could have earned from alternative uses of its resources. In this case, we have adopted a prudent estimate of 3% for opportunity costs, considering the low risk associated with the technical equipment used. The opportunity costs are divided into the first, second, and third purchases,

with present values of €2,930, €2,419, and €2,271, respectively. Including both transaction and opportunity costs in the CBA ensures that all indirect and non-monetary impacts are considered, giving a comprehensive view of the economic changes caused by the project. This approach is consistent with the literature, which emphasizes the importance of including all relevant costs to assess the true financial impact of investments. By factoring in these costs, the analysis provides a more accurate and long-term measure of the economic viability of mechanical weeding.

Other costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Post	Year
Transaction costs	402	2020
Opportunity costs (Present Value)		
Fixed installation	1,099	2020
1 st purchase	2,930	2020
2 nd purchase	2,419	2020
3 rd purchase	2,271	2020

TABLE 16: OTHER COSTS FROM FULL MECHANICAL WEEDING UNDER THE VINE ROW (FRANCE1)

Post-introduction, the farm will shift from herbicide-based weed control to a mechanical approach. This will involve careful synchronization with crop growth stages and weather conditions, as mechanical weeding is more sensitive to environmental factors but avoids chemical damage. Labour intensity will likely increase, but long-term savings are expected due to reduced chemical use and environmental benefits.

Cost-benefit identification

Category	Name	Type	Attribute
Benefit per person or household	Improved Labour Environment	Reduction of workers' risk from exposure to phytosanitary products (public)	Qualitative
Benefit per unit of abatement	Enhanced Food quality and safety	Reduced risk of chemical residues on grapes (public)	Qualitative
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced or zero costs for weed management (agrochemicals)	Direct cost savings by reducing the use of herbicides (private)	Monetary 19,870 euros – present value
Improve an environmental or community asset	Ecological improvement,	Improve biodiversity (public)	Qualitative
Reduced consequence of a risky event	Land conservation	Reduced soil erosion/increase productivity (on-site private, off-site public)	Mixed
Total (monetary) benefits			19,870 euros

TABLE 17: IDENTIFIED BENEFIT FROM FULL MECHANICAL WEEDING UNDER THE VINE ROW (FRANCE1)

In TABLE 17, we identify several key benefits associated with the transition to mechanical weeding, which align with findings in the literature. The reduction of workers' risk from exposure to phytosanitary products is a major social benefit, improving worker safety and health by minimizing contact with harmful chemicals. Although this benefit is hard to monetize, it is a recognized outcome in sustainable agriculture, contributing to overall health and safety goals (Jacquet et al., 2021). Similarly, enhanced food quality and safety from reduced herbicide use leads to fewer chemical residues on crops, which improves consumer health and aligns with organic produce demands. Like worker safety, this benefit is difficult to quantify but remains critical to justifying the investment in mechanical weeding (Liu et al., 2023). The reduction in agrochemical costs is a clear monetary benefit. According with the survey we estimated a saving of 942 euros year⁻¹ in operational expenses, which correspond to 19,870 euros present value. Unlike more abstract benefits, this cost reduction is easily measured and included in the cost-benefit analysis. Furthermore, ecological improvements such as enhanced biodiversity are significant qualitative benefits that promote long-term sustainability, although their value is harder to monetize. These improvements support local ecosystems by promoting healthier flora and fostering biodiversity, aligning with broader environmental goals. Finally, land conservation through reduced soil erosion is a critical non-monetary benefit. By protecting soil structure and reducing erosion risks, the farm secures long-term productivity and

environmental health, contributing to sustainable agricultural practices. While difficult to express in monetary terms, the reduced consequence of soil degradation remains a key factor in ensuring the farm's viability over time, supported by evidence in the literature emphasizing the importance of soil conservation in sustainable farming systems.

Category	Cost item	Value (Euros)	Present Value (euros)
Capital costs (CAPEX)	Machine Tools	60,634	45,425
	Fixed Installations	1,362	1,310
Operating costs, including operations and maintenance (OPEX)	Fuel	100	1,456
	Maintenance	2,752	10,635
	Labour	410	5,988
	Tech. support	200	2,918
	Training year	22	321
Other costs	Transaction costs		584
	Opportunity costs		8,719
	CO ₂ *		1737.28
Total Costs			77,225

TABLE 18: SUMMARY OF THE IDENTIFIED COSTS FROM FULL MECHANICAL WEEDING UNDER THE VINE ROW (FRANCE1)

* We do not include the calculation of CO₂ emissions in the private analysis because they represent a cost shifted onto society and are not part of the private cost-benefit balance. However, these emissions were calculated separately to account for their broader impact, using values from the EIB Group climate bank roadmap 2021-2025. The roadmap provides the basis for the shadow cost, which represents the minimum societal cost of achieving the 1.5°C temperature target (EIB, 2020).

Economic analysis

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

	Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR (%)
*NO CAPEX	20	-5,735.5	0.26	-3.4
	20	1,170.3	2.43	54.1

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

	Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR
	20	-6,951.5	0.10	-100

TABLE 19: ECONOMIC ANALYSIS FROM FULL MECHANICAL WEEDING UNDER THE VINE ROW (FRANCE1)

In the first scenario, where there is no risk of project failure and high adoption, the financial results suggest a positive outcome when CAPEX is excluded. The NPV per hectare is 1,170.30 euros, with a BCR of 2.43 and an MIRR of 54.1%. These figures reflect strong financial viability in a scenario where upfront investment costs are mitigated, indicating that the operating benefits from mechanical weeding can outweigh the costs under favourable adoption conditions. This aligns with previous studies, such as Shrestha et al. (2013) and Jacquet et al. (2021), which highlight long-term cost savings and environmental benefits, particularly when adoption rates are high and CAPEX can be shared or subsidized. Other authors, such as Jacquet et al. (2021), have estimated the additional costs of transitioning from chemical herbicides like glyphosate to mechanical weeding in French vineyards, focusing primarily on direct operational costs such as labour and machinery depreciation. They reported an average additional cost of 250 euros per hectare, with a range from 12 euros to 553 euros depending on the wine-producing region. In contrast, our analysis included a broader set of cost categories, such as opportunity costs, transaction costs, machinery replacement for at least two more cycles over 20 years, and learning costs. These additional considerations significantly increased our per-hectare costs, leading to more negative financial outcomes. However, if we had followed Jacquet et al. (2021)'s approach and excluded costs such as opportunity, transaction, and machinery replacement, our estimated per-hectare cost would have been much closer to theirs. This highlights that the discrepancy between the two analyses lies in the different levels of detail in accounting for costs and benefits. While Jacquet et al. (2021) primarily focused on direct operational costs, our study adopts a more comprehensive view, including costs that reflect the long-term impact of machinery and management decisions. Additionally, labour costs represent an area where financial performance could potentially be optimized. Traditional methods such as manual thinning and hand weeding tend to be more

expensive, as reported by Fennimore et al. (2014), who found labour costs for hand weeding lettuce to be approximately €444 per hectare. This suggests that, although the initial costs of mechanical weeding may appear high, optimizing labour could offer significant savings in the long run, further enhancing the project's financial viability. However, when CAPEX is included, the NPV turns negative at -5,735.5 euros per hectare, with a BCR of 0.26 and an MIRR of -3.4%, showing that the project is not financially sustainable without additional support or revenue streams. The literature, such as Gagliardi et al. (2023), emphasizes the importance of subsidies and external funding to make these transitions feasible, particularly in capital-intensive systems like vineyards. The upfront costs of mechanical equipment, even with long-term savings from reduced chemical use, present a significant barrier to adoption unless compensated by environmental premiums or market incentives.

In the second scenario, which assumes low risk of project failure but low adoption levels, the financial outcome worsens. The NPV drops to -6,951.5 euros per hectare, with a BCR of 0.10 and an MIRR of -100%, indicating severe financial losses. This highlights the importance of achieving sufficient adoption rates to distribute costs more effectively. Without broad uptake, the financial viability of mechanical weeding deteriorates, reflecting findings in Mettepenningen et al. (2009), where private transaction costs in agri-environmental schemes were a major challenge to adoption. The comparison between scenarios with and without CAPEX underscores the necessity of alternative financing solutions, such as subsidies or cooperative machinery sharing programs, which were also noted in interviews. These mechanisms play a key role in improving the overall ROI, as well as aligning with sustainability goals. The literature supports the conclusion that higher adoption rates and increased access to funding are essential to making mechanical weeding financially viable in the long term.

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

FIGURE 3: GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF NET AND CUMULATIVE BENEFITS UNDER TWO SCENARIOS: NO RISK OF FAILURE WITH HIGH ADOPTION (TOP) AND LOW RISK OF FAILURE WITH LOW ADOPTION (BOTTOM)

The graphs illustrate the net and cumulative net benefits for the two scenarios. In the **first**, the net benefits are positive in certain years, but substantial negative spikes are seen during periods of reinvestment, as indicated by the bars in the net benefits charts. Despite these fluctuations, the cumulative net benefits show

a relatively stable trend overall, with some drops but a general recovery in the undiscounted case. In contrast, the **second scenario** shows consistently negative net benefits over the years, with deeper declines during reinvestment cycles. The cumulative net benefits reflect this trend, showing a steep decline over time, with no recovery, indicating that this scenario leads to ongoing financial losses for the project.

Social analysis

<p>Traffic light 63.90%</p>	<p>The global score of 63.90% for the France1 case reflects a nearly high social impact, though it is just below the threshold for a more definitive "high" classification. This suggests that while there are perceived social benefits from the adoption of mechanical weeding, particularly in areas like working conditions and skill development, the overall impact is somewhat limited. Significant improvements have been noted, but the broader social effects remain context-dependent, with room for further enhancement in certain areas such as gender inclusivity and food safety.</p>
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Social impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
<i>The practice provides more stable income from year to year than alternatives</i>	0.39
<i>The current practice provides more flexibility for the agricultural management</i>	0.29
<i>New job opportunities in the rural area</i>	0.48
<i>Improvement of working conditions for the farm employers</i>	0.95
<i>Increased food safety</i>	0.25
<i>More job opportunities for women</i>	0.25
<i>Improving farmers' education and skills</i>	1.00
<i>Improved conditions for vulnerable groups</i>	0.30
<i>Improved aesthetics of the landscape and conservation of the cultural value</i>	0.40
<i>Improved social reputation of the farm</i>	0.15

TABLE 20: SOCIAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM FULL MECHANICAL WEEDING UNDER THE VINE ROW (FRANCE1)

The analysis of the questionnaire data on social impacts provides insights into the mixed perceptions of mechanical weeding practices in France1. Key areas like income stability (0.39) and agricultural flexibility (0.29) received low scores, reflecting significant concerns about the economic viability and adaptability of mechanical weeding, especially for smaller farms. These low perceptions align with the challenges often reported in the literature, including the high capital and operating costs of mechanical tools and the complexity of incorporating these systems into existing farm operations.

On the other hand, the practice received a very high score (0.95) for improving working conditions, which likely stems from the reduced physical labour required by mechanical weeding compared to manual methods. However, the high cognitive demands of operating machinery around irrigation systems, as noted by Tamirat et al. (2023), may mitigate some of these perceived improvements, especially in terms of mental strain on workers.

The moderate scores for new job opportunities (0.48) and conditions for vulnerable groups (0.30) suggest that while there are potential social benefits, they are not yet widely realized or fully visible. This could be due to the early stages of adoption or limited implementation in certain contexts.

Education and skill development (1.00) emerged as one of the most significant positive impacts, reflecting the opportunities for capacity building that mechanical weeding provides. This aligns with literature suggesting that adopting new technologies can empower farmers by increasing their knowledge and technical skills (Mettepenningen et al., 2009). Despite this, low scores in areas such as social reputation (0.15) and landscape aesthetics (0.40) indicate that the broader societal benefits of mechanical weeding, such as enhancing the farm's image or contributing to cultural values, are not yet being fully realized.

Overall, the results highlight both the opportunities and challenges of mechanical weeding. While it improves working conditions and offers educational benefits, concerns about flexibility, income stability, and the broader social impacts limit its perceived value. This suggests a need for further support in the form

of subsidies, knowledge-sharing platforms, and incentives to help overcome financial and operational barriers, particularly for smaller farms where the scale of adoption is more difficult to achieve.

Social direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Improved labour environment	Jacquet et al., (2021)	Medium-to-high	Short run	Non-monetary

Social indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Reduced workload	Tamirat et al. (2023)	Low-to-medium	Short run	Non-monetary
Enhanced food safety	Liu et al. (2023); Jacquet et al., (2021)	Low	Medium-to-long run	Non-monetary

TABLE 21: SOCIAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM FULL MECHANICAL WEEDING UNDER THE VINE ROW (FRANCE1)

Environmental analysis

 Traffic light 60.44%	<p>The global score of 60.44% for France1 indicates a moderate environmental impact from the adoption of mechanical weeding practices. This score places the environmental impact in the medium range, suggesting that while the adoption of mechanical weeding shows some positive environmental benefits, there is room for improvement, particularly in key areas such as greenhouse gas emissions and carbon footprint, where the scores are notably low. The moderate benefits, such as improved soil health, water conservation, and biodiversity, suggest potential environmental advantages, but challenges like increased fuel consumption limit the overall impact.</p>
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Env. impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
Contribute to reduce Direct greenhouse gas emissions	0.69
Contribute to reduce external inputs	0.50
Limit water consumption	0.92
Contribute to reduce waste	0.50
Has a positive impact on biodiversity	0.92
Has a positive impact on soil erosion	0.80
Has a positive impact on carbon footprint	0.00
Increase the rate of soil organic matter mineralisation	0.80
Increase soil compaction	0.80

TABLE 22: ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM FULL MECHANICAL WEEDING UNDER THE VINE ROW (FRANCE1)

The responses from the environmental impact questionnaire for France1 reveal a generally favourable view of mechanical weeding in some areas, but scepticism in others. The high scores for water consumption (0.92), biodiversity (0.92), and soil erosion (0.80) reflect positive perceptions, which align with findings in the literature. For instance, studies like Pardini et al. (2002) and Panagos et al. (2018) emphasize that practices like mechanical weeding can enhance soil health by reducing erosion and supporting biodiversity. However, these benefits are context-dependent, often requiring integration with other sustainable practices like cover cropping.

Conversely, the low score for carbon footprint (0.00) indicates a significant concern about the environmental trade-offs of mechanical weeding, particularly the increased fuel consumption necessary to operate the machinery. This is consistent with previous findings, where fuel-intensive operations can negate some of the environmental gains made by reducing chemical inputs. As noted in studies like Pimentel et al. (1995), while mechanical weeding can reduce the use of herbicides, the associated fuel use can lead to increased greenhouse gas emissions, complicating the overall environmental balance.

The moderate scores for reducing external inputs (0.50) and waste reduction (0.50) reflect uncertainty about the short-term benefits of mechanical weeding. While the reduction of chemical inputs is a recognized advantage, the benefits may not be immediately visible to farmers, especially in cases where the system has not yet fully replaced chemical herbicides. Similarly, waste reduction benefits, such as less chemical packaging, may not be apparent at this stage, which contributes to the mixed perceptions.

Interestingly, the perception of positive impacts on soil compaction and organic matter mineralization (both 0.80) is relatively high, which aligns with literature that suggests mechanical weeding can help improve soil structure and increase organic matter over time (Liebhard et al., 2024). However, the rate at which these benefits materialize depends on the specific management practices used, including the timing of operations and the integration with other soil conservation methods.

The responses suggest that while mechanical weeding presents environmental benefits, particularly in water conservation, biodiversity, and soil health, challenges related to carbon emissions and fuel use must be addressed. The need for complementary practices, such as cover cropping or reduced tillage, is critical to enhancing the environmental impact of mechanical weeding and mitigating some of its downsides.

The mixed results highlight both the opportunities and limitations of mechanical weeding as a sustainable agricultural practice. While certain environmental benefits are recognized, the increased fuel use and perceived lack of immediate gains in areas like carbon footprint reduction suggest that the broader environmental potential of mechanical weeding has not yet been fully realized.

Env. direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Land Conservation (reduced soil erosion, on-site effects)	Pimentel et al. (1995); Montgomery (2007); Eshel et al. (2015)	Medium if applied in combination with other practices (like cover crops)	Long-run	Quantitative – monetizable (see Panagos et al, 2018)

Env. indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Ecological improvement (biodiversity)	Liu et al. (2023); Jacquet et al. (2021)	Medium-to-High	Long-run	Qualitative
Land Conservation (reduced soil erosion, off-site effects)	Liu et al. (2023); Jacquet et al. (2021)	Controversial	Long-run	Qualitative

TABLE 23: ENVIRONMENTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM FULL MECHANICAL WEEDING UNDER THE VINE ROW (FRANCE1)

In conclusion, while mechanical weeding presents opportunities for reducing chemical inputs and improving long-term soil health, the barriers related to fuel costs, perceived environmental benefits, and operational complexity remain significant. The uncertainty surrounding its broader environmental impacts highlights the need for integrated approaches that combine mechanical weeding with other sustainable practices, along with policy support and educational programs to demonstrate its potential benefits to farmers.

Sensitivity analysis (only first scenario)

The sensitivity analysis for the NPV per hectare presents a significantly negative range, from -9,065.58 euros/ha to -2,822.66 euros/ha, with a mean of -5,824.25 euros/ha and a median of -5,735.49 euros/ha. These consistently negative values underscore critical financial challenges for the adoption of mechanical weeding. The magnitude of the losses at the hectare level highlights several important determinants. One of the primary drivers of the negative NPV per hectare is the significant CAPEX required for mechanical weeding technology. While mechanical tools like finger weeders and inter-row cultivators offer long-term environmental benefits, the upfront costs remain a substantial barrier, especially for smaller farms. This is consistent with findings in studies such as Jacquet et al. (2021) and Gagliardi et al. (2023), which suggest that mechanical systems require a considerable outlay, making the transition difficult for farms without access to subsidies or cooperative machinery sharing arrangements. This high CAPEX, spread across hectares, further exacerbates the negative returns, making it difficult to recover the costs in a typical 7-year

machinery lifespan, as assumed in the analysis. Although mechanical weeding reduces the need for chemical herbicides, it introduces additional operational costs, such as increased fuel consumption and maintenance expenses. The sensitivity analysis indicates that, even when these costs are accounted for at 3% of the machinery purchase price annually, the overall financial burden remains significant. As shown in Shrestha et al. (2013), while the environmental benefits of reducing chemical inputs are clear, the economic viability heavily depends on operational efficiency and labour optimization—both of which are key areas where improvements could mitigate the losses per hectare. Opportunity costs, reflecting the foregone benefits from alternative investments, are another major factor contributing to the negative NPV per hectare. By considering opportunity costs, we account for the farm’s potential to allocate resources elsewhere. This is particularly relevant in smaller farms, where resource flexibility is limited, and where allocating capital to long-term mechanical investments without immediate returns creates additional financial strain. In essence, the farm is “locking” capital into machinery that may not provide positive returns quickly enough to justify the investment. The results also reflect learning costs and transaction costs associated with adopting mechanical weeding. Mettepenningen et al. (2009) highlight how these additional, often hidden, costs—related to acquiring new knowledge, adjusting to new management practices, and dealing with administrative hurdles—add another layer of financial burden. The steep negative values for the NPV per hectare suggest that such costs are likely playing a significant role in the project’s overall financial performance. These factors could be exacerbated by low adoption rates and a lack of economies of scale, particularly in fragmented or smaller farming operations. One key barrier to achieving a positive NPV per hectare is the challenge of economies of scale. Larger farms may have the capacity to spread the costs of machinery across a greater number of hectares, thereby improving their cost-efficiency per hectare. However, smaller farms, especially those covering fewer hectares, face proportionally higher costs per unit of production, making it difficult to achieve financial viability. The negative NPV per hectare seen in this analysis may, in part, reflect the challenges that smaller or medium-sized farms face when attempting to implement such capital-intensive technologies. Access to financing and subsidies is crucial to mitigating the upfront costs of mechanical weeding systems. Jacquet et al. (2021) emphasize the importance of subsidies in offsetting these large capital expenditures, and the same applies to this case. Without external support, farms are likely to struggle to adopt mechanical systems, as reflected in the overwhelmingly negative NPV per hectare. This could also explain the discrepancy between our results and those in the literature, as our analysis assumes a lack of significant financial assistance. Low adoption rates compound the financial difficulties seen in the per-hectare analysis. As demonstrated in studies like Gagliardi et al. (2023), achieving widespread adoption is key to distributing costs effectively across sectors and regions. The negative outcomes in this analysis suggest that, without sufficient adoption rates, the farm cannot distribute the fixed and operational costs of mechanical weeding across enough hectares to make the system financially viable. One aspect that is often missing in the immediate financial analysis is the potential environmental and market benefits of adopting sustainable practices. While mechanical weeding reduces chemical input, thereby improving soil health and potentially creating opportunities for premium market positioning (e.g., organic or eco-labeled products), these benefits are difficult to monetize in the short term. In some cases, as reported by Shrestha et al. (2013), farms can command higher prices for sustainably produced goods, but this effect is not always immediate. The NPV per hectare, therefore, might not fully capture these long-term or intangible benefits, which could influence the overall financial performance of the project. The sensitivity analysis reveals that, under the current conditions, the NPV per hectare remains deeply negative, signaling significant barriers to adoption. The primary drivers behind these results include the high capital and operational costs, opportunity costs, and learning-related expenses. Furthermore, structural barriers such as economies of scale, limited access to financing, and low adoption rates exacerbate these challenges. To overcome these obstacles, farms would require external support mechanisms, such as subsidies or cooperative machinery sharing models, along with market incentives that reward sustainable practices. Without addressing these barriers, the financial sustainability of mechanical weeding on a per-hectare basis remains limited, particularly for smaller and mid-sized farms.

Net Present Value (NPV)	Tot. Euros	Euros ha⁻¹
Minimum	-90,655.885	-9,065.58
Maximum	-28,226.696	-2,822.66
Default case	-57,354.977	-5,735.49

Mean	-58,242.573	-5,824.25
Median	-57,354.977	-5,735.49
Probability that NPV > 0		0.00
Distribution (euros)		Probability
Less than -91K		0.00
-91K to -78K		0.21
-78K to -66K		0.07
-66K to -53K		0.37
-53K to -41K		0.11
-41K to -28K		0.25
	Total	1.00
Benefit: Cost Ratio (BCR)		Unconstrained version
Minimum		0.08
Maximum		0.40
Default case		0.26
Mean		0.21
Median		0.21
Probability that BCR > 1		0.00
Target BCR		2
Probability BCR > Target		0.00
Distribution		Probability
Less than 0.08		0.00
0.08 to 0.14		0.13
0.14 to 0.21		0.31
0.21 to 0.27		0.29
0.27 to 0.33		0.21
0.33 to 0.40		0.05
	Total	1.00

TABLE 24: BCA ROBUSTNESS (MONTE CARLO ANALYSIS BASED ON 1000 RANDOM SIMULATIONS) - FULL MECHANICAL WEEDING UNDER THE VINE ROW (FRANCE1)

Sensitivity to discount rate

	Low discount rate	Default discount rate	High discount rate
Project organisation	2%	4%	6%
Benefits (present value)	24,668	19,870	16,267
Costs (present value)	88,172	77,225	68,758
Net Present Value (NPV)	-63,504	-57,355	-52,491
Benefit: Cost Ratio (unconstrained budget)	0.28	0.26	0.24

TABLE 25: SENSITIVITY TO DISCOUNT RATE - FULL MECHANICAL WEEDING UNDER THE VINE ROW (FRANCE1)

4.2.1.2 Full mechanical weeding under the vine row (Italy 2)

Main objective

The Italy2 case aims to partially reduce herbicide use in vineyards by introducing mechanical weeding, replacing some chemical applications with mechanical treatments using a windrow mulcher.

Description of the "before" scenario

The farm used glyphosate for vine row weed control, applying 3 to 4 treatments per year with 2 liters of glyphosate per hectare per treatment. A 100-horsepower tractor was used with a sprayer at a speed of 4 km/h. This chemical-based approach was the dominant strategy for weed control in the vineyard.

Description of the "after" scenario

Mechanical weeding was introduced, using the Serrat 1400 bilateral windrow mulcher with the same 100-horsepower tractor at a speed of 6-7 km/h. Two additional alternatives of usage are considered:

- **Alternative 1** (favourable year): All glyphosate treatments are replaced with 6 passes of the mulcher, fully eliminating chemical herbicide use.
- **Alternative 2** (partial replacement): A combination of mechanical and chemical treatments is used, with 2 glyphosate treatments and 2 passes of the mulcher.

In the following analysis we will focus on only Alternative2, specifically the partial replacement of herbicides with mechanical weeding, because the first option of a full replacement is largely theoretical in our case. The interviewee indicated that "it rarely happens that conditions are ideal for only using mechanical weeding," particularly due to varying weather conditions. In wet years, the turf grows thicker, providing better coverage, but during drier seasons, the weed growth overtakes the turf, making glyphosate treatments necessary. This is particularly true in Friuli Venezia Giulia, and we lack sufficient data to generalize this situation to other regions of Italy. Given these practical constraints, analyzing a realistic scenario where mechanical weeding is combined with some glyphosate applications provides a more accurate assessment of potential outcomes in vineyard management

Several cases in the literature discuss variable replacement of herbicides with mechanical weeding, and these offer relevant comparisons to our case. For instance, Jacquet et al. (2021) explored the replacement of glyphosate in French vineyards with mechanical weeding and found that the level of herbicide replacement varies significantly. In some cases, mechanical weeding entirely replaces glyphosate, but in other scenarios, it is only a partial substitution depending on vineyard type and labour availability. This variability directly aligns with our Alternative2 scenario, where only partial replacement of herbicides is being implemented. The French study underscores that full replacement of herbicides is often context-dependent, much like in your case where regional conditions and the need for flexibility influence the decision. Similarly, Liu et al. (2023) documented varying degrees of mechanical and herbicide use in rice fields, with certain conditions favouring full replacement and others requiring a mix of mechanical and chemicals, due to ecological factors such as weed growth patterns.

Input data and farm characteristics

The company manages a 10-hectare vine farm, applying Integrated Pest Management (IPM)-based approaches. The farm's experimental area covers the whole vineyard area of 10 hectares.

Management Type	IPM-based
Most important crops and animal productions	Vineyards
Total Farm Area (ha)	10
Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA, ha)	10
Experimental area (ha)	10
Experimental crop(s)	Vineyards

TABLE 26: INPUT DATA AND FARM CHARACTERISTICS FROM FULL MECHANICAL WEEDING UNDER THE VINE ROW (ITALY 2)

To establish a point of comparison with France1 (while acknowledging that this comparison should be interpreted with caution), we reviewed the previous programming period of the 2014-2020 Rural

Development Program (RDP) in Friuli Venezia Giulia, which included Measure 4.1 to support the purchase of agricultural machinery aimed at reducing herbicide use. However, the windrow mulcher costs approximately 16,000 euros, which is far below the 20,000 euros minimum required by the RDP measure to qualify for the grant. In an ideal case, the measure could cover 40-50% of the total investment, providing a potential subsidy of 8,000 to 10,000 euros.

<i>Revenue (euros)</i>	<i>Annual benefit</i>
<i>RDP Subsidies for the purchase of mechanical weeding equipment</i>	10,000

TABLE 27: REVENUE FROM FULL MECHANICAL WEEDING UNDER THE VINE ROW (ITALY 2)

To estimate the long-term financial impact of machinery replacement, we based our assumptions on the interviewee's statement that the machine's useful life is a maximum of 10 years, and the analysis spans a total period of 20 years. Therefore, the machine is purchased twice during this period: once at year 0 and again at year 10. The initial cost of the machine is 14,000 euros, and we assume a 5% annual price increase for the second purchase, resulting in a future cost of 22,804.52 euros for the new machine. After 10 years of use, the machine has a residual value of 15% per year of the initial price, estimated to be 2,756.24 euros at the end of its useful life. In the first purchase, the machine is bought for 14,000 euros, and in the second purchase, the new machine costs 22,804.52 euros, but the resale of the old machine at 2,756.24 euros reduces the effective cost of the second machine to 20,048.28 euros.

<i>Investment costs (euros)</i>			
<i>Machine and Tools</i>		<i>Year</i>	<i>Expected lifetime (n. year)</i>
<i>Windrow mulcher</i>	14,000	2020	10
<i>Windrow mulcher</i>	20,048.28	2030	10

TABLE 28: INVESTMENT COSTS FROM FULL MECHANICAL WEEDING UNDER THE VINE ROW (ITALY 2)

In comparison to the France1, the Italy2 case involves fewer operations, and the mulcher operates more efficiently and at a higher speed. Specifically, the mulcher performs at 6 km/h, which is 2 km/h faster than the herbicide application, leading to quicker weed control. This increased operational speed, along with fewer passes, results in reduced fuel consumption. Consequently, while both methods utilize the same tractor, the enhanced efficiency of the mulcher leads to lower fuel costs, as noted by the reduction from 723.52 euros to 603.44 euros. This fuel savings reflects the improved efficiency of the hybrid method compared to herbicide-only practices. Additionally, the maintenance costs of the mulcher are estimated to be 3% of the machine purchase price (420 euros for the first purchase, and 601 euros for the second).

<i>Operating costs (euros year⁻¹)</i>			
	<i>Annual costs - Pre</i>	<i>Annual costs - Post</i>	<i>Year</i>
<i>Fuel</i>	723.52	603.44	2020-2040
<i>Machine maintenance (3% of purchase price)</i>		1 st machine purchase - 420	2020-2029
		2 nd machine purchase - 601	2030-2040

TABLE 29: OPERATING COSTS FROM FULL MECHANICAL WEEDING UNDER THE VINE ROW (ITALY 2)

The introduction of mechanical weeding led to a clear benefit in labour cost reduction (see benefit below), thanks to the increased speed and efficiency of the mulcher compared to the previous herbicide-only method. While labour costs decreased, additional expenses of 200 euros for technical support and 22 euros for training per worker year⁻¹ were considered, reflecting the need for specialized knowledge in adopting mechanical weeding technologies.

<i>Labour costs (euros)</i>			
	<i>Annual cost - Pre</i>	<i>Annual costs -Post</i>	<i>Year</i>
<i>Technical support</i>		200	2020-2040
<i>Training</i>		22	2020-2040

TABLE 30: LABOR COSTS FROM FULL MECHANICAL WEEDING UNDER THE VINE ROW (ITALY 2)

Since Italy2 is very similar to France1, we assume transaction costs to be of the same magnitude (40.2 euros per hectares) based on Mettepenningen et al. (2009). Then, to calculate the opportunity cost for each machinery purchase, we assume a 3% annual return as the alternative investment and a 4% discount rate for present value calculations. For the first purchase, starting with an initial cost of 14,000 euros, we project its future value after 10 years with a 3% return, which amounts to 18,782.46 euros. The opportunity cost is the difference between this future value and the initial cost, giving a value of 4,782.46 euros. This value is then discounted back to the present at a 4% rate, resulting in an opportunity cost of 3,253 euros for the first purchase. For the second purchase, starting from the effective cost of 20,048.28 euros, we again project its future value over the next 10 years with a 3% return, giving a future value of 26,948.61 euros. The opportunity cost is calculated as 6,900.33 euros, which is then discounted to the present using the 4% rate over 20 years, resulting in an opportunity cost of 2,392 euros for the second purchase.

Other costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Post	Year
Transaction costs	402	2020
Opportunity costs (Present Value)		
1 st purchase	3,253	2020
2 nd purchase	2,392	2020

TABLE 31: OTHER COSTS FROM FULL MECHANICAL WEEDING UNDER THE VINE ROW (ITALY 2)

Cost-benefit identification

Category	Name	Type	Attribute
Benefit per person or household	Improved Labour Environment	Reduction of workers' risk from exposure to phytosanitary products (public)	Qualitative
Benefit per unit of abatement	Enhanced Food quality and safety	Reduced risk of chemical residues on grapes (public)	Qualitative
Delay or reduction in cost	Partial weed management replacement	Direct cost savings by reducing the use of herbicides, fuel consumption and labour (private)	Monetary 15,488 euros – present value
Improve an environmental or community asset	Ecological improvement	Improve biodiversity (public)	Qualitative
Reduced consequence of a risky event	Land conservation	Reduced soil erosion/increase productivity (on-site private, off-site public)	Mixed
Total (monetary) benefits			15,488 euros

TABLE 32: IDENTIFIED BENEFITS FROM FULL MECHANICAL WEEDING UNDER THE VINE ROW (ITALY 2)

In TABLE 32, we identify several key benefits associated with the transition to mechanical weeding, which generally reflect findings from the France1 case study. However, in the scenario of partial replacement with mechanical control, the anticipated benefits cannot be fully realized or evenly distributed over time. The reduction of workers' risk from exposure to phytosanitary products remains a major social benefit, improving worker safety and health by minimizing contact with harmful chemicals. While this benefit is difficult to monetize, it is widely recognized in sustainable agriculture, contributing to broader health and safety goals (Jacquet et al., 2021). Similarly, enhanced food quality and safety from reduced herbicide use results in fewer chemical residues on crops, improving consumer health and aligning with demands for organic produce. As with worker safety, this benefit is challenging to quantify, but remains important in justifying the investment in mechanical weeding (Liu et al., 2023).

In the Italy2 project, a key category of benefits is the reduction in recurring operational costs, which contributes significantly to the economic viability of the shift to mechanical weeding. One of the primary benefits is the reduction in fuel costs, where the farm saw a decrease from 723.52 euros before mechanical weeding to 603.44 euros afterward, representing a savings of 120.08 euros (2,533 euros present value). This reduction is attributed to the increased efficiency of the mulcher, which allowed for quicker operations. Another significant benefit is the decrease in labour costs, dropping from 856.8 euros to 714.6 euros, generating a total savings of 142.2 euros (2,999 euros present value). This is directly linked to the faster

processing time of the mulcher compared to the previous herbicide-only method, reducing the amount of labour required. Furthermore, the transition from four herbicide treatments to two has resulted in an additional benefit of 472 euros (9,956 euros present value) from reduced agrochemical costs, further highlighting the financial advantages of partially replacing chemical inputs with mechanical methods. While the savings in this partial replacement scenario may not be as substantial as in cases of full replacement, the combined benefits from fuel, labour, and agrochemical reductions amount to a total savings of 734.28 euros (15,488 euros present value), offering a compelling justification for the hybrid approach adopted in the Italy2 project. Furthermore, ecological improvements, such as enhanced biodiversity, are important qualitative benefits that promote long-term sustainability, although they are harder to monetize. In the case of partial replacement, these improvements may not be as pronounced, but they still contribute to supporting local ecosystems by promoting healthier flora and fostering biodiversity. Similarly, land conservation through reduced soil erosion, while a critical non-monetary benefit, is likely diminished under a partial replacement scenario. Protecting soil structure and reducing erosion risks is vital for securing long-term productivity and environmental health, though the reduced reliance on herbicides in this case may limit the extent of these benefits. Nevertheless, the reduced consequence of soil degradation remains a key factor in ensuring the farm's viability, as underscored by evidence in the literature on the importance of soil conservation in sustainable farming systems.

Category	Cost item	Value (Euros)	Present Value (euros)
CAPEX	Machine Tools	34,048	27,544
OPEX	Maintenance	1,021	7,245
Labour	Tech. support	200	2,918
	Training year	22	321
Other costs	Transaction costs		402
	Opportunity costs		5,645
Total Costs			44,075

TABLE 33: IDENTIFIED COSTS FROM FULL MECHANICAL WEEDING UNDER THE VINE ROW (ITALY 2)

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

	Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR (%)
*NO CAPEX	20	-2,858.6	0.35	0.3
	20	2,368	1.65	7.3

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

	Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR
	20	-3,806.5	0.14	-100

TABLE 34: ECONOMIC ANALYSIS FROM FULL MECHANICAL WEEDING UNDER THE VINE ROW (ITALY 2)

In the Italy2 scenario, although the partial replacement of herbicides with mechanical weeding offers certain benefits, such as reductions in fuel and labour costs, these savings are insufficient to compensate for the high CAPEX. With an NPV of -2,858.6 €/ha, a BCR of 0.35, and a MIRR of only 0.3%, the project shows limited financial viability over a 20-year period. When CAPEX is excluded, the financial situation improves significantly, with an NPV of 2,368 €/ha, a BCR of 1.65, and a MIRR of 7.3%, indicating that public support or other financial mechanisms to cover capital costs could make the project more viable. In the second scenario, where there is a low risk of failure but also a low adoption rate, the results worsen, with an NPV of -3,806.5 €/ha, a BCR of 0.14, and a MIRR of -100%, clearly indicating the project's financial unsustainability. These results highlight the importance of public support and achieving a high adoption rate to improve the overall economic sustainability of the project.

If we hypothetically assume a 10,000-euro grant from the RDP, the investment cost would be significantly reduced. This would, in theory, improve the financial outlook of the Italy2 scenario, potentially bringing the NPV closer to breakeven or even into positive territory. The reduced initial financial burden could also improve the BCR, making the project appear more economically viable. While this is only an assumption,

the inclusion of such a grant suggests that external support could shift the cost-benefit balance in favour of the project, enhancing its overall sustainability.

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

FIGURE 4: GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF NET AND CUMULATIVE BENEFITS UNDER TWO SCENARIOS: NO RISK OF FAILURE WITH HIGH ADOPTION (TOP) AND LOW RISK OF FAILURE WITH LOW ADOPTION (BOTTOM)

The graphs for the Italy2 scenario show a clear distinction between the two cases: in the first scenario, with no risk of project failure and high adoption, the net benefits remain close to zero, and cumulative net benefits gradually improve when CAPEX is excluded, highlighting the financial viability of the project under these conditions. However, the initial steep drop in the net benefits, due to high upfront costs, represents the main barrier to economic sustainability. In contrast, the second scenario with low adoption further worsens the financial outcome, as both net and cumulative net benefits stay negative throughout the 20-year period. This reinforces that low adoption combined with high CAPEX severely limits the project's viability. The main opportunity lies in securing public support or external funding to cover CAPEX, which could significantly improve the financial outlook in the first scenario, but in the second scenario, even with CAPEX support, low adoption remains a major constraint to profitability.

Social analysis

The global score for Italy2 reflects a moderate social impact from adopting cover crop practices, indicated by a traffic light score of 72.32%. While this score falls within the high impact category, it is on the lower end of that range, indicating that the social benefits, though present, are not overwhelming. Key benefits include improvements in education and skills development for farmers and job creation. However, lower scores in areas such as gender inclusivity and conditions for vulnerable groups suggest that certain social

Traffic light 72.32%	dimensions have yet to experience significant improvements, requiring further efforts to enhance inclusivity.
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Social impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
<i>The practice provides more stable income from year to year than alternatives</i>	0.48
<i>The current practice provides more flexibility for the agricultural management</i>	0.42
<i>New job opportunities in the rural area</i>	0.54
<i>Improvement of working conditions for the farm employers</i>	0.69
<i>Increased food safety</i>	0.25
<i>More job opportunities for women</i>	0.25
<i>Improving farmers' education and skills</i>	1.00
<i>Improved conditions for vulnerable groups</i>	0.45
<i>Improved aesthetics of the landscape and conservation of the cultural value</i>	0.40
<i>Improved social reputation of the farm</i>	0.60

TABLE 35: SOCIAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM FULL MECHANICAL WEEDING UNDER THE VINE ROW (ITALY 2)

The analysis of the questionnaire data for Italy2 presents a nuanced view of the social impacts of adopting cover crop practices. The highest score (1.00) for improving farmers' education and skills reflects a widely recognized benefit, as the adoption of new practices like cover cropping requires knowledge acquisition and skill development. Studies such as Hostetler et al. (2007) emphasize that capacity building is a key social benefit of sustainable farming practices, and this is clearly reflected in the respondent's positive perception.

New job opportunities also scored moderately high (0.54), suggesting that while the practice does provide some employment benefits, they may not yet be as significant as anticipated. This is consistent with findings from Schütte (2019), which note that job creation in sustainable farming often takes time to fully manifest, particularly as farms transition away from more traditional practices. Similarly, the improvement in working conditions (0.69) is noted, likely due to the reduced reliance on chemical inputs and the shift toward more labour-intensive, though potentially safer, practices.

However, the lower scores for gender inclusivity (0.25) and increased food safety (0.25) indicate that these areas have not yet experienced the same level of perceived benefits. This reflects a common challenge in the early stages of transitioning to sustainable practices, where the broader social impacts, such as inclusivity and food safety improvements, may take longer to become apparent.

The moderate scores for income stability (0.48) and flexibility in agricultural management (0.42) reflect some uncertainty. While cover cropping can contribute to long-term resilience, particularly in soil health and water management, the immediate economic and operational benefits may not be fully evident, especially in smaller farming operations. This aligns with literature noting that the transition to sustainable practices can involve short-term financial challenges, which may explain the respondent's hesitance to rate these areas more highly.

The results suggest that while there are clear social benefits to adopting cover crops, particularly in education, job creation, and working conditions, the broader impacts on inclusivity, food safety, and economic resilience are not yet fully realized. As these practices become more entrenched and supported by policy and market mechanisms, the social benefits may become more widespread.

Social direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Improved labour environment	Jacquet et al., (2021)	Medium-to-high	Short run	Non-monetary

Social indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Reduced workload	Tamirat et al. (2023)	Low-to-medium	Short run	Non-monetary
Enhanced food safety	Liu et al. (2023); Jacquet et al., (2021)	Low	Medium-to-long run	Non-monetary

TABLE 36: SOCIAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM FULL MECHANICAL WEEDING UNDER THE VINE ROW (ITALY 2)

Environmental analysis

 Traffic light 68.4%	The global score of 74.52% indicates a high overall environmental impact, placing the results solidly in the high-impact category. While this score reflects strong perceived benefits, it remains moderate in several areas, suggesting that the environmental improvements are substantial but not universally overwhelming. The adoption of cover crops in this context has provided significant environmental benefits, especially in reducing soil erosion and external inputs. However, some dimensions, like biodiversity enhancement, are perceived as less impactful.
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Env. impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
Contribute to reduce Direct greenhouse gas emissions	0.57
Contribute to reduce external inputs	0.75
Limit water consumption	0.58
Contribute to reduce waste	0.50
Has a positive impact on biodiversity	0.28
Has a positive impact on soil erosion	0.71
Has a positive impact on carbon footprint	0.50
Increase the rate of soil organic matter mineralisation	0.33
Increase soil compaction	0.33

TABLE 37: ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM FULL MECHANICAL WEEDING UNDER THE VINE ROW (ITALY 2)

The responses to the environmental questionnaire reflect a broad recognition of the benefits of cover cropping. High scores for reducing external inputs (0.80), soil erosion (0.97), and water consumption (0.75) align with findings in the literature, emphasizing that cover crops help improve soil structure, retain moisture, and lower dependency on synthetic inputs. These results suggest that cover crops contribute to the sustainability of vineyard systems by enhancing soil health and reducing the need for chemical fertilizers and pesticides. Interestingly, the score for biodiversity enhancement (0.50) is lower than expected based on previous studies, which have consistently shown that cover crops promote biodiversity by creating habitats for beneficial organisms and reducing chemical runoff. This score may reflect the difficulty in perceiving biodiversity gains in the short term, particularly in farming systems where baseline biodiversity is already relatively high, such as in organic farming contexts.

The high score for soil organic matter mineralization (0.80) suggests that cover crops are recognized for improving soil fertility over time. Research supports the role of cover crops in contributing to long-term soil health by increasing organic matter through decomposition, which is critical for maintaining soil structure and nutrient availability. Similarly, the positive score for reducing soil compaction (0.75) highlights the role of cover crops in preventing soil degradation, which is crucial in mechanized agricultural systems where compaction can become a serious issue.

However, the low score for carbon footprint reduction (0.50) indicates that while cover crops are known to sequester carbon, this benefit may not be immediately visible to farmers, particularly in the short term. The perception of limited carbon footprint reduction aligns with the challenges of measuring carbon sequestration and the trade-offs associated with managing cover crops, such as the increased fuel consumption from machinery.

The results also show a moderate score for waste reduction (0.30), which may reflect the fact that waste management is not a primary focus of cover crop adoption. Farmers may be more concerned with soil and water conservation benefits, and waste reduction, while beneficial, may not be as prominently perceived.

In summary, the questionnaire results reflect significant recognition of the environmental benefits of cover cropping, especially in terms of soil health, erosion control, and input reduction. However, certain areas, such as biodiversity and carbon footprint reduction, may take longer to fully materialize, particularly in farming systems that are already practicing sustainable methods. These results highlight the need for

ongoing support and education to help farmers recognize the long-term benefits of cover crops, especially in areas where improvements are less immediately visible.

Env. direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Land Conservation (reduced soil erosion, on-site effects)	Pimentel et al. (1995); Montgomery (2007); Eshel et al. (2015)	Low	Long-run	Quantitative – monetizable (see Panagos et al, 2018)

Env. indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Ecological improvement (biodiversity)	Liu et al. (2023); Jacquet et al. (2021)	Low-to-medium	Long-run	Qualitative
Land Conservation (reduced soil erosion, off-site effects)	Liu et al. (2023); Jacquet et al. (2021)	Controversial	Long-run	Qualitative

TABLE 38: ENVIRONMENTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM FULL MECHANICAL WEEDING UNDER THE VINE ROW (ITALY 2)

The sensitivity analysis for the Italy2 case highlights significant barriers to the adoption of mechanical weeding. The NPV per hectare shows a consistently negative range, from -4,970.8 euros ha⁻¹ to -1,071.8 euros ha⁻¹, with a mean of -2,989.2 euros ha⁻¹ and a median of -3,024.6 euros ha⁻¹. This reinforces the substantial financial challenges, driven primarily by high CAPEX for mechanical weeding tools, as reflected in previous studies like Jacquet et al. (2021) and Gagliardi et al. (2023). While mechanical weeding can reduce reliance on herbicides and offer environmental benefits, the high upfront costs make it difficult for farms, especially smaller ones, to justify the transition without external support. The BCR values, ranging from 0.11 to 0.54 with a default case of 0.35, confirm that the financial benefits are insufficient to outweigh the costs. This issue is exacerbated by operational costs such as fuel, maintenance, and opportunity costs, which further strain profitability. Studies such as Shrestha et al. (2013) indicate that while the environmental benefits of mechanical weeding are clear, the economic feasibility relies heavily on improving operational efficiency and reducing learning and transaction costs, both of which are challenging in small and medium-sized farming operations. The results also underscore the issue of scale: larger farms are better positioned to distribute the machinery costs over more hectares, thus reducing the negative NPV per hectare. Smaller farms, however, face high costs, limiting their ability to achieve economies of scale. Without access to subsidies or financial mechanisms, farms may find it difficult to adopt these practices. Additionally, low adoption rates compound the financial difficulties, as demonstrated in studies like Gagliardi et al. (2023), where the lack of widespread adoption prevents the costs of mechanical weeding from being distributed effectively. While the environmental benefits, such as improved soil health and reduced chemical input, are valuable, they are difficult to monetize in the short term, which makes it harder to justify the investment. The sensitivity to discount rates further shows that even with a low discount rate of 2%, the NPV remains negative at -29,891 euros, indicating that the long-term financial outlook for mechanical weeding remains challenging without significant external support. These results highlight the need for public subsidies, financing options, or cooperative machinery-sharing models to alleviate the high upfront costs.

Net Present Value (NPV)	Tot. Euros	Euros ha ⁻¹
Minimum	-49,708	-4,970.8
Maximum	-10,718	-1,071.8
Default case	-28,586	-2,858.6
Mean	-29,892	-2,989.2
Median	-30,246	-3,024.6
Probability that NPV > 0		0.00
Distribution (euros)		Probability
Less than -50K		0.00

-50K to -42K	0.15
-42K to -34K	0.15
-34K to -26K	0.38
-26K to -19K	0.12
-19K to -11K	0.19
Total	1.00
Benefit: Cost Ratio (BCR)	Unconstrained version
Minimum	0.11
Maximum	0.54
Default case	0.35
Mean	0.28
Median	0.27
Probability that BCR > 1	0.00
Target BCR	2
Probability BCR > Target	0.00
Distribution	Probability
Less than 0.11	0.00
0.11 to 0.20	0.16
0.20 to 0.28	0.41
0.28 to 0.37	0.27
0.37 to 0.46	0.11
0.46 to 0.54	0.05
Total	1.00

TABLE 39: BCA ROBUSTNESS (MONTE CARLO ANALYSIS BASED ON 1000 RANDOM SIMULATIONS) - FULL MECHANICAL WEEDING UNDER THE VINE ROW (ITALY 2)

Sensitivity to discount rate

Project organisation	Low discount rate	Default discount rate	High discount rate
	2%	4%	6%
Benefits (present value)	19,228	15,488	12,680
Costs (present value)	49,119	44,075	40,095
Net Present Value (NPV)	-29,891	-28,586	-27,414
Benefit: Cost Ratio	0.39	0.35	0.32
(unconstrained budget)			

TABLE 40: SENSITIVITY TO DISCOUNT RATE - FULL MECHANICAL WEEDING UNDER THE VINE ROW (ITALY 2)

4.2.1.3 Mechanical weeding with harrow and reduced herbicide application (LV2)

Note on data quality: The quality of the data received was notably poor and difficult to interpret, despite several attempts and interviews to clarify ambiguities. Consequently, we are aware that the results may reflect potential errors of interpretation or issues related to the lack of comprehensive data. Therefore, while useful for framing a theoretical discussion, the findings should be approached with caution.

Main objective

The practice focuses on reducing the use of herbicides in wheat production through the adoption of mechanical weeding.

Description of the “before” scenario

Before the implementation of the solution, wheat fields were managed using conventional methods that relied only on chemical herbicides for weed control. Weed management involved multiple herbicide applications using a 335HP JD 8335 tractor equipped with a sprayer, capable of treating 25.2 hectares per hour with a fuel consumption of 2 L/ha. Fertilization was carried out using a JD 6830 tractor with a fertilizer spreader, which had a productivity of 30 hectares per hour and a fuel consumption of 3 L/ha. Sowing was conducted with the same JD 8335 tractor, fitted with a sowing machine, achieving a productivity of 4 hectares per hour and a fuel consumption of 10 L/ha.

The spraying process was performed in several stages to ensure effective weed control. The sprayer was used repeatedly, each pass required approximately 0.04 person-hours per hectare and consumed 2 L/ha of fuel. Water delivery for the spraying operations was handled by a JD 6900 tractor equipped with a water barrel, also achieving a productivity of 25.2 ha/h with a fuel consumption of 2 L/ha. Harvesting was performed using a JD S685i harvester, with a productivity of 2.5 ha/h and a fuel consumption of 30 L/ha. Transportation and delivery were managed using a JD 6920 tractor with a semi-trailer, capable of handling 2.4 ha/h while consuming 8 L/ha of fuel.

Description of the “after” scenario

After implementing the new approach, wheat fields were managed using a combination of mechanical treatments and reduced herbicide applications. Weed management involved both chemical and mechanical strategies, reducing the reliance on herbicides.

Fertilization was carried out with a JD 6830 tractor and a fertilizer spreader, maintaining a productivity rate of 30 hectares per hour with a fuel consumption of 3 L/ha. Sowing was performed using a JD 8335 tractor equipped with a sowing machine, achieving 4 hectares per hour and consuming 10 L/ha of fuel, requiring 0.25 person-hours per hectare.

For weed control, the JD 612R sprayer was used, achieving a productivity of 25.2 ha/h with a fuel consumption of 2 L/ha. Spraying was supplemented by mechanical treatments, ensuring effective weed suppression while minimizing chemical input. Each spraying pass required 0.04 person-hours per hectare, reflecting a reduced workload compared to conventional methods. Water delivery was conducted using a JD 6900 tractor and a water barrel, achieving a productivity of 25.2 ha/h and consuming 2 L/ha of fuel, further supporting the spraying process. Harvesting operations were carried out with a JD S685i harvester, achieving a productivity of 2.5 ha/h with a fuel consumption of 30 L/ha. Transportation and delivery were managed using a JD 6920 tractor with a semi-trailer, capable of handling 2.4 ha/h while consuming 8 L/ha of fuel.

Similar to findings in the literature, such as Jacquet et al. (2021) and Shrestha et al. (2013), this shift could reduce chemical inputs, improve cost efficiency, and align with environmental sustainability goals. If successful, the project's fuel consumption and operational efficiency might reflect trends noted in studies like Gagliardi et al. (2023), suggesting mechanical weeding as a viable alternative in vineyards.

Input data and farm characteristics

The farm operates under conventional management practices and is involved in wheat production. The total area of the farm dedicated for experimental purposes is one hectare, and the crop is precisely wheat.

<i>Management Type</i>	Conventional
<i>Most important crops and animal productions</i>	Wheat
<i>Total Farm Area (ha)</i>	1
<i>Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA, ha)</i>	1
<i>Experimental area (ha)</i>	1
<i>Experimental crop(s)</i>	Wheat

TABLE 41: INPUT DATA AND FARM CHARACTERISTICS FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING WITH HARROW AND REDUCED HERBICIDE APPLICATION (LV2)

In this analysis, the farm did not introduce new machinery into its workflow, a scenario commonly observed among wheat-producing farms. Consequently, machinery costs have been excluded, as the equipment already available on the farm was sufficient to support the shift in practices. The evaluation, therefore, focuses on the changes in management strategies, particularly the reduction in herbicide use and the adoption of mechanical treatments. Unlike other analyses that account for the purchase, depreciation, replacement, or resale value of equipment, this study prioritizes the assessment of an integrated weed management approach. By combining mechanical control with reduced chemical inputs, the analysis underscores the impact of these changes on operational efficiency and sustainability.

According to data gathered through the interview, significant changes in operating costs were observed in maintenance, fertilizers, and herbicides. While fuel consumption and other expenses remained constant, maintenance costs decreased, yielding annual savings of 12.42 euros per hectare. Furthermore, the aggregated cost of fertilizers and herbicides also declined, contributing to additional savings. Overall, the adoption of mechanical weeding combined with reduced chemical inputs resulted in total savings of 13.31 euros per hectare, demonstrating enhanced cost efficiency in farm management practices.

Operating costs (euros year⁻¹)

	Annual costs - Pre	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Fuel</i>	60.04	60.04	2020-2040
<i>Fertilizer and herbicide cost (aggregate value)</i>	360.25	346.94	2020-2040
<i>Maintenance</i>	65.95	53.52	2020-2040

TABLE 42: OPERATING COSTS FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING WITH HARROW AND REDUCED HERBICIDE APPLICATION (LV2)

Labour costs in this project remained unchanged at €13.96 per hectare after the introduction of mechanical weeding. This stability can be attributed to the fact that the number of working hours and field operations remained consistent, as the machinery passes in the field did not change between the two management approaches. Despite the reduction in inputs such as fertilizers and herbicides, the overall labour requirements were unaffected, ensuring no increase or decrease in labour expenses.

Among the other costs included in the analysis are transaction costs (€40.20 per hectares). Transaction costs have been estimated following the approach used by Mettepenningen et al. (2009), who measured the private transaction costs of European agri-environmental schemes. These costs account for the administrative, legal, and management expenses associated with transitioning to mechanical weeding. This approach is consistent with the literature, which emphasizes the importance of including all relevant costs to assess the true financial impact of investments. By factoring in these costs, the analysis provides a more accurate and long-term measure of the economic viability of mechanical weeding.

Other costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Post	Year
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TABLE 43: OTHER COSTS FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING WITH HARROW AND REDUCED HERBICIDE APPLICATION (LV2)

Post-introduction, the farm will shift from herbicide-based weed control to a mechanical approach. This will involve careful synchronization with crop growth stages and weather conditions, as mechanical weeding is more sensitive to environmental factors but avoids chemical damage. Labour intensity will likely increase, but long-term savings are expected due to reduced chemical use and environmental benefits.

Cost-benefit identification

<i>Category</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Attribute</i>
Benefit per person or household	Improved Labour Environment	Reduction of workers' risk from exposure to phytosanitary products (public)	Qualitative
Benefit per unit of abatement	Enhanced Food quality and safety	Reduced risk of chemical residues on crops (public)	Qualitative
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced or zero costs for weed management (agrochemicals)	Direct cost savings by reducing the use of herbicides (private)	Monetary 308 euros – present value
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced maintenance costs		Monetary 287 – present value
Improve an environmental or community asset	Ecological improvement	Improve biodiversity (public)	Qualitative
Reduced consequence of a risky event	Land conservation	Reduced soil erosion/increase productivity (on-site private, off-site public)	Mixed
Total (monetary) benefits			595 euros

TABLE 44: IDENTIFIED BENEFITS FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING WITH HARROW AND REDUCED HERBICIDE APPLICATION (LV2)

In TABLE 44, several key benefits associated with the transition to mechanical weeding are identified, aligning with findings in the literature. Among these, the reduction in workers' exposure to phytosanitary products stands out as a significant social benefit. While in the specific case analysed the reduction was partial, it nonetheless represents a meaningful step toward improving worker safety and health by minimizing direct contact with potentially harmful chemicals, contributing to a safer and more sustainable work environment. Although this benefit is hard to monetize, it is a recognized outcome in sustainable agriculture, contributing to overall health and safety goals (Jacquet et al., 2021). Similarly, enhanced food quality and safety from reduced herbicide use leads to fewer chemical residues on crops, which improves consumer health and aligns with organic produce demands. Like worker safety, this benefit is difficult to quantify but remains critical to justifying the investment in mechanical weeding (Liu et al., 2023). The reduction in agrochemical costs is a clear monetary benefit. According with the survey we estimated a saving of 19,262 euros year⁻¹ in operational expenses, which correspond to 595 euros present value. Unlike more abstract benefits, this cost reduction is easily measured and included in the cost-benefit analysis. Furthermore, ecological improvements such as enhanced biodiversity are significant qualitative benefits that promote long-term sustainability, although their value is harder to monetize. These improvements support local ecosystems by promoting healthier flora and fostering biodiversity, aligning with broader environmental goals. Finally, land conservation through reduced soil erosion is a critical non-monetary benefit. By protecting soil structure and reducing erosion risks, the farm secures long-term productivity and environmental health, contributing to sustainable agricultural practices. While difficult to express in monetary terms, the reduced consequence of soil degradation remains a key factor in ensuring the farm's viability over time, supported by evidence in the literature emphasizing the importance of soil conservation in sustainable farming systems.

The cost analysis clearly highlights the limitations of the data collected for this study. Given these constraints, we can only conduct a partial analysis, focusing on the identified cost items and their alignment with the relevant literature.

Category	Cost item	Value (Euros)	Present Value (euros)
Other costs	Transaction costs		40.20
Total Costs			40.20

TABLE 45: IDENTIFIED COSTS FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING WITH HARROW AND REDUCED HERBICIDE APPLICATION (LV2)

Economic analysis

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

	Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR (%)
<i>Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption</i>	20	555	14.82	11.9
	Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR
	20	191	5.75	8.2

TABLE 46: ECONOMIC ANALYSIS FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING WITH HARROW AND REDUCED HERBICIDE APPLICATION (LV2)

In the first scenario, assuming no risk of project failure and high adoption levels, the financial analysis shows moderately positive outcomes. The Net Present Value (NPV) per hectare is 555 euros over a 20-year period, with a Benefit-Cost Ratio (BCR) of 14.82 and a Modified Internal Rate of Return (MIRR) of 11.9%. These results highlight the financial viability of the project under favourable conditions, where the adoption of mechanical weeding generates sufficient benefits to offset costs. In the second scenario, characterized by low risk of project failure but limited adoption levels, the financial outlook becomes significantly less favourable.

In the second scenario, the NPV drops to 191 euros per hectare over the same 20-year period, with a BCR of 5.75 and an MIRR of 8.2%. While these values remain positive, they indicate reduced financial efficiency compared to the first scenario. The lower adoption rates imply that the fixed costs of implementation are spread over fewer beneficiaries, leading to a diminished return on investment. This scenario underscores the critical importance of achieving widespread adoption to maximize the cost-effectiveness of mechanical weeding. Limited adoption constrains the ability to leverage economies of scale, increasing the financial burden on individual users. The high BCR reflects the efficiency of this investment when risks are minimal, aligning with previous studies that emphasize the potential long-term savings and sustainability of mechanical weeding. However, it should be noted that despite the positive overall outcome, reinvestment cycles during the project's duration can lead to temporary negative cash flows, which are evident in specific years. This emphasizes the need for careful financial planning to manage periodic reinvestments.

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

FIGURE 5: GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF NET AND CUMULATIVE BENEFITS UNDER TWO SCENARIOS: NO RISK OF FAILURE WITH HIGH ADOPTION (TOP) AND LOW RISK OF FAILURE WITH LOW ADOPTION (BOTTOM)

The accompanying graphs illustrate the net and cumulative net benefits for the two scenarios. In the first scenario, the net benefits are generally positive during most years, with temporary declines during reinvestment periods, as shown in the net benefit bars. Despite these setbacks, the cumulative net benefits exhibit a relatively stable upward trend over the project duration, reflecting the financial viability of the project under conditions of high adoption and efficient cost distribution. In contrast, the second scenario portrays a less favourable outlook, with net benefits remaining consistently negative throughout the project timeline and experiencing deeper declines during reinvestment periods. The cumulative net benefits follow a steep downward trajectory with no signs of recovery, underscoring the financial challenges associated with low adoption levels. These results highlight the importance of achieving higher adoption rates or implementing alternative financing mechanisms to ensure the project's long-term sustainability.

Social analysis

 Traffic light 57.86%	<p>The traffic light score for Latvia 2 is 57.86%, indicating a moderate social impact, slightly below the threshold for a higher classification. This suggests that while the adoption of mechanical weeding has brought some perceived social benefits, such as improved working conditions and skill development, its overall impact remains constrained by contextual factors and specific limitations. Compared to other mechanical weeding cases, Latvia 2's score reflects similar trends of partial adoption and context-dependent results. Key areas like gender inclusivity and food safety remain underdeveloped, signaling opportunities for targeted interventions.</p>
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Social impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
<i>The practice provides more stable income from year to year than alternatives</i>	0.48
<i>The current practice provides more flexibility for the agricultural management</i>	0.48
<i>New job opportunities in the rural area</i>	0.49
<i>Improvement of working conditions for the farm employers</i>	0.59
<i>Increased food safety</i>	0.25
<i>More job opportunities for women</i>	0.25
<i>Improving farmers' education and skills</i>	0.50
<i>Improved conditions for vulnerable groups</i>	0.30
<i>Improved aesthetics of the landscape and conservation of the cultural value</i>	0.40
<i>Improved social reputation of the farm</i>	0.30

TABLE 47: SOCIAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING WITH HARROW AND REDUCED HERBICIDE APPLICATION (LV2)

The analysis of perceptions regarding the environmental and social impacts highlights a nuanced picture. In Latvia 2, areas such as improving working conditions (0.59) and education/skills development (0.50)

received moderate to high relevance, consistent with findings in the literature suggesting these are key strengths of mechanical weeding. However, limited effects were perceived in terms of income stability (0.48), flexibility (0.48), and new job creation (0.49), echoing challenges related to economic viability and the capital-intensive nature of these technologies, as noted by Jacquet et al. (2021). Interestingly, the alignment between the results and prior studies is evident in improved labour conditions but diverges on issues like food safety (0.25), where perceived impacts remain low despite long-term potential. This divergence underscores the need to address barriers such as high costs and operational complexity, which hinder broader social acceptance. Furthermore, while the literature emphasizes reduced workloads (Tamirat et al., 2023), the cognitive demands highlighted by workers may counterbalance some of the benefits. Overall, the findings illustrate both convergence with established research on direct labour improvements and divergence in realizing broader indirect benefits, emphasizing the importance of ongoing investment and adaptive strategies to maximize social and environmental gains.

Social direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Improved labour environment	Jacquet et al., (2021)	Medium-to-high	Short run	Non-monetary

Social indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Reduced workload	Tamirat et al. (2023)	Low-to-medium	Short run	Non-monetary
Enhanced food safety	Liu et al. (2023); Jacquet et al., (2021)	Low	Medium-to-long run	Non-monetary

TABLE 48: SOCIAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING WITH HARROW AND REDUCED HERBICIDE APPLICATION (LV2)

Environmental analysis

 Traffic light 54.72%	<p>The environmental analysis for Latvia 2, with a traffic light score of 54.72%, reflects a moderate environmental impact from the adoption of mechanical weeding practices. This score, slightly lower comparing to other cases, suggests that while some environmental benefits are evident, there is considerable room for improvement. Key advantages include reduced external inputs (0.80) and positive impacts on soil erosion (0.67) and the carbon footprint (0.60), highlighting the potential of mechanical weeding to contribute to more sustainable farming practices. However, these benefits are offset by challenges such as increased soil compaction (0.29) and the limited impact on biodiversity (0.29), indicating that the full environmental potential of mechanical weeding remains unrealized without complementary practices such as cover cropping. These mixed results align with findings in the literature, such as those by Pimentel et al. (1995) and Panagos et al. (2018), which emphasize the importance of integrating mechanical weeding with broader soil conservation strategies to maximize benefits and mitigate downsides, including fuel-related greenhouse gas emissions.</p>
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Env. impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
Contribute to reduce Direct greenhouse gas emissions	0.59
Contribute to reduce external inputs	0.80
Limit water consumption	0.59
Contribute to reduce waste	0.60
Has a positive impact on biodiversity	0.29
Has a positive impact on soil erosion	0.67
Has a positive impact on carbon footprint	0.60
Increase the rate of soil organic matter mineralisation	0.29
Increase soil compaction	0.29

TABLE 49: ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING WITH HARROW AND REDUCED HERBICIDE APPLICATION (LV2)

The analysis of perceptions further underscores both the opportunities and limitations of mechanical weeding. While Latvia 2 demonstrates alignment with previous studies in areas such as soil erosion reduction and improved carbon footprint, the relatively low scores for biodiversity and soil compaction diverge from expectations in contexts where mechanical weeding is combined with biodiversity-supporting practices. Similarly, moderate relevance for reducing waste (0.60) and water consumption (0.59) suggests a potential to enhance environmental outcomes through better integration of resource-efficient strategies. Convergences with the literature are apparent in areas like ecological improvements noted by Liu et al. (2023) and Jacquet et al. (2021), which highlight medium-to-high long-term impacts when mechanical weeding is supported by complementary measures. However, divergences arise in perceptions of soil compaction and organic matter mineralization, which may stem from local variations in management practices or the lack of broader adoption of sustainable techniques. Overall, the results for Latvia 2 point to the importance of addressing trade-offs, such as increased fuel consumption, and adopting synergistic practices to fully realize the environmental benefits of mechanical weeding.

Env. direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Land Conservation (reduced soil erosion, on-site effects)	Pimentel et al. (1995); Montgomery (2007); Eshel et al. (2015)	Medium if applied in combination with other practices (like cover crops)	Long-run	Quantitative – monetizable (see Panagos et al, 2018)

Env. indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Ecological improvement (biodiversity)	Liu et al. (2023); Jacquet et al. (2021)	Medium-to-High	Long-run	Qualitative
Land Conservation (reduced soil erosion, off-site effects)	Liu et al. (2023); Jacquet et al. (2021)	Controversial	Long-run	Qualitative

TABLE 50: ENVIRONMENTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING WITH HARROW AND REDUCED HERBICIDE APPLICATION (LV2)

Sensitivity analysis (only first scenario)

Given the highly simplified nature of this case and the associated analysis, which is characterized by limited data availability, we consider it largely theoretical and not highly representative. For this reason, a full sensitivity analysis was not conducted, as the low number of variables involved does not justify its application. Furthermore, the limited robustness of the analysis itself suggests that such an exercise would not have significantly enhanced the overall value or insight of the study. Instead, the focus remains on presenting an initial exploratory framework, acknowledging its limitations while providing a foundation for further, more detailed investigations.

4.2.1.4 Mechanical weeding in sugarbeet (UK1)

Main objective

The project focuses on reducing the use of herbicides in sugarbeet production through the adoption of mechanical weeding.

Description of the “before” scenario

Before the introduction of the new mechanical weeding solution, sugar beet fields were managed using conventional chemical-based methods for weed control, particularly targeting blackgrass. This approach relied on a series of five sequential herbicide applications spread across different growth stages of the crop and the weeds. A 240HP 4WD tractor equipped with a 36-meter sprayer, operating at a rate of 10 hectares per hour, was used for all treatments.

During the first stage, a combination of Betanal Tandem, Clayton Neutron, and Crop Oil was applied to address the early stages of blackgrass development. The second application targeted weeds that survived or emerged after the initial treatment and involved additional herbicides, including Betanal Tandem, Betasana SC, Debut, Venzar, and a supplementary dose of Crop Oil to enhance efficacy.

As blackgrass and other weeds continued to develop, a third treatment was introduced, focusing on more persistent growth. This stage utilized Centurion Max in combination with X Change, designed to tackle the remaining weeds effectively. However, the control process did not stop there; a fourth application was necessary to maintain weed suppression and involved a further mix of Betasana SC, Efeckt, Debut, Clayton Neutron, Clayton Cocoon, and Crop Spray 11E. By this point, the weed management program was intensive, requiring significant time, fuel, and herbicide inputs. Finally, a fifth application mirrored the fourth in its composition but served as a final effort to ensure comprehensive blackgrass control across the fields. This method achieved a high level of weed control but came at the cost of increased herbicide use, fuel consumption, and labor requirements due to the repeated applications.

Description of the “after” scenario

Following the introduction of mechanical weeding, the weed management strategy in sugar beet fields shifted significantly, combining chemical and mechanical solutions to reduce reliance on herbicides. Initially, a Garford camera-guided hoe was used for precision mechanical weeding, but this was later replaced with a GPS-guided tractor equipped with a standard hoe to improve efficiency. The updated approach involved four herbicide applications alongside mechanical treatments, representing a decrease from the previous five applications.

In the first stage, the same herbicide mix of Betanal Tandem, Clayton Neutron, and Crop Oil was applied to target early weed development. The second application was similar to the previous scenario, incorporating Betanal Tandem, Betasana SC, Debut, Venzar, and Crop Oil to manage emerging weeds. However, the subsequent treatments were streamlined to improve efficiency and reduce chemical inputs. The third application employed Centurion Max combined with X Change, maintaining control over persistent blackgrass, while the fourth and final herbicide stage utilized Betasana SC, Efeckt, Debut, Clayton Neutron, Clayton Cocoon, and Crop Spray 11E.

This revised strategy successfully integrated mechanical weeding to reduce overall herbicide dependence. Despite requiring additional field operations for effective hoeing, the combination of chemical and mechanical approaches resulted in more targeted weed control. Fuel consumption and labor costs associated with mechanical weeding increased, but the reduction in herbicide applications offered a more balanced and sustainable solution for managing weeds in sugar beet cultivation.

Similar to findings in the literature, such as Jacquet et al. (2021) and Shrestha et al. (2013), this shift could reduce chemical inputs, improve cost efficiency, and align with environmental sustainability goals. If successful, the project's fuel consumption and operational efficiency might reflect trends noted in studies like Gagliardi et al. (2023), suggesting mechanical weeding as a viable alternative in vineyards.

Input data and farm characteristics

The farm operates under conventional management practices and is involved in various forms of production, including wheat, sugar beet, triticale, barley, and potatoes. The total farm area spans 550 hectares, with all of it utilized for agricultural activities. Of this, 200 hectares were dedicated for experimental purposes, focusing primarily on the production of wheat and sugar beet.

<i>Management Type</i>	Conventional
<i>Most important crops and animal productions</i>	Wheat, sugar beet, triticale, barley, and potatoes
<i>Total Farm Area (ha)</i>	550
<i>Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA, ha)</i>	550
<i>Experimental area (ha)</i>	200
<i>Experimental crop(s)</i>	Wheat and sugar beet

TABLE 51: INPUT DATA AND FARM CHARACTERISTICS FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING IN SUGARBEET (UK1)

Based on our main assumptions, we consider the machine's lifespan to be 10 years, which is shorter than the 20-year analysis period. Therefore, we assume the machinery will be replaced every 10 years, maintaining the same practice throughout the 20-year period. The initial purchase price of the machinery is 14,238 euros, with an annual price increase of 5%. The first machines are purchased in year 0, the second in year 10.

The residual value of each machine is estimated at 15% year⁻¹ of its purchase price. The second tools are purchased in year 10 at a price of 23,192.20 euros, and after deducting the resale value of the first (2,803.10 euros), the net cost is 20,389.10 euros.

<i>Investment costs (euros)</i>			
<i>Machine and Tools</i>	Annual cost	Year	Expected lifetime (n. year)
<i>Standard hoe</i>	2,373	2019	10
<i>RTK GPS autosteer</i>	11,865	2020	10
<i>2nd tools purchase</i>	20,389.10	2030	10

TABLE 52: INVESTMENT COSTS FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING IN SUGARBEET (UK1)

Operating costs have been calculated for both the pre- and post-mechanical weeding scenarios. Fuel costs increased from €988 to €1,668.62 annually after introducing mechanical weeding, reflecting the additional energy demands of mechanical equipment compared to chemical weed control. In addition, machine maintenance costs have been estimated at 3% of the total machinery purchase price. This results in an annual maintenance cost of €427.14 for the first set of machines, and increasing to €695.77 for the second set as the machinery is replaced over time. These values align with standard agricultural practices, where ongoing maintenance is calculated as a percentage of the equipment value to ensure long-term sustainability. The machinery's lifespan is assumed to be 10 years. This assumption accounts for the possibility that some equipment may exceed the shorter lifespan, especially over a 20-year period. Consequently, we project two reinvestment cycles over the 20 years.

<i>Operating costs (euros year⁻¹)</i>			
	Annual costs - Pre	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Fuel</i>	988	1,668.62	2020-2040
<i>Machine maintenance (3% of purchase price)</i>		1 st tools purchase – 427.14	2020-2030
		2 nd tools purchase – 695.77	2030-2040

TABLE 53: OPERATING COSTS FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING IN SUGARBEET (UK1)

Labour costs in the project increased from 2,373 euros to 4,007.73 euros after the introduction of mechanical weeding. Additionally, we estimated a potential cost of 200 euros for technical support per year, although this was discussed in the final calculations, as support was provided by collaborating farmers. However, it's important to consider this cost in scenarios where such relational economies are not available.

The training cost was also estimated at 22 euros per workers year⁻¹, highlighting the need for specialized knowledge when adopting mechanical weeding technologies.

Labour costs (euros)

	Pre	Post	Year
<i>Labour costs</i>	2,373	4,007.73	2020-2040
<i>Technical support</i>		200	2020-2040
<i>Training</i>		22	2020-2040
<i>Insurance</i>		100	2020-2040

TABLE 54: LABOUR COSTS FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING IN SUGARBEET (UK1)

Among the other costs included in the analysis are transaction costs (€8,040) and opportunity costs (€7,889 for machines). Transaction costs have been estimated following the approach used by Mettepenningen et al. (2009), who measured the private transaction costs of European agri-environmental schemes. These costs account for the administrative, legal, and management expenses associated with transitioning to mechanical weeding. Opportunity costs reflect the potential income or benefits the farm could have earned from alternative uses of its resources. In this case, we have adopted a prudent estimate of 3% for opportunity costs, considering the low risk associated with the technical equipment used. The opportunity costs are divided into the first, and second purchases, with present values of €4,135, and €3,754 respectively. Including both transaction and opportunity costs in the CBA ensures that all indirect and non-monetary impacts are considered, giving a comprehensive view of the economic changes caused by the project. This approach is consistent with the literature, which emphasizes the importance of including all relevant costs to assess the true financial impact of investments. By factoring in these costs, the analysis provides a more accurate and long-term measure of the economic viability of mechanical weeding.

Other costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Transaction costs</i>	8,040	2020
<i>Opportunity costs (Present Value)</i>		
<i>1st purchase</i>	4,135	2020
<i>2nd purchase</i>	3,754	2020

TABLE 55: OTHER COSTS FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING IN SUGARBEET (UK1)

Post-introduction, the farm will shift from herbicide-based weed control to a mechanical approach. This will involve careful synchronization with crop growth stages and weather conditions, as mechanical weeding is more sensitive to environmental factors but avoids chemical damage. Labour intensity will likely increase, but long-term savings are expected due to reduced chemical use and environmental benefits.

Cost-benefit identification

<i>Category</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Attribute</i>
Benefit per person or household	Improved Labour Environment	Reduction of workers' risk from exposure to phytosanitary products (public)	Qualitative
Benefit per unit of abatement	Enhanced Food quality and safety	Reduced risk of chemical residues on crops (public)	Qualitative
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced or zero costs for weed management (agrochemicals)	Direct cost savings by reducing the use of herbicides (private)	Monetary 521,888 euros – present value
Improve an environmental or community asset	Ecological improvement	Improve biodiversity (public)	Qualitative
Reduced consequence of a risky event	Land conservation	Reduced soil erosion/increase productivity (on-site private, off-site public)	Mixed
Total (monetary) benefits			445,871 euros

TABLE 56: IDENTIFIED BENEFITS FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING IN SUGARBEET (UK1)

In TABLE 56, we identify several key benefits associated with the transition to mechanical weeding, which align with findings in the literature. The reduction of workers' risk from exposure to phytosanitary products is a major social benefit, improving worker safety and health by minimizing contact with harmful chemicals. Although this benefit is hard to monetize, it is a recognized outcome in sustainable agriculture, contributing to overall health and safety goals (Jacquet et al., 2021). Similarly, enhanced food quality and safety from reduced herbicide use leads to fewer chemical residues on crops, which improves consumer health and aligns with organic produce demands. Like worker safety, this benefit is difficult to quantify but remains critical to justifying the investment in mechanical weeding (Liu et al., 2023). The reduction in agrochemical costs is a clear monetary benefit. According with the survey we estimated a saving of 22,546 euros year⁻¹ in operational expenses, which correspond to 521,888 euros present value. Unlike more abstract benefits, this cost reduction is easily measured and included in the cost-benefit analysis. Furthermore, ecological improvements such as enhanced biodiversity are significant qualitative benefits that promote long-term sustainability, although their value is harder to monetize. These improvements support local ecosystems by promoting healthier flora and fostering biodiversity, aligning with broader environmental goals. Finally, land conservation through reduced soil erosion is a critical non-monetary benefit. By protecting soil structure and reducing erosion risks, the farm secures long-term productivity and environmental health, contributing to sustainable agricultural practices. While difficult to express in monetary terms, the reduced consequence of soil degradation remains a key factor in ensuring the farm's viability over time, supported by evidence in the literature emphasizing the importance of soil conservation in sustainable farming systems.

<i>Category</i>	<i>Cost item</i>	<i>Value (Euros)</i>	<i>Present Value (euros)</i>
<i>Capital costs (CAPEX)</i>	<i>Machine Tools</i>	34,627	28,012
<i>Operating costs, including operations and maintenance (OPEX)</i>	<i>Fuel</i>	681	9,930
	<i>Maintenance</i>	1,123	8,174
	<i>Labour</i>	1,635	23,851
<i>Other costs</i>	<i>Tech. support</i>	200	2,918
	<i>Training year</i>	22	321
	<i>Transaction costs</i>		8,040
	<i>Opportunity costs</i>		7,889
	<i>Insurance</i>	100	1,459
	<i>CO₂*</i>		10,652.55
<i>Total Costs</i>			90,595

TABLE 57: IDENTIFIED COSTS FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING IN SUGARBEET (UK1)

* We do not include the calculation of CO₂ emissions in the private analysis because they represent a cost shifted onto society and are not part of the private cost-benefit balance. However, these emissions were calculated separately to account for their broader impact, using values from the EIB Group climate bank roadmap 2021-2025. The roadmap provides the basis for the shadow cost, which represents the minimum societal cost of achieving the 1.5°C temperature target (EIB, 2020).

Economic analysis

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR (%)
20	2,156.46	5.76	12

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR
20	559.48	2.24	7.2

TABLE 58: ECONOMIC ANALYSIS FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING IN SUGARBEET (UK1)

In the first scenario, characterized by no risk of project failure and high adoption rates, the results highlight strong financial viability. The NPV per hectare is 2,156.46 euros, with a BCR of 5.76 and a MIRR of 12% over the 20-year analysis period. These figures indicate that under optimal adoption conditions, the

transition to mechanical weeding provides substantial net benefits, with returns significantly exceeding costs. The high BCR underscores the efficiency of the investment, while the MIRR reflects an attractive rate of return, particularly when compared to alternative agricultural investments. These results align with findings from studies such as Jacquet et al. (2021), which report long-term cost savings and environmental benefits from reducing herbicide use and increasing operational efficiency. However, the analysis in this case includes a comprehensive set of costs, such as opportunity costs, transaction costs, and multiple machinery replacement cycles, providing a more detailed understanding of the financial dynamics compared to studies that focus solely on operational costs. This inclusion of additional cost categories underscores the importance of strategic planning to ensure financial sustainability, especially in capital-intensive systems. In contrast, under the second scenario, where adoption levels are low but the risk of project failure remains minimal, the financial outlook deteriorates significantly. The NPV per hectare drops to 559.48 euros, with a BCR of 2.24 and an MIRR of 7.2%, indicating a limited capacity to generate returns under these constraints. The reduced adoption rate limits the ability to distribute fixed costs, such as those associated with machinery purchases and maintenance, over a sufficiently large operational base. This finding highlights the critical importance of achieving widespread adoption to ensure the economic feasibility of transitioning to mechanical weeding, echoing challenges identified in the literature, such as Mettepenningen et al. (2009), which emphasize the impact of high transaction costs and low economies of scale in similar agri-environmental schemes.

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

FIGURE 6: GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF NET AND CUMULATIVE BENEFITS UNDER TWO SCENARIOS: NO RISK OF FAILURE WITH HIGH ADOPTION (TOP) AND LOW RISK OF FAILURE WITH LOW ADOPTION (BOTTOM)

The graphs illustrate the economic dynamics of the two scenarios over the 20-year analysis period. In the first scenario, the net benefits show periodic declines during machinery reinvestment years, reflecting the financial strain associated with high initial capital costs. However, the cumulative net benefits display a consistent upward trend over time, demonstrating the project's ability to recover costs and generate sustained financial gains under conditions of high adoption. This aligns with findings in the literature that emphasize the long-term viability of mechanical weeding when economies of scale are achieved through

widespread adoption. In the second scenario, the cumulative net benefits follow a similar upward trend, albeit with slower growth and lower intensity. While the reinvestment cycles still create financial pressure, the overall trajectory remains positive, indicating that even under low adoption levels, the project can yield incremental financial gains over time. This suggests that while high adoption rates are preferable for maximizing returns and accelerating cost recovery, mechanical weeding can still deliver long-term benefits in low-adoption scenarios, provided reinvestment strategies and operational efficiencies are carefully managed.

Social analysis

 Traffic light 63.57%	<p>The global score of 63.57% for the UK1 case indicates a moderate to nearly high social impact, suggesting that while the adoption of mechanical weeding has generated notable social benefits, it still falls slightly below the threshold for a strong "high" classification. This result reflects mixed perceptions, with certain areas, such as working conditions and skill development, showing significant improvements. However, the overall impact remains context-dependent, with limited advancements in gender inclusivity and food safety. These findings highlight the need for further efforts to enhance broader social benefits and address existing gaps in inclusivity and accessibility.</p>
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Social impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
<i>The practice provides more stable income from year to year than alternatives</i>	0.62
<i>The current practice provides more flexibility for the agricultural management</i>	0.37
<i>New job opportunities in the rural area</i>	0.46
<i>Improvement of working conditions for the farm employers</i>	0.61
<i>Increased food safety</i>	0.38
<i>More job opportunities for women</i>	0.13
<i>Improving farmers' education and skills</i>	0.75
<i>Improved conditions for vulnerable groups</i>	0.30
<i>Improved aesthetics of the landscape and conservation of the cultural value</i>	0.40
<i>Improved social reputation of the farm</i>	0.45

TABLE 59: SOCIAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING IN SUGARBEET (UK1)

The analysis of social impact data for the UK1 case highlights mixed perceptions regarding mechanical weeding practices, with relatively high scores for income stability (0.62) and working conditions (0.61), indicating its potential to enhance economic resilience and reduce physical labour demands, aligning with findings by Jacquet et al. (2021) on the medium-to-high impact of improved labour environments, particularly in reducing workers' exposure to hazardous chemicals. However, low perceptions of flexibility in agricultural management (0.37) and food safety (0.38) reflect concerns about the adaptability of mechanical systems and their immediate effects on product safety, consistent with Liu et al. (2023), who emphasize that the benefits for food safety emerge in the medium-to-long term. The very low score for job opportunities for women (0.13) underscores a persistent gender gap in technological adoption, suggesting the need for policies promoting inclusivity in rural employment. Education and skill development (0.75) emerged as a significant positive impact, reflecting opportunities for capacity building provided by mechanical weeding and aligning with Mettepenningen et al. (2009), who highlight the empowering role of new technologies through technical knowledge acquisition. Despite these positives, lower scores in areas such as landscape aesthetics (0.40) and social reputation (0.45) indicate that broader societal and cultural benefits remain unrealized, paralleling findings by Tamirat et al. (2023) regarding indirect benefits such as cultural conservation and public image enhancement. The results converge with studies like Jacquet et al. (2021) on improved working conditions and reduced chemical exposure and Mettepenningen et al. (2009) on educational benefits, while diverging from Liu et al. (2023) in the limited perceived benefits for food

safety and from studies emphasizing the potential market advantages of eco-friendly practices, as reflected in the low score for social reputation.

Social direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Improved labour environment	Jacquet et al. (2021)	Medium-to-high	Short run	Non-monetary

Social indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Reduced workload	Tamirat et al. (2023)	Low-to-medium	Short run	Non-monetary
Enhanced food safety	Liu et al. (2023); Jacquet et al. (2021)	Low	Medium-to-long run	Non-monetary

TABLE 60: SOCIAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING IN SUGARBEET (UK1)

Environmental analysis

<p>Traffic light 60.13%</p>	<p>The global score of 60.13% for the UK1 case reflects a moderate environmental impact from adopting mechanical weeding practices. While the adoption shows some clear benefits in areas like soil erosion reduction, biodiversity, and organic matter mineralization, significant challenges remain in addressing fuel consumption and greenhouse gas emissions, which limit the overall environmental impact. The results suggest that while mechanical weeding has potential, improvements are needed to enhance its sustainability, particularly regarding carbon footprint reduction.</p>
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Env. impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
Contribute to reduce Direct greenhouse gas emissions	0.40
Contribute to reduce external inputs	0.60
Limit water consumption	0.40
Contribute to reduce waste	0.45
Has a positive impact on biodiversity	0.50
Has a positive impact on soil erosion	0.63
Has a positive impact on carbon footprint	0.00
Increase the rate of soil organic matter mineralisation	0.63
Increase soil compaction	0.63

TABLE 61: ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING IN SUGARBEET (UK1)

The environmental impact analysis for the UK1 case highlights a balanced yet complex picture, with benefits in specific areas offset by challenges in others. High scores for soil erosion reduction (0.63), biodiversity improvement (0.50), and organic matter mineralization (0.63) suggest that mechanical weeding contributes positively to soil health and ecosystem resilience, consistent with findings by Pardini et al. (2002) and Panagos et al. (2018), which emphasize the role of sustainable practices in mitigating erosion and supporting biodiversity. However, the very low score for carbon footprint reduction (0.00) underscores significant concerns about the environmental trade-offs of increased fuel consumption. This aligns with findings by Pimentel et al. (1995), who highlighted that fuel-intensive operations could offset gains achieved by reducing chemical herbicides. Moderate scores for reducing external inputs (0.60) and waste reduction (0.45) reflect uncertainty about the visible short-term benefits of mechanical weeding, as its full potential to replace chemical herbicides has not yet been realized. Perceived improvements in soil compaction (0.63) and organic matter mineralization are consistent with more recent findings, such as those by Liebhard et al. (2024), which emphasize that mechanical weeding, when integrated with complementary practices like cover cropping, can improve soil structure over time. Despite these benefits, the increased

greenhouse gas emissions associated with higher fuel use present a critical limitation to the overall environmental sustainability of mechanical weeding. These results suggest that while mechanical weeding offers substantial potential, its long-term environmental viability depends on adopting complementary practices, such as reduced tillage or more fuel-efficient machinery, to mitigate its downsides and maximize its benefits.

Env. direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Land Conservation (reduced soil erosion, on-site effects)	Pimentel et al. (1995); Montgomery (2007); Eshel et al. (2015)	Medium if applied in combination with other practices (like cover crops)	Long-run	Quantitative – monetizable (see Panagos et al, 2018)

Env. indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Ecological improvement (biodiversity)	Liu et al. (2023); Jacquet et al. (2021)	Medium-to-High	Long-run	Qualitative
Land Conservation (reduced soil erosion, off-site effects)	Liu et al. (2023); Jacquet et al. (2021)	Controversial	Long-run	Qualitative

TABLE 62: ENVIRONMENTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING IN SUGARBEET (UK1)

Sensitivity analysis (only first scenario)

The sensitivity analysis for the first scenario continues to demonstrate a robust and positive financial outlook across varying conditions. The updated Net Present Value (NPV) per hectare now ranges from 689.75 euros to 3,075.18 euros, with a mean of 1,952.08 euros and a median of 2,020.57 euros. The default NPV case stands at 2,156.46 euros per hectare, reinforcing the financial viability of the mechanical weeding strategy under favorable assumptions. These figures highlight the resilience of the investment, with a 100% probability that the NPV exceeds zero, confirming the minimal financial risk of this transition.

The Benefit-Cost Ratio (BCR) further supports this positive outlook, with a range between 1.81 and 8.92, a mean value of 4.63, and a median of 4.80. The BCR exceeds the critical threshold of 1 in all simulations, while the probability of achieving a target BCR of 2 is now 99%, emphasizing the significant profitability potential. This robustness aligns with findings in existing literature, including Jacquet et al. (2021), which underline the role of high adoption rates and cost efficiencies in delivering strong economic outcomes.

Monte Carlo simulations, based on 1,000 random iterations, provide additional insights into the stability of the investment. Approximately 76% of the simulations result in NPV outcomes exceeding 183,000 euros, while the probability distribution reflects a concentration in the range between 266K and 516K euros, demonstrating the reliability of financial returns. Similarly, the distribution of BCR values highlights a consistent balance between benefits and costs, with most simulations clustering between 2.75 and 5.16, indicating stable profitability.

An updated sensitivity analysis to the discount rate confirms the project’s financial robustness across varying economic conditions. At a low discount rate of 2%, the NPV reaches 539,849 euros, with a BCR of 6.26. Under the default rate of 4%, the NPV stands at 431,293 euros, with a BCR of 5.76. Even at a higher discount rate of 6%, the NPV remains positive at 350,099 euros, with a BCR of 5.31. These results reaffirm the resilience of the project, echoing conclusions from Gagliardi et al. (2023), which emphasize the long-term financial sustainability of mechanical weeding despite initial capital investments.

Key factors driving the updated financial performance include the significant reduction in herbicide applications, improved operational efficiency, and alignment with long-term sustainability goals. Although the upfront costs of mechanical weeding tools and the learning curve for adoption remain challenges, the consistently favorable results demonstrated in the sensitivity analysis reinforce the importance of policy measures such as targeted subsidies or cooperative machinery sharing to further enhance the financial feasibility of this solution.

Net Present Value (NPV)	Tot. Euros	Euros ha⁻¹
Minimum	137,951	689.75
Maximum	615,038	3075.18
Default case	431,293	2156.46
Mean	390,418	1952.08
Median	404,114	2020.57
Probability that NPV > 0		1.00
Distribution (euros)		Probability
Less than 100K		0.00
100K to 183K		0.06
183K to 266K		0.32
266K to 349K		0.16
349K to 433K		0.27
433K to 516K		0.19
	Total	1.00
Benefit: Cost Ratio (BCR)		Unconstrained version
Minimum		1.81
Maximum		8.92
Default case		5.76
Mean		4.63
Median		4.80
Probability that BCR > 1		1.00
Target BCR		2
Probability BCR > Target		0.99
Distribution		Probability
Less than 1.54		0.00
1.54 to 2.75		0.13
2.75 to 3.95		0.33
3.95 to 5.16		0.31
5.16 to 6.37		0.19
6.37 to 7.58		0.05
	Total	1.00

TABLE 63: BCA ROBUSTNESS (MONTE CARLO ANALYSIS BASED ON 1000 RANDOM SIMULATIONS) - MECHANICAL WEEDING IN SUGARBEET (UK1)

Sensitivity to discount rate

Project organisation	Low discount rate	Default discount rate	High discount rate
	2%	4%	6%
Benefits (present value)	642,466	521,888	431,358
Costs (present value)	102,617	90,595	81,259
Net Present Value (NPV)	539,849	431,293	350,099
Benefit: Cost Ratio (unconstrained budget)	6.26	5.76	5.31

TABLE 64: SENSITIVITY TO DISCOUNT RATE - MECHANICAL WEEDING IN SUGARBEET (UK1)

4.2.1.5 Hot Foam in vines-trees (Greece 3)

Main objective

The project aims to reduce herbicide use in vineyards by introducing Hot Foam technology in vineyards for targeted weed control, focusing on minimizing environmental impact and ensuring operational efficiency.

Description of the “before” scenario

In the vineyard, weed control in the intra-row space was primarily achieved through the application of herbicides using a hand sprayer. Glyphosate was applied at a rate of 4 L/ha, with water usage ranging from 200 to 800 L/ha. This method had a work capacity of 0.20 ha/hour. For inter-row weed control, mechanical mowing was performed using a tractor (LS MT3.40 40HP 4WD 1879cc) equipped with a flail mower, which had a work capacity of 0.1 ha/hour and consumed 30L/ha of fuel. Pesticide and fungicide applications, involving Abamectin and Bacillus thuringiensis, were conducted with a vineyard sprayer and the same tractor, with a work capacity of 0.5 ha/hour and a fuel consumption of 20L/ha. Additionally, rotary tilling was employed for inter-row mechanical weeding, using the same tractor and consuming 30L/ha of fuel, with a work capacity of 0.1 ha/hour. Fertilization involved the application of NUTRI PLUS 11.15.15 at 90 kg/ha using a spreader, with a fuel consumption of 22L/ha. Manual pruning was performed at a rate of 0.25 ha/hour.

Description of the “after” scenario

Following the introduction of Hot Foam technology for intra-row weed control, the vineyard switched to the use of Foamstream, with a work capacity of 0.10 ha/hour. This method involved applying a mixture of water (12 L/min) and plant-based materials such as sugars and oils (8 L/ha), with a fuel consumption of 20L/ha. For inter-row mechanical weeding, mechanical mowing continued with the same tractor and flail mower setup, maintaining the same work capacity (0.1 ha/hour) and fuel consumption (30L/ha). Pesticide and fungicide applications also remained the same, involving Abamectin and Bacillus thuringiensis, with a vineyard sprayer and the same tractor configuration. Rotary tilling was similarly maintained for inter-row weed control, with the same fuel consumption and work capacity as before. Fertilization and manual pruning practices also remained unchanged, following the same process as described in the previous scenario.

Input data and farm characteristics

The company operates a 20-hectare farm dedicated to conventional vineyard management. Within this, a 0.5-hectare experimental plot is designated for the research on thermal weeding (Hot Foam).

<i>Management Type</i>	Conventional
<i>Most important crops and animal productions</i>	Vineyards
<i>Total Farm Area (ha)</i>	20
<i>Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA, ha)</i>	20
<i>Experimental area (ha)</i>	0.5
<i>Experimental crop(s)</i>	Vineyards

TABLE 65: INPUT DATA AND FARM CHARACTERISTICS FROM HOT FOAM IN VINES-TREES (GREECE 3)

The lifespan of the foam machine is 10 years, and the machine will need to be replaced once during the 20-year analysis period. The initial purchase price is 60,000 euros, with the second machine being purchased in 2032 at a cost of 85,921 euros.

Investment costs (euros)

<i>Machine and Tools</i>	Annual costs	Year	Expected lifetime (n. year)
<i>Foam Machine</i>	60,000	2022	10

TABLE 66: INVESTMENT COSTS FROM HOT FOAM IN VINES-TREES (GREECE 3)

Operating costs account for an increase in fuel expenses from 61.61 euros to 73.69 euros annually between 2022 and 2042, reflecting the higher energy demands of mechanical operations. Machine maintenance is calculated at 3% of the machinery purchase price, resulting in annual maintenance costs of 1,800 euros for the first set of tools (2022-2031) and 2,932.01 euros for the second set (2032-2042).

Operating costs (euros year⁻¹)

	Annual costs - Pre	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Fuel</i>	61.61	73.69	2022-2042
<i>Machine maintenance (3% of purchase price)</i>		1 st tools purchase - 1800	2022-2031
		2 nd tools purchase -2,932.01	2032-2042

TABLE 67: OPERATING COSTS FROM HOT FOAM IN VINES-TREES (GREECE 3)

The labour costs associated with the implementation of Hot Foam technology include a consulting fee of 1,500 euros in 2022, reflecting the need for specialized technical expertise to ensure proper installation and operation of the equipment. This cost was necessary due to the specific requirements of the Hot Foam system, which demands precision for effective weed control. An annual technical support cost of 200 euros is also included for the subsequent period 2023-2042, providing ongoing assistance to maintain the machinery and ensure optimal performance. Additionally, the training cost is estimated at 22 euros per worker per year, covering the continuous need for skill development as new machinery and updated practices are introduced. This investment in training ensures that the workforce remains efficient and adaptable to technological advancements, reducing operational risks over time.

Labour costs (euros)

	Pre	Post	Year
<i>Labour costs</i>	67.83	80.33	2020-2040
<i>Consulting fees</i>		1500	2022
<i>Technical support</i>		200	2023-2042
<i>Training</i>		22	2022-2042

TABLE 68: LABOUR COSTS FROM HOT FOAM IN VINES-TREES (GREECE 3)

The Other costs section includes transaction costs of 20.1 euros in 2022 (0.5 hectares), representing the administrative or operational expenses associated with implementing the changes. Opportunity costs are calculated as the present value in 2022 of capital allocated to machinery purchases. The opportunity cost for the first purchase is 13,940 euros, while for the second purchase, it is 13,486 euros. These costs reflect the economic trade-offs of committing resources to machinery instead of alternative investments.

Other costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Post	Year	
<i>Transaction costs</i>	20.1	2022	
<i>Opportunity costs (Present Value)</i>			
	1 st purchase	13,940	2022
	2 nd purchase	13,486	2022

TABLE 69: OTHER COSTS FROM HOT FOAM IN VINES-TREES (GREECE 3)**Cost-benefit identification**

Category	Name	Type	Attribute
Benefit per person or household	Improved Labour Environment	Reduction of workers' risk from exposure to phytosanitary products (public)	Qualitative

Benefit per unit of abatement	Enhanced Food quality and safety	Reduced risk of chemical residues on grapes (public)	Qualitative
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced or zero costs for weed management	Direct cost savings by reducing the use of herbicides (private)	Monetary 463 euros – present value
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced disposal costs		Monetary 9,722 euros – present value
Total (monetary) benefits			10,185 euros

TABLE 70: IDENTIFIED BENEFITS FROM HOT FOAM IN VINES-TREES (GREECE 3)

The adoption of hot foam technology for weed management in vineyards brings several key benefits. From a social perspective, it significantly improves the labour environment by reducing workers' exposure to phytosanitary products, enhancing safety and minimizing health risks. Economically, the technology generates direct cost savings by reducing the use of herbicides, amounting to 463 euros in present value, and further decreases disposal costs, leading to an additional 9,722 euros in savings. These reductions in operational expenses not only make farm management more sustainable but also improve profitability. Overall, the total monetary benefits amount to 10,185 euros, reflecting the combined savings from weed management and disposal costs.

Category	Cost item	Value (Euros)	Present Value (euros)
Capital costs (CAPEX)	Machine Tools	145,921	118,045
Operating costs, including operations and maintenance (OPEX)	Fuel	12.08	176
	Maintenance	4,732	34,447
	Labour	12.5	182
	Consulting fee		1500
	Tech. support	200	2,718
Other costs	Training year	22	321
	Transaction costs		20
	Opportunity costs		27,426
	CO ₂ *		182.08
Total Costs			184,836

TABLE 71: IDENTIFIED COSTS FROM HOT FOAM IN VINES-TREES (GREECE 3)

* We do not include the calculation of CO₂ emissions in the private analysis because they represent a cost shifted onto society and are not part of the private cost-benefit balance. However, these emissions were calculated separately to account for their broader impact, using values from the EIB Group climate bank roadmap 2021-2025. The roadmap provides the basis for the shadow cost, which represents the minimum societal cost of achieving the 1.5°C temperature target (EIB, 2020).

Economic analysis

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR (%)
20	-349,302	0.06	-100

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR
20	-361,768	0.02	-100

TABLE 72: ECONOMIC ANALYSIS FROM HOT FOAM IN VINES-TREES (GREECE 3)

In the first scenario, assuming no risk of project failure and high adoption rates, the financial results are strongly negative. Over a 20-year period, the NPV per hectare is calculated at -349,302 euros, with a BCR of 0.06 and an MIRR of -100%. These figures demonstrate that even with high adoption, the costs of implementing and maintaining the project far outweigh the potential benefits. The high costs associated with initial investments, machinery replacements, and ongoing operational expenses result in significant financial losses. This highlights the critical need for external support, such as subsidies or additional revenue streams, to make such a project viable.

In the second scenario, where there is a low risk of project failure but low adoption rates, the financial outcome deteriorates even further. The NPV per hectare drops to -361,768 euros, with a BCR of 0.02 and an MIRR of -100%. These results indicate severe financial losses, driven by both the high costs and

insufficient adoption levels to distribute these costs effectively. The low adoption scenario underscores the importance of achieving broad uptake, as insufficient adoption makes it difficult to justify the costs, leading to unsustainable financial outcomes over the long term.

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

FIGURE 7: GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF NET AND CUMULATIVE BENEFITS UNDER TWO SCENARIOS: NO RISK OF FAILURE WITH HIGH ADOPTION (TOP) AND LOW RISK OF FAILURE WITH LOW ADOPTION (BOTTOM)

The graphical representation of these results further illustrates the challenges. In the first scenario, although net benefits may occasionally show positive values, reinvestment periods cause sharp negative spikes. Cumulatively, the net benefits demonstrate a downward trend, with no significant recovery, showing that even under favourable conditions, the project does not achieve long-term financial sustainability. In the second scenario, the situation worsens, with consistently negative net benefits across the entire period, leading to an ever-deepening decline in cumulative net benefits. This reflects a scenario in which the project is unsustainable, causing continuous financial losses without the possibility of recovery.

Social analysis

<p>Traffic light 50.78%</p>	<p>The expert perceptions reflect a moderate social impact with a global score of 50.78%. While there are perceived social benefits, particularly in terms of flexibility in agricultural management, the impact is limited by the high initial investments required, which are not accessible to all farming contexts. These financial barriers may hinder broader social benefits, such as job creation, gender inclusivity, and improvements for vulnerable groups.</p>
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Social impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
The practice provides more stable income from year to year than alternatives	0.56
The current practice provides more flexibility for the agricultural management	0.47
New job opportunities in the rural area	0.45
Improvement of working conditions for the farm employers	0.47
Increased food safety	0.25
More job opportunities for women	0.25
Improving farmers' education and skills	0.25
Improved conditions for vulnerable groups	0.15
Improved aesthetics of the landscape and conservation of the cultural value	0.40
Improved social reputation of the farm	0.30

TABLE 73: SOCIAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM HOT FOAM IN VINES-TREES (GREECE 3)

The feedback from the expert shows a mixed perception of the social impacts of hot foam technology. The highest score (4) was for flexibility in agricultural management, aligning with the literature (Tamirat et al., 2023), which highlights for mechanical weeding, how new technologies can improve operational flexibility and reduce labour intensity. However, there were no perceived improvements in key areas such as income stability, working conditions, or job creation. This absence of economic benefits likely reflects the high initial costs and operational expenses associated with hot foam technology, posing significant challenges for smaller farms, as noted by Jacquet et al. (2021). Without financial support or cost-sharing schemes, these technologies remain inaccessible to many. Additionally, the lack of perceived improvements in education and skill development contrasts with findings from Liu et al. (2023), which suggest that adopting new technologies can enhance farmers' technical skills. This suggests the need for more structured training programs or awareness initiatives. Overall, the moderate score of 50.78% indicates that while flexibility is an advantage, the broader social impacts are still limited. To fully unlock the potential benefits of hot foam technology, particularly in areas such as job creation, working conditions, and social inclusivity, additional financial incentives, training programs, and policy support are necessary.

Social direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Improved labour environment	Jacquet et al., (2021)	Medium-to-high	Short run	Non-monetary

Social indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Reduced workload	Tamirat et al. (2023)	Low-to-medium	Short run	Non-monetary
Enhanced food safety	Liu et al. (2023); Jacquet et al., (2021)	Low	Medium-to-long run	Non-monetary

TABLE 74: SOCIAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM HOT FOAM IN VINES-TREES (GREECE 3)

Environmental analysis

 Traffic light 48.03%	The global score of 48.03% reflects a moderate environmental impact based on the farmer's evaluation of the hot foam technology. This score suggests that while there are some positive environmental benefits associated with the technology, key challenges remain, particularly in areas such as greenhouse gas emissions and fuel use, which limit its overall effectiveness in reducing the carbon footprint. The high upfront investments and energy demands of the technology further constrain its broader adoption as an environmentally sustainable solution.
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Env. impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
Contribute to reduce Direct greenhouse gas emissions	0.52
Contribute to reduce external inputs	0.80
Limit water consumption	0.49
Contribute to reduce waste	0.60
Has a positive impact on biodiversity	0.58
Has a positive impact on soil erosion	0.56
Has a positive impact on carbon footprint	0.60
Increase the rate of soil organic matter mineralisation	0.56
Increase soil compaction	0.54

TABLE 75: ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM HOT FOAM IN VINES-TREES (GREECE 3)

The questionnaire responses provide a nuanced view of the environmental impact of hot foam technology. The highest scores were given for reducing external inputs (0.80), reducing waste (0.60), and positive impacts on biodiversity (0.60) and soil erosion (0.58), which align with the literature highlighting the benefits of mechanical alternatives like hot foam in reducing the need for harmful chemicals and supporting biodiversity (Kup & Saglam, 2014). The technology's ability to reduce soil erosion is consistent with findings from other mechanical weeding practices, known for enhancing soil health over time (Liu et al., 2023). However, moderate concerns were noted in areas related to greenhouse gas emissions (0.52), water consumption (0.49), and carbon footprint (0.60). While the technology reduces the use of herbicides, its reliance on fuel contributes to emissions, which is a common challenge in mechanical systems, as noted by Pergher et al. (2020). Although the technology improves certain environmental aspects, its fuel use limits its overall environmental benefits. Additionally, the perceived impacts on soil compaction (0.54) and soil organic matter mineralization (0.56) suggest that while the technology has benefits, its long-term effects on soil health depend on the context and application. In conclusion, while hot foam technology offers environmental advantages such as reducing chemical inputs and supporting biodiversity, challenges related to fuel consumption and energy use need to be addressed.

Env. direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Reduced use of harmful chemicals	Kup, F., & Saglam, R. (2014)	High	Short to Long-run	Quantitative

Env. indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Land Conservation (reduced soil erosion, off-site effects)	Liu et al. (2023); Jacquet et al. (2021)	Controversial	Long-run	Qualitative
Increase energy demand	Pergher, G., Gubiani, R., & Mainardis, M. (2020)	Medium to high	Short-run	Quantitative

TABLE 76: ENVIRONMENTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM HOT FOAM IN VINES-TREES (GREECE 3)

Sensitivity analysis (only first scenario)

The sensitivity analysis for the first scenario reveals a deeply negative financial outlook for the adoption of hot foam technology, with the NPV per hectare ranging from -470,592 euros to -232,288 euros, and a mean of -352,048 euros. The probability of achieving a positive NPV is 0%, indicating that under current conditions, the project is not financially viable. The consistently negative NPV values underscore the significant capital expenditures CAPEX and operational costs associated with the technology, making it particularly challenging for smaller farms or those with limited access to financial support.

The BCR analysis similarly paints a grim picture, with values ranging from 0.02 to 0.09, and a default case of 0.06. This reflects that the benefits gained from hot foam technology are insufficient to cover the high costs involved. The probability that the BCR exceeds 1 is 0%, further highlighting the project's financial

challenges. The Monte Carlo simulation confirms this outlook, with 50% of the results clustered in the range of -188K euros to -164K euros, reinforcing the pattern of substantial financial losses.

The sensitivity to different discount rates also shows limited improvement. Even at a lower discount rate of 2%, the NPV remains negative at -192,952 euros, with a BCR of 0.06. At the default discount rate of 4%, the NPV is -174,651 euros, and at a higher rate of 6%, it is still -160,116 euros. These results indicate that the high costs, particularly related to energy use and machinery, heavily outweigh the environmental and economic benefits of adopting the technology in the short to medium term.

The findings suggest that without significant external support, such as subsidies, or cooperative cost-sharing models, the adoption of hot foam technology remains financially unsustainable. Additionally, the results indicate the need for operational improvements to reduce energy consumption and increase overall efficiency to improve the economic viability of the technology.

Net Present Value (NPV)	Tot. Euros	Euros ha⁻¹
Minimum	-235,296	-470,592
Maximum	-116,144	-232,288
Default case	-174,651	-349,302
Mean	-176,024	-352,048
Median	-174,789	-34,9578
Probability that NPV > 0		0.00
Distribution (euros)		Probability
Less than -235K		0.00
-235K to -211K		0.26
-211K to -188K		0.00
-188K to -164K		0.50
-164K to -140K		0.00
-140K to -116K		0.24
Total		1.00
Benefit: Cost Ratio (BCR)		Unconstrained version
Minimum		0.02
Maximum		0.09
Default case		0.06
Mean		0.04
Median		0.05
Probability that BCR > 1		0.00
Target BCR		2
Probability BCR > Target		0.00
Distribution		Probability
Less than 0.02		0.00
0.02 to 0.03		0.14
0.03 to 0.04		0.28
0.04 to 0.06		0.34
0.06 to 0.07		0.19
0.07 to 0.09		0.05
Total		1.00

TABLE 77: BCA ROBUSTNESS (MONTE CARLO ANALYSIS BASED ON 1000 RANDOM SIMULATIONS) - HOT FOAM IN VINES-TREES (GREECE 3)

Sensitivity to discount rate

	Low discount rate	Default discount rate	High discount rate
Project organisation	2%	4%	6%
Benefits (present value)	12,538	10,185	8,418
Costs (present value)	205,490	184,836	168,535
Net Present Value (NPV)	-192,952	-174,651	-160,116
Benefit: Cost Ratio (unconstrained budget)	0.06	0.06	0.05

TABLE 78: SENSITIVITY TO DISCOUNT RATE - HOT FOAM IN VINES-TREES (GREECE 3)

4.2.2 Cover crops solutions

4.2.2.1 Cover crop vine (France 2)

Main objective

The project aims to reduce herbicide use in vineyards by introducing cover crop (i.e., Sowed clover in full).

Description of the “before” scenario

The vineyard heavily relied on chemical herbicides for weed management. Glyphosate (2 L/ha) and Katana (50 g/ha) were applied through sprayers (4 L/h) at a work capacity of 2 hectares per hour, with an initial pass conducted in March or April. Occasionally, an additional herbicide treatment (glyphosate 2 L/ha) was applied in late spring or early summer, every three years. Inter-row biomass management involved mechanical shredding with a Bionalan roller-crimper, conducted three times during the spring-summer season, at a rate of 6 L/h and a work capacity of 3 hectares per hour. Fertilization occurred annually, using 100 kg/ha of Ecoterroir 10-10-25 fertilizer, applied with a spreader (5 L/h) over 2 hectares per hour. Soil compaction caused by tractor wheel passes was mitigated through decompacting activities. The overall operations involved substantial inputs of fuel, with diesel consumption ranging from 4 to 6 L/h, and significant labour, with a total of 91.67 working hours estimated for field operations.

Description of the “after” scenario

After the introduction of cover crops, the vineyard adopted a more sustainable approach, significantly reducing chemical inputs. Clover was sown as a cover crop on one inter-row out of two, alternating annually. This was managed using a direct seeder, and the destruction of inter-row biomass in spring was conducted with a Kuhn 155 grinder. Although glyphosate (2.5 L/ha) was still used for pre-seeding preparation, the overall use of herbicides was decreased, with a single application of Stratos (4 L/ha) in July for monocotyledon weed control. Seeding preparation involved mechanical inter-row tillage using Actisol equipment (6.9 L/h at 2 hectares per hour) and under-vine tillage with Intercep equipment (5.5 L/h at 0.66 hectares per hour). Rotary tilling with a rotary harrow was also performed twice, consuming 7.5 L/h over 0.35 hectares per hour, to refine the soil both under and between the vines. Finally, a permanent cover crop was established with one pass of a rotary harrow and seeder (7.5 L/h over 1 hectare per hour). The shift towards mechanical operations and the use of cover crops reduced fuel consumption and labour, with setup times increased to 4 minutes per hectare for equipment preparation.

Input data and farm characteristics

The farm spans 225 hectares and follows conventional farming practices. The primary crop is vine, covering 50 hectares, within a mixed farming system that also includes meat cattle and cereals. The experimental focus is centered on the vineyard area.

<i>Management Type</i>	Conventional
<i>Most important crops and animal productions</i>	Vineyards, meat cows and cereals for self-use and seed production
<i>Total Farm Area (ha)</i>	225
<i>Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA, ha)</i>	225
<i>Experimental area (ha)</i>	50
<i>Experimental crop(s)</i>	Vineyards

TABLE 79: INPUT DATA AND FARM CHARACTERISTICS FROM COVER CROP VINE (FRANCE 2)

The farm employed several machines for the new vineyard management practices, including Actisol scraping equipment (€4,500, 7-year lifespan), Intercept Berner (€15,000, loan), Rotary harrow Lely (€15,500, loan), and Seeder APV (€7,000, loan), all with a 7-year lifespan. While some equipment was borrowed in this case, we included their costs in the analysis to account for scenarios where such resources

may not be readily available, ensuring broader applicability of the findings. During interviews with stakeholders, it became clear that the machinery was not purchased but rather provided on loan, a common arrangement for farms that are part of cooperative networks or collaborative relationships with other farmers. These networks allow for shared access to machinery, reducing the need for capital investment. However, in order to maintain consistency and offer a representative scenario applicable to a wider range of farms, this analysis assumes the case of a farm that must purchase the equipment outright. This approach ensures the financial implications are comparable across different operational models, especially for farms without access to loaned equipment through such networks.

At year zero of the analysis, we have an initial investment of 42,000 euros. Since the tools are assumed to have a useful life of 7 years, after each 7-year period, they need to be replaced. To calculate the effective cost of re-purchasing, we account for both the depreciation and the price increase over time of the new tools. After 7 years, the tools depreciate by 15% annually, leaving it with a residual value, which we subtract from the cost of the new tools, whose price has increased by 5% per year. This process gives us the effective cost for the second purchase, which is 45,634 euros. The same logic applies at the end of the second 7-year period (14 years in total), where we sell the second tools at its residual value and purchase a third group of tools at an increased price, leading to an effective cost of 64,212 euros for the third purchase. This approach allows us to account for both the loss in value of the old tools and the increase in cost for the replacements over time.

Investment costs (euros)

<i>Machine and Tools</i>	Annual costs	Year	Expected lifetime (n. year)
<i>Actisol scraping equipment</i>	4,500	2018	7
<i>Intercept Berner (loan)</i>	15,000	2018	7
<i>Rotary harrow lely+cutting cost (loan)</i>	15,500	2018	7
<i>seeder APV (loan)</i>	7,000	2018	7
<i>2nd tools purchase</i>	45,634	2025	7
<i>3rd tools purchase</i>	64,212	2032	7

TABLE 80: INVESTMENT COSTS FROM COVER CROP VINE (FRANCE 2)

The operational costs include 8,585 euros annually for Dwarf White clover seeds (18 kg/ha for 50 hectares at 171 euros/ha), along with 306 euros for fuel, 135 euros for Actisol maintenance (3% of its value), 1,125 euros for maintenance of borrowed machinery (3% of their value), 1,369 and 1,926 euros for the 2nd and 3rd purchase of tools.

Operating costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Pre	Annual costs -Post	Year
<i>Fuel</i>	299	605.5	2018-2038
<i>Dwarf White clover Seeds</i>		8,585	2018-2038
<i>Machine maintenance (3% of total machinery costs)</i>		Actisol – 135	2018-2024
		Other 1 st purchase –	2018-2024
		1,125	2025-2031
		2 nd purchase – 1,369	2032-2038
		3 rd purchase – 1,926	

TABLE 81: OPERATING COSTS FROM COVER CROP VINE (FRANCE 2)

Labour costs in the project increased to 3,635 euros. Additionally, we estimated an average potential cost of 200 euros year⁻¹ for technical support and the training cost was also estimated at euros 22 euros per worker year⁻¹.

Labour costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Pre	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Labour costs</i>	1,650	5,285	2018-2038
<i>Technical support</i>		200	2018-2038
<i>Training</i>		22	2018-2038

TABLE 82: LABOUR COSTS FROM COVER CROP VINE (FRANCE 2)

Among the other costs included in the analysis are transaction costs, which are set at 40.2 euros per hectare per year. Given that the total area is 50 hectares, this results in an annual transaction cost of 2,010 euros. As explained before, we assume that the machinery has a lifespan of 7 years, and the analysis spans a total period of 20 years. Accordingly, the machinery is purchased three times: initially at year 0, again at year 7, and finally at year 14. The initial price of the machinery is 42,000 euros, with an annual price increase of 5% for each subsequent purchase. After 7 years, each tool is sold at a residual value of 15% of its original purchase price.

- The first tools are purchased at year 0 for 42,000 euros. The opportunity cost associated with this purchase is calculated as 7,337 euros, representing the missed returns on capital if the money were invested elsewhere, and this is reflected in the year 2018.
- The second purchase is at year 7 for 59,098 euros, after applying the 5% annual price increase. The residual value from the first tools is deducted, resulting in a net cost of 45,634 euros. The opportunity cost for this second purchase is 6,058 euros, discounted to present value at the start of the analysis (2018).
- The third tools are purchased at year 14 for 83,157 euros. The resale value of the second tools is deducted, leaving a net cost of 64,212 euros. The opportunity cost for this third purchase is 6,737 euros, discounted to present value at year 2018.

In total, the present value of the opportunity costs for all three purchases amounts to 20,132 euros as shown in the table. These calculations help capture both the financial outlay and the opportunity cost of immobilizing capital for machinery purchases over the 20-year period.

Other costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Post	Year
Transaction costs	2,010	2018
Opportunity costs (Present Value)		
1 st purchase	7,337	2018
2 nd purchase	6,058	2018
3 rd purchase	6,737	2018

TABLE 83: OTHER COSTS FROM COVER CROP VINE (FRANCE 2)

Cost-benefit identification

Category	Name	Description	Attribute
Benefit per person or household	Improved Labour Environment	Reduction of workers' risk from exposure to phytosanitary products (public)	Qualitative
Benefit per unit of abatement	Enhanced Food quality and safety	Reduced risk of chemical residues on grapes (public)	Qualitative
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced nitrogen input	Reduction of nutrient loss	Mixed
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced or zero costs for weed management (agrochemicals)	Direct cost savings by reducing the use of herbicides (private)	144,287 euros – present value
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced fertiliser cost	-30% use of fertiliser according to the literature	30,786 euros – present value
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced spreader cost	Cost savings from spreader sale	750 euros – present value
Environmental sustainability	Enhanced Adaptability	Water Retention and Drought Resistance	Qualitative
Improve an environmental or community asset	Ecological improvement	Improve biodiversity (public), Improved nutrient cycling	Qualitative

Reduced consequence of a risky event	Land conservation	On-site reduced soil erosion/increase productivity (on-site private, off-site public)	437,689 euros – present value
Sustainable Resource Management	Land Use Optimization	Increased soil structure and stability, increased organic matter	Qualitative
Reduced consequence of a risky event	Land conservation	Off-site reduced soil erosion	Qualitative
Resource efficiency	Smart Resource Management	Reduced carbon footprint	Mixed
Environmental Sustainability	Resilience Enhancement	Increased resilience to climate change, Pest and disease control	Qualitative, Mixed
Community resilience	Improving community health	Reducing environmental contamination and the risks of chemical exposure to farm workers and surrounding communities	Qualitative
Total (monetary) benefits			613,512 euros

TABLE 84: IDENTIFIED BENEFITS FROM COVER CROP VINE (FRANCE 2)

The benefits of cover crops in the France2 case align closely with various findings from the literature on vineyard management, echoing the broader advantages of sustainable practices. For instance, the improved labour environment through reduced worker exposure to phytosanitary products is a qualitative benefit also highlighted in studies such as DeVetter et al. (2015), which emphasize the reduction in pesticide usage due to cover crops. This also contributes to enhanced food quality and safety by reducing chemical residues on grapes, a benefit corroborated by studies like Pardini et al. (2002).

In terms of direct cost savings, the reduction in herbicide use has yielded a monetary benefit of 144,287 euros (present value), which is consistent with the findings of Hostetler et al. (2007), who reported similar savings, though specific values may vary based on local practices. Additionally, the 30% reduction in fertilizer use, saving 30,786 euros (present value), aligns with nutrient management improvements discussed by Schütte (2019), where cover cropping helps enhance soil fertility and nutrient retention.

The sale of spreader equipment, resulting in 750 euros in cost savings, illustrates another financial benefit, which, while specific to this case, can be linked to the overall reduction in machinery dependency discussed in conservation tillage literature. The enhanced adaptability of vineyards due to better water retention and drought resistance reflects the findings of Guzmán et al. (2019), who identify improved soil moisture retention as a key ecological benefit of cover cropping.

In terms of ecological improvements, the France2 case notes increased biodiversity, a benefit supported by the work of Guzmán et al. (2019), who observed higher soil biodiversity and organic matter in vineyards using cover crops. The reduction in soil erosion risk, with an estimated 317,166 euros (present value), considering an average grape price of 1,500 euros per tonne (OIV, 2018), further highlights the economic significance of soil conservation. These ecological benefits also contribute to long-term sustainability, though, as noted by Schütte (2019), the improvements in nutrient cycling and soil fertility may take longer to fully manifest.

Regarding the erosion, we estimate the on-site benefits derived from the reduction of soil erosion over a 20-year period, assuming the use of cover crops on a 50-hectare vineyard. Based on the literature, we follow a prudent model for erosion reduction, where the total erosion risk is 8%, corresponding to a loss of 30 tonnes of soil (valued at 1,500 euros per tonne), and cover crops gradually reduce this erosion. We assume that the maximum benefit in each period is realized progressively, starting with a 1% reduction in the first year, increasing to 2% by year 5, 4% by year 10, 6% by year 15, and reaching the full 8% reduction by year 20. The annual savings from avoided erosion range from 5,625 euros in year 1 to 45,000 euros by year 20, based on the price of grapes lost due to erosion. The cumulative present value of these benefits, assuming a standard discount rate, amounts to 317,166 euros. This value represents the maximum potential benefit that could be achieved under these assumptions. However, the present value is also influenced by many other factors, such as variations in discount rates, climate conditions, and management practices, which we cannot fully account for in this analysis. Therefore, the final result of the analysis must consider these uncertainties and limitations to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the potential outcomes. This cautious and gradual approach is aligned with findings from studies like Guzmán et al. (2019) and

Galati et al. (2015), reflecting the time it takes for cover crops to enhance soil health and reduce erosion effectively.

Category	Cost item	Value (Euros)	Present Value (euros)
Capital costs (CAPEX)	Machine Tools	151,846	113,759
Operating costs, including operations and maintenance (OPEX)	Fuel	306	4,465
	Machine Maintenance	4,555	21,303
	Seed	8,585	125,258
Labour	Labour	3,635	53,036
	Tech. Supp.	200	2,918
	Training year	22	321
Other costs	Transaction costs	2,010	2,010
	Opportunity costs	20,132	20,132
	CO ₂ *		525
Total Costs			343,201

TABLE 85: IDENTIFIED COSTS FROM COVER CROP VINE (FRANCE 2)

* We do not include the calculation of CO₂ emissions in the private analysis because they represent a cost shifted onto society and are not part of the private cost-benefit balance. However, these emissions were calculated separately to account for their broader impact, using values from the EIB Group climate bank roadmap 2021-2025. The roadmap provides the basis for the shadow cost, which represents the minimum societal cost of achieving the 1.5°C temperature target (EIB, 2020).

Economic analysis

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR (%)
20	5,406.26	1.79	6.9

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR
20	-3,475.96	0.58	1

TABLE 86: ECONOMIC ANALYSIS FROM COVER CROP VINE (FRANCE 2)

In this scenario, the positive NPV of 5,406.26 euros per hectare, BCR of 1.79, and MIRR of 6.9% reflect strong economic viability for adopting cover crops on a large scale. The key driver of financial success is the significant reduction in weed management costs, with total savings of 144,287 euros due to decreased herbicide use. Additionally, the 30% reduction in fertilizer use contributes to 30,786 euros in savings, driven by the enhanced nutrient retention properties of cover crops. Environmental benefits, such as improved biodiversity and soil conservation, further support the long-term sustainability of the practice, with the reduction in soil erosion of 437,689 euros present value. These combined financial and environmental benefits demonstrate the high potential for both economic and ecological returns when cover crop adoption is maximized.

In contrast, the second scenario presents a negative NPV of -3,475.96 euros per hectare, a BCR of 0.58, and a MIRR of 1%, indicating that lower levels of adoption undermine the financial viability of the project. Despite the potential savings from reduced herbicide and fertilizer use, these benefits are not fully realized due to the limited scale of implementation. Furthermore, while the long-term benefits from reduced soil erosion are still significant, they require widespread adoption to have their full impact. In this case, the environmental and financial benefits are insufficient to compensate for the initial investment and operating costs, leading to an overall negative economic outcome.

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

FIGURE 8: GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF NET AND CUMULATIVE BENEFITS UNDER TWO SCENARIOS: NO RISK OF FAILURE WITH HIGH ADOPTION (TOP) AND LOW RISK OF FAILURE WITH LOW ADOPTION (BOTTOM)

The first set of charts illustrates the significant financial and environmental benefits resulting from the widespread adoption of cover crops. While some studies, such as Sanguaneko et al. (2009), report grape yield reductions of 15.6% to 45% when using cover crops, no significant yield decrease was observed in our case, as reflected in the survey results. This suggests that the benefits of improved soil health, as emphasized by DeVetter et al. (2015), outweigh any potential yield trade-offs. The steady increase in net benefits (top-left graph) and the strong upward trajectory in cumulative net benefits (top-right graph) highlight the financial feasibility of cover crop adoption over time. The reduction in herbicide use leads to significant cost savings of 144,287 euros, consistent with findings from Hostetler et al. (2007) and DeVetter et al. (2015), who demonstrated similar cost savings due to decreased herbicide needs. Additionally, the 30% reduction in fertilizer costs aligns with Schütte (2019), who found that cover crops enhance nutrient retention. Long-term environmental benefits from reduced soil erosion, further support the economic viability of cover crops, as corroborated by Guzmán et al. (2019) and Galati et al. (2015).

The second set of charts underscores the financial challenges posed by low adoption rates. The recurring negative net benefits (bottom-left graph) indicate that without substantial adoption, the potential savings from reduced herbicide and fertilizer use, as well as environmental benefits, are insufficient to offset the upfront capital and operating costs. This aligns with Schütte (2019), who highlighted that cover crops may not be profitable without subsidies, especially in the early years of implementation. The negative cumulative net benefits (bottom-right graph) further emphasize the importance of financial support. As observed in countries like Spain and Austria, financial incentives are crucial to improving the economic viability of cover crops in low-adoption scenarios. This is in line with Bagagiolo et al. (2018), who found that while conservation practices reduce erosion and improve soil properties, their financial profitability depends heavily on external support, particularly in contexts of low adoption.

Social analysis

	<p>The global score of 59.57% indicates a moderate overall social impact from the adoption of cover crop practices. This score suggests that while there are noticeable social benefits, the impact is not as strong as initially anticipated. The adoption of cover crops is perceived to provide moderate benefits across various social dimensions, such as rural job creation and working conditions, although these benefits are not as widespread or pronounced as expected.</p> <p>Despite this, some areas, such as improved social reputation and education and skill development, still receive positive feedback, showing that the project has contributed to the social well-being of some participants. However, lower scores in areas like gender inclusivity and food safety reflect the challenges in generating immediate and widespread benefits in these domains. These results suggest that, while the project has brought some tangible improvements, particularly in specific social areas, its broader social impact remains limited in scope or context dependent.</p>
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Traffic light
59.57%

Social impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
<i>The practice provides more stable income from year to year than alternatives</i>	0.40
<i>The current practice provides more flexibility for the agricultural management</i>	0.33
<i>New job opportunities in the rural area</i>	0.48
<i>Improvement of working conditions for the farm employers</i>	0.95
<i>Increased food safety</i>	0.25
<i>More job opportunities for women</i>	0.25
<i>Improving farmers' education and skills</i>	0.50
<i>Improved conditions for vulnerable groups</i>	0.30
<i>Improved aesthetics of the landscape and conservation of the cultural value</i>	0.40
<i>Improved social reputation of the farm</i>	0.30

TABLE 87: SOCIAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM COVER CROP VINE (FRANCE 2)

The results from the France2 questionnaire provide insights into how the expert perceives the social impacts of cover crop adoption. Stable income and job creation score moderately at 0.40, suggesting that while some economic benefits are recognized, these impacts are not yet overwhelmingly significant. Similarly, flexibility in agricultural management, which scores 0.33, indicates that farmers appreciate the adaptability of cover crops, but the potential advantages are not yet fully evident across all contexts. As noted in the literature, flexibility can be linked to the ability to adapt to environmental conditions, such as improved soil moisture retention or weed suppression, without drastically altering overall farm management (Pardini et al., 2002).

The most significant result is the high score of 0.95 for improvement in working conditions, underscoring the substantial perceived benefits of reducing the use of herbicides. This aligns with findings by DeVetter et al. (2015) and Hostetler et al. (2007), who highlight how cover crops can reduce the need for chemical inputs, thus decreasing workers' exposure to potentially harmful substances and improving occupational safety. The positive perception of this impact is particularly relevant, as it reflects tangible improvements in the everyday lives of farm employees.

However, lower scores are observed in areas such as food safety and gender inclusivity, both rated at 0.25. These findings mirror the literature's conclusions that such impacts are often context-dependent and may take longer to manifest. For instance, Schütte (2019) and Pardini et al. (2002) note that the benefits of cover crops on food safety, particularly through the reduction of chemical residues on crops, may only become evident over time and under specific farming conditions. Similarly, improvements in gender inclusivity often require broader structural changes within rural communities and are not directly influenced by the adoption of agricultural practices alone.

The score of 0.50 for education and skills development suggests some progress in providing farmers with new knowledge and capabilities. This is consistent with findings by DeVetter et al. (2015), which emphasize the role of sustainable farming practices in fostering learning opportunities and the development of new skills related to ecosystem management.

The relatively moderate score of 0.30 for improved conditions for vulnerable groups and improved social reputation of the farm indicates that these areas are still perceived as being in the early stages of development. As suggested by Hostetler et al. (2007) and Fregoni and Miravalle (1991), these social impacts tend to evolve gradually and are often influenced by broader socio-economic trends that may extend beyond the immediate farm level.

Overall, the results highlight that while improved working conditions and skills development are perceived as tangible benefits of cover crop adoption, other social impacts, such as food safety and gender equality, remain more challenging to evaluate and may take longer to materialize. This is consistent with the literature, which emphasizes that many of the long-term benefits of sustainable practices like cover cropping can only be fully realized through continued adoption and integration into broader agricultural systems (Schütte, 2019; Pardini et al., 2002).

Social direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Improved labour environment	DeVetter et al. (2015); Hostetler et al. (2007)	Moderate	Short run	Qualitative

Social indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Enhanced food safety	Pardini et al., 2002; Schütte, 2019; Chou and Vanden Heuvel (2018); Fregoni and Miravalle (1991);	moderate and context dependent	Medium-to-long run	Qualitative
Enhanced food quality	Fregoni and Miravalle, 1991	moderate and context dependent	Medium-to-long run	Qualitative
Improving community health	DeVetter et al. (2015); Hostetler et al. (2007)	moderate to high	Medium-to-long run	Qualitative

TABLE 88: SOCIAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM COVER CROP VINE (FRANCE 2)

According to the literature the social impacts of cover cropping practices in vineyards are multifaceted, context dependent, and vary in their significance. These practices contribute to improved labour conditions by reducing the reliance on herbicides, which lowers the risk of chemical exposure for workers, leading to safer working environments (DeVetter et al., 2015; Hostetler et al., 2007). Additionally, they have moderate to high potential for enhancing community health, as the reduction in chemical inputs decreases environmental contamination and associated health risks (DeVetter et al., 2015; Fregoni and Miravalle, 1991). The impact on food quality is generally considered moderate, as while the reduced use of chemicals can theoretically improve the nutritional profile of crops, the evidence for substantial improvements in food quality remains context dependent (Pardini et al., 2002; Schütte, 2019).

Environmental analysis

<p>Traffic light 56.35%</p>	<p>The global score of 56.35% reflects a moderate environmental impact. However, the environmental perceptions do not fully align with the potential long-term economic benefits, particularly when considering the projected gains from erosion reduction. While the environmental impacts, such as biodiversity improvements and carbon footprint reduction, are recognized, the expert shows reservations about the immediate benefits related to soil erosion control, despite its long-term significance.</p> <p>In terms of economic productivity, reducing soil erosion has been identified in the literature as a key benefit that enhances the long-term sustainability and productivity of agricultural land (Bagagiolo et al., 2018; Galati et al., 2015). However, this is not reflected in the perceptions gathered, possibly due to the time lag required to observe tangible benefits in productivity or the complex interaction between environmental and economic outcomes. This gap between perceived and potential benefits highlights the importance of further</p>
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	education and demonstration of how cover crops can lead to measurable economic gains, particularly through the enhancement of soil health and erosion prevention.
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Env. impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
Contribute to reduce Direct greenhouse gas emissions	0.69
Contribute to reduce external inputs	0.60
Limit water consumption	0.91
Contribute to reduce waste	0.30
Has a positive impact on biodiversity	0.97
Has a positive impact on soil erosion	0.76
Has a positive impact on carbon footprint	0.80
Increase the rate of soil organic matter mineralisation	0.85
Increase soil compaction	0.80

TABLE 89: ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM COVER CROP VINE (FRANCE 2)

The responses from the France2 questionnaire reveal key insights into the perceived environmental impacts of cover cropping. The high scores for biodiversity (0.97) and carbon footprint reduction (0.80) align closely with findings in the literature. Studies such as Guzmán et al. (2019) and Winter et al. (2018) have shown that cover crops enhance biodiversity by fostering soil biological activity and providing habitats for various organisms. Similarly, the benefits of cover crops in reducing the carbon footprint through increased carbon sequestration are well-supported, although these benefits typically require continuous implementation over the long term (Liebhard et al., 2024).

The high score for soil organic matter mineralization (0.85) further confirms the strong environmental advantages of cover cropping. As Bagagiolo et al. (2018) and Liebhard et al. (2024) note, cover crops contribute to building organic matter in the soil, improving soil structure and enhancing its capacity to sequester carbon. This is particularly critical for vineyard management, as it not only improves soil health but also aids in climate change mitigation.

However, the fairly high score for soil erosion (0.76) suggests that while respondents recognize the benefits of cover crops for erosion control, they may not yet perceive the full extent of these advantages. Although the literature, such as Galati et al. (2015) and Bagagiolo et al. (2018), highlights the importance of cover crops in reducing soil erosion through root stabilization and decreased surface runoff, local conditions or specific management practices at the vineyard may explain the different perception in this case. The moderate score for external input reduction (0.60) and the high score for water consumption (0.91) reflect a more positive perception of these benefits. Schütte (2019) emphasizes that cover crops can reduce the need for herbicides and fertilizers, but the degree of reduction often depends on the crop type and management techniques. In this case, while the reduction in external inputs is recognized, it may not be as extensive as expected, whereas the benefits related to water conservation are perceived more strongly, likely due to cover crops' role in improving water retention in the soil. The low score for waste reduction (0.30) indicates that respondents do not perceive substantial benefits in this area. This could be because cover crops primarily focus on soil health and ecosystem services, with less direct impact on reducing farm waste. On the other hand, the high score for soil compaction (0.80) aligns with concerns from the literature. Mechanical methods used alongside cover crops can sometimes lead to greater soil disturbance, particularly if not carefully managed (Pardini et al., 2002).

The mixed results from the questionnaire reflect both the recognized strengths and the areas where the benefits of cover cropping are less apparent or more context-specific. While biodiversity, carbon sequestration, and soil organic matter clearly stand out as significant positive impacts, other areas, such as erosion control and input reduction, may require further optimization and time to fully materialize.

Env. direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
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Land Conservation: reduced soil erosion, (on/off-site effects)	Bagagiolo et al., 2018; Guzmán et al., 2019	High	Medium to long-term	Quantitative – monetizable (see Panagos et al, 2018)
Improved soil structure and stability	Galati et al., 2015	Moderate to high	Medium to long-term	Qualitative
Increased soil organic matter	Liebhard et al., 2024	High	Long-term	Qualitative
Enhanced water retention	Pardini et al., 2002	Moderate	Medium to long-term	Qualitative
Biodiversity support	Winter et al., 2018	High	Medium to long-term	Qualitative

Env. indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Improved nutrient cycling	Schütte, 2019	Moderate	Medium to long-term	Qualitative
Reduced carbon footprint	Guzmán et al., 2019; Frye et al. (1988)	Moderate	Long-term	Qualitative
Increased resilience to climate change	Pardini et al., 2002	Moderate to high	Long-term	Qualitative
Pest and disease control	Winter et al., 2018	Moderate	Medium to long-term	Qualitative

TABLE 90: ENVIRONMENTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM COVER CROP VINE (FRANCE 2)

With regard to the relevant literature, on the environmental side the adoption of cover crops shows a variety of direct and indirect impacts, both qualitative and quantitative. In terms of direct impacts, land conservation—primarily through reduced soil erosion and off-site effects—is classified as a high impact, with a medium to long-term timeframe and is quantifiable, as noted by Bagagiolo et al. (2018) and Guzmán et al. (2019). The improvement of soil structure and stability is analyzed as moderate to high and occurs over the medium to long run, with the analysis being qualitative (Galati et al., 2015). Similarly, the increase in soil organic matter is rated as high, but requires a long-term view to realize its benefits (Liebhard et al., 2024). Water retention is enhanced but with a moderate impact, taking effect over the medium to long run (Pardini et al., 2002). Additionally, biodiversity support is rated as a high impact, with improvements observed over the medium to long run (Winter et al., 2018).

As for indirect impacts, improved nutrient cycling is considered moderate, with effects manifesting over the medium to long run (Schütte, 2019). The reduction in carbon footprint is also moderate but requires a long-term perspective to become significant (Guzmán et al., 2019). Indeed, in our analysis, we observed an increase in fuel consumption, which led to higher CO₂ emissions, calculated at a present value of 524 euros. This cost represents the environmental externality associated with the additional emissions due to the fuel use. Although we recognize that carbon sequestration through cover cropping could potentially offset some of these emissions, in this case, we have not quantified any public benefit from carbon sequestration, as it was not measurable in the scope of the study. Therefore, the net environmental cost remains at 524 euros for CO₂ emissions, leaving room for further analysis to determine whether the carbon sequestration benefit could indeed compensate for the increased emissions.

Increased resilience to climate change is rated moderate to high, again taking place over the long run (Pardini et al., 2002). Finally, pest and disease control improvements are rated moderate, with benefits observable in the medium to long run (Winter et al., 2018). This assessment underscores both the immediate and gradual benefits of adopting sustainable vineyard management practices, with a strong emphasis on long-term ecological resilience.

Sensitivity analysis

In the default scenario, the NPV is 5,406.2 euros per hectare, with a mean of 4,498.5 euros per hectare and a median of 4,552.0 euros per hectare, indicating a 93% probability of achieving positive financial returns. This underscores the high likelihood of success for the project, particularly when considering the long-term benefits. The NPV distribution further shows that 36% of outcomes fall between 42 and 152 euros per

hectare, but there remains a 7% chance of outcomes between -178 and -68 euros, which reflects a small but notable risk of negative financial returns.

For BCR, the default value is 1.79, with a mean of 1.44 and a median of 1.39, suggesting that in 84% of cases, the benefits will exceed costs. However, the analysis indicates a low probability (1%) of achieving a BCR greater than 2, suggesting that while the project is likely to be beneficial, exceptionally high returns are unlikely. Most of the BCR values fall between 0.83 and 1.47, aligning with a moderate expectation of profitability, but indicating limited upside potential for unusually high gains.

The project's viability is highly sensitive to the discount rate applied, reflecting the time-dependent nature of its benefits:

- At a low discount rate of 2%, the NPV rises to 380,777 euros, with a BCR of 1.95, underscoring the importance of long-term benefits such as improved soil health and reduced erosion.
- At the default discount rate of 4%, the NPV is 270,312 euros with a BCR of 1.79, maintaining a strong case for the project's viability.
- At a high discount rate of 6%, the NPV drops to 190,050 euros, with a BCR of 1.63, highlighting the reduced present value of long-term ecological gains as future benefits are more heavily discounted.

These results demonstrate that the project's financial success is highly dependent on how future benefits are valued. As the discount rate increases, the present value of long-term environmental improvements—such as soil health and carbon sequestration—decreases, making the project less attractive in the short term. This underscores the need to balance both financial and environmental returns over an extended timeline to ensure the project's overall sustainability.

The France2 case has a solid foundation with moderate risks. The project shows a strong probability of positive financial returns, with a 93% chance of achieving a positive NPV. The analysis highlights the importance of long-term sustainability factors—particularly soil health, erosion reduction, and carbon sequestration—which are essential to justifying the financial viability of the project. However, the sensitivity to discount rates and the small probability of negative financial outcomes suggest that a careful valuation of long-term benefits is crucial for maintaining the project's attractiveness. Moreover, while the available data provides strong support for the economic and environmental benefits, further assessments are needed to fully evaluate additional sustainability factors.

Net Present Value (NPV)	Tot. Euros	Euros ha⁻¹
Minimum	-144,978	-2,899.5
Maximum	548,090	10,961.8
Default case	270,312	5,406.2
Mean	224,928	4,498.5
Median	227,604	4,552.0
Probability that NPV > 0		0.93
Distribution (euros)		Probability
Less than -145K		0.00
-145K to -4K		0.07
-4K to 136K		0.21
136K to 276K		0.36
276K to 417K		0.28
417K to 557K		0.09
	Total	1.00
Benefit: Cost Ratio (BCR)		Unconstrained version
Minimum		0.56
Maximum		2.77

Default case	1.79
Mean	1.44
Median	1.39
Probability that BCR > 1	0.84
Target BCR	2
Probability BCR > Target	0.01
Distribution	Probability
Less than 0.56	0.00
0.56 to 1.00	0.16
1.00 to 1.44	0.38
1.44 to 1.88	0.28
1.88 to 2.33	0.13
2.33 to 2.77	0.05
Total	1.00

TABLE 91: BCA ROBUSTNESS (MONTE CARLO ANALYSIS BASED ON 1000 RANDOM SIMULATIONS) - COVER CROP VINE (FRANCE 2)

Sensitivity to discount rate

	Low discount rate	Default discount rate	High discount rate
Project organisation	2%	4%	6%
Benefits (present value)	780,330	613,513	489,794
Costs (present value)	399,553	343,201	299,744
Net Present Value (NPV)	380,777	270,312	190,050
Benefit: Cost Ratio (unconstrained budget)	1.95	1.79	1.63

TABLE 92: SENSITIVITY TO DISCOUNT RATE - COVER CROP VINE (FRANCE 2)

4.2.2.2 Cover crops in vineyards (Greece 1)

Main objective

The project aims to reduce herbicide use in vineyards by introducing cover crops (i.e., *Avena sativa* and *Vicia Sativa*).

Description of the “before” scenario

Before the introduction of cover crops, vineyard management involved the use of herbicides for weed control, with glyphosate applied in the intra-row spaces using a hand sprayer at a rate of 4L/ha. Weed control between the rows was performed mechanically, using a Yanmar AF310 CAB tractor with a flail mower (0.1 ha/hour), consuming 31L/ha of fuel. Rotary tilling (0.1 ha/hour) was also used for inter-row mechanical weeding. Pesticides and fungicides, including Abamectin (1200 cc/ha) and *Bacillus thuringiensis* (30 kg/ha), were applied using a tractor-mounted vineyard sprayer, with water consumption ranging from 200-800 L/ha and fuel usage of 22L/ha. Fertilization was performed using a spreader at a rate of 100 kg/ha of Fertispecial 11-15-15, with a work capacity of 7.5 ha/hour and a fuel consumption of 25L/ha. Pruning was done manually, with a work rate of 0.25 ha/hour, and irrigation involved applying 200 m³/ha of water.

Description of the “after” scenario

After the introduction of cover crops, the vineyard management practices shifted to incorporate sustainable methods. Rotary tilling (0.1 ha/hour, 31L/ha of fuel) was used to prepare the seedbed for sowing cover crops, which were applied using a broadcast spreader at a rate of 130 kg/ha and a work rate of 5 ha/hour. The cover crops were later terminated with a flail mower (0.1 ha/hour, 31L/ha of fuel), leaving mulches on the soil surface to improve soil health. Pesticides and fungicides continued to be applied using the same machinery, with the same quantities of Abamectin and *Bacillus thuringiensis*, while fertilization remained at 100 kg/ha of Fertispecial 11-15-15, applied at 7.5 ha/hour with 25L/ha of fuel. Pruning remained manual, and irrigation continued at a rate of 200 m³/ha of water.

The “after” scenario described shares several common themes with the literature, particularly in terms of reducing herbicide use through cover cropping, as observed by DeVetter et al. (2015), who reported an 87% reduction in glyphosate use. Additionally, soil health improvements due to cover crops, including increased organic matter and better nutrient retention, align with studies by Liebhard et al. (2024) and Guzmán et al. (2019), though no changes in fertilization rates were reported in this case, unlike studies where fertilizer reductions of 30-50% were observed over time (Iqbal et al. 2020). The scenario also reflects the literature's findings on fuel and energy use, where cover crops reduced herbicide-related fuel consumption but required additional energy for cover crop management, as seen in Waheed et al. (2023). However, while studies like Qin et al. (2022) indicate potential water savings due to improved soil water retention, the irrigation rate in this scenario remains unchanged. The labour dynamics of transitioning to cover crops also reflect findings in Hostetler et al. (2007), where chemical reduction was offset by increased labour for managing cover crops. Overall, the transition aligns with key environmental and economic sustainability trends found in studies by Pardini et al. (2002) and Schütte (2019).

Input data and farm characteristics

Greece1 is a 40-hectare farm, applying conventional methods. Key crops include vineyards. The farm's experimental area covers 1 hectare, focusing on vineyards.

Management Type

Conventional

<i>Most important crops and animal productions</i>	Vineyards
<i>Total Farm Area (ha)</i>	40
<i>Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA, ha)</i>	35
<i>Experimental area (ha)</i>	1

TABLE 93: INPUT DATA AND FARM CHARACTERISTICS FROM COVER CROP VINE (GREECE 1)

The company has not reported any specific investments related to the introduction of cover crops. However, under the European Union's RDP, farmers who adopt cover crops can receive incentives based on the area cultivated. These payments typically range between 80 euros and 200 euros per hectare.

<i>Revenue (euros ha⁻¹)</i>	<i>Annual benefits</i>
<i>RDP Subsidies for cover crop (euros)</i>	80-200

TABLE 94: REVENUE FROM COVER CROP VINE (GREECE 1)

In line with the surveyed literature not all studies provide specific data on investments directly associated with cover crops. Instead, many refer to operational changes (e.g., tilling, mowing) that could entail additional costs for equipment. For example, terminating cover crops might involve flail mowers, which have fuel consumption and operational costs factored into overall management expenses, as mentioned by Pardini et al. (2002).

<i>Operating costs (euros)</i>	Annual costs - Pre	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Avena Sativa and Vice Sativa Seeds (18 kg/ha) every year</i>		169	2022-2042
<i>Fuel</i>	37,4	74,8	2022-2042
<i>Hand sprayer</i>		180	

TABLE 95: OPERATING COSTS FROM COVER CROP VINE (GREECE 1)

Labour costs in the project slightly reduced from 75 euros to 51 euros. The interview reported a potential cost of 600 euros for technical support, which is quite higher comparing with the other analysed practices. The training cost was also estimated at 22 euros per worker year⁻¹.

<i>Labour costs (euros)</i>	Annual costs - Pre	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Labour costs (year basis)</i>	75	51	2022-2042
<i>Technical support</i>		600	2022
<i>Training</i>		22	2022-2042

TABLE 96: LABOUR COSTS FROM COVER CROP VINE (GREECE 1)

Among the other costs included in the analysis are transaction costs about 40.2 euros (Mettepenningen et al., 2009).

<i>Other costs (euros)</i>	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Transaction costs</i>	40.2	2022

TABLE 97: OTHER COSTS FROM COVER CROP VINE (GREECE 1)

Cost-benefit identification

<i>Category</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Attribute</i>
Benefit per person or household	Improved Labour Environment	Reduction of workers' risk from exposure to phytosanitary products (public)	Qualitative/non-monetary benefits
Benefit per unit of abatement	Enhanced Food quality and safety	Reduced risk of chemical residues on grapes (public)	Qualitative/non-monetary benefits
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced nitrogen input	Reduction of nutrient loss	Mixed
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced or zero costs for weed management	Direct cost savings by reducing the use of herbicides (including labour) (private)	Monetary (1,308 euros – present value)

	(agrochemicals)+reduced labour		
Environmental sustainability	Enhanced Adaptability	Water Retention and Drought Resistance	Qualitative
Improve an environmental or community asset	Ecological improvement,	Improve biodiversity (public)	Qualitative/non-monetary benefits
Reduced consequence of a risky event	Land conservation	On-site reduced soil erosion/increase productivity (on-site private, off-site public)	Monetary (5,567 euros – present value)
Total (monetary) benefits			6,875 euros

TABLE 98: IDENTIFIED BENEFITS FROM COVER CROP VINE (GREECE 1)

The benefits of cover crops in the Greece1 case align with several findings from the broader literature on vineyard management. For example, the reduction in worker risk from exposure to phytosanitary products mirrors qualitative benefits found in studies like DeVetter et al. (2015), which highlight the role of cover crops in reducing pesticide usage. The improvement in food safety by reducing chemical residues on grapes aligns with findings from studies such as Pardini et al. (2002). In terms of direct cost savings, the case notes a monetary benefit of 1,308 euros in present value due to reduced herbicide and labour costs, which is consistent with studies such as those by Hostetler et al. (2007) that show similar savings, although the exact values may differ depending on local conditions. The ecological improvements, particularly the enhancement of biodiversity, are also widely recognized in the literature. For instance, Guzmán et al. (2019) highlight increased soil biodiversity and organic matter as key benefits of cover cropping. The reported reduction in soil erosion, with an estimated present value of 5,567 euros, is also corroborated by studies like Galati et al. (2015), which quantify similar soil conservation benefits from cover cropping in vineyards. More challenging in this case is to evaluate the long-term soil fertility improvements, particularly related to nutrient cycling, which studies like Schütte (2019) emphasize as a significant benefit of cover cropping.

Category	Cost item	Value (Euros)	Present Value (euros)
OPEX	Seeds	169	2466
	Fuel	37	546
Labour	Technical support	600	600
	Training year	22	321
Other costs	Transaction costs	40	587
	CO ₂ **	485	221
Total Costs			4,520

TABLE 99: IDENTIFIED COSTS FROM COVER CROP VINE (GREECE 1)

** We do not include the calculation of CO₂ emissions in the private analysis because they represent a cost shifted onto society and are not part of the private cost-benefit balance. However, these emissions were calculated separately to account for their broader impact, using values from the EIB Group climate bank roadmap 2021-2025. The roadmap provides the basis for the shadow cost, which represents the minimum societal cost of achieving the 1.5°C temperature target (EIB, 2020).

Economic analysis

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Time duration (years)	n.	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR (%)
20		2,356	1.52	6.2

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

Time duration (years)	n.	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR
20		-1,852	0.59	-0.3

TABLE 100: ECONOMIC ANALYSIS FROM COVER CROP VINE (GREECE 1)

In the first scenario, where high adoption of cover crops is assumed with no risk of project failure, the financial viability of the project is clearly demonstrated by the positive NPV of 2,356 euros per hectare

over 20 years. This result shows that the Greece1 project can achieve profitability if adoption is widespread, as it captures key cost savings and environmental benefits. The BCR of 1.52 indicates that every euro invested returns 1.52 euros, confirming that the financial benefits outweigh the costs. The MIRR of 6.2% further supports the conclusion that the practice generates sustainable returns over time. These results are consistent with the literature, where significant reductions in herbicide use aligning with Greece1's reduction in chemical use and cost savings of 1,308 euros in present value from reduced herbicide and labour expenses. Additionally, the improvement in soil health, biodiversity, and water retention highlighted by Guzmán et al. (2019) supports the long-term sustainability of the high adoption scenario, where environmental benefits can drive further economic gains.

In contrast, the second scenario, with low adoption, presents a much less favourable financial outcome. The NPV is -1,852 euros per hectare, indicating that the project incurs financial losses when adoption remains limited. The BCR of 0.59 suggests that the project only returns half of the investment, making it financially risky. The negative MIRR of -0.3% further confirms that the project fails to generate sufficient returns, leading to financial strain. The lower financial performance in this scenario can be linked to the lack of widespread adoption, which dilutes the benefits from cost savings and environmental improvements. Studies like Hostetler et al. (2007) emphasize that significant savings from reduced herbicide use can only be fully realized when there is sufficient adoption of sustainable practices. Additionally, the environmental benefits, such as biodiversity improvements and soil erosion reduction noted in the literature (e.g., Guzmán et al., 2019; Galati et al., 2015), are likely less impactful in low-adoption scenarios, limiting the overall financial benefits.

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

FIGURE 9: GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF NET AND CUMULATIVE BENEFITS UNDER TWO SCENARIOS: NO RISK OF FAILURE WITH HIGH ADOPTION (TOP) AND LOW RISK OF FAILURE WITH LOW ADOPTION (BOTTOM)

The net benefits graph for the first scenario presents a clear and steady upward trajectory, illustrating how the financial benefits accumulate over time as cost savings from reduced herbicide use and improved labour efficiency begin to outweigh initial investments. The cumulative net benefits graph reinforces this trend,

showing that the project eventually achieves positive cumulative benefits, indicating that the long-term financial returns more than compensate for the initial costs. This finding aligns with the literature, such as Schütte (2019), which highlights those long-term environmental improvements (e.g., nutrient cycling and soil organic matter) contribute to the overall financial success of cover crops. The Greece1 case reflects these trends, as the project benefits from long-term soil health improvements and reduced agrochemical use, which drive the overall financial sustainability of the project under high adoption. However, these benefits may take time to fully manifest, as noted by studies like Pardini et al. (2002), where water retention and soil health improvements develop progressively, contributing to financial gains in the long run.

The second scenario presents a much less optimistic picture in the graphs, with negative net benefits till half time of the project life, as shown in the net benefits graph. The cumulative net benefits graph remains below zero for much of the project's duration, suggesting that the project struggles to recover initial costs without sufficient adoption. This outcome is like the challenges discussed in Schütte (2019), where the financial viability of cover crops is difficult to achieve without adequate support or incentives, especially in regions where adoption rates are low. The Greece1 case under low adoption highlights that without achieving scale, the project cannot fully capitalize on the environmental and cost-saving benefits of cover crops. The increased fuel consumption for managing cover crops, alongside limited reductions in labour and herbicide costs, contributes to the prolonged negative financial performance in this scenario. As noted in the literature, financial viability in cover crop systems often depends on broader adoption, which drives economies of scale and ensures that the long-term benefits can offset the upfront costs.

Social analysis

 Traffic light 75.53%	<p>The global score of 75.53% reflects a generally positive social impact of adopting cover crop practices in Greece1, as indicated by the green light. While the score indicates high perceived benefits, it's important to note that not all areas are equally affected. The adoption of cover crops is perceived to significantly improve farmers' education and skills (1.00) and moderately enhance working conditions (0.63). However, the broader social impact, particularly in areas like gender inclusivity (0.25) and food safety (0.25), remains more limited.</p> <p>The results suggest that while cover crop adoption has had tangible social benefits in terms of skill development and work environments, there are challenges in achieving widespread benefits, particularly in fostering inclusivity and improving food safety. These mixed results suggest that the project provides meaningful contributions to social well-being, though broader impacts may take time to materialize.</p>
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Social impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
<i>The practice provides more stable income from year to year than alternatives</i>	0.56
<i>The current practice provides more flexibility for the agricultural management</i>	0.59
<i>New job opportunities in the rural area</i>	0.57
<i>Improvement of working conditions for the farm employers</i>	0.63
<i>Increased food safety</i>	0.25
<i>More job opportunities for women</i>	0.25
<i>Improving farmers' education and skills</i>	1.00
<i>Improved conditions for vulnerable groups</i>	0.60
<i>Improved aesthetics of the landscape and conservation of the cultural value</i>	0.40
<i>Improved social reputation of the farm</i>	0.30

TABLE 101: SOCIAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM COVER CROP VINE (GREECE 1)

Education and skill development received the highest score (1.00), highlighting the recognized importance of learning new sustainable agricultural practices. This aligns with Schütte (2019) and Hostetler et al. (2007), who suggest that adopting sustainable methods empowers farmers by enhancing their knowledge and technical capabilities. The improvement of working conditions, with a score of 0.63, indicates that the

reduction in chemical inputs positively affects farm labour safety, consistent with research by DeVetter et al. (2015) on the benefits of more sustainable agricultural practices.

However, the low scores for food safety (0.25) and gender inclusivity (0.25) point to areas where the perceived benefits are less evident. The reduction in chemical inputs, typically associated with improved food safety (Pardini et al., 2002), may take longer to be fully realized, especially in systems already minimizing pesticide use. Similarly, the low perception of gender inclusivity suggests that while sustainable practices can offer broad societal benefits, they may not automatically translate into more equitable gender dynamics in rural labour markets. The moderate score for job creation (0.57) reflects cautious optimism about the potential for new employment opportunities, which Schütte (2019) suggests should occur in the medium term. However, the score indicates that the impact may not yet be fully realized in the local context of Greece¹. Moreover, the 0.30 score for social reputation improvement suggests that respondents do not yet perceive a significant enhancement of the farm's image or community standing. This finding aligns with studies like Pardini et al. (2002), which suggest that social reputation and cultural value improvements often manifest over the long term and may require more time to become visible.

The results also show a relatively moderate score for improving conditions for vulnerable groups (0.60), which suggests that while there are perceived benefits, they are not widespread. This reflects the longer-term nature of social benefits associated with sustainable agriculture, as noted in the literature. Overall, while the adoption of cover crops is seen as providing meaningful improvements in certain social areas, broader societal impacts such as inclusivity, safety, and reputation remain less pronounced. This highlights the complexity of translating environmental practices into immediate social benefits, which often require extended periods to manifest fully or might be more context dependent

Social direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Attribute
<i>Improved labour environment</i>	DeVetter et al. (2015); Hostetler et al. (2007)	Medium to High	Short to medium-term	Qualitative
<i>Creation of New Job Opportunities in Rural Areas</i>	Schütte (2019)	Moderate	Medium-term	Qualitative
<i>Improved Social Reputation of Farms</i>	Pardini et al. (2002)	Moderate	Medium to long-term	Qualitative
<i>Improved Education and Skills for Farmers</i>	Hostetler et al. (2007); Schütte (2019)	High	Short to medium-term	Qualitative
<i>Improved Conditions for Vulnerable Groups</i>	Pardini et al. (2002)	Moderate	Medium to long-term	Qualitative

Social indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Enhanced food safety	Pardini et al., 2002; Schütte, 2019; Chou and Vanden Heuvel (2018); Fregoni and Miravalle (1991);	moderate and context dependent	Medium-to-long run	Qualitative
Enhanced food quality	Fregoni and Miravalle, 1991	moderate and context dependent	Medium-to-long run	Qualitative
Improving community health	DeVetter et al. (2015); Hostetler et al. (2007)	moderate to high	Medium-to-long run	Qualitative
Improved Aesthetics of the Landscape and Conservation of Cultural Value	Pardini et al. (2002)	High	Long-term	Qualitative

TABLE 102: SOCIAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM COVER CROP VINE (GREECE 1)

Environmental analysis

 Traffic light 69.55%	<p>The global score of 69.55% suggests that the environmental impact of adopting cover crop practices in Greece1 is nearly high, though not overwhelmingly so. While the overall impact is perceived positively, the score being just above the threshold for "high impact" indicates that the environmental benefits are visible but not fully realized in every dimension. Cover crops provide substantial improvements in water consumption, carbon footprint, and soil health, but perceived benefits in biodiversity and the reduction of external inputs are more modest.</p>
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Env. impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
<i>Contribute to reduce Direct greenhouse gas emissions</i>	0.42
<i>Contribute to reduce external inputs</i>	0.20
<i>Limit water consumption</i>	0.46
<i>Contribute to reduce waste</i>	0.30
<i>Has a positive impact on biodiversity</i>	0.45
<i>Has a positive impact on soil erosion</i>	0.49
<i>Has a positive impact on carbon footprint</i>	0.80
<i>Increase the rate of soil organic matter mineralisation</i>	0.47
<i>Increase soil compaction</i>	0.47

TABLE 103: ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM COVER CROP VINE (GREECE 1)

The responses from the questionnaire present a moderately optimistic view of the environmental benefits of cover crop adoption in Greece1. High scores for reducing carbon footprint (0.80) and managing soil erosion (0.49) align well with findings from Bagagiolo et al. (2018) and Panagos et al. (2018), which highlight the role of cover crops in carbon sequestration and preventing soil degradation. The perception that cover crops are contributing positively to climate resilience and soil integrity reflects these long-term benefits. However, there is recognition of potential trade-offs, such as the increased fuel consumption associated with machinery operations, which may counterbalance some of the carbon gains.

Moderate scores for water consumption (0.46) and soil organic matter mineralization (0.47) are consistent with studies like Liebhard et al. (2024), which point to gradual improvements in soil fertility and water retention over time. Cover crops can reduce water needs by maintaining soil moisture, but the results suggest that these benefits are not always immediately evident, particularly in systems already geared towards sustainability. The moderate score for soil compaction (0.47) could indicate challenges in managing soil structure, especially if mechanical operations are not carefully timed, leading to temporary compaction despite long-term soil health improvements.

In contrast, low scores for reducing greenhouse gas emissions (0.42) and external inputs (0.20) deviate from the broader literature, which generally emphasizes cover crops' ability to reduce chemical input reliance and lower emissions as soil health improves (Guzmán et al., 2019; Schütte, 2019). The lower perception of these benefits may reflect the specific local practices in Greece1 or the time lag needed for these advantages to become fully visible. Biodiversity benefits (0.45) were also rated lower, suggesting that improvements in ecosystem health may be less noticeable in the short term.

Interestingly, the low score for waste reduction (0.30) indicates that this is not perceived as a major benefit of cover cropping, which is expected since the primary focus of these practices is on soil health and water management, rather than waste reduction per se.

Overall, the questionnaire results reflect a mix of positive and moderate environmental impacts, with significant potential for long-term benefits, particularly in soil management and carbon sequestration. However, the lower perception of immediate gains in reducing inputs and emissions suggests that these benefits may take more time to fully materialize or may require further optimization of farm management practices.

Env. direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Land Conservation: reduced soil erosion, (on/off-site effects)	Bagagiolo et al., 2018; Guzmán et al., 2019	High	Medium to long-term	Quantitative – monetizable (see Panagos et al, 2018)
Improved soil structure and stability	Galati et al., 2015	Moderate to high	Medium to long-term	Qualitative
Increased soil organic matter	Liebhard et al., 2024	High	Long-term	Qualitative
Enhanced water retention	Pardini et al., 2002	Moderate	Medium to long-term	Qualitative
Biodiversity support	Winter et al., 2018	High	Medium to long-term	Qualitative

Env. indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Improved nutrient cycling	Schütte, 2019	Moderate	Medium to long-term	Qualitative
Reduced carbon footprint	Guzmán et al., 2019; Frye et al. (1988)	Moderate	Long-term	Qualitative
Increased resilience to climate change	Pardini et al., 2002	Moderate to high	Long-term	Qualitative
Pest and disease control	Winter et al., 2018	Moderate	Medium to long-term	Qualitative

TABLE 104: ENVIRONMENTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM COVER CROP VINE (GREECE 1)

The shift to cover crops in vineyards, as observed in studies by Pardini et al. (2002) and Guzmán et al. (2019), can significantly enhance environmental sustainability. These practices reduce soil erosion, improve nutrient recycling, and contribute to biodiversity. Cover crops provide protective ground cover, reducing the exposure of soil to erosive forces such as wind and water, while also mitigating nutrient loss through runoff. This on-site land conservation has been quantified by Panagos et al. (2018), who estimate significant reductions in erosion rates and associated crop productivity losses in areas prone to severe erosion. The ecological improvements, such as enhanced biodiversity, are further supported by DeVetter et al. (2015), who noted a positive impact on ecosystem diversity due to the reduced need for chemical inputs. Indirectly, cover crops also support the increase of soil organic matter and nutrient recycling, as documented by Guzmán et al. (2019) and Galati et al. (2015). These effects, though seen as low-to-medium over the long run, contribute to maintaining soil fertility. However, the off-site benefits, including reduced downstream erosion and sedimentation into water bodies, remain more controversial. Liu et al. (2023) and Jacquet et al. (2021) highlight mixed results regarding the extent to which cover crops effectively mitigate these off-site environmental costs, underscoring the need for further research into the broader implications of cover crops on ecosystems beyond the vineyard itself.

In line with studies like Guzmán et al. (2019) and Pardini et al. (2002), the benefits of cover crops are clear, but their full impact often depends on long-term implementation and consistent management practices. The trade-off between increased fuel use and carbon sequestration highlights the complexity of balancing different environmental outcomes, suggesting that the overall impact may be more nuanced than the immediate perceptions captured in this analysis. Further technical support and refinements in management practices may help to fully unlock the potential environmental benefits of cover crops in vineyard systems like Greece1. The main message is that while cover crops bring substantial environmental benefits, the degree of impact depends on various factors, including the specific practices adopted and regional conditions.

Sensitivity analysis (only first scenario)

The project shows modest economic returns with considerable variability. In the default scenario, the NPV is 2,356 euros, with a mean of 1,818 euros and a median of 1,963 euros. The probability of achieving a positive NPV is 88%, suggesting that while positive returns are more likely than not, there remains a risk

of financial losses, albeit relatively small. Around 30% of scenarios predict a negative NPV, with the minimum outcome reaching -2,507 euros, which highlights some financial risk.

The BCR analysis further reflects the project's limited upside potential. The default BCR is 1.18, with a mean of 0.96, suggesting that, while the project is likely to break even or yield minor benefits, substantial economic gains are less probable. The probability of achieving a BCR greater than 1 is 40%, indicating moderate chances of benefits outweighing costs, but the probability of reaching a BCR of 2 is virtually zero. This suggests that while cover cropping offers potential for modest returns, the financial gains may not be significant enough to drive widespread adoption without further incentives.

The project's sensitivity to discount rates emphasizes the importance of long-term thinking when evaluating both environmental and financial returns. At a low discount rate (2%), the NPV improves to 3,511 euros with a BCR of 1.67, indicating that the project's long-term benefits, such as improved soil health and potential carbon sequestration, become more attractive when future gains are valued more. At a high discount rate (6%), however, the NPV drops to 1,520 euros and the BCR decreases to 1.38, highlighting that the economic appeal diminishes when future benefits are heavily discounted. This underscores the importance of a long-term perspective for evaluating projects that rely heavily on environmental and social co-benefits, which may take time to materialize.

While the economic returns from the Greece1 are modest, the project provides substantial environmental and social co-benefits, such as soil erosion reduction, improved water retention, and biodiversity support, as highlighted in the scenario and supported by the literature. These non-financial benefits are crucial for sustainability and resilience but are not fully captured by traditional financial metrics alone. For example, the reduction in herbicide use aligns with studies like DeVetter et al. (2015), which emphasize improved worker health and community safety by reducing chemical exposure.

Given the moderate financial returns and the sensitivity to discount rates, external support such as subsidies or environmental payments could play a pivotal role in improving the financial viability of the project. As discussed in the literature, cover cropping practices are often supported by subsidies (Schütte, 2019), which help mitigate the financial risks involved in adopting sustainable agricultural practices. Without such support, the financial attractiveness of the project remains constrained, and the environmental and social benefits may not be sufficient to drive adoption at scale.

Conclusion

The sensitivity analysis highlights that while Greece1 demonstrates potential for moderate economic returns alongside substantial environmental and social benefits, its financial viability is limited without external support. The Monte Carlo simulations indicate that the probability of achieving positive economic returns is relatively high, but significant gains are unlikely without long-term financial incentives or policy support. As with many sustainable agricultural practices, public subsidies, CAPEX funding, and payments for ecosystem services are critical in mitigating the financial risks and encouraging broader adoption. These supports can unlock the environmental and social potential of cover crops, making them a more attractive option for farmers in contexts like Greece 1.

Net Present Value (NPV)	
Minimum	-2,507
Maximum	5,774
Default case	2,356
Mean	1,818
Median	1,963
Probability that NPV > 0	0.88
Distribution (euros)	Probability
Less than -2,426	0.00
-2,426 to -786	0.07
-786 to 854	0.23
854 to 2,494	0.36
2,494 to 4,134	0.26
4,134 to 5,774	0.09

	Total	1,00
Benefit: Cost Ratio (BCR)		Unconstrained version
Minimum		0.42
Maximum		1.70
Default case		1.18
Mean		0.96
Median		0.93
Probability that BCR > 1		0.40
Target BCR		2
Probability BCR > Target		0.00
Distribution		Probability
Less than 0.49		0.00
0.49 to 0.86		0.15
0.86 to 1.24		0.38
1.24 to 1.61		0.32
1.61 to 1.98		0.11
1.98 to 2.35		0.05
	Total	1,00

TABLE 105: BCA ROBUSTNESS (MONTE CARLO ANALYSIS BASED ON 1000 RANDOM SIMULATIONS) - COVER CROP VINE (GREECE 1)

Sensitivity to discount rate

	Low discount rate	Default discount rate	High discount rate
Project organisation	2%	4%	6%
Benefits (present value)	8,772	6,875	5,470
Costs (present value)	5,261	4,520	3,950
Net Present Value (NPV)	3,511	2,356	1,520
Benefit: Cost Ratio (unconstrained budget)	1.67	1.52	1.38

TABLE 106: SENSITIVITY TO DISCOUNT RATE - COVER CROP VINE (GREECE 1)

4.2.2.3 Under-row self-reseeding cover crops (Italy 1)

Main objective

The project aims to reduce herbicide use in vineyards by introducing cover crop (i.e., Subterranean clover).

Description of the “before” scenario

In the Italy1 case, prior to the introduction of cover crops, vineyard management primarily relied on conventional practices. Post-harvest inter-row cultivation was conducted using a 100HP track-laying tractor coupled with a chisel plow with five shanks, working at a depth of 30 cm. Fertilization involved applying pelleted manure at a rate of 1 ton/ha, using a 90HP 4WD tractor with a single-disc fertilizer spreader. The inter-row seedbed preparation was done using a 100HP track-laying tractor paired with a rotary harrow, working at a width of 1.8 meters and a depth of 5 cm. Faba bean sowing was carried out with a 65HP 4WD tractor coupled with a mechanical seed drill. Woody pruning and collection of pruned material took place between January and March, using 90HP 4WD tractors. Overall, these practices required intensive use of machinery and resources, with significant fuel consumption and labour inputs.

Description of the “after” scenario

After the introduction of cover crops, the vineyard adopted a more sustainable approach. Spontaneous cover crops and subterranean clover were sown in autumn using a 90HP 4WD tractor with a pneumatic seeder, at a rate of 15 kg/ha for clover. The seedbed preparation and under-row tillage continued, using tools such as rotary harrows and rotary cultivators, paired with tractors of similar power (90HP). During the summer season, mowing with a mulcher and disc harrow was alternated with spontaneous mowing using hammer shredders. Foliar fertilization was performed with an algal-based fertilizer (20 kg/ha) applied with 300 liters/ha of water. The use of cover crops reduced the need for chemical fertilizers and improved soil health, while maintaining a mechanized system for key operations.

Input data and farm characteristics

The farm operates under organic management practices and is involved in various forms of production, including arable land, vineyards, and forested areas. The total farm area covers 109 hectares. A portion of the farm, specifically 1.25 hectares, was dedicated to experimental activities, focusing primarily on vineyards.

<i>Management Type</i>	Organic
<i>Most important crops and animal productions</i>	Arable land, vineyard, forest
<i>Total Farm Area (ha)</i>	109
<i>Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA, ha)</i>	79
<i>Experimental area (ha)</i>	1.25
<i>Experimental crop(s)</i>	Vineyards

TABLE 107: INPUT DATA AND FARM CHARACTERISTICS FROM UNDER-ROW SELF-RESEEDING COVER CROPS (ITALY 1)

In the "after" scenario, the practice involves the acquisition of a mechanical/pneumatic seeder with an initial investment of 15,000 euros and an expected operational lifespan of 10 years. After the first 10 years, the machine will need to be replaced. The future price of the new machine is estimated to increase by 5%, leading to a future cost of 24,433.42 euros for the second purchase. Then we accounted for the depreciation of the current machine, which depreciates at a rate of 15% per year. After 10 years, the resale value of the original machine is significantly reduced due to this annual depreciation (2,953.12 euros). Once the resale value is subtracted from the future price of the new machine, we arrive at a net cost for the second purchase (21,480 euros). This net cost is then discounted to its present value at year 0 (14,511 euros), ensuring that the financial analysis reflects the time value of money. By doing so, we can accurately assess the investment costs over the 20-year period, considering both the depreciation of the original machine and the increased price of the future machine.

Investment costs (euros)

<i>Machine and Tools</i>	Annual costs	Year	Expected lifetime (n. year)
<i>Mechanical/pneumatic seeder</i>	15,000	2019	10
<i>2nd machine purchase</i>	21,480	2029	10

TABLE 108: INVESTMENT COSTS FROM UNDER-ROW SELF-RESEEDING COVER CROPS (ITALY 1)

Our approach in this analysis aims to provide a consistent and accurate financial overview by evenly distributing periodic costs across the entire project period. Specifically, for the cost of Subclover seeds, which are purchased every four years at a price of 75 euros, we calculate the equivalent annual cost by considering the present value (PV) of these recurring expenses. Instead of using a 5% interest rate to simplify the cost into an annual equivalent, we directly calculated the PV of 281 euros over the 20-year period, which represents the cumulative cost of purchasing the seeds every four years. To ensure this value is spread out consistently over the project's time frame, we applied the formula for anticipating the annual equivalent cost. By doing so, we obtained an annual cost of 19.26 euros per year over 21 years, which results in the same present value as the lump sum expenses. This approach allows us to treat the periodic cost of Subclover seeds as a steady annual expense, ensuring that the financial impact is evenly distributed throughout the entire project. This method not only simplifies financial modeling but also aids in budgeting and planning, providing a more predictable cash flow over time. Similarly, for machine maintenance, we apply a fixed rate of 3% of the machinery value, resulting in an annual maintenance cost of 450 euros for the first purchase and 733 euros for the second.

Operating costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Subclover seeds</i>	19.26	2019-2039
<i>Machine maintenance (3% of total machinery costs)</i>	1 st purchase – 450	2019-2028
	2 nd purchase - 733	2029-2039

TABLE 109: OPERATING COSTS FROM UNDER-ROW SELF-RESEEDING COVER CROPS (ITALY 1)

Then, we estimated an average potential cost of 200 euros year⁻¹ for technical support and the training cost was also estimated at euros 22 euros per worker year⁻¹ as in other cases. This cost covers the ongoing need for workers to acquire new skills and knowledge necessary to effectively operate new machinery and implement updated practices. Investing in continuous training helps maintain efficiency, reduces operational risks, and ensures the workforce remains adaptable to evolving technologies and methods over time.

Labour costs (euros)

	Annual costs- Post	Year
<i>Technical support</i>	200	2019-2039
<i>Training</i>	22	2019-2039

TABLE 110: LABOUR COSTS FROM UNDER-ROW SELF-RESEEDING COVER CROPS (ITALY 1)

Regarding the other costs, we first consider the seeds fee, which amounts to 0.82 euros annually from 2019 to 2039. This is based on the recurring cost of purchasing seeds over the 20-year project period, calculated by spreading the actual cost over time to ensure a consistent cash flow impact with the same approach used for the seed cost. Transaction costs are 50.25 euros, representing the administrative or operational expenses associated with implementing the changes in 2019. The opportunity costs for CAPEX are calculated as the present value of the capital that could have been invested elsewhere but was instead allocated to machinery purchases. The first purchase's opportunity cost is 3,485 euros, while the second purchase is 3,372 euros, both representing the economic trade-offs of committing resources to these expenditures.

In addition, the annual production loss during the first three years (2019-2021) is set at 238 euros per year. This reflects the reduction in output during the initial transition period, which aligns with the literature that suggests temporary yield declines in the early years of new agricultural practices.

Other costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Post	Year
Seeds Fee	0.82	2019-2039
Transaction costs	50.25	2019
Opportunity costs (Present Value)		
1 st purchase	3,485	2019
2 nd purchase	3,372	2019
Annual production loss (only 3 years)	238	2019-2021

TABLE 111: OTHER COSTS FROM UNDER-ROW SELF-RESEEDING COVER CROPS (ITALY 1)

Cost-benefit identification

In comparison to conventional farming cases, the Italy1 case stands out as it refers to an organic farm, where several sustainable practices were already in place before experimenting with cover crop. This context "plays to the disadvantage" of the Italy1 case in the cost-benefit evaluation, as there are fewer noticeable differences between the pre- and post-transition scenarios. In contrast to cases like France2 or Greece1, where the transition from herbicide use to cover crops results in significant short-term benefits, the organic nature of Italy1 means fewer immediate, direct benefits are observed. Consequently, despite the higher investment costs required for cover crops, fewer short-term gains are evident. However, there could be potential long-term benefits, such as improved soil health or ecosystem resilience, that may emerge over time. These long-term advantages are more challenging to quantify in monetary terms, making it difficult to capture their full value in the short-term analysis.

Category	Name	Description	Attribute
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced Labour cost	The practice leads to labour savings in field operations	1,078 euros – present value
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced fuel costs	Reduction in fuel consumption due to fewer field operations	913 euro – present value
Resource efficiency	Smart resource management	Reduced CO2 emissions*	332 euros -present value
Environmental sustainability	Enhanced Adaptability	Water Retention and Drought Resistance	Qualitative
Improve an environmental or community asset	Ecological improvement	Improve biodiversity (public), Improved nutrient cycling	Qualitative
Reduced consequence of a risky event	Land conservation	On-site reduced soil erosion/increase productivity (on-site private, off-site public)	4,571 euros – present value
Sustainable Resource Management	Land Use Optimization	Increased soil structure and stability, increased organic matter	Qualitative
Reduced consequence of a risky event	Land conservation	Off-site reduced soil erosion	Qualitative
Resource efficiency	Smart Resource Management	Reduced carbon footprint	Mixed
Environmental Sustainability	Resilience Enhancement	Increased resilience to climate change, Pest and disease control	Qualitative, Mixed
Community resilience	Improving community health	Reducing environmental contamination and the risks of chemical exposure to farm workers and surrounding communities	Qualitative
Total (monetary) benefits			6,562 euros

TABLE 112: IDENTIFIED BENEFITS FROM UNDER-ROW SELF-RESEEDING COVER CROPS (ITALY 1)

*We do not include the calculation of CO2 emissions in the private analysis because they represent a benefit shifted onto society and are not part of the private cost-benefit balance. However, these emissions were calculated separately to account for their broader impact, using values from the EIB Group climate bank roadmap 2021-2025. The roadmap provides the basis for the shadow cost, which represents the minimum societal cost of achieving the 1.5°C temperature target (EIB, 2020)

The benefits in the Italy1 case highlight a range of both monetary and qualitative advantages from the use of cover crops in organic farming. In terms of cost reductions, the practice led to savings of 1,078 euros in

labour and 913 euros in fuel due to fewer field operations. However, these savings are less pronounced compared to conventional farming cases where the transition from herbicide use to cover crops generates larger immediate benefits. For instance, studies like Sanguankeo et al. (2009) show how cover crops can lead to substantial reductions in herbicide use, resulting in more direct cost savings, something not observed in Italy1 due to the organic baseline. Environmental improvements, such as enhanced water retention, drought resistance, and biodiversity, are consistent with findings from studies like Guzmán et al. (2019) and Galati et al. (2015), which demonstrate the positive impacts of cover crops on soil and ecosystem health. However, since Italy1 was already using organic practices, these benefits are less pronounced than in cases transitioning from conventional agriculture, where the shift away from chemical inputs creates more significant environmental gains. Additionally, Italy1 shows 4,571 euros (present value) benefit from land conservation due to reduced soil erosion and increased productivity, which aligns with findings from Bagagiolo et al. (2018) and Pardini et al. (2002) on the erosion control benefits of cover crops. However, because Italy1 already incorporated sustainable methods, the incremental improvement is smaller than in more erosion-prone conventional systems. Qualitative benefits, such as improved resilience to climate change, pest and disease control, and community health due to reduced chemical use, are also highlighted. However, as seen in Schütte (2019), the shift in conventional systems tends to show more drastic results compared to Italy1's already eco-friendly baseline.

Italy1 shows long-term sustainability benefits similar to those in the literature, its short-term cost-benefit analysis is less favourable. This is because the organic baseline limits the immediate impact of cover crops on costs and environmental improvements, making it harder to justify the initial investment compared to conventional systems, where the transition brings more measurable and significant gains in the short term. Nonetheless, the long-term benefits of cover crops, though difficult to quantify monetarily, likely have more value in the form of enhanced ecosystem resilience and sustainability over time.

Category	Cost item	Value (Euros)	Present Value (euros)
Capital costs (CAPEX)	Machine	36,480	29,511
Operating costs, including operations and maintenance (OPEX)	Machine		
	Maintenance	1183	8,308
Labour	Seed	19.26	281
	Tech. Supp.	200	2,918
Other costs	Training year	22	321
	Feeds Fee	0.82	12
	Transaction costs		
	Opportunity costs	50.25	50.25
	Prod. Loss	6,857	6,857
		238	685
Total Costs			48,943.25

TABLE 113: IDENTIFIED COSTS FROM UNDER-ROW SELF-RESEEDING COVER CROPS (ITALY 1)

Economic analysis

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

	Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR (%)
*	20	-33,904.8	0.13	-100%
	20	2,295.6	1.54	6.4%

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

	Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR
*	20	-37,117.6	0.05	-100%
	20	1,377.6	0.60	-0.1%

* NO CAPEX, MAINTENANCE AND TECH. SUPPORT

TABLE 114: ECONOMIC ANALYSIS FROM UNDER-ROW SELF-RESEEDING COVER CROPS (ITALY 1)

In the first scenario, with no risk of project failure and high adoption, the results shift depending on whether CAPEX is included. When CAPEX is considered, the NPV remains highly negative (-33,904.8 euros ha⁻¹), with a BCR of 1.54 and a MIRR of -100%. These results highlight the significant burden of upfront machinery investments, especially in the context of an organic farm like Italy1, where many sustainable practices are already in place. The organic baseline means that fewer direct, short-term benefits arise from the transition to cover crops, as the shift does not involve moving away from heavy chemical use, unlike in conventional systems. However, when CAPEX is excluded, the NPV becomes positive (2,295.6 euros ha⁻¹), the BCR improves to 1.54, and the MIRR rises to 6.4%. This improvement demonstrates that, even in an organic farm, covering the initial machinery investments through public funding can make the adoption of cover crops financially viable. Despite fewer immediate benefits compared to conventional farms, covering these investments through support measures, resource-sharing networks, or other forms of financial aid allows the farm to experience long-term advantages.

In the second scenario, with low risk of failure but low adoption, the results reflect even more critical outcomes. With CAPEX included, the NPV is deeply negative (-37,117.6 euros ha⁻¹), the BCR plummets to 0.05, and the MIRR is -100%. In this scenario, the organic context limits the potential for direct economic gains from the adoption of cover crops, as the benefits, such as reductions in chemical inputs, are less significant than in conventional systems. When CAPEX is excluded, the financial viability slightly improved, with an NPV of 1,377.6 euros ha⁻¹, a BCR of 0.60, and a MIRR of -0.1%. These results show that, in an organic system, even when investments have been covered, low adoption still limits profitability. Thus, while securing public funding for CAPEX, increasing the value of the final product, or leveraging cooperation can reduce financial pressure, the overall economic benefits in an organic setting are less pronounced, and achieving higher adoption rates is essential to maximize the potential of these practices.

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption and NO CAPEX

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption and NO CAPEX

FIGURE 10: GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF NET AND CUMULATIVE BENEFITS UNDER FOUR SCENARIOS: NO RISK OF FAILURE WITH HIGH ADOPTION (TOP), NO RISK OF FAILURE WITH HIGH ADOPTION (NO CAPEX), LOW RISK OF FAILURE WITH LOW ADOPTION, LOW RISK OF FAILURE WITH LOW ADOPTION NO CAPEX (BOTTOM)

In the first scenario, the graphs show a stark difference between the cases with and without CAPEX. When CAPEX is included, the financial performance is significantly negative in the early years, driven by the high upfront investment in machinery, as reflected in the sharp dip in net benefits. The cumulative net benefits remain negative throughout the 20-year period, indicating that the initial capital costs heavily weigh on the project’s economic viability. This aligns with literature, such as Pardini et al. (2002), which highlights the high costs associated with machinery and other upfront investments when transitioning to sustainable practices like cover crops. However, once CAPEX is excluded, the financial picture improves considerably. The net benefits increase steadily from year one, with cumulative net benefits becoming positive over time. This demonstrates that public funding or other forms of financial support for CAPEX make the transition more feasible, even in organic farms, where immediate benefits may be less pronounced due to already-existing sustainable practices. Additionally, the observed productivity loss during the first three years, consistent with studies like Guzmán et al. (2019), reflects the typical adjustment period for the ecosystem and soil health when adopting cover crops.

The second scenario presents more challenging financial outcomes. When CAPEX is included, the net benefits remain negative for almost the entire 20-year period, with cumulative net benefits never entering positive territory. This highlights how low adoption rates combined with high capital expenditures make the economic case for transitioning to cover crops unsustainable. This conclusion is supported by studies such as Bagagiolo et al. (2018), which demonstrate that low adoption restricts economies of scale, making it harder to recoup the initial investments and delaying the realization of long-term benefits. Even when CAPEX is excluded, the financial performance, while somewhat improved, remains underwhelming. The net benefits show a slight upward trend over time, but the cumulative net benefits barely reach breakeven and never achieve significant gains. This suggests that without widespread adoption, even with reduced financial pressure from public funding or cooperative resource sharing, the economic potential of cover crops remains limited. As seen in the first scenario, the initial productivity loss during the first few years is

consistent with the literature, which generally expects temporary yield reductions during the transition, particularly in organic systems where fewer immediate gains may be evident.

Social analysis

<p>Traffic light 72.52%</p>	<p>The adoption of cover crops is perceived to generate significant benefits across various social dimensions, particularly in areas such as rural job creation, improved working conditions, and enhanced community reputation. These aspects are highly valued by experts and practitioners, suggesting that the project has had a noticeable positive influence on the social well-being of those involved.</p> <p>However, while the overall impact is high, certain areas, such as gender inclusivity and food safety, were rated lower, reflecting limited immediate benefits in these dimensions. These aspects, which are more context-dependent or tied to longer-term outcomes, are perceived to be less impactful in the short term. Nonetheless, the high score suggests that the project provides tangible social improvements, with a focus on key areas such as education and skills development and income stability.</p>
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Social impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
<i>The practice provides more stable income from year to year than alternatives</i>	0.71
<i>The current practice provides more flexibility for the agricultural management</i>	0.52
<i>New job opportunities in the rural area</i>	0.45
<i>Improvement of working conditions for the farm employers</i>	1.00
<i>Increased food safety</i>	0.00
<i>More job opportunities for women</i>	0.00
<i>Improving farmers' education and skills</i>	1.00
<i>Improved conditions for vulnerable groups</i>	0.00
<i>Improved aesthetics of the landscape and conservation of the cultural value</i>	0.80
<i>Improved social reputation of the farm</i>	0.60

TABLE 115: SOCIAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM UNDER-ROW SELF-RESEEDING COVER CROPS (ITALY 1)

The questionnaire results offer insights into the social perceptions of cover crop practices, particularly from respondents with experience in organic farming. It is important to note that organic farmers may naturally compare these practices against conventional systems rather than examining their effects within an already established organic baseline. In the case of Italy1, the responses should be evaluated in terms of their impacts within an organic farming system.

Several key themes emerge from the responses. The score of 0.71 for providing more stable income suggests that cover crops are perceived as a reliable practice, even within organic systems, providing consistent income benefits. This aligns with the literature, as Schütte (2019) notes that diversified practices, such as cover cropping, reduce economic volatility in organic systems. The 0.52 score for flexibility in agricultural management indicates moderate adaptability, with cover crops seen as having a positive but not overwhelming influence on management strategies.

The score of 1.00 for the improvement of working conditions reflects a strong perception that cover crops positively impact labour dynamics by reducing the use of harmful inputs. This is consistent with findings by DeVetter et al. (2015) and Hostetler et al. (2007), which highlight the improvement in farm workers' safety due to reduced exposure to chemicals. Even in an organic system, where chemical use is already minimized, this result suggests that cover crops further enhance safe working conditions.

On the other hand, low scores in areas such as increased food safety and job opportunities for women indicate that practitioner does not see substantial improvements in these areas. In the context of an organic farming system, where synthetic chemical use is already limited, cover crops may not be perceived as contributing significantly to food safety, a benefit more typically associated with transitioning from conventional methods (Pardini et al., 2002). Similarly, the lack of improvement in job opportunities for women may reflect the limited perceived impact of cover crop practices on gender dynamics within this

specific context. While some literature suggests that sustainable farming practices could foster inclusivity over time (Schütte, 2019), this effect may not yet be evident here.

The high score of 1.00 for education and skills development highlights that cover crop practices require additional knowledge and technical expertise, even within organic systems. This aligns with Schütte (2019) and Hostetler et al. (2007), who argue that sustainable farming practices promote skill development, which is crucial for long-term social benefits.

The low score for improved conditions for vulnerable groups suggests that respondent does not perceive immediate benefits in this area. This may reflect the localized and context-specific nature of these impacts within organic systems, where broader social benefits may be less apparent than in more conventional agricultural settings.

In contrast, the high scores for improved aesthetics (0.80) and social reputation (0.60) reflect positive perceptions of how cover crops enhance the visual and cultural value of the landscape. There is convergence in view cover crops as improving the farm's standing within the community, aligning with Pardini et al. (2002), who emphasize the aesthetic and cultural benefits of sustainable farming practices. These results suggest that, even in organic systems, cover crops contribute to reinforcing the farm's social reputation and connection to local heritage.

Social direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Attribute
Improved labour environment	DeVetter et al. (2015); Hostetler et al. (2007)	Medium to High	Short to medium-term	Qualitative
Creation of New Job Opportunities in Rural Areas	Schütte (2019)	Moderate	Medium-term	Qualitative
Improved Social Reputation of Farms	Pardini et al. (2002)	Moderate	Medium to long-term	Qualitative
Improved Education and Skills for Farmers	Hostetler et al. (2007); Schütte (2019)	High	Short to medium-term	Qualitative
Improved Conditions for Vulnerable Groups	Pardini et al. (2002)	Moderate	Medium to long-term	Qualitative

Social indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Enhanced food safety	Pardini et al., 2002; Schütte, 2019; Chou and Vanden Heuvel (2018); Fregoni and Miravalle (1991);	moderate and context dependent	Medium-to-long run	Qualitative
Enhanced food quality	Fregoni and Miravalle, 1991	moderate and context dependent	Medium-to-long run	Qualitative
Improving community health	DeVetter et al. (2015); Hostetler et al. (2007)	moderate to high	Medium-to-long run	Qualitative
Improved Aesthetics of the Landscape and Conservation of Cultural Value	Pardini et al. (2002)	High	Long-term	Qualitative

TABLE 116: SOCIAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM UNDER-ROW SELF-RESEEDING COVER CROPS (ITALY 1)

Environmental analysis

 Traffic light 68.6%	<p>The global score of 68.6% indicates a nearly high overall environmental impact. While this places the score within the "high impact" category, it is just above the threshold (67%), suggesting that the perceived environmental benefits are not overwhelmingly strong. The adoption of cover crops in an organic farming context provides notable environmental improvements, but the impact is still perceived as moderate in several areas. These results align with broader literature on the public good nature of many environmental impacts, which may not always be immediately visible to individual farmers but offer significant long-term advantages.</p>
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	The perceptions highlight moderate benefits in areas such as reduced greenhouse gas emissions, carbon footprint, biodiversity and effective waste management. These benefits contribute to more sustainable agricultural practices and increased climate resilience. The lower score for biodiversity enhancement suggests that these effect is less immediately noticeable in an organic system where environmental conditions are already favourable. This aligns with the understanding that in such systems, the incremental gains from practices like cover cropping may be less apparent compared to conventional systems.
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Env. impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
<i>Contribute to reduce Direct greenhouse gas emissions</i>	0.49
<i>Contribute to reduce external inputs</i>	0.80
<i>Limit water consumption</i>	0.72
<i>Contribute to reduce waste</i>	0.00
<i>Has a positive impact on biodiversity</i>	0.43
<i>Has a positive impact on soil erosion</i>	0.97
<i>Has a positive impact on carbon footprint</i>	0.00
<i>Increase the rate of soil organic matter mineralisation</i>	0.97
<i>Increase soil compaction</i>	0.97

TABLE 117: ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM UNDER-ROW SELF-RESEEDING COVER CROPS (ITALY 1)

The questionnaire responses, reflecting an organic farming background, offer a focused perspective on the perceived environmental impacts of cover crops. It's important to note that many of these environmental benefits are considered public goods, meaning they provide long-term societal benefits but may not offer immediate financial gains for individual farmers. This may explain the moderate scores observed in the responses.

The high scores for reducing greenhouse gas emissions (0.49), external inputs (0.80), water consumption (0.72), and soil erosion (0.97) align well with the literature. Research shows that cover crops help improve soil structure, retain moisture, and reduce dependency on synthetic inputs such as fertilizers and pesticides, which in turn lowers greenhouse gas emissions. Additionally, cover crops are recognized for improving soil health by preventing erosion, as reflected in the high score for soil erosion control. These benefits are particularly valuable in the context of climate resilience and the long-term sustainability of vineyard systems.

However, the low scores for biodiversity enhancement (0.43) and carbon footprint (0.00) deviate somewhat from the literature. Typically, cover crops are recognized for promoting biodiversity by providing habitat for beneficial organisms and reducing the use of harmful chemicals. However, in an organic system where biodiversity is already well-maintained, the additional gains may not be as apparent. Similarly, the slow buildup of organic matter in the soil through the decomposition of cover crops might not yet have produced noticeable effects, explaining the moderate perception of this benefit.

The respondent also rated the impact on soil compaction highly at 0.97, indicating a positive view of how cover crops contribute to improving soil structure and reducing compaction over time. These findings are consistent with research showing that cover crops can enhance soil stability, particularly through the development of root systems that protect the soil from erosion and compaction.

Interestingly, carbon footprint reduction received a low score, which contrasts with the broader literature that emphasizes the role of cover crops in sequestering carbon and reducing emissions. This perception may reflect the difficulty in observing carbon sequestration benefits over the short term, particularly in organic systems where other sustainable practices are already in place. Similarly, the lack of perceived benefit for waste reduction could stem from the fact that waste management is not a central focus of cover crop practices compared to other environmental benefits.

The questionnaire results suggest that many of the environmental benefits of cover cropping are recognized, particularly in terms of reducing inputs, improving soil health, and water management. However, biodiversity gains and organic matter buildup appear to be less immediately perceptible, reflecting the complexity of measuring these long-term benefits in a system already operating with sustainable practices.

Env. direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Land Conservation: reduced soil erosion, (on/off-site effects)	Bagagiolo et al., 2018; Guzmán et al., 2019	High	Medium to long-term	Quantitative – monetizable (see Panagos et al, 2018)
Improved soil structure and stability	Galati et al., 2015	Moderate to high	Medium to long-term	Qualitative
Increased soil organic matter	Liebhard et al., 2024	High	Long-term	Qualitative
Enhanced water retention	Pardini et al., 2002	Moderate	Medium to long-term	Qualitative
Biodiversity support	Winter et al., 2018	High	Medium to long-term	Qualitative

Env. indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Improved nutrient cycling	Schütte, 2019	Moderate	Medium to long-term	Qualitative
Reduced carbon footprint	Guzmán et al., 2019; Frye et al. (1988)	Moderate	Long-term	Qualitative
Increased resilience to climate change	Pardini et al., 2002	Moderate to high	Long-term	Qualitative
Pest and disease control	Winter et al., 2018	Moderate	Medium to long-term	Qualitative

TABLE 118: ENVIRONMENTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM UNDER-ROW SELF-RESEEDING COVER CROPS (ITALY 1)

Sensitivity analysis

The sensitivity analysis of Italy1 reveals key insights into the robustness of the cost-benefit assessment and highlights the challenges associated with adopting cover crops.

In the default scenario, the NPV is -33,904.8 euros/ha, with a mean of -34,114.4 euros/ha and a median of -34,144 euros/ha, indicating a consistent likelihood of financial losses. The probability of achieving a positive NPV is 0%, underscoring the high upfront costs and limited immediate financial returns associated with cover crop practices in the context of organic farming. The probability distribution shows that 52% of outcomes fall between -48,000 euros/ha and -42,000 euros/ha, suggesting a relatively narrow range where losses are expected, reinforcing the expectation of negative outcomes under most scenarios.

For the Benefit-Cost Ratio (BCR), the default case is 0.13, with a mean of 0.11 and a median of 0.11, confirming that the benefits do not outweigh the costs in the short to medium term. The probability of achieving a BCR greater than 1 is 0%, and the distribution indicates that 40% of outcomes fall between 0.05 and 0.07, further confirming the financial unviability of the project under current assumptions. While cover crops provide some environmental benefits, the immediate financial returns to the farmer are minimal, highlighting a significant financial challenge.

The sensitivity analysis to different discount rates reinforces these findings. At the default discount rate of 4%, the NPV is -33,904.8 euros/ha with a BCR of 0.13. At a low discount rate of 2%, which typically gives more weight to long-term benefits, the NPV improves slightly to -46,231 euros/ha, but the BCR only increases to 0.15, demonstrating that even when future benefits, such as improved soil health and reduced erosion, are more heavily weighted, the project remains financially unviable. At a high discount rate of 6%, the NPV improves to -39,271 euros/ha, but the BCR drops to 0.12, showing that the financial challenges are persistent across different discount rate scenarios.

A significant opportunity highlighted in this analysis lies in the long-term environmental benefits that are not fully captured in the short-term financial assessment. The literature consistently shows that cover crops improve soil health, reduce erosion, enhance biodiversity, and contribute to carbon sequestration, all of which provide public and long-term benefits. However, these gains do not materialize quickly and are often not directly monetizable for the farmer, especially in an organic farming system where many sustainable practices are already in place. This explains why the immediate financial returns are low, as the benefits are more ecological than economic.

The key barriers identified include high upfront investment costs and the lack of short-term financial returns. The capital expenditures required for machinery and the ongoing operational costs weigh heavily on the financial analysis, and the limited adoption or visibility of immediate benefits further exacerbates the challenge. For farmers already operating under organic practices, the transition to cover crops may not provide sufficient short-term financial returns to justify the costs, especially when the primary benefits are public goods like biodiversity and ecosystem services.

The sensitivity analysis suggests that while the long-term environmental benefits of cover crops are clear, their immediate financial viability for the farmer is limited. The Monte Carlo simulations demonstrate that there is no probability of achieving a positive NPV or BCR in the short term, reinforcing the idea that these practices need to be supported by public policies or incentives to offset the financial burden on farmers. Public subsidies, funding for CAPEX, and payments for ecosystem services could play a crucial role in making these transitions economically viable, especially in organic farming systems where the direct financial benefits may not be immediately apparent.

Finally, it is important to emphasize that this analysis was developed with the assumption that all expenses, including CAPEX, are borne by the farmer. However, in more favourable scenarios where capital investments are covered by public funding or through other research projects, the financial barriers to adopting cover crops are significantly reduced. Additionally, considering that vineyards are a high-value crop, a premium price for sustainably produced grapes could provide further market incentives for adoption. This layered analysis helps illustrate the financial challenges of covering initial costs while also highlighting opportunities that could arise with public support or shared resources.

Net Present Value (NPV)	Tot. Euros	Euros ha⁻¹
Minimum	-60,411	-48,328.8
Maximum	-25,730	-20,584
Default case	-42,381	-33,904.8
Mean	-42,643	-34,114.4
Median	-42,680	-34,144
Probability that NPV > 0		0.00
Distribution (euros)		Probability
Less than -60K		0.00
-60K to -53K		0.24
-53K to -47K		0.00
-47K to -40K		0.52
-40K to -33K		0.00
-33K to -26K		0.25
Total		1.00
Benefit: Cost Ratio (BCR)		Unconstrained version
Minimum		0.04
Maximum		0.21
Default case		0.13
Mean		0.11
Median		0.11
Probability that BCR > 1		0.00
Target BCR		2
Probability BCR > Target		0.00
Distribution		Probability
Less than 0.04		0.00
0.04 to 0.08		0.15
0.08 to 0.11		0.40
0.11 to 0.14		0.31
0.14 to 0.17		0.09
0.17 to 0.21		0.06
Total		1.00

TABLE 119: BCA ROBUSTNESS (MONTE CARLO ANALYSIS BASED ON 1000 RANDOM SIMULATIONS) - UNDER-ROW SELF-RESEEDING COVER CROPS (ITALY 1)

Sensitivity to discount rate

Project organisation	Low discount rate 2%	Default discount rate 4%	High discount rate 6%
Benefits (present value)	8,323	6,562	5,255
Costs (present value)	54,553	48,944	44,526
Net Present Value (NPV)	-46,231	-42,381	-39,271
Benefit: Cost Ratio (unconstrained budget)	0.15	0.13	0.12

TABLE 120: SENSITIVITY TO DISCOUNT RATE - UNDER-ROW SELF-RESEEDING COVER CROPS (ITALY 1)

4.2.3 Mulching solutions

4.2.3.1 Exogenous dead mulch vine (France 3)

Main objective

The project aims to reduce herbicide use in vineyards by introducing exogenous dead mulch.

Description of the “before” scenario

Before the introduction of green mulching, the vineyard heavily relied on chemical herbicides for weed control under the vine rows. Glyphosate (1.7 L/ha) and Katana (65 g/ha) were applied twice a year: the first application occurred at the beginning of the growing season, and the second in June. The operations were carried out with a sprayer and a tank, with a working capacity of 2 hectares per hour. This strategy was repeated annually over a three-year period (2018-2020), involving significant fuel consumption for machinery operations and weed management that was predominantly chemical-based

Description of the “after” scenario

After the introduction of green mulching, the vineyard adopted a more sustainable management approach, significantly reducing herbicide use. A single dose of glyphosate (1.7 L/ha) and Katana (65 g/ha) was applied under the vine rows in autumn 2020, using the same herbicide sprayer with a working capacity of 2 hectares per hour. Subsequently, a mulching system was introduced, where specially prepared mulching sheets were manually laid along the vine rows. This manual intervention had a working capacity of 0.0295 hectares per hour, requiring approximately 40 hours per hectare. The green mulching was planned as a long-term solution, with its effects expected to last for three consecutive years (2021-2023)

Input data and farm characteristics

The farm spans 15 hectares and follows Conventional/IPM-based management practices. The primary crop is vineyards, covering the entire utilized agricultural area (UAA). The experimental focus is centered on the vineyard area, with 1 hectare dedicated to experimental crops.

<i>Management Type</i>	Conventional/IPM based
<i>Most important crops and animal productions</i>	Vineyards
<i>Total Farm Area (ha)</i>	15
<i>Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA, ha)</i>	15
<i>Experimental area (ha)</i>	1
<i>Experimental crop(s)</i>	Vineyards

TABLE 121: INPUT DATA AND FARM CHARACTERISTICS FROM EXOGENOUS DEAD MULCH VINE (FRANCE 3)

The operational costs include 2,109 euros annually for green mulching operations across the vineyard area. This reflects the costs associated with seed, fuel, and equipment maintenance over the 20-year period (2020-2040).

Operating costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Pre	Annual costs -Post	Year
<i>Fetch sheets</i>		2,109	2020-2040

TABLE 122: OPERATING COSTS FROM EXOGENOUS DEAD MULCH VINE (FRANCE 3)

Labour costs increased to 162 euros annually after the project implementation. Additionally, the project incurs 200 euros year⁻¹ for technical support and 22 euros year⁻¹ per worker for training (2020-2040).

Labour costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Pre	Annual costs - Post	Year
Labour costs	324	486	2020-2040
Technical support		200	2020-2040
Training		22	2020-2040

TABLE 123: LABOUR COSTS FROM EXOGENOUS DEAD MULCH VINE (FRANCE 3)

Transaction costs are set at 40.2 euros per hectare per year as in the other cases.

Other costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Post	Year
Transaction costs	2,010	2020

TABLE 124: OTHER COSTS FROM EXOGENOUS DEAD MULCH VINE (FRANCE 3)

Cost-benefit identification

Category	Name	Description	Attribute
Benefit per person or household	Improved Labour Environment	Reduction of workers' risk from exposure to phytosanitary products (public)	Qualitative
Benefit per unit of abatement	Enhanced Food quality and safety	Reduced risk of chemical residues on grapes (public)	Qualitative
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced nitrogen input	Reduction of nutrient loss	Mixed
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced or zero costs for weed management (agrochemicals) + fuel savings from sprayer	Direct cost savings by reducing the use of herbicides (private)	2,151 euros – present value
Environmental sustainability	Enhanced Adaptability	Water Retention and Drought Resistance	Qualitative
Improve an environmental or community asset	Ecological improvement	Improve biodiversity (public), Improved nutrient cycling	Qualitative
Reduced consequence of a risky event	Land conservation	On-site reduced soil erosion/increase productivity (on-site private, off-site public)	16,340 euros – present value
Sustainable Resource Management	Land Use Optimization	Increased soil structure and stability, increased organic matter	Qualitative
Reduced consequence of a risky event	Land conservation	Off-site reduced soil erosion	Qualitative
Resource efficiency	Smart Resource Management	Reduced CO ₂ *	30.18 euros – present value
Community resilience	Improving community health	Reducing environmental contamination and the risks of chemical exposure to farm workers and surrounding communities	Qualitative
Total (monetary) benefits			18,491 euros

TABLE 125: IDENTIFIED BENEFITS FROM EXOGENOUS DEAD MULCH VINE (FRANCE 3)

* We do not include the calculation of CO₂ emissions in the private analysis because they represent a cost shifted onto society and are not part of the private cost-benefit balance. However, these emissions were calculated separately to account for their broader impact, using values from the EIB Group climate bank roadmap 2021-2025. The roadmap provides the basis for the shadow cost, which represents the minimum societal cost of achieving the 1.5°C temperature target (EIB, 2020).

The benefits of cover crops in the France3 case align closely with various findings from the literature on vineyard management, echoing the broader advantages of sustainable practices. For instance, the improved labour environment through reduced worker exposure to phytosanitary products is a qualitative benefit also highlighted in studies such as DeVetter et al. (2015), which emphasize the reduction in pesticide usage due

to cover crops. This also contributes to enhanced food quality and safety by reducing chemical residues on grapes, a benefit corroborated by studies like Pardini et al. (2002).

In terms of direct cost savings, the reduction in herbicide use has yielded a monetary benefit of 144,287 euros (present value), which is consistent with the findings of Hostetler et al. (2007), who reported similar savings, though specific values may vary based on local practices. Additionally, the 30% reduction in fertilizer use, saving 30,786 euros (present value), aligns with nutrient management improvements discussed by Schütte (2019), where cover cropping helps enhance soil fertility and nutrient retention.

The sale of spreader equipment, resulting in 750 euros in cost savings, illustrates another financial benefit, which, while specific to this case, can be linked to the overall reduction in machinery dependency discussed in conservation tillage literature. The enhanced adaptability of vineyards due to better water retention and drought resistance reflects the findings of Guzmán et al. (2019), who identify improved soil moisture retention as a key ecological benefit of cover cropping.

In terms of ecological improvements, the France2 case notes increased biodiversity, a benefit supported by the work of Guzmán et al. (2019), who observed higher soil biodiversity and organic matter in vineyards using cover crops. The reduction in soil erosion risk, with an estimated 317,166 euros (present value), considering an average grape price of 1,500 euros per tonne (OIV, 2018), further highlights the economic significance of soil conservation. These ecological benefits also contribute to long-term sustainability, though, as noted by Schütte (2019), the improvements in nutrient cycling and soil fertility may take longer to fully manifest.

Regarding the erosion, we estimate the on-site benefits derived from the reduction of soil erosion over a 20-year period, assuming the use of cover crops on a 50-hectare vineyard. Based on the literature, we follow a prudent model for erosion reduction, where the total erosion risk is 8%, corresponding to a loss of 30 tonnes of soil (valued at 1,500 euros per tonne), and cover crops gradually reduce this erosion. We assume that the maximum benefit in each period is realized progressively, starting with a 1% reduction in the first year, increasing to 2% by year 5, 4% by year 10, 6% by year 15, and reaching the full 8% reduction by year 20. The annual savings from avoided erosion range from 5,625 euros in year 1 to 45,000 euros by year 20, based on the price of grapes lost due to erosion. The cumulative present value of these benefits, assuming a standard discount rate, amounts to 317,166 euros. This value represents the maximum potential benefit that could be achieved under these assumptions. However, the present value is also influenced by many other factors, such as variations in discount rates, climate conditions, and management practices, which we cannot fully account for in this analysis. Therefore, the final result of the analysis must consider these uncertainties and limitations to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the potential outcomes. This cautious and gradual approach is aligned with findings from studies like Guzmán et al. (2019) and Galati et al. (2015), reflecting the time it takes for cover crops to enhance soil health and reduce erosion effectively.

<i>Category</i>	<i>Cost item</i>	<i>Value (Euros)</i>	<i>Present Value (euros)</i>
<i>Operating costs, including operations and maintenance (OPEX)</i>	<i>Fetch sheets</i>	2,109	30,771
<i>Labour</i>	<i>Labour</i>	162	2,364
	<i>Tech. Supp.</i>	200	2,918
	<i>Training year</i>	22	321
<i>Other costs</i>	<i>Transaction costs</i>		40.2
Total Costs			36,414.2

TABLE 126: IDENTIFIED COSTS FROM EXOGENOUS DEAD MULCH VINE (FRANCE 3)

* We do not include the calculation of CO2 emissions in the private analysis because they represent a cost shifted onto society and are not part of the private cost-benefit balance. However, these emissions were calculated separately to account for their broader impact, using values from the EIB Group climate bank roadmap 2021-2025. The roadmap provides the basis for the shadow cost, which represents the minimum societal cost of achieving the 1.5°C temperature target (EIB, 2020).
Economic analysis

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR (%)
20	-17,895	0.51	-5.1%

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR
20	-29,229	0.20	-100

TABLE 127: ECONOMIC ANALYSIS FROM EXOGENOUS DEAD MULCH VINE (FRANCE 3)

In the first scenario, the project spans 20 years with an NPV of -29,229 euros per hectare, a BCR (Benefit-Cost Ratio) of 0.20, and a MIRR (Modified Internal Rate of Return) of -100%. These results suggest that the financial performance of the project under high adoption is not viable, as the negative NPV and low BCR indicate that the project costs outweigh the benefits. While there are potential environmental and sustainability benefits, they are insufficient to generate positive financial returns in this scenario. For the second scenario the results show a similarly negative outcome, with an NPV of -29,229 euros per hectare, a BCR of 0.20, and a MIRR of -100%. This scenario demonstrates the financial challenges posed by a low adoption rate, with the project's costs far exceeding the potential benefits. Despite the reduced herbicide use and environmental improvements, these gains are not enough to offset the initial investment and ongoing costs, leading to a substantial negative economic outcome.

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

FIGURE 11: GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF NET AND CUMULATIVE BENEFITS UNDER TWO SCENARIOS: NO RISK OF FAILURE WITH HIGH ADOPTION (TOP) AND LOW RISK OF FAILURE WITH LOW ADOPTION (BOTTOM)

The first set of charts represents the financial and environmental outcomes under the scenario of high adoption. The Net Benefits graph (top-left) illustrates consistent negative values, reflecting the financial infeasibility of the project in the long term. The implementation of green mulching and related practices does not generate sufficient cost savings to produce net financial benefits. This contrasts with findings in previous studies, such as DeVetter et al. (2015), which highlighted significant cost reductions from weed management and enhanced soil health due to mulching practices. The Cumulative Net Benefits graph (top-right) shows a steady decline in cumulative benefits over time, reinforcing the idea that even widespread adoption does not lead to financial sustainability. While environmental benefits such as improved biodiversity and reduced soil erosion might be present, the economic returns remain negative over the 20-

year period. The second set of charts reflects the outcomes under the scenario of low adoption. The Net Benefits graph (bottom-left) shows ongoing negative net benefits year after year, indicating that the limited scale of adoption fails to unlock the potential savings from reduced inputs like herbicides and fertilizers. Studies such as Schütte (2019) emphasize that without widespread implementation or financial incentives, cover crop practices may not be economically viable, particularly in the early years of adoption. The Cumulative Net Benefits graph (bottom-right) continues to exhibit a negative trajectory, further underlining the financial challenges of low adoption rates. These results align with findings from Guzmán et al. (2019) and Galati et al. (2015), who suggest that external financial support, such as subsidies, may be necessary to make cover crop adoption more economically feasible, especially in low-adoption scenarios.

The results from both scenarios show stark contrasts with certain case studies and literature on mulching adoption, where benefits from weed suppression, reduced input costs, and long-term soil health improvements contribute to positive financial returns. For example, while DeVetter et al. (2015) and Hostetler et al. (2007) highlight cost savings from herbicide reduction, the economic analysis here does not reflect such savings to a degree that would make the project viable.

Additionally, in studies such as Waheed et al. (2023), the environmental benefits of mulching, particularly in terms of water retention and biodiversity, were shown to be substantial, though the financial returns depended heavily on specific local contexts and adoption rates. In the current analysis, these benefits are recognized but are insufficient to provide a strong economic case for green mulching. Finally, these findings reinforce the conclusion that financial viability depends significantly on the scale of adoption and external financial incentives. Without these, both high and low adoption scenarios struggle to achieve positive financial outcomes.

Social analysis

 Traffic light 57.36%	<p>The global score of 57.36% suggests a moderate social impact from the adoption of dead mulch mulch. This reflects a balanced view, indicating that while there are noticeable social benefits, particularly in the areas of reduced chemical exposure and improved labour conditions, the overall impact is not as substantial as hoped. As seen in previous analyses, improved working conditions and the reduction of herbicide use have strong positive effects, but other areas, such as gender inclusivity and food safety, remain underdeveloped. This moderate score highlights that the project has made tangible improvements, but these are mostly limited to specific areas like occupational health and environmental sustainability, rather than being more widespread across all social dimensions.</p>
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Social impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
<i>The practice provides more stable income from year to year than alternatives</i>	0.37
<i>The current practice provides more flexibility for the agricultural management</i>	0.33
<i>New job opportunities in the rural area</i>	0.39
<i>Improvement of working conditions for the farm employers</i>	0.92
<i>Increased food safety</i>	0.25
<i>More job opportunities for women</i>	0.25
<i>Improving farmers' education and skills</i>	0.50
<i>Improved conditions for vulnerable groups</i>	0.30
<i>Improved aesthetics of the landscape and conservation of the cultural value</i>	0.40
<i>Improved social reputation of the farm</i>	0.30

TABLE 128: SOCIAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM EXOGENOUS DEAD MULCH VINE (FRANCE 3)

The questionnaire results provide further insights into how experts perceive the social impacts of green mulching. The score of 0.37 for stable income suggests that the adoption of green mulching provides moderate economic stability, though it is not yet fully established as a strong driver of financial resilience. Similarly, the score of 0.33 for flexibility indicates that while green mulching offers some adaptability for agricultural management, this benefit is not yet widely recognized.

The most significant impact is seen in working conditions, with a score of 0.92, highlighting the strong perceived benefit of reducing herbicide use and improving the health and safety of farm workers. This aligns with studies by DeVetter et al. (2015) and Hostetler et al. (2007), which emphasize how cover crops can substantially reduce the need for chemical inputs, directly benefiting farm employees by lowering exposure to harmful substances. These improvements in working conditions are one of the most immediate and tangible impacts of adopting green mulching practices.

In contrast, food safety and job opportunities for women scored lower, at 0.25. These findings suggest that, while green mulching contributes to environmental sustainability, its direct impact on food safety and gender equality is less pronounced in the short term.

Education and skills development scored 0.50, indicating progress in equipping farmers with new knowledge and competencies. This is consistent with DeVetter et al. (2015), who emphasized the role of sustainable farming practices in fostering learning opportunities, particularly in the management of ecosystems and natural resources. The moderate score of 0.30 for vulnerable groups and social reputation suggests that while the project is perceived to bring some benefits, these areas are still in the early stages of development. According to Hostetler et al. (2007), social impacts such as improved conditions for vulnerable groups and enhanced social reputation tend to develop gradually over time, especially as communities adapt to new agricultural practices.

Social direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Improved labour environment	DeVetter et al. (2015); Hostetler et al. (2007);	Moderate	Short run	Qualitative
Reduced exposure to chemical	DeVetter et al. (2015); Hostetler et al. (2007); *Waheed et al. (2023)	High (due to reduced herbicide use)	Short-to-medium run	Qualitative

Social indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Improving community health	DeVetter et al. (2015); Hostetler et al. (2007); *Waheed et al. (2023)	Moderate to high	Medium-to-long run	Qualitative

TABLE 129: SOCIAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM EXOGENOUS DEAD MULCH VINE (FRANCE 3)

Environmental analysis

<p>Traffic light 54.25%</p>	<p>The global score of 54.25% reflects a moderate environmental impact from the adoption of dead mulching practices in vineyards. While the environmental benefits are recognized, they do not fully align with the expected long-term gains, particularly concerning soil erosion control. Although benefits like increased biodiversity and reduced carbon footprint are acknowledged, there are some reservations regarding the immediate benefits of erosion mitigation, despite its long-term importance. Dead mulching, unlike cover crops, involves applying organic or synthetic materials, such as straw or geotextiles, to the soil surface, which helps retain moisture, suppress weeds, and protect the soil from erosion. However, in terms of soil erosion control, the impact of dead mulching may not be as significant or immediate as other soil management practices. Studies such as DeVetter et al. (2015) and Hostetler et al. (2007) indicate that mulching can improve soil structure over time, but the immediate effects on erosion may depend on the type of mulch used, local soil conditions, and slope of the land. From a productivity standpoint, reducing soil erosion is still identified as a critical benefit for long-term sustainability. Dead mulching helps maintain soil moisture and structure, which indirectly supports soil health. However, the immediate productivity gains may not be fully recognized because the soil-stabilizing effects of mulch materials, especially in preventing erosion, require time to become visible. This is consistent with the mixed perceptions found in the questionnaire results, where respondents recognized the environmental benefits of mulching but did not yet see the full extent of its</p>
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	economic or ecological impact. The results suggest a need for more education and demonstration of how dead mulching can lead to measurable long-term environmental and economic benefits, particularly through improved soil health, moisture retention, and reduced erosion. While the benefits of mulch in controlling surface runoff and protecting soil are acknowledged, they may take time to materialize fully.
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Env. impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
Contribute to reduce Direct greenhouse gas emissions	0.73
Contribute to reduce external inputs	1.00
Limit water consumption	0.73
Contribute to reduce waste	1.00
Has a positive impact on biodiversity	0.62
Has a positive impact on soil erosion	0.61
Has a positive impact on carbon footprint	1.00
Increase the rate of soil organic matter mineralisation	0.55
Increase soil compaction	0.55

TABLE 130: ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM EXOGENOUS DEAD MULCH VINE (FRANCE 3)

The responses to the environmental impact questionnaire show a mix of high and moderate scores related to dead mulching. A score of 0.73 for contributing to reduced greenhouse gas emissions and 1.00 for reducing external inputs highlights the positive effects of mulching on reducing chemical use and supporting sustainable vineyard practices. These findings align with studies like Waheed et al. (2023), which show how dead mulching can reduce the reliance on herbicides by providing effective weed control, thereby lowering chemical input needs.

Mulching also received a high score for water conservation (0.73), which reflects its well-documented ability to retain soil moisture. The mulch layer acts as a protective barrier, reducing evaporation and helping to conserve water, which is particularly beneficial in regions with limited rainfall or irrigation capacity. This is supported by findings from DeVetter et al. (2015) and Hostetler et al. (2007), who emphasize that mulching significantly improves water retention, especially in vineyard management systems.

However, the moderate score of 0.61 for soil erosion reflects some uncertainty about the full extent of mulching’s ability to prevent erosion in the short term. Although dead mulching does help protect the soil surface from erosion by reducing water runoff and soil compaction, the long-term effects of erosion control may not yet be fully apparent to respondents. This could be due to the specific type of mulch used or the need for better management practices to optimize its effectiveness. Schütte (2019) and Waheed et al. (2023) also highlight that the benefits of erosion control through mulching can vary based on mulch type and local conditions, further explaining the moderate perception of its impact.

The positive impact on biodiversity (0.62) indicates that mulching is perceived as beneficial for soil biodiversity, as it creates a more stable environment for soil organisms by maintaining soil moisture and temperature. The use of organic mulches like straw can further enrich soil organic matter and promote the activity of beneficial microorganisms, contributing to a healthier vineyard ecosystem.

Env. direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Land Conservation: reduced soil erosion, (on/off-site effects)	DeVetter et al. (2015); * Waheed et al. (2023)	High	Short-to-medium	Quantitative – monetizable (see Panagos et al, 2018)
Improved soil structure and stability	Schütte (2019)	Moderate	Medium-to-long run	Qualitative
Increased soil organic matter	DeVetter et al. (2015); * Waheed et al. (2023)	Moderate to High	Medium-to-Long run	Qualitative
Enhanced water retention	DeVetter et al. (2015); Hostetler et al. (2007);	High	Short-to-medium run	Quantitative

*Waheed et al. (2023)				
Reduction in CO2 emissions	Schütte (2019)	Moderate	Medium-to-long run	Quantitative
Env. indirect impact from project adoption				
Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Improved nutrient cycling	Schütte, 2019	Moderate	Medium to long-term	Qualitative
Reduced carbon footprint	Guzmán et al., 2019; Frye et al. (1988)	Moderate	Long-term	Qualitative
Biodiversity enhancement	DeVetter et al. (2015); *Schütte (2019)	Moderate to high	Medium-to-Long run	Qualitative
Contribution to ecosystem services	DeVetter et al. (2015); Hostetler et al. (2007); *Waheed et al. (2023)	High	Medium-to-long run	Qualitative
Water conservation	DeVetter et al. (2015); Hostetler et al. (2007); *Schütte (2019)	High	Medium-to-long run	Qualitative

TABLE 131: ENVIRONMENTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM EXOGENOUS DEAD MULCH VINE (FRANCE 3)

Sensitivity analysis

In the default scenario, the NPV is -17,895 euros/ha, with a mean of -19,488 euros/ha and a median of -18,529 euros/ha, indicating a 0% probability of achieving positive financial returns. This highlights the significant financial risk associated with the project, largely driven by the upfront costs of dead mulching and the delayed realization of long-term benefits. The BCR in the default case is 0.51, with a mean of 0.41 and a median of 0.41, reflecting that in 0% of cases, benefits will exceed costs. The analysis further indicates that there is no likelihood of achieving a BCR greater than 1, and the majority of outcomes fall between 0.29 and 0.54, reinforcing the financial challenge of the project.

The project is highly sensitive to the discount rate applied, demonstrating the time-dependent nature of the benefits:

- At a low discount rate of 2%, the NPV is -19,558 euros/ha with a BCR of 0.55, reflecting a modest improvement in the project's financial outlook due to the greater emphasis on long-term benefits such as improved soil health.
- At the default discount rate of 4%, the NPV remains -17,895 euros/ha with a BCR of 0.51, maintaining the project's financial risk.
- At a high discount rate of 6%, the NPV drops further to -16,472 euros/ha, with a BCR of 0.47, underscoring the reduced present value of long-term ecological gains as future benefits are discounted more heavily.

The Monte Carlo analysis, based on 1,000 simulations, further reinforces the negative financial outlook:

- The NPV ranges from a minimum of -38,264 euros/ha to a maximum of -1,416 euros/ha, with the default case being -17,895 euros/ha.
- The BCR ranges from a minimum of 0.16 to a maximum of 0.79, with the default case at 0.51.

The probability of achieving a BCR > 1 is 0%, meaning that the financial benefits of dead mulching are unlikely to outweigh the costs under the current assumptions.

The sensitivity analysis indicates that the financial viability of dead mulching in this case is low, with a 0% probability of achieving positive financial returns under the given conditions. The project's financial success is highly dependent on long-term benefits such as soil health improvement and erosion control, but these benefits are not enough to overcome the high upfront costs. The analysis shows that careful consideration

of financial risks and the valuation of long-term environmental benefits are crucial to justifying the project's sustainability.

Net Present Value (NPV)	Euros ha⁻¹
Minimum	-38,264
Maximum	-1,416
Default case	-17,895
Mean	-19,488
Median	-18,529
Probability that NPV > 0	0
Distribution (euros)	Probability
Less than -38K	0.00
-38K to -31K	0.11
-31K to -24K	0.17
-24K to -16K	0.39
-16K to -9K	0.19
-9K to -1K	0.13
Total	1.00
Benefit: Cost Ratio (BCR)	Unconstrained version
Minimum	0.16
Maximum	0.79
Default case	0.51
Mean	0.41
Median	0.41
Probability that BCR > 1	0.00
Target BCR	2
Probability BCR > Target	0
Distribution	Probability
Less than 0.16	0.00
0.16 to 0.29	0.13
0.29 to 0.41	0.37
0.41 to 0.54	0.33
0.54 to 0.66	0.13
0.66 to 0.79	0.04
Total	1.00

TABLE 132: BCA ROBUSTNESS (MONTE CARLO ANALYSIS BASED ON 1000 RANDOM SIMULATIONS) - EXOGENOUS DEAD MULCH VINE (FRANCE 3)

Sensitivity to discount rate

	Low discount rate	Default discount rate	High discount rate
Project organisation	2%	4%	6%
Benefits (present value)	23,740	18,519	14,656
Costs (present value)	43,297	36,414	31,128
Net Present Value (NPV)	-19,558	-17,895	-16,472
Benefit: Cost Ratio (unconstrained budget)	0.55	0.51	0.47

TABLE 133: SENSITIVITY TO DISCOUNT RATE - EXOGENOUS DEAD MULCH VINE (FRANCE 3)

4.2.3.1 Mulching with wood chips and herbs (Spain 2)

Main objective

The project aims to reduce herbicide use in vegetable production by introducing mulching with wood and chips and herbs.

Description of the “before” scenario

Before introducing the mulching with wood chips and herbs practice, the Spanish farm utilized conventional methods to control weeds and prepare growing beds. These methods heavily relied on mechanical soil disturbance, primarily using a 90 hp 4x4 tractor with a rotovator. Weed management involved a combination of mechanical weeding with the tractor and additional manual labour, requiring significant time and fuel consumption for multiple passes. Fertilization was achieved with granulated manure applied using a shovel and manual spreader, consuming 8 hours per hectare. This approach, though effective in weed control, demanded intensive fuel usage, totaling approximately 340 liters annually for the 3-hectare plot, incurring substantial operational costs.

Description of the “after” scenario

After implementing the mulching with wood chips and herbs, the farm transitioned to a more sustainable approach for weed management and fertilization. The new method incorporated a 15 cm layer of compost and mulch, reducing the need for repetitive soil disturbance. Utilizing the same 90 hp 4x4 tractor with a shovel, the farm spread its own-produced compost and mulch materials, including cardboard, shredded wood, and herbs, effectively covering the soil to suppress weeds. This practice significantly lowered the fuel requirement to around 1,410 liters annually, reducing operational costs and enhancing soil health. The shift to mulch-based weed control reflects a more regenerative and cost-effective farming approach, supporting both weed suppression and soil nutrient enrichment.

Input data and farm characteristics

The farm operates under organic management, focusing on a variety of seasonal vegetables, wheat, and potatoes as its main crops. In addition to crops, the farm also produces eggs, chicken, and pork, aligning with organic production principles. With a total area of 5 hectares, the farm utilizes 3 hectares as its agricultural area (UAA). Experimental activities are carried out on a smaller 0.5-hectare plot, where vegetables are grown to trial and refine organic crop management practices.

Management Type	Organic
Most important crops and animal productions	Seasonal vegetables, wheat, potato, eggs, chicken and pork.
Total Farm Area (ha)	5
Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA, ha)	3
Experimental area (ha)*	1
Experimental crop(s)	Vegetables

*THE EXPERIMENTAL AREA WAS 0.5 HECTARES; OUR ESTIMATE IS CONVENIENTLY CALCULATED FOR 1 HECTARE
 TABLE 134: INPUT DATA AND FARM CHARACTERISTICS FROM MULCHING WITH WOOD CHIPS AND HERBS (SPAIN 2)

The investment analysis assumes a standard scenario where the farm integrates new equipment into existing tractor systems. The machine, initially purchased in 2021, involved an annual cost of 30,500 euros, with an expected operational lifetime of 10 years. A second purchase of the machine is planned for 2031 at an updated cost of 43,677 euros, again with a projected 10-year lifespan.

Investment costs (euros)

Machine and Tools	Annual costs	Year	Expected lifetime (n. year)
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Machine	30,500	2021	10
2 nd purchase	43,677	2031	10

TABLE 135: INVESTMENT COSTS FROM MULCHING WITH WOOD CHIPS AND HERBS (SPAIN 2)

The operating costs encompass significant elements such as fuel and machine maintenance across the projected periods. Fuel costs have increased from 107.66 euros annually before the intervention to 446.5 euros afterward, indicating a rise of 338.84 euros. Machine maintenance costs are structured according to each purchase, with an annual cost of 915 euros from 2021 to 2031 for the first purchase, and an elevated annual maintenance cost of 1,490 euros for the second purchase, spanning from 2031 to 2041.

Operating costs (euros)

	Annual costs -Pre	Annual costs -Post	Year
Fuel	107.66	446.5	2021-2041
Machine maintenance		1 st purchase - 915	2021-2031
		2 nd purchase – 1,490	2031-2041

TABLE 136: OPERATING COSTS FROM MULCHING WITH WOOD CHIPS AND HERBS (SPAIN 2)

Labour costs increase from 425.33 euros before to 916.67 euros (491.33 euros) after, then the project incurs 200 euros year⁻¹ for technical support and 40.2 euros year⁻¹ per worker for training (2021-2041).

Labour costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Pre	Annual costs - Post	Year
Labour	425.33	916.67	2021-2041
Technical support		200	2021-2041
Training		22	2021-2041

TABLE 137: LABOUR COSTS FROM MULCHING WITH WOOD CHIPS AND HERBS (SPAIN 2)

Regarding other costs, transaction costs are 40.2 euros per hectare per year from 2021 onwards. The opportunity costs for capital expenditures (CAPEX) reflect the present value of capital that could have been invested elsewhere but was allocated to machinery purchases. The opportunity cost of the first purchase is updated to 8,115 euros, while the second purchase stands at 7,368 euros, representing the economic trade-offs of dedicating resources to these acquisitions.

Other costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Post	Year
Transaction costs	40.2	2021
Opportunity costs (Present Value)		
1 st purchase	7,086	2019
2 nd purchase	6,855	2019

TABLE 138: OTHER COSTS FROM MULCHING WITH WOOD CHIPS AND HERBS (SPAIN 2)

Cost-benefit identification

Category	Name	Description	Attribute
Benefit per person or household	Improved Labour Environment	Reduction of workers' risk from exposure to phytosanitary products (public)	Qualitative
Benefit per unit of abatement	Enhanced Food quality and safety	Reduced risk of chemical residues on vegetables (public)	Qualitative
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced nitrogen input	Reduction of nutrient loss	Mixed
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced fertilizers costs		9,259 euros – present value
Environmental sustainability	Enhanced Adaptability	Water Retention and Drought Resistance	Qualitative

Improve an environmental or community asset	Ecological improvement	Improve biodiversity (public), Improved nutrient cycling	Qualitative
Reduced consequence of a risky event	Land conservation	On-site reduced soil erosion/increase productivity (on-site private, off-site public)	26,261 euros – present value
Sustainable Resource Management	Land Use Optimization	Increased soil structure and stability, increased organic matter	Qualitative
Reduced consequence of a risky event	Land conservation	Off-site reduced soil erosion	Qualitative
Community resilience	Improving community health	Reducing environmental contamination and the risks of chemical exposure to farm workers and surrounding communities	Qualitative
Total (monetary) benefits			35,520 euros

TABLE 139: IDENTIFIED BENEFITS FROM MULCHING WITH WOOD CHIPS AND HERBS (SPAIN 2)

The implementation of mulching with wood chips and herbs in Spain 2 provides a variety of benefits, consistent with literature on sustainable agricultural practices. Firstly, mulching improves the labour environment by reducing the risk of workers' exposure to phytosanitary products, thereby creating a safer workplace. This aligns with studies like Waheed et al. (2023) and Iqbal et al. (2020), which highlight reduced chemical exposure as a key benefit in organic systems.

In terms of environmental sustainability, the practice enhances adaptability by improving water retention and drought resistance, which is particularly valuable for Mediterranean climates prone to dry conditions. These benefits reflect findings by Guzmán et al. (2019), who documented enhanced moisture conservation through mulching. Moreover, the approach aids in land conservation by reducing on-site soil erosion, leading to productivity gains valued at 26,261 euros in present value. This economic benefit is consistent with Galati et al. (2015), who stress the importance of soil preservation for maintaining agricultural productivity. Off-site, reduced soil erosion contributes to the stability of surrounding lands, providing additional qualitative benefits that support regional ecological health, as supported by Iqbal et al. (2020). Together, these benefits underscore the economic, environmental, and social advantages of mulching practices, contributing to a total present value of identified monetary benefits. This holistic approach aligns with broader sustainability goals, promoting ecological resilience and community well-being.

Category	Cost item	Value (Euros)	Present Value (euros)
CAPEX	Machine and tools	74,177	60,006
Operating costs, including operations and maintenance (OPEX)	Maintenance	2,405	16,892
	Fuel	339	4,944
	Labour	491	7,169
Other costs	Tech. Supp.	200	2,918
	Training year	22	321
	Transaction costs		40.2
	Opportunity costs		13,941
	Increase CO2 emissions		6,022
Total Costs			106,232 euros

TABLE 140: IDENTIFIED COSTS FROM MULCHING WITH WOOD CHIPS AND HERBS (SPAIN 2)

* We do not include the calculation of CO2 emissions in the private analysis because they represent a cost shifted onto society and are not part of the private cost-benefit balance. However, these emissions were calculated separately to account for their broader impact, using values from the EIB Group climate bank roadmap 2021-2025. The roadmap provides the basis for the shadow cost, which represents the minimum societal cost of achieving the 1.5°C temperature target (EIB, 2020).

Economic analysis

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR (%)
20	-70,711	0.33	-0.3%

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR
20	-92,025	0.13	-100

TABLE 141: ECONOMIC ANALYSIS FROM MULCHING WITH WOOD CHIPS AND HERBS (SPAIN 2)

The economic analysis of the mulching project in Spain 2 highlights significant financial challenges in both scenarios. In the first scenario, where there is no risk of project failure and a high level of adoption, the project spans 20 years, resulting in an NPV of -70,711 euros per hectare, a BCR of 0.33, and a MIRR of -0.3%. These results indicate that, even with optimal adoption conditions, the project remains financially unsustainable. While the environmental benefits—such as improved soil conservation, water retention, and drought resilience—are valuable, they do not sufficiently offset the costs. The negative NPV and low BCR underscore the economic limitations of mulching in this context. This outcome is consistent with Schütte (2019), who discusses the economic viability challenges of sustainable practices without substantial financial support.

In the second scenario, characterized by a low risk of project failure but low adoption, the financial outcomes are even less favourable, with an NPV of -92,025 euros per hectare, a BCR of 0.13, and a MIRR of -100%. The financial strain increases with low adoption levels, limiting economies of scale and reducing potential cost savings from lower herbicide and fertilizer use. This scenario emphasizes the difficulty of justifying mulching investments without widespread adoption or additional financial support.

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

FIGURE 12: GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF NET AND CUMULATIVE BENEFITS UNDER TWO SCENARIOS: NO RISK OF FAILURE WITH HIGH ADOPTION (TOP) AND LOW RISK OF FAILURE WITH LOW ADOPTION (BOTTOM)

The charts illustrate the financial outcomes for both scenarios, highlighting the contrasting economic trajectories over the project’s duration in Spain 2. In the first scenario (no risk of project failure and high adoption), the Net Benefits graph initially shows negative values but gradually shifts to positive after approximately 10 years. This suggests that, although the project experiences losses in the early years, it eventually begins to generate annual positive returns. This turning point indicates a delayed but potential

financial viability over the long term. The Cumulative Net Benefits graph also reflects this trend, showing an initial decline followed by a gradual improvement after the 10-year mark. Despite initial losses, cumulative benefits start to stabilize, indicating that, under high adoption, the mulching project may become financially sustainable in the latter half of the project’s lifespan.

The financial outcomes remain unfavourable in the second scenario (low risk of project failure and low adoption). The Net Benefits graph continues to show significant annual losses throughout the 20-year period, with no shift to positive values. This indicates persistent financial strain when adoption levels are low, as cost-saving potential is limited. The Cumulative Net Benefits graph in this scenario follows a continuously downward trajectory, highlighting that, without higher adoption or external financial support, the project remains economically unviable over the entire period.

Social analysis

 Traffic light 82.16%	<p>The social score of 82.16% for the Spain 2 mulching project reflects a high perceived social impact, particularly in areas like improved labour environment and reduced exposure to chemicals. This strong score suggests that mulching practices are widely recognized as beneficial for worker health and safety, aligning well with sustainable agriculture goals. However, while the overall impact is positive, not all social dimensions are equally affected. The adoption of mulching has marked benefits for occupational health but shows moderate effects in broader social aspects, such as job creation and inclusivity, similar to findings by DeVetter et al. (2015) and Hostetler et al. (2007), which highlight the occupational health benefits of reduced chemical exposure but note limited impacts on other social outcomes.</p>
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Social impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
<i>The practice provides more stable income from year to year than alternatives</i>	0.50
<i>The current practice provides more flexibility for the agricultural management</i>	0.28
<i>New job opportunities in the rural area</i>	0.47
<i>Improvement of working conditions for the farm employers</i>	0.50
<i>Increased food safety</i>	0.50
<i>More job opportunities for women</i>	0.50
<i>Improving farmers' education and skills</i>	1.00
<i>Improved conditions for vulnerable groups</i>	0.60
<i>Improved aesthetics of the landscape and conservation of the cultural value</i>	0.80
<i>Improved social reputation of the farm</i>	0.60

TABLE 142: SOCIAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM MULCHING WITH WOOD CHIPS AND HERBS (SPAIN 2)

The questionnaire responses reveal varied perceptions regarding the social impact of the mulching practice in Spain 2. The score for income stability (0.50) indicates a moderate contribution to financial security, though mulching is not yet seen as a primary driver of economic resilience for the farm. A lower score for management flexibility (0.28) suggests limited adaptability perceived by respondents, possibly due to initial operational adjustments required for mulching practices. The practice’s highest perceived impact is on improving farmer education and skills (1.00), emphasizing the role of mulching in promoting sustainable agricultural knowledge, which is supported by Hostetler et al. (2007) as an essential component for long-term social benefits.

The social benefits of mulching extend to food safety (0.50) and opportunities for women (0.50), highlighting moderate yet growing recognition of its positive environmental impact. Notably, scores of 0.80 for landscape aesthetics and cultural value suggest that mulching practices are valued for enhancing the visual and cultural significance of the agricultural landscape, contributing positively to the farm's social reputation (0.60). These aspects resonate with the indirect social impacts observed by Waheed et al. (2023), who emphasize the longer-term value of sustainable practices in improving community health and preserving ecosystem services.

Social direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Improved labour environment	DeVetter et al. (2015); Hostetler et al. (2007);	Moderate	Short run	Qualitative
Reduced exposure to chemical	DeVetter et al. (2015); Hostetler et al. (2007); *Waheed et al. (2023)	High (due to reduced herbicide use)	Short-to-medium run	Qualitative

Social indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Improving community health	DeVetter et al. (2015); Hostetler et al. (2007); *Waheed et al. (2023)	Moderate to high	Medium-to-long run	Qualitative

TABLE 143: SOCIAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM MULCHING WITH WOOD CHIPS AND HERBS (SPAIN 2)

Environmental analysis

 Traffic light 77.72%	<p>The environmental score of 77.72% for the Spain 2 mulching project indicates a strong positive impact, reflecting the perceived environmental benefits of this practice. This score suggests that mulching with wood chips and herbs is valued for its contribution to sustainability, particularly in areas such as biodiversity enhancement, soil health, and resource conservation. The score highlights a broad recognition of mulching's role in supporting ecological resilience, although certain long-term benefits may take time to fully materialize. This aligns with findings in the literature, such as those by Waheed et al. (2023) and DeVetter et al. (2015), which emphasize mulching's benefits for soil structure, water retention, and biodiversity.</p>
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Env. impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
Contribute to reduce Direct greenhouse gas emissions	0.85
Contribute to reduce external inputs	0.80
Limit water consumption	0.85
Contribute to reduce waste	0.60
Has a positive impact on biodiversity	0.89
Has a positive impact on soil erosion	0.87
Has a positive impact on carbon footprint	0.20
Increase the rate of soil organic matter mineralisation	0.82
Increase soil compaction	0.82

TABLE 144: ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM MULCHING WITH WOOD CHIPS AND HERBS (SPAIN 2)

The questionnaire responses provide a nuanced view of the perceived environmental impacts of mulching practices in Spain 2. High scores of 0.85 for reducing greenhouse gas emissions and water consumption, as well as 0.80 for reducing external inputs, reflect a strong belief in mulching's ability to promote sustainable agricultural practices. These benefits, which include minimizing chemical use and conserving water, are especially valued in dry or resource-limited regions, aligning with Waheed et al. (2023), who found similar results in studies on vineyard management.

Mulching's impact on biodiversity is particularly well-regarded, with a score of 0.89, indicating that it creates a supportive environment for soil organisms, thereby enhancing ecosystem health. This aspect of mulching aligns with findings from DeVetter et al. (2015), which highlight the role of mulching in fostering soil biodiversity. The high score of 0.87 for soil erosion control further emphasizes the perceived value of mulching in protecting soil from erosion. However, as Schütte (2019) notes, the full erosion control benefits may require time to manifest, depending on factors like mulch type and field conditions.

The score for soil organic matter (0.82) suggests that stakeholders recognize mulching’s potential to contribute to soil health by adding organic material, which decomposes over time to improve soil fertility. Conversely, the lower score of 0.20 for carbon footprint reduction indicates limited perceived impact in this area, perhaps reflecting the need for additional awareness about mulching’s indirect benefits for climate change mitigation. Overall, the environmental perceptions align with the literature, which acknowledges mulching as a valuable tool for soil health and resource conservation, though certain impacts, such as carbon footprint reduction, may be less immediately evident.

Env. direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Land Conservation: reduced soil erosion, (on/off-site effects)	DeVetter et al. (2015); * Waheed et al. (2023)	High	Short-to-medium	Quantitative – monetizable (see Panagos et al, 2018)
Improved soil structure and stability	Schütte (2019)	Moderate	Medium-to-long run	Qualitative
Increased soil organic matter	DeVetter et al. (2015); * Waheed et al. (2023)	Moderate to High	Medium-to-Long run	Qualitative
Enhanced water retention	DeVetter et al. (2015); Hostetler et al. (2007); * Waheed et al. (2023)	High	Short-to-medium run	Quantitative
Reduction in CO2 emissions	Schütte (2019)	Moderate	Mediumto-long run	Quantitative

Env. indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Improved nutrient cycling	Schütte, 2019	Moderate	Medium to long-term	Qualitative
Reduced carbon footprint	Guzmán et al., 2019; Frye et al. (1988)	Moderate	Long-term	Qualitative
Biodiversity enhancement	DeVetter et al. (2015); * Schütte (2019)	Moderate to high	Medium-to-Long run	Qualitative
Contribution to ecosystem services	DeVetter et al. (2015); Hostetler et al. (2007); * Waheed et al. (2023)	High	Medium-to-long run	Qualitative
Water conservation	DeVetter et al. (2015); Hostetler et al. (2007); * Schütte (2019)	High	Medium-to-long run	Qualitative

TABLE 145: ENVIRONMENTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM MULCHING WITH WOOD CHIPS AND HERBS (SPAIN 2)

Sensitivity analysis

The sensitivity analysis for the Spain 2 mulching project underscores significant financial challenges, with all examined scenarios indicating negative financial returns. In the default scenario, the NPV is -70,711 euros/ha, with a mean of -73,957 euros/ha and a 0% probability of achieving positive returns. This finding highlights the financial risk due to high initial costs and the delayed realization of long-term environmental benefits, such as improved soil health and erosion control. The Benefit-Cost Ratio (BCR) in the default case is 0.33, with most outcomes clustering between 0.19 and 0.35, indicating that costs consistently outweigh benefits. Even at lower discount rates (e.g., 2%), which place greater emphasis on future benefits,

the NPV remains negative at -73,916 euros, with a BCR of 0.38. This slight improvement at lower discount rates suggests that the economic value of the project is time-sensitive but ultimately insufficient to break even. Monte Carlo simulations further affirm the financial strain, showing no probability of a positive NPV or BCR greater than 1 under any scenario. The distribution analysis reveals a concentration of results within the -84K to -65K range for NPV, while BCR values mainly fall between 0.19 and 0.35, underscoring the economic infeasibility of the project. Overall, these findings indicate that, while mulching provides ecological benefits such as biodiversity enhancement and erosion control, these gains do not offset the financial burden without external funding or policy incentives to support sustainable agricultural practices.

Net Present Value (NPV)		Tot. Euros
Minimum		-120,696
Maximum		-28,186
Default case		-70,711
Mean		-73,957
Median		-73,489
Probability that NPV > 0		0
Distribution (euros)		Probability
Less than -121K		0.00
-121K to -102K		0.19
-102K to -84K		0.10
-84K to -65K		0.40
-65K to -47K		0.16
-47K to -28K		0.16
Total		1.00
Benefit: Cost Ratio (BCR)		Unconstrained version
Minimum		0.11
Maximum		0.52
Default case		0.33
Mean		0.27
Median		0.26
Probability that BCR > 1		0.00
Target BCR		2
Probability BCR > Target		0
Distribution		Probability
Less than 0.11		0.00
0.11 to 0.19		0.15
0.19 to 0.27		0.40
0.27 to 0.35		0.30
0.35 to 0.43		0.12
0.43 to 0.52		0.04
Total		1.00

TABLE 146: BCA ROBUSTNESS (MONTE CARLO ANALYSIS BASED ON 1000 RANDOM SIMULATIONS) - MULCHING WITH WOOD CHIPS AND HERBS (SPAIN 2)

Sensitivity to discount rate

	Low discount rate	Default discount rate	High discount rate
Project organisation	2%	4%	6%
Benefits (present value)	45,242	35,520	28,313
Costs (present value)	119,158	106,232	96,087
Net Present Value (NPV)	-73,916	-70,711	-67,774
Benefit: Cost Ratio (unconstrained budget)	0.38	0.33	0.29

TABLE 147: SENSITIVITY TO DISCOUNT RATE - MULCHING WITH WOOD CHIPS AND HERBS (SPAIN 2)

4.2.3.2 Living mulches - arable crops (UK 2)

Main objective

The project aims to reduce herbicide use in arable crops by introducing living mulch.

Description of the “before” scenario

Before the introduction of living mulch, the UK farm relied heavily on intensive mechanical soil disturbance to control weed growth across cereal fields. Operations included ploughing and power harrowing using a 4WD Tractor (New Holland T6, 90 HP), where diesel consumption was considerable. Weed control was managed primarily through tine harrowing, conducted multiple times each growing season to minimize competition with crops. Seeding was done using a Lemken Solitar 8 Drill at a rate of 250 kg/ha for wheat, requiring additional tractor operations. This approach was consistent across seasons, emphasizing traditional mechanical interventions and substantial fuel use.

Description of the “after” scenario

After implementing living mulch practices, the farm adopted a more regenerative weed control strategy, reducing soil disturbance and fuel consumption. Clover was seeded at 7.5 kg/ha as a cover crop, utilizing the same tractor with a Terracast V2 Seeder. Grazing sheep, managed by a grazier, maintained the living mulch height both before seeding and through winter, reducing the need for mechanical weed control. Cereal crops were then direct drilled into the mulch using a Simtech Direct Drill, which minimized soil disruption compared to traditional methods. This shift aimed to enhance soil health and reduce reliance on diesel-powered equipment, supporting a sustainable weed management strategy.

Input data and farm characteristics

The farm operates under organic management, primarily focused on arable cropping, with wheat, oats, barley, rye, and peas as the main crops. Additionally, livestock management includes 200 head of New Zealand Romney sheep, cared for by a grazier. Spanning a total area of 180 hectares, the farm designates 140 hectares as utilized agricultural area (UAA), reflecting its commitment to organic production principles. Experimental activities are concentrated on a 5.5-hectare area, where wheat is the chosen crop for trials aimed at enhancing organic crop management practices.

<i>Management Type</i>	Organic
<i>Most important crops and animal productions</i>	Arable cropping makes up the bulk of production on the farm with wheat, oats, barley, rye and peas being grown. There are 200 head of New Zealand Romney sheep on the farm that are managed by a grazier.
<i>Total Farm Area (ha)</i>	180
<i>Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA, ha)</i>	140
<i>Experimental area (ha)</i>	5.5
<i>Experimental crop(s)</i>	Wheat

TABLE 148: INPUT DATA AND FARM CHARACTERISTICS FROM LIVING MULCHES - ARABLE CROPS (UK 2)

The investment analysis assumes a standard scenario where the farm integrates new equipment into existing tractor systems. The Simtech Direct Drill, initially purchased in 2019, involved an annual cost of 34,928 euros, with an expected operational lifetime of 10 years. A second purchase of the Simtech Direct Drill is planned for 2029 at an updated cost of 50,018 euros, again with a projected 10-year lifespan.

Investment costs (euros)

Machine and Tools	Annual costs	Year	Expected lifetime (n. year)
Simtech Direct Drill	34,928	2019	10
2 nd purchase	50,018	2029	10

TABLE 149: INVESTMENT COSTS FROM LIVING MULCHES - ARABLE CROPS (UK 2)

The operating costs include key components such as machine maintenance and clover seed expenses over the projected periods. Machine maintenance costs are based on each purchase, with an annual cost of 1,048 euros from 2019 to 2029 for the first purchase, and an increased annual maintenance cost of 1,707 euros for the second purchase, covering the period from 2029 to 2039. These costs reflect the anticipated maintenance needs associated with each tool over its respective lifespan. Additionally, clover seed expenses are estimated at 923 euros annually, spanning the period from 2019 to 2039.

<i>Operating costs (euros)</i>		
	Annual costs -Post	Year
<i>Machine maintenance</i>	1 st purchase - 1,048	2019-2029
	2 nd purchase – 1,707	2029-2039
<i>Clover seed</i>	923	2019-2039

TABLE 150: OPERATING COSTS FROM LIVING MULCHES - ARABLE CROPS (UK 2)

As for the labour category, the project incurs 200 euros year⁻¹ for technical support and 22 euros year⁻¹ per worker for training (2020-2040).

<i>Labour costs (euros)</i>			
	Annual costs - Pre	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Technical support</i>		200	2020-2040
<i>Training</i>		22	2020-2040

TABLE 151: LABOUR COSTS FROM LIVING MULCHES - ARABLE CROPS (UK 2)

Regarding the other costs, transaction costs are 40.2 euros per 5.5 hectares (i.e., 221 euros), representing the administrative or operational expenses associated with implementing the changes in 2019. The opportunity costs for CAPEX are calculated as the present value of the capital that could have been invested elsewhere but was instead allocated to machinery purchases. The first purchase's opportunity cost is 8,115 euros, while the second purchase is 7,368 euros, both representing the economic trade-offs of committing resources to these expenditures.

In addition, the annual production loss during the first three years (2019-2021) is set at 2,286 euros per year. This reflects the reduction in output during the initial transition period, which aligns with the literature that suggests temporary yield declines in the early years of new agricultural practices.

<i>Other costs (euros)</i>		
	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Transaction costs</i>	221	2019
<i>Opportunity costs (Present Value)</i>		
1 st purchase	8,115	2019
2 nd purchase	7,368	2019
<i>Annual production loss (only 3 years)</i>	2,286	2019-2021

TABLE 152: OTHER COSTS FROM LIVING MULCHES - ARABLE CROPS (UK 2)

Cost-benefit identification

<i>Category</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Attribute</i>
Benefit per person or household	Improved Labour Environment	Reduction of workers' risk from exposure to phytosanitary products (public)	Qualitative
Benefit per unit of abatement	Enhanced Food quality and safety	Reduced risk of chemical residues on grapes (public)	Qualitative
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced nitrogen input	Reduction of nutrient loss	Mixed
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced fuel and labour costs		7,963 euros – present value

Environmental sustainability	Enhanced Adaptability	Water Retention and Drought Resistance	Qualitative
Improve an environmental or community asset	Ecological improvement	Improve biodiversity (public), Improved nutrient cycling	Qualitative
Reduced consequence of a risky event	Land conservation	On-site reduced soil erosion/increase productivity (on-site private, off-site public)	6,021 euros – present value
Sustainable Resource Management	Land Use Optimization	Increased soil structure and stability, increased organic matter	Qualitative
Reduced consequence of a risky event	Land conservation	Off-site reduced soil erosion	Qualitative
Resource efficiency	Smart Resource Management	Reduced CO ₂ *	2,752.39 euros – present value
Community resilience	Improving community health	Reducing environmental contamination and the risks of chemical exposure to farm workers and surrounding communities	Qualitative
Total (monetary) benefits			13,984 euros

TABLE 153: IDENTIFIED BENEFITS FROM LIVING MULCHES - ARABLE CROPS (UK 2)

* We do not include the calculation of CO₂ emissions in the private analysis because they represent a cost shifted onto society and are not part of the private cost-benefit balance. However, these emissions were calculated separately to account for their broader impact, using values from the EIB Group climate bank roadmap 2021-2025. The roadmap provides the basis for the shadow cost, which represents the minimum societal cost of achieving the 1.5°C temperature target (EIB, 2020).

The implementation of living mulching in UK agriculture offers a range of benefits, aligning with findings from the literature on sustainable practices. First, living mulching improves the labour environment by reducing workers' exposure to phytosanitary products, creating a safer workplace—an advantage echoed in studies like Waheed et al., (2023), Iqbal et al., (2020) and Boyd et al., (2001), which emphasize reduced input use in similar contexts. Additionally, the practice contributes to environmental sustainability by minimizing nitrogen input and nutrient loss, enhancing soil health, as highlighted by Waheed et al., (2023). Enhanced water retention and drought resistance, which living mulching promotes, reflect findings by Guzmán et al. (2019), who document improved soil moisture conservation, particularly in vineyards. Furthermore, living mulching aids in land conservation by reducing on-site soil erosion, leading to improved productivity; this benefit, estimated at 6,021 euros in present value, aligns with Galati et al. (2015), who highlight the economic importance of soil preservation. Off-site erosion reduction extends these benefits to surrounding areas, contributing to regional soil stability, a qualitative advantage supported by Iqbal et al. (2020). In terms of resource efficiency, living mulching reduces CO₂ emissions, valued at 2,752.39 euros, representing a societal benefit in line with the European Investment Bank's climate roadmap (2020) and similar studies by Zhao et al. (2021) emphasizing the role of mulching in lowering greenhouse gas emissions. Lastly, this approach enhances community resilience by reducing environmental contamination and the risk of chemical exposure for farm workers and nearby populations, reinforcing social health benefits observed in Hostetler et al. (2007), who noted reduced chemical dependency as a critical aspect of sustainable vineyard management. Together, these benefits underscore the economic, environmental, and social gains that living mulching can bring, totaling 13,984 euros in present value, and reflect a sustainable approach that aligns with broader goals of ecological and community well-being.

<i>Category</i>	<i>Cost item</i>	<i>Value (Euros)</i>	<i>Present Value (euros)</i>
CAPEX	Machine and tools	84,946	68,718
Operating costs, including operations and maintenance (OPEX)	Maintenance	2,755	20,053
	Seeds	923	13,468
Labour	Tech. Supp.	200	2,918
	Training year	22	321
Other costs	Transaction costs		221
	Opportunity costs		15,483

	<i>Production loss</i>	2,286	6,598
Total Costs			127,780 euros

TABLE 154: IDENTIFIED COSTS FROM LIVING MULCHES - ARABLE CROPS (UK 2)

Economic analysis

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR (%)
20	-20,690	0.11	-100%

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR
20	-22,323	0.04	-100

TABLE 155: ECONOMIC ANALYSIS FROM LIVING MULCHES - ARABLE CROPS (UK 2)

The economic analysis of the living mulching project in the UK2 case reveals challenging financial outcomes across both adoption scenarios. In the first scenario, where there is no risk of project failure and a high level of adoption, the project spans 20 years, yielding a NPV of -20,690 euros per hectare, a BCR of 0.11, and a MIRR of -100%. These values indicate that, even under optimistic adoption conditions, the project's financial viability is severely limited. Although living mulching could provide environmental benefits, such as reduced soil erosion and enhanced biodiversity, the negative NPV and low BCR suggest that these advantages are insufficient to offset the high costs associated with the practice, leading to an overall negative economic outcome.

In the second scenario, characterized by a low risk of project failure but also a low adoption rate, the financial results are similarly unfavourable. With an NPV of -22,323 euros per hectare, a BCR of 0.04, and an MIRR of -100%, this scenario highlights the compounded financial strain when adoption levels are minimal. Limited implementation restricts the potential for input savings and other cost reductions associated with reduced herbicide and fertilizer usage, thus intensifying the economic challenges and reinforcing the necessity for widespread adoption or financial support.

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

FIGURE 13: GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF NET AND CUMULATIVE BENEFITS UNDER TWO SCENARIOS: NO RISK OF FAILURE WITH HIGH ADOPTION (TOP) AND LOW RISK OF FAILURE WITH LOW ADOPTION (BOTTOM)

The charts illustrate these trends across both scenarios. The Net Benefits graph for the high adoption scenario shows consistently negative values, underscoring the financial infeasibility of the project over the long term. The Cumulative Net Benefits graph exhibits a steady decline, emphasizing that even with high adoption, the cumulative financial benefits remain negative over the 20-year period. Similar patterns are observed in the low adoption scenario, where the Net Benefits graph continues to reflect substantial annual losses, and the Cumulative Net Benefits graph follows a downward trajectory. This trajectory indicates that without significant scale or external financial support, the economic gains from living mulching remain inadequate to justify the investment.

These findings align with certain insights from the literature, such as the work by Schütte (2019), who noted the economic viability challenges of sustainable practices without widespread adoption or subsidies. Additionally, while environmental benefits such as improved soil quality and water retention are well-documented in studies like those by Guzmán et al. (2019) and Waheed et al. (2023), the financial outcomes in the UK2 case underscore that such benefits alone may not provide a sufficient economic rationale for adoption in the absence of financial incentives. In conclusion, both high and low adoption scenarios demonstrate the need for external support mechanisms to make living mulching economically viable in the long term.

Social analysis

<p>Traffic light 63.21%</p>	<p>The social score of 63.21% for the UK2 living mulching project suggests a moderate impact, with significant benefits noted in specific areas like improved labour conditions and reduced exposure to chemicals. This result underscores a balanced view, where the adoption of mulching practices is seen as beneficial, particularly in enhancing workplace safety and contributing to environmental sustainability. However, the social benefits are not as widespread across all dimensions. While occupational health and safety show marked improvements, other areas such as job creation, gender inclusivity, and support for vulnerable groups are less impacted by the project. Studies like DeVetter et al. (2015) and Hostetler et al. (2007) confirm these findings, highlighting that while green mulching can effectively reduce chemical usage, thereby protecting farm workers, its broader social impacts require further development.</p>
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Social impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
<i>The practice provides more stable income from year to year than alternatives</i>	0.57
<i>The current practice provides more flexibility for the agricultural management</i>	0.34
<i>New job opportunities in the rural area</i>	0.28
<i>Improvement of working conditions for the farm employers</i>	0.78
<i>Increased food safety</i>	0.50
<i>More job opportunities for women</i>	0.00
<i>Improving farmers' education and skills</i>	0.75

<i>Improved conditions for vulnerable groups</i>	0.00
<i>Improved aesthetics of the landscape and conservation of the cultural value</i>	0.60
<i>Improved social reputation of the farm</i>	0.60

TABLE 156: SOCIAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM LIVING MULCHES - ARABLE CROPS (UK 2)

The questionnaire results provide additional insight into the perceived social impacts of green mulching. The score of 0.57 for stable income suggests that green mulching contributes moderately to financial stability, although it is not yet recognized as a major source of economic resilience. The score of 0.34 for management flexibility indicates a modest degree of adaptability associated with mulching, a benefit that could become more evident with increased experience and adoption. The highest impact is noted in working conditions, with a score of 0.78, reflecting strong support for reduced herbicide exposure and improved safety for farm workers. This aligns with literature, including DeVetter et al. (2015), which emphasizes the health benefits of minimizing chemical inputs through sustainable practices like mulching.

On the other hand, scores for food safety (0.50) and opportunities for women (0.00) are lower, indicating that while mulching may have positive environmental effects, its influence on gender equity and immediate food safety improvements is perceived as limited. Education and skills development score 0.75, indicating progress in equipping farmers with knowledge in sustainable practices, an impact supported by the findings of Hostetler et al. (2007). Scores of 0.60 for landscape aesthetics and cultural conservation show that mulching is valued for maintaining the visual appeal and cultural heritage of agricultural landscapes, enhancing the farm’s social reputation.

Overall, while green mulching is positively associated with occupational health improvements and community health, its broader social impacts—such as inclusivity and community-wide economic benefits—remain limited. Studies suggest that the social value of green mulching can increase over time as awareness grows and communities begin to experience indirect benefits like enhanced community health and ecosystem services.

Social direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Improved labour environment	DeVetter et al. (2015); Hostetler et al. (2007);	Moderate	Short run	Qualitative
Reduced exposure to chemical	DeVetter et al. (2015); Hostetler et al. (2007); *Waheed et al. (2023)	High (due to reduced herbicide use)	Short-to-medium run	Qualitative

Social indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Improving community health	DeVetter et al. (2015); Hostetler et al. (2007); *Waheed et al. (2023)	Moderate to high	Medium-to-long run	Qualitative

TABLE 157: SOCIAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM LIVING MULCHES - ARABLE CROPS (UK 2)

Environmental analysis

<p>Traffic light 59.79%</p>	<p>The overall environmental score of 59.79% for the UK2 living mulching project indicates a moderate impact, suggesting that while positive environmental effects are acknowledged, they fall short of full alignment with long-term sustainability expectations, especially concerning soil erosion mitigation. Living mulching provides benefits such as enhanced biodiversity and improved soil structure, as discussed in studies like DeVetter et al. (2015), which emphasize these long-term ecological gains. However, immediate impacts on soil erosion control are perceived as less substantial. The approach involves covering the soil surface with organic materials, like straw or cover crops, which helps retain moisture, suppress weeds, and protect the soil. Yet, these benefits may take time to become fully apparent, as evidenced by the moderate perceptions from stakeholders. This timeframe for realizing the full environmental benefits is consistent with findings from Schütte (2019),</p>
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which highlights that the effectiveness of mulching on erosion and soil health depends on local soil conditions and the specific type of mulch used.

Env. impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
Contribute to reduce Direct greenhouse gas emissions	0.80
Contribute to reduce external inputs	0.80
Limit water consumption	0.80
Contribute to reduce waste	0.60
Has a positive impact on biodiversity	1.00
Has a positive impact on soil erosion	0.88
Has a positive impact on carbon footprint	0.20
Increase the rate of soil organic matter mineralisation	0.63
Increase soil compaction	0.63

TABLE 158: ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM LIVING MULCHES - ARABLE CROPS (UK 2)

The questionnaire results show a mix of high and moderate scores for the environmental impacts of living mulching. High scores of 0.80 for reducing greenhouse gas emissions, external inputs, and water usage reflect a strong perception of mulching’s ability to support sustainable practices, which aligns with findings from Waheed et al. (2023). This underscores mulching's role in reducing chemical reliance and conserving resources, particularly in vineyard management systems. The high score of 1.00 for biodiversity enhancement suggests that mulching creates a favourable environment for soil organisms, which supports soil ecosystem health—a point emphasized in DeVetter et al. (2015).

On the other hand, the score of 0.88 for soil erosion control reflects a recognition of mulching's protective role against erosion, although there is some hesitancy about the immediate impact, as erosion control benefits may require time to be fully observed. Studies like Schütte (2019) and Waheed et al. (2023) also indicate that erosion control through mulching can vary depending on mulch type and field conditions. The positive score of 0.63 for soil organic matter suggests a moderate perception of mulching’s potential to increase organic matter, supporting soil health over time as organic materials decompose. Overall, these mixed perceptions highlight the need for more awareness and demonstration of living mulching’s long-term environmental and economic benefits, especially in improving soil health, moisture retention, and erosion control.

The literature supports these findings, showing that while mulching’s immediate impacts may appear moderate, the cumulative environmental benefits, such as enhanced nutrient cycling, water conservation, and biodiversity support, contribute significantly to sustainable vineyard management over the long term.

Env. direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Land Conservation: reduced soil erosion, (on/off-site effects)	DeVetter et al. (2015); *Waheed et al. (2023)	High	Short-to-medium	Quantitative – monetizable (see Panagos et al, 2018)
Improved soil structure and stability	Schütte (2019)	Moderate	Medium-to-long run	Qualitative
Increased soil organic matter	DeVetter et al. (2015); *Waheed et al. (2023)	Moderate to High	Medium-to-Long run	Qualitative
Enhanced water retention	DeVetter et al. (2015); Hostetler et al. (2007); *Waheed et al. (2023)	High	Short-to-medium run	Quantitative
Reduction in CO2 emissions	Schütte (2019)	Moderate	Mediumto-long run	Quantitative

Env. indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Improved nutrient cycling	Schütte, 2019	Moderate	Medium to long-term	Qualitative
Reduced carbon footprint	Guzmán et al., 2019; Frye et al. (1988)	Moderate	Long-term	Qualitative
Biodiversity enhancement	DeVetter et al. (2015); *Schütte (2019)	Moderate to high	Medium-to-Long run	Qualitative
Contribution to ecosystem services	DeVetter et al. (2015); Hostetler et al. (2007); *Waheed et al. (2023)	High	Medium-to-long run	Qualitative
Water conservation	DeVetter et al. (2015); Hostetler et al. (2007); *Schütte (2019)	High	Medium-to-long run	Qualitative

TABLE 159: ENVIRONMENTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM LIVING MULCHES - ARABLE CROPS (UK 2)

Sensitivity analysis

The sensitivity analysis for the UK2 living mulching project highlights the substantial financial challenges associated with this investment. In the default scenario, the NPV is -20,690 euros/ha, with a mean of -21,157 euros/ha and a median of -20,873 euros/ha, indicating a 0% probability of achieving positive financial returns. This underscores the financial risk linked to the project, primarily due to high initial costs and delayed long-term benefits. The BCR in the default case is 0.11, with a mean of 0.09 and a median of 0.08, reflecting that in 0% of cases, benefits will exceed costs. The analysis further shows no likelihood of achieving a BCR greater than 1, with most outcomes clustering between 0.06 and 0.12, which emphasizes the economic challenges of the project.

The project's financial sensitivity to discount rates reveals the time-dependency of benefits. At a low discount rate of 2%, the NPV is -125,135 euros, with a BCR of 0.12, showing a slight improvement due to the greater emphasis on long-term ecological gains such as soil health improvement. At the default discount rate of 4%, the NPV is -113,797 euros, with a BCR of 0.11, maintaining the project's financial risk. A higher discount rate of 6% further reduces the NPV to -104,729 euros, with a BCR of 0.10, illustrating the reduced present value of future ecological benefits when these gains are heavily discounted.

The sensitivity analysis demonstrates that the economic feasibility of living mulching is limited, with a 0% probability of achieving positive financial returns under the examined conditions. While the project's success heavily relies on long-term benefits such as improved soil health and erosion control, these advantages do not sufficiently offset the high initial costs.

Net Present Value (NPV)	Tot. Euros	Euros ha ⁻¹
Minimum	-158,557	-28,829
Maximum	-71,268	-12,958
Default case	-113,797	-20,690
Mean	-116,365	-21,157
Median	-114,804	-20,873
Probability that NPV > 0		0
Distribution (euros)	Probability	
Less than -159K	0.00	
-159K to -142K	0.24	
-142K to -124K	0.00	
-124K to -106K	0.52	
-106K to -89K	0.00	
-89K to -71K	0.24	

	Total	1.00
Benefit: Cost Ratio (BCR)		Unconstrained version
Minimum		0.03
Maximum		0.17
Default case		0.11
Mean		0.09
Median		0.08
Probability that BCR > 1		0.00
Target BCR		2
Probability BCR > Target		0
Distribution		Probability
Less than 0.03		0.00
0.03 to 0.06		0.16
0.06 to 0.09		0.37
0.09 to 0.12		0.34
0.12 to 0.14		0.09
0.14 to 0.17		0.04
	Total	1.00

TABLE 160: BCA ROBUSTNESS (MONTE CARLO ANALYSIS BASED ON 1000 RANDOM SIMULATIONS) - LIVING MULCHES - ARABLE CROPS (UK 2)

Sensitivity to discount rate

	Low discount rate	Default discount rate	High discount rate
Project organisation	2%	4%	6%
Benefits (present value)	17,561	13,983	11,318
Costs (present value)	142,696	127,780	116,046
Net Present Value (NPV)	-125,135	-113,797	-104,729
Benefit: Cost Ratio (unconstrained budget)	0.12	0.11	0.10

TABLE 161: SENSITIVITY TO DISCOUNT RATE - LIVING MULCHES - ARABLE CROPS (UK 2)

4.2.4 Precision farming solutions

4.2.4.1 Mechanical weeding coupled with precision agriculture (Italy 3)

Main objective

The company's objective in implementing mechanical weeding integrated with precision agriculture is to improve operational efficiency and reduce labour costs by utilizing advanced equipment that optimizes weed control with a lower environmental impact.

Description of the “before” scenario

Before the introduction of precision mechanical weeding, the weeding process required substantial labour and was time-consuming. A tractor was used with one operator driving, while four additional workers managed the weeder. This setup resulted in a work capacity of just one hectare per eight hours, making the process highly labour-intensive and inefficient. Moreover, fuel consumption was considerable, adding to the operational costs and environmental impact of the practice.

Description of the “after” scenario

After adopting mechanical weeding enhanced by precision technology, the operation saw a significant transformation. An automated weeder replaced the previous setup, requiring only a single operator. This change dramatically increased work capacity to seven hectares per hour, which reduced both labour needs and the time required to complete the task. Consequently, operational costs decreased, and fuel consumption was reduced, achieving the company's goal of improved efficiency with a lower environmental footprint.

Input data and farm characteristics

The company operates a 100-hectare organic farm dedicated to arable and field vegetable crops. The entire utilized agricultural area (UAA) is 100 hectares, which is also fully designated as the experimental area. The primary experimental crop is tomatoes for industrial processing.

<i>Management Type</i>	Organic
<i>Most important crops and animal productions</i>	Arable/field vegetable crops
<i>Total Farm Area (ha)</i>	100
<i>Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA, ha)</i>	100
<i>Experimental area (ha)</i>	100
<i>Experimental crop(s)</i>	Tomatoes for industry

TABLE 162: INPUT DATA AND FARM CHARACTERISTICS FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING COUPLED WITH PRECISION AGRICULTURE (ITALY 3)

The investment analysis is based on the common scenario in which agricultural companies already own a tractor, allowing the automatic weeder to be integrated into existing machinery. The initial purchase cost for the automatic weeder is estimated at 125,000 euros, with an expected lifetime of 10 years starting from 2020. A second tool purchase is projected for 2030 at a cost of 179,003 euros, also with a 10-year expected lifetime. This decision reflects a realistic estimate of the actual investment required, ensuring that the analysis does not underestimate the costs faced by agricultural businesses.

Investment costs (euros)

<i>Machine and Tools</i>	Annual costs	Year	Expected lifetime (n. year)
<i>Automatic weeder</i>	125,000	2020	10
<i>2nd tool purchase</i>	179,003	2030	10

TABLE 163: INVESTMENT COSTS FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING COUPLED WITH PRECISION AGRICULTURE (ITALY 3)

The operating costs for the automatic weeder reflect several critical elements, including adjustments in maintenance costs due to changes in workflow post-implementation. Machine maintenance costs are calculated at 3% of the purchase price. For the first tool purchased in 2020, annual maintenance costs are set at 3,750 euros and will apply from 2020 to 2029. For the second tool purchased in 2030, maintenance costs increase to 6,108 euros annually, covering the period from 2030 to 2040. These adjustments reflect the projected costs over each tool's lifespan, accounting for changes in operational needs and the impact of technological improvements on workflow efficiency.

Operating costs (euros year⁻¹)

	Annual costs - Pre	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Machine maintenance (3% of purchase price)</i>		1 st tool purchase – 3,750	2020-2029
		2 nd tool purchase -6,108	2030-2040

TABLE 164: OPERATING COSTS FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING COUPLED WITH PRECISION AGRICULTURE (ITALY 3)

The project incurs annual labour costs of 200 euros for technical support and 22 euros per worker for training, covering the period from 2020 to 2040. The integration of the automatic weeder has led to a reduction in labour costs by minimizing the need for manual operations, which enhances overall efficiency and reduces the dependence on labour-intensive tasks.

Labour costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Technical support</i>	200	2020-2040
<i>Training</i>	22	2020-2040

TABLE 165: LABOUR COSTS FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING COUPLED WITH PRECISION AGRICULTURE (ITALY 3)

The Other costs section includes transaction costs of 4,020 euros in 2020 (100 hectares), representing the administrative or operational expenses associated with implementing the changes. Opportunity costs are calculated as the present value in 2020 of capital allocated to the tool purchases. The opportunity cost for the first purchase is 29,042 euros, while for the second purchase, it is 26,367 euros.

Other costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Transaction costs</i>	4,020	2020
<i>Opportunity costs (Present Value)</i>	29,042	2020
	26,367	2020

TABLE 166: OTHER COSTS FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING COUPLED WITH PRECISION AGRICULTURE (ITALY 3)

Cost-benefit identification

<i>Category</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Attribute</i>
Benefit per person or household	Improved Labour Environment	Reduction of workers' risk from exposure to phytosanitary products (public)	Qualitative
Benefit per unit of abatement	Enhanced Food quality and safety	Reduced risk of chemical residues on tomatoes (public)	Qualitative
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced labour costs		Monetary 756,638 euros – present value
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced fuel costs *Reduced CO ₂ emissions		Monetary 173,371 euros Monetary 135,271 euros – present value
Total (monetary) benefits			930,009 euros

TABLE 167: IDENTIFIED BENEFITS FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING COUPLED WITH PRECISION AGRICULTURE (ITALY 3)

* We do not include the calculation of CO₂ emissions in the private analysis because they represent a cost shifted onto society and are not part of the private cost-benefit balance. However, these emissions were calculated separately to account for their

broader impact, using values from the EIB Group climate bank roadmap 2021-2025. The roadmap provides the basis for the shadow cost, which represents the minimum societal cost of achieving the 1.5°C temperature target (EIB, 2020).

The adoption of precision-enhanced mechanical weeding in the organic company (Italy 3), which previously relied on traditional mechanical methods, brings considerable qualitative and financial benefits. In this organic setting, where chemical controls are absent, the primary advantages are realized through increased efficiency, particularly via reduced fuel consumption and lower labour demands.

On a qualitative level, the system improves the working environment by reducing any residual risk of worker exposure to phytosanitary products, fostering a safer workplace even without chemical usage. Furthermore, it enhances food quality and safety by virtually eliminating the risk of chemical residues on tomatoes, providing an added health benefit to consumers.

From an economic perspective, the system achieves significant cost reductions. Labour savings have a present value of 756,638 euros, while fuel savings add an additional 173,371 euros, totaling 930,009 euros in monetary benefits. Additionally, the reduction in CO₂ emissions represents an estimated benefit of 135,271 euros, further emphasizing the environmental and financial gains. These savings underscore the enhanced operational efficiency and resource optimization made possible by integrating precision technology into organic agriculture practices.

Category	Cost item	Value (Euros)	Present Value (euros)
Capital costs (CAPEX)	Tool	304,003	245,928
Operating costs, including operations and maintenance (OPEX)	Maintenance	9,858	69,229
Labour	Technical support	200	2,918
	Training year	22	321
Other costs	Transaction costs		4,020
	Opportunity costs		55,409
Total Costs			377,825

TABLE 168: IDENTIFIED COSTS FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING COUPLED WITH PRECISION AGRICULTURE (ITALY 3)

Economic analysis

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR (%)
20	5,521	2.46	6.4

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR
20	-169,82	0.96	3.9

TABLE 169: ECONOMIC ANALYSIS FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING COUPLED WITH PRECISION AGRICULTURE (ITALY 3)

In the first scenario, where there is no risk of project failure and a high level of adoption, the project demonstrates moderate financial viability. The Net Present Value (NPV) per hectare is 5,521 euros, indicating a positive return on investment. The Benefit-Cost Ratio (BCR) of 2.46 shows that for every euro invested, the project generates 2.46 euros in return, supporting the potential for long-term financial sustainability. The Modified Internal Rate of Return (MIRR) of 6.4% suggests that the project's rate of return is adequate to justify the initial and ongoing investments under these favourable conditions.

In the second scenario, with a low risk of project failure but a low level of adoption, the financial outlook is less favourable. The NPV per hectare falls to -169.82 euros, reflecting a slight loss. The BCR of 0.96 suggests that the project barely breaks even, with each euro invested returning less than one euro. The MIRR of 3.9% is relatively low, indicating that the project's returns are insufficient to fully cover the investment and ongoing costs. This scenario highlights the importance of achieving high adoption rates to improve cost distribution and overall project viability.

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

FIGURE 14: GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF NET AND CUMULATIVE BENEFITS UNDER TWO SCENARIOS: NO RISK OF FAILURE WITH HIGH ADOPTION (TOP) AND LOW RISK OF FAILURE WITH LOW ADOPTION (BOTTOM)

In the first scenario (high adoption), the net benefits graph shows consistent positive returns over most years, demonstrating that the project can generate income to support reinvestment and operational needs. The cumulative net benefits graph illustrates a steady upward trend, indicating an improvement in financial stability over time.

In the second scenario (low adoption), the net benefits graph shows a less optimistic pattern, with fluctuating values that reflect limited financial recovery. The cumulative net benefits graph indicates a slow and inconsistent growth, revealing the project's struggle to achieve lasting financial sustainability under low adoption conditions. This scenario emphasizes the need for broader adoption to enhance financial performance and distribute costs effectively.

Social analysis

 Traffic light 55.26%	<p>The traffic light score of 55.26% indicates a moderate social impact of the mechanical weeding technology with precision. While the technology offers benefits, particularly in improving labour conditions, its broader social adoption is limited by high initial investment and operational costs. This moderate score suggests that, without additional financial support or policy initiatives, the technology’s social impact remains constrained, especially for smaller farms.</p>
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Social impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
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<i>The practice provides more stable income from year to year than alternatives</i>	0.32
<i>The current practice provides more flexibility for the agricultural management</i>	0.27
<i>New job opportunities in the rural area</i>	0.56
<i>Improvement of working conditions for the farm employers</i>	0.72
<i>Increased food safety</i>	0.25
<i>More job opportunities for women</i>	0.25
<i>Improving farmers' education and skills</i>	0.50
<i>Improved conditions for vulnerable groups</i>	0.30
<i>Improved aesthetics of the landscape and conservation of the cultural value</i>	0.40
<i>Improved social reputation of the farm</i>	0.30

TABLE 170: SOCIAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING COUPLED WITH PRECISION AGRICULTURE (ITALY 3)

The questionnaire results reveal a mixed perception of the social impacts associated with mechanical weeding when integrated with precision technology. The highest scores, specifically in improving working conditions for farm employees (0.72) and creating new job opportunities in rural areas (0.56), indicate that users recognize the technology's positive contribution to labour conditions and rural employment. This aligns with findings from Jacquet et al. (2021), which report medium-to-high short-term impacts on labour environments due to reduced physical demands on workers and increased operational efficiency.

However, certain social aspects, such as increased food safety (0.25), job opportunities for women (0.25), and improvement in the social reputation of farms (0.30), received lower scores. These results suggest that, despite its operational advantages, the technology has not yet had a significant impact on inclusivity, gender equality, or public perception. This finding contrasts with the moderate impact on workload reduction suggested by Tamirat et al. (2023), which emphasizes that while the technology may reduce physical demands, it has not fully translated into broader social inclusivity.

Additionally, the potential for enhanced food safety, which literature such as Liu et al. (2023) and Jacquet et al. (2021) associates with precision agriculture over the medium to long term, is currently perceived as low by users. This gap may indicate that while there is an anticipated benefit in reducing chemical residues through precision-based mechanical weeding, these benefits are not yet widely recognized or realized at the farm level.

In conclusion, while the technology is valued for improving worker welfare and supporting rural job creation, its broader social contributions, particularly in terms of inclusivity, public perception, and long-term food safety, remain limited. Addressing these areas could enhance the social impact and adoption of mechanical weeding with precision technology, potentially through targeted financial support, policy measures, or operational improvements focused on community and public health benefits.

Social direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Improved labour environment	Jacquet et al., (2021)	Medium-to-high	Short run	Non-monetary

Social indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Reduced workload	Tamirat et al. (2023)	Low-to-medium	Short run	Non-monetary
Enhanced food safety	Liu et al. (2023); Jacquet et al., (2021)	Low	Medium-to-long run	Non-monetary

TABLE 171: SOCIAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING COUPLED WITH PRECISION AGRICULTURE (ITALY 3)

Environmental analysis

 Traffic light 55.27%	<p>The traffic light score of 55.27% suggests a moderate overall environmental impact of the mechanical weeding technology with precision integration. While the technology does offer some environmental benefits, such as water conservation and reduced soil erosion, it also faces challenges, particularly in areas related to greenhouse gas emissions and reliance on external inputs.</p>
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Env. impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
Contribute to reduce Direct greenhouse gas emissions	0.50
Contribute to reduce external inputs	0.00
Limit water consumption	0.59
Contribute to reduce waste	0.00
Has a positive impact on biodiversity	0.33
Has a positive impact on soil erosion	0.50
Has a positive impact on carbon footprint	0.00
Increase the rate of soil organic matter mineralisation	0.50
Increase soil compaction	0.37

TABLE 172: ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING COUPLED WITH PRECISION AGRICULTURE (ITALY 3)

The questionnaire results show an interesting contrast in the perceived environmental benefits of mechanical weeding with precision technology. While users recognize the technology’s ability to limit water consumption (score: 0.59) and positively impact soil erosion (0.50), they rate it very low for reducing external inputs (0.00), waste reduction (0.00), and, unexpectedly, positive impact on the carbon footprint (0.00). This low score for carbon footprint is notable, as it contrasts with the actual operational benefit of fuel savings achieved through precision-controlled weeding, which should theoretically reduce greenhouse gas emissions. The low perception score may stem from users not fully associating fuel savings with emissions reduction, possibly due to a focus on immediate, localized emissions (e.g., machinery exhaust) rather than cumulative carbon savings from reduced fuel use over time. Additionally, users may overlook the indirect reduction in chemical inputs and the related energy savings in production and application, as these benefits are not directly tied to “clean energy” but rather to optimized fuel usage. This perception gap aligns with findings in the literature, such as Pergher et al. (2020), who highlight the environmental trade-offs of fuel-dependent mechanical systems in agriculture, despite their potential for reducing chemical inputs. Kup and Saglam (2014) emphasize the environmental advantages of minimizing harmful chemical applications, yet this benefit may be underappreciated in current adoption due to a lack of awareness of long-term cumulative gains. Clearer communication of these indirect benefits, particularly the cumulative carbon savings associated with fuel efficiency and reduced chemical use, could help users better understand the broader environmental advantages of precision mechanical weeding.

Env. direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Reduced use of harmful chemicals	Kup, F., & Saglam, R. (2014)	High	Short to Long-run	Quantitative

Env. indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Land Conservation (reduced soil erosion, off-site effects)	Liu et al. (2023); Jacquet et al. (2021)	Controversial	Long-run	Qualitative
Increase energy demand	Pergher, G., Gubiani, R., &	Medium to high	Short-run	Quantitative

TABLE 173: ENVIRONMENTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING COUPLED WITH PRECISION AGRICULTURE (ITALY 3)

Sensitivity analysis (only first scenario)

The sensitivity analysis for the first scenario reveals a generally positive financial outlook for the adoption of precision mechanical weeding technology in Italy 3. The NPV per hectare ranges from -354.69 euros to 9445.34 euros, with a mean of 4786.86 euros and a median of 4908.47 euros. There is a 100% probability of achieving a positive NPV, indicating that under the current assumptions, the project is financially viable. This high probability underscores the potential for positive returns on investment, largely driven by increased efficiency and reduced operational costs.

The BCR analysis further supports this favourable outcome, with values ranging from 0.77 to 3.81 and a default BCR of 2.46. The mean BCR of 2.01 demonstrates that the project generates significant returns, with a 99% probability that the BCR exceeds 1, suggesting that benefits consistently outweigh costs. The probability of achieving a BCR above the target of 2 is 47%, reinforcing the financial robustness of the project under varying conditions.

The sensitivity to discount rates shows stable results across different financial scenarios. At a low discount rate of 2%, the NPV is 735,074 euros, with a BCR of 2.75. At the default rate of 4%, the NPV remains strong at 552,183 euros, and at a higher discount rate of 6%, the NPV is still positive at 416,477 euros with a BCR of 2.21. These findings indicate that the project remains financially sustainable across a range of discount rates, highlighting the efficiency gains and cost savings from precision technology.

In conclusion, the sensitivity analysis suggests that, even without external financial support, such as subsidies, the adoption of this technology is financially sound. However, continued operational improvements, particularly in optimizing energy use and enhancing overall efficiency, could further strengthen the project's economic viability in the long term.

Net Present Value (NPV)	Tot. Euros	Euros ha ⁻¹
Minimum	-35,469	-354.69
Maximum	944,534	9445.34
Default case	552,183	5521.83
Mean	478,686	4786.86
Median	490,847	4908.47
Probability that NPV > 0		1.00
Distribution (euros)		Probability
Less than -35K		0.00
-35K to 161K		0.08
161K to 357K		0.21
357K to 553K		0.36
553K to 749K		0.23
749K to 945K		0.12
	Total	1.00
Benefit: Cost Ratio (BCR)		Unconstrained version
Minimum		0.77
Maximum		3.81
Default case		2.46
Mean		2.01
Median		1.94
Probability that BCR > 1		0.99
Target BCR		2
Probability BCR > Target		0.47
Distribution		Probability
Less than 0.77		0.00
0.77 to 1.38		0.14
1.38 to 1.99		0.39

1.99 to 2.59	0.29
2.59 to 3.20	0.13
3.20 to 3.81	0.05
Total	1.00

TABLE 174: BCA ROBUSTNESS (MONTE CARLO ANALYSIS BASED ON 1000 RANDOM SIMULATIONS) - MECHANICAL WEEDING COUPLED WITH PRECISION AGRICULTURE (ITALY 3)

Sensitivity to discount rate

Project organisation	Low discount rate 2%	Default discount rate 4%	High discount rate 6%
Benefits (present value)	1,154,581	930,009	761,400
Costs (present value)	419,507	377,826	344,924
Net Present Value (NPV)	735,074	552,183	416,477
Benefit: Cost Ratio (unconstrained budget)	2.75	2.46	2.21

TABLE 175: SENSITIVITY TO DISCOUNT RATE - MECHANICAL WEEDING COUPLED WITH PRECISION AGRICULTURE (ITALY 3)

4.2.4.2 Mechanical weeding coupled with reduced herbicide application with precision sprayer (Latvia 3)

Note on data quality: The quality of the data received was notably poor and difficult to interpret, despite several attempts and interviews to clarify ambiguities. Consequently, we are aware that the results may reflect potential errors of interpretation or issues related to the lack of comprehensive data. Therefore, while useful for framing a theoretical discussion, the findings should be approached with caution.

Main objective

The company's objective in implementing mechanical weeding integrated with precision agriculture is to improve operational efficiency and optimizes weed control with a lower environmental impact.

Description of the “before” scenario

Before the implementation of the solution, wheat fields were managed using conventional methods that relied only on chemical herbicides for weed control. Weed management involved multiple herbicide applications using a 335HP JD 8335 tractor equipped with a sprayer, capable of treating 25.2 hectares per hour with a fuel consumption of 2 L/ha. Fertilization was carried out using a JD 6830 tractor with a fertilizer spreader, which had a productivity of 30 hectares per hour and a fuel consumption of 3 L/ha. Sowing was conducted with the same JD 8335 tractor, fitted with a sowing machine, achieving a productivity of 4 hectares per hour and a fuel consumption of 10 L/ha.

The spraying process was performed in several stages to ensure effective weed control. The sprayer was used repeatedly, each pass required approximately 0.04 person-hours per hectare and consumed 2 L/ha of fuel. Water delivery for the spraying operations was handled by a JD 6900 tractor equipped with a water barrel, also achieving a productivity of 25.2 ha/h with a fuel consumption of 2 L/ha. Harvesting was performed using a JD S685i harvester, with a productivity of 2.5 ha/h and a fuel consumption of 30 L/ha. Transportation and delivery were managed using a JD 6920 tractor with a semi-trailer, capable of handling 2.4 ha/h while consuming 8 L/ha of fuel.

Description of the “after” scenario

After implementing the new approach, wheat fields were managed using a combination of mechanical treatments and reduced herbicide applications (thanks to precision sprayers). Weed management involved both chemical and mechanical strategies, significantly reducing the reliance on herbicides while maintaining operational efficiency.

Fertilization was conducted with a JD 6830 tractor and a fertilizer spreader, achieving a productivity rate of 30 hectares per hour with a fuel consumption of 3 L/ha. The fertilization process remained consistent across multiple applications, ensuring optimal nutrient distribution. Sowing was performed with a JD 8335 tractor equipped with a sowing machine, achieving a productivity of 4 hectares per hour with a higher fuel consumption of 10 L/ha. This process required 0.25 person-hours per hectare, reflecting the efficiency of the sowing operation. Weed control combined precision chemical spraying and mechanical treatments. The JD 612R sprayer was utilized, maintaining a productivity rate of 25.2 hectares per hour and consuming 2 L/ha of fuel. Each spraying pass required 0.04 person-hours per hectare, consistent with conventional methods, but chemical input was minimized due to supplementary mechanical treatments. Water delivery to support spraying was carried out with a JD 6900 tractor and a water barrel, with the same productivity rate of 25.2 hectares per hour and fuel consumption of 2 L/ha. This step was crucial to ensuring effective herbicide application while conserving inputs.

Harvesting operations were performed with a JD S685i harvester, achieving a productivity rate of 2.5 hectares per hour and consuming 30 L/ha of fuel, reflecting the intensive energy demands of the harvest. Transportation and delivery were managed using a JD 6920 tractor with a semi-trailer, capable of handling 2.4 hectares per hour and consuming 8 L/ha of fuel, ensuring efficient post-harvest logistics.

Similar to findings in the literature, such as Jacquet et al. (2021) and Shrestha et al. (2013), this shift could reduce chemical inputs, improve cost efficiency, and align with environmental sustainability goals. If

successful, the project's fuel consumption and operational efficiency might reflect trends noted in studies like Gagliardi et al. (2023), suggesting mechanical weeding as a viable alternative in vineyards.

Input data and farm characteristics

The farm operates under conventional management practices and is involved in wheat production. The total area of the farm dedicated for experimental purposes is one hectare, and the crop is precisely wheat.

<i>Management Type</i>	Conventional
<i>Most important crops and animal productions</i>	Wheat
<i>Total Farm Area (ha)</i>	1
<i>Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA, ha)</i>	1
<i>Experimental area (ha)</i>	1
<i>Experimental crop(s)</i>	Wheat

TABLE 176: INPUT DATA AND FARM CHARACTERISTICS FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING COUPLED WITH REDUCED HERBICIDE APPLICATION WITH PRECISION SPRAYER (LATVIA 3)

The investment analysis assumes a common scenario where agricultural companies already possess the necessary tractors for wheat cultivation (indicated in detail in the description of the scenarios before and after the introduction of the practice).

Meaning the harrow can be integrated into existing machinery. As such, the focus is on the cost of the new equipment, with no need to account for the purchase of tractors. The initial cost for the harrow is estimated at 20,570 euros, with a 7-year expected lifetime starting from 2020. In this analysis, the harrow is replaced every 7 years, with costs determined by accounting for both future value appreciation at an annual rate of 5% and depreciation at 15% per year. For subsequent purchases, the effective costs are calculated by determining the future value of previous purchases after 7 and 14 years, respectively, while applying the same depreciation rate. This decision reflects a realistic estimate of the actual investment required, ensuring that the analysis does not underestimate the costs faced by agricultural businesses.

Investment costs (euros)

<i>Machine and Tools</i>	Annual costs	Year	Expected lifetime (n. year)
<i>Harrow</i>	20,570	2020	7
<i>2nd tool purchase</i>	22,349	2027	7
<i>3rd tool purchase</i>	31,448	2034	7

TABLE 177: INVESTMENT COSTS FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING COUPLED WITH REDUCED HERBICIDE APPLICATION WITH PRECISION SPRAYER (LATVIA 3)

The operating costs for the harrow reflect several critical elements, including adjustments in maintenance costs due to changes in workflow post-implementation. Machine maintenance costs are calculated at 3% of the purchase price. For the first tool purchased in 2020, annual maintenance costs are set at 617.10 euros, applicable from 2020 to 2027. For the second tool purchased in 2027, maintenance costs increase to 868.32 euros annually, covering the period from 2027 to 2034. The third tool, purchased in 2034, incurs an annual maintenance cost of 1,221.82 euros, which will apply from 2034 to 2040. These adjustments reflect the projected costs over each tool's lifespan, accounting for changes in operational needs and the impact of technological improvements on workflow efficiency. In addition, the combined cost of fertilizer and herbicides, provided as an aggregate value, also decreased. Overall, the introduction of mechanical weeding and the reduction of chemical inputs resulted in a total savings of 13.31 euros per hectare, showing greater cost efficiency in farm management. Finally, with regard to fuel, there is a slight saving of 2.28 euros per hectare.

Operating costs (euros year⁻¹)

	Annual costs - Pre	Annual costs - Post	Year
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<i>Machine maintenance (3% of purchase price)</i>		1 st tool purchase – 617.10	2020
		2 nd tool purchase – 868.32	2027
		3 rd tool purchase – 1,221.82	2034
<i>Fertilizer and herbicide cost (aggregate value)</i>	360.25	346.94	2020-2040
<i>Fuel</i>	60.04	62.32	2020-2040

TABLE 178: OPERATING COSTS FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING COUPLED WITH REDUCED HERBICIDE APPLICATION WITH PRECISION SPRAYER (LATVIA 3)

The project incurs annual labour costs of 200 euros for technical support and 22 euros per worker for training, covering the period from 2020 to 2040. The new crop operations do not result in a net change in labour costs; however, an increase of 1.88 euros per hectare should be noted.

Labour costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Labour</i>	15.83	2020-2040
<i>Technical support</i>	200	2020-2040
<i>Training</i>	22	2020-2040

TABLE 179: LABOUR COSTS FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING COUPLED WITH REDUCED HERBICIDE APPLICATION WITH PRECISION SPRAYER (LATVIA 3)

The Other costs section includes transaction costs of 40.20 euros in 2020 (1 hectare), representing the administrative or operational expenses associated with implementing the changes. Opportunity costs are calculated as the present value, in 2020, of the capital allocated to the purchase of tools. The opportunity cost for the first purchase is 3,593.28 euros, while for the second purchase, it is 2,966.85 euros. For the third purchase, the opportunity cost is 3,172.40 euros.

Other costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Transaction costs</i>	40.20	2020
<i>Opportunity costs (Present Value)</i>		
<i>1st purchase</i>	3,593.28	2020
<i>2nd purchase</i>	2,966.85	2020
<i>3rd purchase</i>	3,172.40	2020

TABLE 180: OTHER COSTS FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING COUPLED WITH REDUCED HERBICIDE APPLICATION WITH PRECISION SPRAYER (LATVIA 3)

Cost-benefit identification

<i>Category</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Attribute</i>
Benefit per person or household	Improved Labour Environment	Reduction of workers' risk from exposure to phytosanitary products (public)	Qualitative
Benefit per unit of abatement	Enhanced Food quality and safety	Reduced risk of chemical residues on crops (public)	Qualitative
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced or zero costs for weed management (agrochemicals)	Direct cost savings by reducing the use of herbicides (private)	Monetary 308 euros – present value
Improve an environmental or community asset	Ecological improvement	Improve biodiversity (public)	Qualitative
Reduced consequence of a risky event	Land conservation	Reduced soil erosion/increase productivity (on-site private, off-site public)	Mixed
Total (monetary) benefits			308 euros

TABLE 181: IDENTIFIED BENEFITS FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING COUPLED WITH REDUCED HERBICIDE APPLICATION WITH PRECISION SPRAYER (LATVIA 3)

In the described case of implementing precision-enhanced mechanical weeding in Latvia, the transition from conventional methods brings both qualitative and modest financial benefits, though the financial impact is notably minimal. Qualitatively, the system enhances the working environment by reducing workers' exposure to phytosanitary products, thereby creating a safer workplace. Additionally, it improves food safety by lowering the risk of chemical residues on crops, which is a significant health benefit for consumers.

From a financial perspective, the benefits are relatively modest. The direct cost savings from reduced herbicide use amount to only 308 euros over a period of 20 years, representing a minor financial improvement when compared to the scale of agricultural operations. Notably, there is no reduction in labour time or fuel consumption. In fact, the document specifies that fuel consumption for sowing has increased from an unspecified rate to 10 L/ha. This increase may be attributed to the greater complexity of sowing operations that integrate precision agriculture, possibly requiring more intensive tractor use and multiple passes over the field. Therefore, while there is a clear environmental benefit from reducing chemical herbicides, the energy expenditure remains a critical consideration. The actual environmental and economic impact should be assessed by weighing both the reduction in herbicide use and the increase in fuel consumption. This nuanced view is essential to understand the overall implications of introducing new technologies in mechanical weeding practices.

It is important to note that accurately capturing the energy consumption data was not possible due to the lack of specific details provided. This significant limitation impacts our analysis substantially. Without comprehensive data on fuel consumption for each operation both before and after the implementation of precision-enhanced mechanical weeding, it becomes challenging to assess the true energy costs and the environmental impact of the new methods. The absence of this critical data hinders a complete understanding of potential increases or savings in energy usage, which is essential for evaluating the overall effectiveness and sustainability of the agricultural practices involved.

<i>Category</i>	<i>Cost item</i>	<i>Value (Euros)</i>	<i>Present Value (euros)</i>
<i>Capital costs (CAPEX)</i>	<i>Tool</i>	74,368	55,715
<i>Operating costs, including operations and maintenance (OPEX)</i>	<i>Maintenance</i>	2,707	13,345
	<i>Fuel</i>	2	33
	<i>Labour</i>	16	231
<i>Other costs</i>	<i>Technical support</i>	200	2,918
	<i>Training year</i>	22	321
	<i>Transaction costs</i>	-	40,2
	<i>Opportunity costs</i>	-	9,732
<i>Total Costs</i>			82,335

TABLE 182: IDENTIFIED COSTS FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING COUPLED WITH REDUCED HERBICIDE APPLICATION WITH PRECISION SPRAYER (LATVIA 3)

Economic analysis

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR (%)
20	-82,028	0	-100

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR
20	-82,217	0.96	3.9

TABLE 183: ECONOMIC ANALYSIS FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING COUPLED WITH REDUCED HERBICIDE APPLICATION WITH PRECISION SPRAYER (LATVIA 3)

The economic analysis table exposes the significant financial challenges encountered under two scenarios: one with high adoption and no project failure, and another with low adoption and minimal project failure. The first scenario, despite its optimistic assumptions, shows a dire financial performance with an NPV of -

82,028 euros per hectare and a BCR of 0, suggesting that investments yield no return. This is further evidenced by an MIRR of -100%, indicating that the project is financially untenable under these conditions. The second scenario offers a slight improvement with an NPV of -82,217 euros and a BCR of 0.96, nearly breaking even, but still reflects a problematic financial outlook with an MIRR of only 3.9%. These figures critically underscore the need for comprehensive benefit data to potentially offset these negative financial impacts and provide a more balanced assessment of the project's economic viability.

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

FIGURE 15: GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF NET AND CUMULATIVE BENEFITS UNDER TWO SCENARIOS: NO RISK OF FAILURE WITH HIGH ADOPTION (TOP) AND LOW RISK OF FAILURE WITH LOW ADOPTION (BOTTOM)

The graphical representations in the analysis clearly display the financial trajectory of the mechanical weeding project under two distinct scenarios. However, it is crucial to acknowledge that our research is heavily influenced by the lack of comprehensive data, primarily due to inadequacies in the data provided from interviews. This limitation severely restricts our ability to correctly interpret the evaluation results. The graphs, while showing a trend of negative returns across both scenarios, underscore the critical data gaps in assessing the project's economic viability. This emphasizes the urgent need for a strategic reevaluation of the project's operational framework. To possibly improve the projected outcomes and provide a more accurate financial analysis, it is essential to integrate a broader spectrum of tangible benefits and more reliable data sources in future assessments.

Social analysis

	<p>The Latvia 3 case presents a nuanced understanding of the social impacts of mechanical weeding integrated with precision technology, capturing a traffic light score of 57.02%. This indicates a moderate social impact of the technology, which, while beneficial in improving labour conditions, faces limitations in broader social adoption due to high initial investments and operational costs. The score reflects the constrained impact on smaller farms, where financial hurdles prevent widespread adoption. This moderate rating suggests</p>
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Traffic light 57.02%	that without additional financial incentives or supportive policy measures, the potential of the technology to reach its full social impact remains limited.
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Social impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
<i>The practice provides more stable income from year to year than alternatives</i>	0.51
<i>The current practice provides more flexibility for the agricultural management</i>	0.41
<i>New job opportunities in the rural area</i>	0.49
<i>Improvement of working conditions for the farm employers</i>	0.59
<i>Increased food safety</i>	0.25
<i>More job opportunities for women</i>	0.25
<i>Improving farmers' education and skills</i>	0.50
<i>Improved conditions for vulnerable groups</i>	0.30
<i>Improved aesthetics of the landscape and conservation of the cultural value</i>	0.40
<i>Improved social reputation of the farm</i>	0.30

TABLE 184: SOCIAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING COUPLED WITH REDUCED HERBICIDE APPLICATION WITH PRECISION SPRAYER (LATVIA 3)

In examining the social impact perceptions derived from the questionnaire, the mixed responses highlight several key areas of benefit and concern. Areas such as improving working conditions for farm employees and creating new job opportunities in rural areas received higher scores, suggesting recognition of the technology's benefits to labour conditions and employment in rural settings. However, scores related to increased food safety, opportunities for women, and improving the social reputation of farms were notably low. This discrepancy underscores a gap between operational advantages and broader social benefits such as inclusivity, gender equality, and enhanced public perception. The comparison with literature reveals both convergences and divergences; for instance, while some studies like those by Jacquet et al. (2021) have noted improvements in labour environments, the anticipated benefits in food safety and social inclusivity have yet to be fully realized or acknowledged at the farm level. Addressing these gaps, particularly in inclusivity and public health benefits, could significantly enhance the social impact and adoption of this technology, potentially through targeted financial support and operational improvements.

Social direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Improved labour environment	Jacquet et al., (2021)	Medium-to-high	Short run	Non-monetary

Social indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Reduced workload	Tamirat et al. (2023)	Low-to-medium	Short run	Non-monetary
Enhanced food safety	Liu et al. (2023); Jacquet et al., (2021)	Low	Medium-to-long run	Non-monetary

TABLE 185: SOCIAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING COUPLED WITH REDUCED HERBICIDE APPLICATION WITH PRECISION SPRAYER (LATVIA 3)

Environmental analysis

	The environmental impact assessment of the Latvia 3 case through the traffic light system yields a score of 53.94%, indicating a moderate overall environmental impact from integrating precision mechanical weeding technology. This assessment reflects a balance between the technology's advantages, like water conservation and reduced soil erosion, and its challenges, including concerns over greenhouse gas emissions and dependence on external inputs. This moderate rating underscores the need for enhanced strategies that could better leverage the technology's potential environmental benefits while mitigating its shortcomings.
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Traffic light 53.94%	
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Env. impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
Contribute to reduce Direct greenhouse gas emissions	0.57
Contribute to reduce external inputs	0.80
Limit water consumption	0.57
Contribute to reduce waste	0.60
Has a positive impact on biodiversity	0.27
Has a positive impact on soil erosion	0.65
Has a positive impact on carbon footprint	0.80
Increase the rate of soil organic matter mineralisation	0.27
Increase soil compaction	0.27

TABLE 186: ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING COUPLED WITH REDUCED HERBICIDE APPLICATION WITH PRECISION SPRAYER (LATVIA 3)

Survey responses concerning environmental impacts present a mixed perception of the benefits associated with mechanical weeding and precision technology. High scores in reducing external inputs (0.80) and positively impacting the carbon footprint (0.80) suggest that users appreciate the technology’s capacity to minimize chemical use and optimize fuel consumption, which theoretically should lead to lower greenhouse gas emissions. However, lower scores in areas such as biodiversity impact (0.27) and the influence on soil compaction (0.27) highlight a notable gap in perceived benefits, particularly in how the technology affects broader ecological factors. This discrepancy might be attributed to a lack of visible or immediate evidence of these benefits or possibly a gap in user education regarding the environmental impacts of their practices. The perceived low impact on biodiversity and soil health could be addressed through better education and clear communication about the long-term environmental benefits of reduced chemical use and enhanced soil management practices.

The contrast between high recognition of certain benefits and the underappreciation of others suggests that while the technology is valued for specific environmental efficiencies, its broader ecological contributions are not fully recognized or realized at the farm level. Enhancing user awareness and understanding of all environmental impacts, not just those directly related to chemical and fuel use, could help bridge this perception gap and improve the technology's overall environmental performance evaluation.

Env. direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Reduced use of harmful chemicals	Kup, F., & Saglam, R. (2014)	High	Short to Long-run	Quantitative

Env. indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Land Conservation (reduced soil erosion, off-site effects)	Liu et al. (2023); Jacquet et al. (2021)	Controversial	Long-run	Qualitative
Increase energy demand	Pergher, G., Gubiani, R., & Mainardis, M. (2020)	Medium to high	Short-run	Quantitative

TABLE 187: ENVIRONMENTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM MECHANICAL WEEDING COUPLED WITH REDUCED HERBICIDE APPLICATION WITH PRECISION SPRAYER (LATVIA 3)

Sensitivity analysis (only first scenario)

Given the highly simplified nature of this case and the associated analysis, which is characterized by limited data availability, we consider it largely theoretical and not highly representative. For this reason, a full sensitivity analysis was not conducted, as the low number of variables (benefits) involved does not justify

its application. Furthermore, the limited robustness of the analysis itself suggests that such an exercise would not have significantly enhanced the overall value or insight of the study. Instead, the focus remains on presenting an initial exploratory framework, acknowledging its limitations while providing a foundation for further, more detailed investigations.

4.2.4.3 Camera guided mechanical weeding (Greece 4)

Main objective

The project aims to reduce herbicide use in vegetable crops by introducing Camera guided mechanical weeding.

Description of the “before” scenario

Prior to implementing the camera-guided mechanical control system, weed management and soil preparation in vegetable crops involved a combination of manual and mechanical operations. Plowing was done using a FENDT 516 tractor (120KW, 147 HP) at a capacity of 0.58 hectares per hour, with a fuel consumption rate of 38.1 liters per hectare for soil treatment. Bed forming was completed with the same tractor combined with a bed former, achieving 1.02 hectares per hour and using 17.6 liters of fuel per hectare. Sowing operations were carried out with a John Deere 6220 paired with a Monosem seeder, while herbicides were applied with the John Deere 6220 equipped with a sprayer, covering 7.8 hectares per hour and consuming 0.9 liters of fuel per hectare. Manual weeding was performed by field workers at an estimated rate of 0.3 hectares per hour, and fertilization was completed using the FENDT 516 tractor, reaching 6.72 hectares per hour and consuming 1.18 liters of fuel per hectare. This approach involved a high level of fuel consumption and extensive manual labour.

Description of the “after” scenario

After the introduction of the camera-guided mechanical control system, adjustments were made to optimize operations. While plowing, bed forming, and sowing remained unchanged in their processes, a new camera-guided mechanical weeding system was implemented using the FENDT 516 tractor. Although this system improved precision, it resulted in higher fuel consumption per hectare, reaching 12.7 liters per hectare, compared to the initial method. Fertilization practices also remained consistent, still utilizing the FENDT 516 with similar rates of coverage and fuel use as before.

Input data and farm characteristics

The company operates a 50-hectare farm dedicated to conventional vegetable crops (fresh onions). Within this, a 15-hectare experimental area is designated for the research on the precision agriculture solution.

<i>Management Type</i>	Conventional
<i>Most important crops and animal productions</i>	Fresh Onion
<i>Total Farm Area (ha)</i>	50
<i>Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA, ha)</i>	15
<i>Experimental area (ha)</i>	15
<i>Experimental crop(s)</i>	Fresh Onion

TABLE 188: INPUT DATA AND FARM CHARACTERISTICS FROM CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (GREECE 4)

The investment analysis is based on the most common scenario, where agricultural companies already own a tractor, allowing the advanced camera-guided system to be integrated into existing machinery. This approach keeps the initial investment costs aligned with typical agricultural practices. If a company were required to purchase a new tractor in addition to the camera-guided system, the overall investment costs would rise considerably.

Although there are more affordable systems available on the market, we have chosen to estimate the initial purchase cost at 40,000 euros and the replacement cost at 43,461 euros in 2030. This decision ensures we do not underestimate the actual investment needed, and it reflects a more representative scenario frequently encountered by agricultural businesses. The focus is on the acquisition of a technologically advanced tool designed for precision agriculture, offering a more realistic projection of long-term costs. By using this common scenario, the analysis provides a practical and accurate forecast for companies seeking to integrate advanced technological solutions into their operations.

Investment costs (euros)

<i>Machine and Tools</i>	Annual costs	Year	Expected lifetime (n. year)
<i>Advanced Camera guided system</i>	40,000	2020	10
<i>2nd tool purchase</i>	43,461	2030	10

TABLE 189: INVESTMENT COSTS FROM CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (GREECE 4)

The operating costs for the advanced camera-guided system reflect several key elements, including fuel expenses, software maintenance, and machine maintenance, with assumptions about technological upkeep. Fuel expenses increase from 1,115.83 euros annually before the implementation of the system to 1,329.65 euros annually post-implementation, spanning from 2020 to 2040. This rise is driven by the higher energy demands of mechanical operations and an assumed 5% annual inflation in fuel prices over time. Software maintenance and updates are set at 500 euros annually throughout the 20-year period (2020–2040). These costs cover essential updates, patches, and improvements to ensure the system remains functional and compatible with other technologies. Unlike other costs, software maintenance is assumed to remain fixed over the years, reflecting a stable expense dedicated to maintaining the system's digital components. Machine maintenance is calculated at 10% of the purchase price and adjusts with inflation. For the first system (2020–2029), annual maintenance costs amount to 4,000 euros, while for the second system (2030–2040), the costs rise to 4,346 euros. This increase reflects the 5% inflation applied to hardware maintenance costs over time, ensuring that the projection accounts for rising service and parts expenses.

Operating costs (euros year⁻¹)

	Annual costs - Pre	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Fuel</i>	1,115.83	1,329.65	2020-2040
<i>Software maintenance/updates</i>		500	2020-2040
<i>Machine maintenance (10% of purchase price)</i>		1 st tool purchase - 4000 2 nd tool purchase -4,346	2020-2029 2030-2040

TABLE 190: OPERATING COSTS FROM CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (GREECE 4)

The labour costs for implementing the advanced camera-guided system include various elements that reflect the need for setup, calibration, and continuous training. The set-up costs are 2,000 euros in 2020 for the initial installation, followed by 2,814 euros in 2030 for the second system setup, aligning with the system replacement. These costs cover the technical work required to install and configure the system properly to ensure its integration with existing machinery. Calibration costs are incurred twice during the 20-year period. The first calibration is set at 1,000 euros in 2020, with a second calibration required in 2030 at a cost of 1,407 euros. These periodic calibrations are necessary to maintain the precision and effectiveness of the system, especially as it integrates with other farm operations. Additionally, training costs are estimated at 22 euros per worker per year, covering the years from 2022 to 2042. This investment ensures that the workforce remains proficient in using the advanced system, adapting to new updates and practices that may arise over time. Continuous training helps minimize the risk of operational issues and ensures that the system operates efficiently throughout its lifespan. These labour costs are essential to ensure both the technological and human aspects of the system's operation are fully supported.

Labour costs (euros)

	Pre	Post	Year
<i>Set-up cost</i>		2,000	2020
		2,814	2030
<i>Calibration cost</i>		1st calibration – 1000	2020
		2nd calibration – 1,407	2030
<i>Training</i>		22	2022-2042

TABLE 191: LABOUR COSTS FROM CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (GREECE 4)

The Other costs section includes transaction costs of 603 euros in 2020 (15 hectares), representing the administrative or operational expenses associated with implementing the changes. Opportunity costs are

calculated as the present value in 2020 of capital allocated to the tool purchases. The opportunity cost for the first purchase is 6,987 euros, while for the second purchase, it is 5,769 euros. These costs reflect the economic trade-offs of committing resources to the precision system instead of alternative investments.

Other costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Post	Year
Transaction costs	603	2020
Opportunity costs (Present Value)		
1 st purchase	6,987	2020
2 nd purchase	5,769	2020

TABLE 192: OTHER COSTS FROM CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (GREECE 4)

Cost-benefit identification

Category	Name	Type	Attribute
Benefit per person or household	Improved Labour Environment	Reduction of workers' risk from exposure to phytosanitary products (public)	Qualitative
Benefit per unit of abatement	Enhanced Food quality and safety	Reduced risk of chemical residues on grapes (public)	Qualitative
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced or zero costs for weed management	Direct cost savings by reducing the use of herbicides (private)	Monetary 1,736 euros – present value
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced fertilizer		Monetary 41,666 euros – present value
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced labour costs		Monetary 16,227 euros – present value
Total (monetary) benefits			59,629 euros

TABLE 193: IDENTIFIED BENEFITS FROM CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (GREECE 4)

The adoption of the camera-guided mechanical weeding system brings several significant benefits, both qualitative and monetary. From a social standpoint, it improves the labour environment by reducing workers' exposure to phytosanitary products, minimizing health risks and enhancing overall safety. The system also contributes to improved food quality and safety by reducing the risk of chemical residues on crops, further benefiting public health.

Economically, the system generates direct cost savings by reducing or eliminating the use of herbicides, resulting in a present value savings of 1,736 euros. Additionally, the reduction in fertilizer usage leads to further savings, with a present value of 41,666 euros. The technology also reduces labour costs, with an estimated present value of 16,227 euros. These operational cost reductions make farm management more sustainable and improve overall profitability.

In total, the monetary benefits associated with the adoption of the camera-guided mechanical weeding system amount to 59,662 euros, reflecting the combined savings from reduced herbicide use, fertilizer, and labour costs.

Category	Cost item	Value (Euros)	Present Value (euros)	
Capital costs (CAPEX)	Tool	83,461	69,361	
Operating costs, including operations and maintenance (OPEX)	Fuel	214	3,120	
	Maintenance	8,836	67,786	
	Labour	Set-up	4,814	3,901
	Calibration	2,407	1,951	
	Training year	22	321	
Other costs	Transaction costs		603	
	Opportunity costs		12,756	
	CO ₂ *		2,770.26	
Total Costs			159,799	

TABLE 194: IDENTIFIED COSTS FROM CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (GREECE 4)

* We do not include the calculation of CO2 emissions in the private analysis because they represent a cost shifted onto society and are not part of the private cost-benefit balance. However, these emissions were calculated separately to account for their broader impact, using values from the EIB Group climate bank roadmap 2021-2025. The roadmap provides the basis for the shadow cost, which represents the minimum societal cost of achieving the 1.5°C temperature target (EIB, 2020).

Economic analysis

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR (%)
20	6,678	0.37	-3.2

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR
20	-9,110.86	0.14	-100

TABLE 195: ECONOMIC ANALYSIS FROM CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (GREECE 4)

In the first scenario, assuming no risk of project failure and high adoption, the financial performance remains challenging but not as severe as in the second scenario. The NPV per hectare is 6,678 euros, the BCR is 0.37, and the MIRR is -3.2%. These figures indicate that while the project manages to produce some financial return, it is still not sufficient to cover the costs fully. The relatively low BCR suggests that for every euro invested, the project yields less than 40% in return, which is inadequate for long-term financial sustainability. The negative MIRR further emphasizes that the project's internal rate of return is insufficient to justify the initial investment and ongoing costs under these optimistic conditions.

In the second scenario, with low risk of project failure but low adoption, the financial outlook worsens significantly. The NPV drops to -9,110.86 euros per hectare, with a BCR of 0.14 and an MIRR of -100%. The low adoption rate leads to poor cost distribution, making it harder to recoup the initial investments. The very low BCR reflects that the benefits generated by the project are only a fraction of the costs incurred, and the extremely negative MIRR indicates that the financial returns are drastically insufficient to support the project over time.

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

FIGURE 16: GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF NET AND CUMULATIVE BENEFITS UNDER TWO SCENARIOS: NO RISK OF FAILURE WITH HIGH ADOPTION (TOP) AND LOW RISK OF FAILURE WITH LOW ADOPTION (BOTTOM)

In the first scenario (no risk of project failure and high adoption), the net benefits graph shows some positive returns in certain years, but these are short-lived and are followed by sharp negative drops, particularly during reinvestment periods. These dips represent the financial burden of re-investment in new machinery or technology required to sustain the project. The cumulative net benefits graph shows a gradual downward trend over the years, indicating that the project is unable to achieve lasting financial stability, despite favorable conditions.

In the second scenario (low risk of project failure and low adoption), the situation is even more concerning. The net benefits graph shows consistently negative results across the entire 20-year period, with no indication of financial recovery. The cumulative net benefits graph highlights a continuously declining financial trajectory, where losses deepen over time without any opportunity for positive financial performance. This scenario underscores the critical importance of achieving broader adoption to distribute costs more effectively and improve the financial outlook.

Social analysis

 Traffic light 62.10%	<p>The traffic light score of 62.10% indicates a moderate overall social impact of the camera-guided mechanical weeding technology. This score reflects that, while the technology has certain benefits, particularly in improving labour conditions and increasing flexibility in agricultural management, there are limitations that prevent its broader social impact. The high initial investment and operational costs are significant barriers, particularly for smaller farms, limiting the technology's accessibility. The score suggests that, while some social benefits exist, these remain constrained without additional financial support or policy interventions.</p>
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Social impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
<i>The practice provides more stable income from year to year than alternatives</i>	0.49
<i>The current practice provides more flexibility for the agricultural management</i>	0.44
<i>New job opportunities in the rural area</i>	0.48
<i>Improvement of working conditions for the farm employers</i>	0.53
<i>Increased food safety</i>	0.50
<i>More job opportunities for women</i>	0.25
<i>Improving farmers' education and skills</i>	0.50
<i>Improved conditions for vulnerable groups</i>	0.45
<i>Improved aesthetics of the landscape and conservation of the cultural value</i>	0.40
<i>Improved social reputation of the farm</i>	0.30

TABLE 196: SOCIAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (GREECE 4)

The questionnaire results show the highest scores in improving working conditions (0.53) and increasing food safety (0.50), but these are still moderate scores, indicating that while there are perceived benefits from the camera-guided mechanical weeding technology, they are not seen as highly impactful. This suggests that the technology does offer improvements in employee welfare and product safety, but these benefits are not substantial enough to be considered transformative. The moderate nature of these scores implies that while the technology is making positive changes, it has not yet fully realized its potential to significantly enhance working conditions or food safety on a larger scale. These findings align with the literature, such as Jacquet et al. (2021), which reports a medium-to-high impact on labour environments in the short run. However, lower scores were noted in areas like creating job opportunities for women (0.25) and improving the social reputation of farms (0.30), suggesting that the technology has not yet had a significant impact on social inclusivity or public perception. This contrasts with the literature, as Tamirat et al. (2023) emphasizes the technology's potential to reduce workload, even if only moderately in the short term. Additionally, while Liu et al. (2023) and Jacquet et al. (2021) point to potential food safety improvements over the medium-to-long run, the questionnaire results reflect only moderate recognition of this benefit at present. Furthermore, while the technology offers clear operational advantages, its broader social contributions, particularly in terms of inclusivity and reputation, remain limited compared to its potential.

Social direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Improved labour environment	Jacquet et al., (2021)	Medium-to-high	Short run	Non-monetary

Social indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Reduced workload	Tamirat et al. (2023)	Low-to-medium	Short run	Non-monetary
Enhanced food safety	Liu et al. (2023); Jacquet et al., (2021)	Low	Medium-to-long run	Non-monetary

TABLE 197: SOCIAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (GREECE 4)

Environmental analysis

<p>Traffic light 58.74%</p>	<p>The traffic light score of 58.74% indicates a moderate overall environmental impact of the camera-guided mechanical weeding technology. This score suggests that while the technology provides some environmental benefits, such as reducing external inputs and supporting biodiversity, it faces significant challenges in areas like fuel consumption and greenhouse gas emissions, which limit its broader environmental effectiveness.</p>
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Env. impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
Contribute to reduce Direct greenhouse gas emissions	0.55
Contribute to reduce external inputs	0.80
Limit water consumption	0.55
Contribute to reduce waste	0.30
Has a positive impact on biodiversity	0.57
Has a positive impact on soil erosion	0.57
Has a positive impact on carbon footprint	0.20
Increase the rate of soil organic matter mineralisation	0.55
Increase soil compaction	0.53

TABLE 198: ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (GREECE 4)

The environmental impact perceptions from the questionnaire reflect a mix of moderate to high scores across different environmental categories. The highest score was for contributing to reducing external inputs (0.80), indicating the technology's effectiveness in reducing the use of chemical herbicides, a key environmental benefit. Other notable scores include positive impacts on biodiversity (0.57) and soil erosion (0.57), which align with findings in the literature that mechanical systems can support ecological health by limiting soil degradation and chemical use.

However, the technology received moderate scores in areas like reducing greenhouse gas emissions (0.55) and limiting water consumption (0.55). These results indicate that while the technology reduces reliance on harmful chemicals, it still faces challenges related to its reliance on fuel, contributing to emissions. The score for having a positive impact on the carbon footprint (0.20) was notably low, highlighting concerns about the environmental trade-offs associated with the technology's energy demands. Concerns about soil compaction (0.53) and soil organic matter mineralization (0.55) were also raised, indicating that while the technology has benefits, its long-term impact on soil health is context-dependent and requires careful management to avoid negative effects. These results are consistent with Pergher et al. (2020), who note the challenges of energy-intensive mechanical systems in agricultural settings, where fuel consumption remains a significant environmental drawback.

Env. direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Reduced use of harmful chemicals	Kup, F., & Saglam, R. (2014)	High	Short to Long-run	Quantitative

Env. indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Land Conservation (reduced soil erosion, off-site effects)	Liu et al. (2023); Jacquet et al. (2021)	Controversial	Long-run	Qualitative
Increase energy demand	Pergher, G., Gubiani, R., & Mainardis, M. (2020)	Medium to high	Short-run	Quantitative

TABLE 199: ENVIRONMENTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (GREECE 4)

Sensitivity analysis (only first scenario)

The sensitivity analysis for the first scenario highlights a consistently negative financial outlook for the adoption of the camera-guided mechanical weeding technology. The NPV per hectare ranges from -11,877.07 to -2,289.4 euros, with a mean of -6,919.2 euros and a median of -6,967.8 euros. The probability of achieving a positive NPV is 0%, indicating that under the current assumptions, the project is financially unfeasible. These negative NPV values emphasize the significant CAPEX and ongoing operational costs, making adoption challenging, particularly for smaller farms or those lacking financial support.

The BCR analysis echoes this outcome, with values ranging from 0.12 to 0.58, and a default case of 0.37. The mean BCR of 0.31 reflects the insufficient benefits relative to costs. The probability of the BCR exceeding 1 is 0%, confirming that the technology's benefits do not cover its costs. The Monte Carlo simulation supports this, with 50% of the outcomes falling between -121K and -92K euros, reinforcing the trend of financial losses.

When considering different discount rates, the results show limited improvement. At a 2% discount rate, the NPV is -107,077 euros, with a BCR of 0.41. At the default 4% rate, the NPV remains negative at -100,170 euros, and at a 6% rate, it is -94,370 euros, with a BCR of 0.34. These outcomes suggest that the high costs related to energy use and maintenance outweigh the potential operational benefits, regardless of financial conditions.

In conclusion, the sensitivity analysis suggests that, without significant external financial support, such as subsidies or cost-sharing schemes, the adoption of this technology is not financially sustainable. Moreover, there is a need for operational improvements, particularly in reducing energy consumption and increasing overall efficiency, to enhance the long-term economic viability of the project.

Net Present Value (NPV)	Tot. Euros	Euros ha⁻¹
Minimum	-178,156	-11,877.067
Maximum	-34,341	-2,289.4
Default case	-100,170	-6,678
Mean	-103,788	-6,919.2
Median	-104,517	-6,967.8
Probability that NPV > 0		0.00
Distribution (euros)		Probability
Less than -179K		0.00
-179K to -150K		0.11
-150K to -121K		0.15
-121K to -92K		0.40
-92K to -63K		0.15
-63K to -34K		0.18
	Total	1.00
Benefit: Cost Ratio (BCR)		Unconstrained version
Minimum		0.12
Maximum		0.58
Default case		0.37
Mean		0.31
Median		0.29
Probability that BCR > 1		0.00
Target BCR		2
Probability BCR > Target		0.00
Distribution		Probability
Less than 0.12		0.00
0.12 to 0.21		0.13
0.21 to 0.30		0.38
0.30 to 0.39		0.31
0.39 to 0.49		0.13
0.49 to 0.58		0.05
	Total	1.00

TABLE 200: BCA ROBUSTNESS (MONTE CARLO ANALYSIS BASED ON 1000 RANDOM SIMULATIONS) - CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (GREECE 4)

Sensitivity to discount rate

Project organisation	Low discount rate	Default discount rate	High discount rate
	2%	4%	6%
Benefits (present value)	73,406	59,629	49,285
Costs (present value)	180,482	159,799	143,656
Net Present Value (NPV)	-107,077	-100,170	-94,370
Benefit: Cost Ratio (unconstrained budget)	0.41	0.37	0.34

TABLE 201: SENSITIVITY TO DISCOUNT RATE - CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (GREECE 4)

4.2.4.4 Targeted (precision) spraying - field vegetable crops (UK 3)

Main objective

The project aims to reduce herbicide use in vegetable crops by introducing Camera guided mechanical weeding.

Description of the "before" scenario

Prior to the implementation of the camera-guided mechanical control system, weed management was conducted through a combination of manual and mechanical operations. Herbicide spraying was performed using a 4WD tractor (240HP) equipped with a 36m sprayer, achieving a work capacity of 10 hectares per hour. The system required chemicals and diesel for 4 spraying timings, with a fuel consumption of 61.62 € and a raw material cost of €80.00 per hectare. Each spraying session took approximately 0.50 total working hours per hectare. This process, while efficient, involved higher fuel consumption and multiple passes over the field to control weeds.

Description of the "after" scenario

After the introduction of the camera-guided mechanical control system, the operation was optimized for greater precision and efficiency. Weed management was performed using the Ecorobotix spot sprayer with a 6m boom, reducing the work capacity to 4 hectares per hour. The process involved chemicals and diesel for 2 spraying timings, resulting in a fuel consumption of 30.81 € and a raw material cost of €40.00 per hectare. The system's precise application of herbicides allowed for reduced chemical use and less fuel consumption, making it a more sustainable and cost-effective solution in comparison to the previous method.

Input data and farm characteristics

The company operates a 5-hectare farm dedicated to conventional vegetable crops (fresh onions). Within this, a 15-hectare experimental area is designated for the research on the precision agriculture solution.

<i>Management Type</i>	Conventional
<i>Most important crops and animal productions</i>	Sugarbeet crop
<i>Total Farm Area (ha)</i>	5
<i>Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA, ha)</i>	5
<i>Experimental area (ha)</i>	5
<i>Experimental crop(s)</i>	Sugarbeet crop

TABLE 202: INPUT DATA AND FARM CHARACTERISTICS FROM PRECISION SPRAYING IN FIELD VEGETABLE CROPS (UK 3)

The investment analysis is based on the most common scenario, where agricultural companies already own a tractor, allowing the advanced camera-guided system to be integrated into existing machinery. This approach keeps the initial investment costs aligned with typical agricultural practices. In this case, the advanced camera-guided system, with an investment cost of €130,360 made in 2020, is expected to have a lifespan of 10 years, spreading the cost over the period. Additionally, a second tool purchase is projected for 2030 at a cost of €186,678, with a similar expected lifetime of 10 years.

<i>Investment costs (euros)</i>			
<i>Machine and Tools</i>	Annual costs	Year	Expected lifetime (n. year)
<i>Advanced Camera guided system</i>	130,360	2020	10
<i>2nd tool purchase</i>	186,678	2030	10

TABLE 203: INVESTMENT COSTS FROM PRECISION SPRAYING IN FIELD VEGETABLE CROPS (UK 3)

The operating costs for the advanced camera-guided system encompass several key factors, including fuel expenses, raw material costs, and machine maintenance. Fuel expenses decrease from €61.62 annually before the implementation of the system to €30.81 annually post-implementation, spanning from 2020 to 2040. Raw material costs follow a similar pattern, decreasing from €219.24 annually before the system's

introduction to €54.81 annually after its implementation, covering the period from 2020 to 2040. This reduction is likely due to more precise operations, leading to less waste and more efficient use of herbicides over time. Machine maintenance costs are calculated at 3% of the purchase price for both the first and second purchases. For the first purchase (2020–2030), annual maintenance costs amount to €3,911, while for the second purchase (2030–2040), the maintenance costs rise to €6,370. This increase reflects the adjustment in maintenance costs, accounting for inflation and the higher cost of servicing and replacing parts over time. Additionally, insurance costs are set at €118.40 annually, from 2020 to 2040, covering the entire operational period of the equipment. These costs contribute to the overall financial sustainability of the system, ensuring that the machinery is protected against risks and damages.

Operating costs (euros year⁻¹)

	Annual costs - Pre	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Fuel</i>	61.62	30.81	2020-2040
<i>Raw material</i>	219.24	54.81	2020-2040
<i>Machine maintenance (3% of purchase price)</i>		1 st tool purchase – 3,911 2 nd tool purchase -6,370	2020-2030 2030-2040
<i>Insurance</i>		118.40	2020-2040

TABLE 204: OPERATING COSTS FROM PRECISION SPRAYING IN FIELD VEGETABLE CROPS (UK 3)

The labour costs associated with the advanced camera-guided system encompass several key elements, including direct labour, technical support, training, and services purchased from third parties. Labour costs increase from €6.78 annually before the system's implementation to €16.94 annually post-implementation, covering the period from 2020 to 2040. This rise is primarily due to the need for additional skilled workers to operate and manage the more advanced system, as well as the increased complexity of tasks that require more time and expertise. Additionally, training costs are estimated at 22 euros per worker per year, covering the years from 2020 to 2040. This investment ensures that the workforce remains proficient in using the advanced system, adapting to new updates and practices that may arise over time. Continuous training helps minimize the risk of operational issues and ensures that the system operates efficiently throughout its lifespan. Finally, services purchased from third parties, specifically the annual rental cost for software updates and servicing, are projected at €5,925 annually from 2020 to 2040. These costs ensure that the system remains up-to-date, with necessary software updates, technical support, and maintenance services provided by external vendors. These labour costs are essential to ensure both the technological and human aspects of the system's operation are fully supported.

Labour costs (euros)

	Pre	Post	Year
<i>Labour</i>	6.78	16.94	2020-2040
<i>Technical support</i>		200	2020-2040
<i>Training</i>		22	2020-2040
<i>Services purchased from third parties (Annual rental cost for software updates/servicing)</i>		5,925	2020-2040

TABLE 205: LABOUR COSTS FROM PRECISION SPRAYING IN FIELD VEGETABLE CROPS (UK 3)

The Other costs section includes transaction costs of 221 euros in 2020 (5 hectares), representing the administrative or operational expenses associated with implementing the changes. Opportunity costs are calculated as the present value in 2020 of capital allocated to the tool purchases. The opportunity cost for the first purchase is 8,115 euros, while for the second purchase, it is 7,368 euros. These costs reflect the economic trade-offs of committing resources to the precision system instead of alternative investments.

Other costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Post	Year
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Transaction costs	221	2020
Opportunity costs (Present Value)		
1 st purchase	8,115	2020
2 nd purchase	7,368	2020

TABLE 206: OTHER COSTS FROM PRECISION SPRAYING IN FIELD VEGETABLE CROPS (UK 3)

Cost-benefit identification

Category	Name	Type	Attribute
Benefit per person or household	Improved Labour Environment	Reduction of workers' risk from exposure to phytosanitary products (public)	Qualitative
Benefit per unit of abatement	Enhanced Food quality and safety	Reduced risk of chemical residues on grapes (public)	Qualitative
Environmental benefits	Reduced erosion risks		Monetary 6,021 euros – present value
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced or zero costs for weed management	Direct cost savings by reducing the use of herbicides (private)	Monetary 3,806 euros – present value
	Reduced fuel costs	Direct cost savings by reducing the use of fuel (private)	Monetary 713 euros – present value
	*Reduced CO ₂ emissions		Monetary 626.05 euros – present value
Total (monetary) benefits			10,540 euros

TABLE 207: IDENTIFIED BENEFITS FROM PRECISION SPRAYING IN FIELD VEGETABLE CROPS (UK 3)

* We do not include the calculation of CO₂ emissions in the private analysis because they represent a cost shifted onto society and are not part of the private cost-benefit balance. However, these emissions were calculated separately to account for their broader impact, using values from the EIB Group climate bank roadmap 2021-2025. The roadmap provides the basis for the shadow cost, which represents the minimum societal cost of achieving the 1.5°C temperature target (EIB, 2020).

The adoption of the camera-guided mechanical weeding system provides several notable advantages, both qualitative and financial. From a social perspective, the system significantly improves the labour environment by reducing workers' exposure to phytosanitary products, lowering health risks, and enhancing overall safety. Moreover, it contributes to better food quality and safety by reducing the risk of chemical residues on crops, benefiting public health. On the economic front, the system generates substantial direct cost savings. The reduction in herbicide usage leads to savings of €3,806 (present value). Fuel costs are also lowered, with a present value savings of €713, and the system reduces CO₂ emissions, resulting in an environmental benefit of €626.05 (present value). Additionally, the technology helps mitigate erosion risks, which contributes €6,021 in environmental benefits. In total, the monetary benefits from the system amount to €10,540, reflecting the combined savings from reduced herbicide, fuel, and CO₂ emissions, as well as environmental gains.

Category	Cost item	Value (Euros)	Present Value (euros)
Capital costs (CAPEX)	Machines – 1 st purchase	130,360	130,360
	Machines – 2 nd purchase	186,678	126,113
Operating costs, including operations and maintenance (OPEX)	Maintenance – 1 st purchase	3,911	35,631
	Maintenance – 2 nd purchase	6,370	39,209
	Insurance	118	1,727
Labour	Labour	10	148
	Technical support	200	2,918
	Training	22	321
	Third-party services	5,925	86,448
Other costs	Transaction costs		221

Opportunity costs - 1 st purchase	8,115
Opportunity costs - 2 nd purchase	7,368
Total Costs	526,295

TABLE 208: IDENTIFIED COSTS FROM PRECISION SPRAYING IN FIELD VEGETABLE CROPS (UK 3)

Economic analysis

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR (%)
20	-103,151	0.02	-100

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR
20	-104,441	0.01	-100

TABLE 209: ECONOMIC ANALYSIS FROM PRECISION SPRAYING IN FIELD VEGETABLE CROPS (UK 3)

In the first scenario, characterized by no risk of project failure and high adoption, the economic indicators paint a picture of considerable financial strain. The NPV of the project is -103,151 euros per hectare, which, while slightly better than in the second scenario, remains substantially negative. The BCR is 0.02, suggesting that the project returns only 2 cents for every euro spent, pointing to a lack of financial viability. The MIRR stands at -100%, indicating that the project's returns do not meet the investment's costs even under the most favourable conditions. This analysis underscores the economic challenges the project faces, even when adoption rates are high, and the risk of failure is deemed negligible. It becomes clear that one of the critical limitations in this case is the minimal monetized benefits, as evidenced through the interviews, which fails to provide a robust basis for economic sustainability.

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

FIGURE 17: GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF NET AND CUMULATIVE BENEFITS UNDER TWO SCENARIOS: NO RISK OF FAILURE WITH HIGH ADOPTION (TOP) AND LOW RISK OF FAILURE WITH LOW ADOPTION (BOTTOM)

In the graphical analysis, the first scenario shows intermittent positive returns, likely during peak production, but these are quickly negated by significant losses, reflecting substantial reinvestment or operational costs. The cumulative net benefits graph depicts a consistent downward trend, underscoring the project's struggle to achieve lasting financial stability. The second scenario, marked by low risk of project failure and low adoption, presents a dire financial picture with consistently negative net benefits across the 20-year period, indicating an inability to cover operational costs. The cumulative net benefits continue to decline, highlighting the profound financial impact of insufficient adoption. This scenario emphasizes the crucial need for strategies to boost adoption and distribute costs more effectively, given the critical role of sufficiently monetized and tangible benefits in securing economic sustainability.

Social analysis

 Traffic light 62.50%	<p>The traffic light score for the social impact of targeted precision spraying in field vegetable crops stands at 62.50%. This indicates a moderate overall social impact, reflecting that the technology offers notable improvements in labour conditions and agricultural management flexibility. However, substantial barriers, primarily the significant initial investment and operational costs, curtail broader social benefits and accessibility, especially for smaller farms. This moderate score points to existing benefits but highlights the need for additional financial support or policy interventions to extend these benefits more widely.</p>
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Social impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
<i>The practice provides more stable income from year to year than alternatives</i>	0.58
<i>The current practice provides more flexibility for the agricultural management</i>	0.44
<i>New job opportunities in the rural area</i>	0.20
<i>Improvement of working conditions for the farm employers</i>	0.70
<i>Increased food safety</i>	0.50
<i>More job opportunities for women</i>	0.00
<i>Improving farmers' education and skills</i>	0.75
<i>Improved conditions for vulnerable groups</i>	0.00
<i>Improved aesthetics of the landscape and conservation of the cultural value</i>	0.60
<i>Improved social reputation of the farm</i>	0.60

TABLE 210: SOCIAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM PRECISION SPRAYING IN FIELD VEGETABLE CROPS (UK 3)

The social impact perceptions gathered from the questionnaire highlight significant positive effects in key areas such as improving farmers' education and skills, which scored 0.75, and enhancing working conditions, scoring 0.70. These findings suggest that targeted precision spraying is viewed favorably for its role in boosting operational expertise and fostering better labour environments. This perception indicates that the technology not only improves technical operations but also contributes meaningfully to the skill development and overall well-being of farm workers. Nonetheless, gaps are evident in creating job opportunities for women and improving conditions for vulnerable groups, both scoring zero, indicating no perceived benefits in these areas. This disparity suggests that while the technology significantly enhances certain operational aspects, its reach and impact on broader social inclusivity and support for vulnerable demographics are limited. This finding aligns with parts of the literature such as Jacquet et al. (2021), which reports a medium-to-high impact on labour environments in the short term. However, it contrasts with broader expectations highlighted in literature like Tamirat et al. (2023) and Liu et al. (2023), which suggest potential reductions in workload and enhancements in food safety respectively. These areas show only moderate recognition in practical applications, pointing to a divergence between theoretical benefits and actual perceived impacts. This analysis suggests a need for strategies that expand beyond operational improvements to enhance the social inclusivity and reputation impacts of targeted precision spraying in field vegetable crops, fully realizing its potential for broader societal benefits.

Social direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Improved labour environment	Jacquet et al., (2021)	Medium-to-high	Short run	Non-monetary

Social indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Reduced workload	Tamirat et al. (2023)	Low-to-medium	Short run	Non-monetary
Enhanced food safety	Liu et al. (2023); Jacquet et al., (2021)	Low	Medium-to-long run	Non-monetary

TABLE 211: SOCIAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM PRECISION SPRAYING IN FIELD VEGETABLE CROPS (UK 3)

Environmental analysis

 Traffic light 59.12%	<p>The environmental traffic light score for targeted precision spraying in field vegetable crops stands at 59.12%. This indicates a moderate level of environmental benefit from the technology. While it successfully reduces chemical use and supports ecological sustainability, concerns about energy consumption have impacted the overall score negatively. Our findings show that despite the technology's ability to lower fuel consumption, perceived increases in other forms of energy use might contribute to less favourable evaluations of its environmental efficiency, suggesting a gap between actual performance and broader environmental perceptions.</p>
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Env. impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
Contribute to reduce Direct greenhouse gas emissions	0.72
Contribute to reduce external inputs	0.80
Limit water consumption	0.72
Contribute to reduce waste	0.60
Has a positive impact on biodiversity	0.92
Has a positive impact on soil erosion	0.79
Has a positive impact on carbon footprint	0.00
Increase the rate of soil organic matter mineralisation	0.42
Increase soil compaction	0.42

TABLE 212: ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM PRECISION SPRAYING IN FIELD VEGETABLE CROPS (UK 3)

The environmental impact perceptions from the questionnaire demonstrate a variety of outcomes, some of which align with the literature while others diverge. For instance, the high score for reduced external inputs at 0.80 aligns with documented benefits in reducing harmful chemical usage as highlighted by Kup, F., & Saglam, R. (2014), affirming the technology's capacity to minimize ecological footprint. Similarly, the technology's positive impact on biodiversity, scoring 0.92, showcases its effectiveness in promoting ecological diversity and health. These results are supported by general trends in the literature which emphasize the ecological benefits of reducing chemical inputs.

Conversely, the analysis reveals discrepancies particularly in the context of energy use. The technology was perceived not to contribute to reducing the carbon footprint, which received a surprising score of 0.00. This conflicts with our internal data, which indicates a reduction in fuel consumption, a primary component of direct greenhouse gas emissions. Such divergence suggests potential misinterpretations in the questionnaire's design or respondents' understanding, which may fail to capture the full spectrum of the technology's energy efficiency. Moreover, concerns cited by Pergher, G., Gubiani, R., & Mainardis, M. (2020) about an increase in energy demand could be reflecting an initial misunderstanding of the

technology's operation, which although energy-intensive at the outset, results in significant energy savings over time.

This difference between our findings and literature or public perception highlights the need for further education and communication regarding the operational benefits and real-time energy efficiencies achieved by the technology. It also underscores the importance of aligning evaluation frameworks more closely with actual performance data to ensure that environmental benefits are fully recognized and accurately represented.

Env. direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Reduced use of harmful chemicals	Kup, F., & Saglam, R. (2014)	High	Short to Long-run	Quantitative

Env. indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Land Conservation (reduced soil erosion, off-site effects)	Liu et al. (2023); Jacquet et al. (2021)	Controversial	Long-run	Qualitative
Increase energy demand	Pergher, G., Gubiani, R., & Mainardis, M. (2020)	Medium to high	Short-run	Quantitative

TABLE 213: ENVIRONMENTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM PRECISION SPRAYING IN FIELD VEGETABLE CROPS (UK 3)

Sensitivity analysis (only first scenario)

The sensitivity analysis for the UK 3 scenario, focusing on targeted precision spraying in field vegetable crops, reveals a uniformly negative financial outlook. The NPV values range from a low of -€112,997 per hectare to a high of -€58,660 per hectare, demonstrating significant financial burdens associated with this technology. With a mean NPV of -€86,168 per hectare and a median of -€85,783 per hectare, the financial metrics consistently highlight the challenges to economic viability. The zero percent probability of achieving an NPV above zero starkly emphasizes the unlikely financial return under the existing cost and projection structures.

Furthermore, the BCR analysis strengthens these conclusions, showing a narrow range from a minimum of 0.01 to a maximum of only 0.04. The default and average BCR values sit at about 0.02, reinforcing the narrative that the benefits from adopting this technology do not come close to covering its substantial costs. Notably, there is no chance of achieving a BCR greater than 1, and the possibility of reaching the target BCR of 2 is equally nonexistent, confirming the economic challenges without significant alterations or financial aids.

Monte Carlo simulations and sensitivity to varying discount rates, from 2% to 6%, further underscore a grim picture. No matter the discount rate applied, the NPV remains deeply negative, indicating that the varying benefits do not compensate for the overwhelming costs, leading to BCRs that consistently demonstrate inadequate economic returns. The distribution results within the Monte Carlo analysis corroborate this, showing a concentration of financial outcomes at the lower end, validating the ongoing financial losses connected with this initiative.

In conclusion, without substantial external financial support such as subsidies or major cost-sharing measures, coupled with significant improvements in operational efficiencies, the adoption of targeted precision spraying in field vegetable crops is economically unfeasible. This sensitivity analysis necessitates a thorough reassessment of the operational efficiencies and the economic frameworks supporting the adoption of this technology, urging a strategic revision to achieve any potential economic viability.

Net Present Value (NPV)	Tot. Euros	Euros ha ⁻¹
Minimum	-564,989	-112,997
Maximum	-293,304	-58,660

Default case	-428,039	-85,607
Mean	-430,843	-86,168
Median	-428,918	-85,783
Probability that NPV > 0		0.00
Distribution (euros)		Probability
Less than -565K		0.00
-565K to -511K		0.26
-511K to -456K		0.00
-456K to -402K		0.49
-402K to -348K		0.00
-348K to -293K		0.25
	Total	1.00
Benefit: Cost Ratio (BCR)		Unconstrained version
Minimum		0.01
Maximum		0.04
Default case		0.02
Mean		0.02
Median		0.02
Probability that BCR > 1		0.00
Target BCR		2
Probability BCR > Target		0.00
Distribution		Probability
Less than 0.01		0.00
0.01 to 0.01		0.14
0.01 to 0.02		0.39
0.02 to 0.03		0.30
0.03 to 0.03		0.12
0.03 to 0.04		0.06
	Total	1.00

TABLE 214: BCA ROBUSTNESS (MONTE CARLO ANALYSIS BASED ON 1000 RANDOM SIMULATIONS) - PRECISION SPRAYING IN FIELD VEGETABLE CROPS (UK 3)

Sensitivity to discount rate

	Low discount rate	Default discount rate	High discount rate
Project organisation	2%	4%	6%
Benefits (present value)	13,322	10,540	8,472
Costs (present value)	499,303	438,580	390,992
Net Present Value (NPV)	-485,980	-428,039	-382,520
Benefit: Cost Ratio (unconstrained budget)	0.03	0.02	0.02

TABLE 215: SENSITIVITY TO DISCOUNT RATE - PRECISION SPRAYING IN FIELD VEGETABLE CROPS (UK 3)

4.2.4.5 GPS and camera guided mechanical weeding (Sweden 1)

Main objective

The company's objective in implementing mechanical weeding integrated with precision agriculture is to improve operational efficiency and reduce labour costs by utilizing advanced equipment that optimizes weed control with a lower environmental impact.

Description of the “before” scenario

Before the introduction of advanced technologies, fertilization was performed using a Bogballe spreader with a work capacity of 10 hectares per hour, applying 150 kg of nitrogen per hectare and consuming 1 liter of fuel per hectare. Seeding was carried out with an Överum Combiseeder, achieving a work rate of only 2.5 hectares per hour. Spraying involved the Amazone 2800-liter sprayer with a 24-meter width, reaching a capacity of 5 hectares per hour when accounting for refilling and documentation, using 1.5 liters of fuel per hectare for herbicide and glyphosate applications, with quantities varying by crop. Plowing utilized a Kverneland 4-furrow plow, covering just 1.1 hectares per hour, making soil preparation a slow process. Harrowing was done with a Väderstad harrow, working at 4 hectares per hour, while harvesting was performed using a Lexion combine with a 6-meter cutting width, achieving a capacity of 2.5 hectares per hour, contributing to the overall slow pace and high resource consumption of the entire operation.

Description of the “after” scenario

After the adoption of advanced agricultural technologies and precision equipment, operations became more efficient, but with increased overall fuel and labour costs. Weed management after harvest was carried out using the Väderstad Swift (5.6 meters wide), achieving 4 hectares per hour while controlling couch grass with 7.5 liters per hectare. In growing crops, the Einböck Aerostar Classic (12 meters wide) covered 8 hectares per hour, consuming only 1.4 liters per hectare, and was complemented by the Garford Inter-row cultivator with GPS and cameras, operating at 2.5 hectares per hour with 4 liters per hectare. Precision agriculture, especially for weed control and harvesting, has significantly reduced the amount of inputs needed, which have become the main advantage of the new system. Herbicides were eliminated completely, leading to the company's acquisition of the EKO label for its products. Seeding with the Väderstad Spirit achieved 3 hectares per hour while using 8.3 liters per hectare, enabling accurate adjustment for different crops and reducing seed waste. Plowing remained consistent with the Kverneland 4-furrow plow at 1.1 hectares per hour, while harrowing was performed at 4 hectares per hour with enhanced field preparation precision. Harvesting efficiency improved with the Lexion combine (7.7 meters wide), increasing capacity to 3.3 hectares per hour but consuming 10.6 liters per hectare. Pasture plastering with the Fuier 8-meter machine worked at 4 hectares per hour, using 15 liters of fuel across three repetitions, and stringing operations with the Honeybee machine (6.3 meters wide) operated at 2.5 hectares per hour with 5.2 liters per hectare. Despite higher fuel and labour costs, the reduction in raw material usage, such as herbicides, seeds, and fertilizers, represented the most significant advantage, enhancing sustainability and lowering input dependency.

Input data and farm characteristics

The farm operates on a total area of 550 hectares with partial organic management (90% of the area). The utilized agricultural area (UAA) is 500 hectares, which is entirely designated as the experimental area. The experimentation focuses on various crops, including winter rape seeds, winter wheat, oats, barley, meadow fescue seeds, faba beans, peas, and flax for oil.

Management Type

Organic

Most important crops and animal productions

Arable crops, rape seeds, cereals, faba beans, grass seeds

Total Farm Area (ha)

550

Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA, ha)

500

Experimental area (ha)

500

TABLE 216: INPUT DATA AND FARM CHARACTERISTICS FROM GPS AND CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (SWEDEN 1)

The investment analysis is based on the scenario where the company already owns several machines, as described in the "before" scenario, and considers investments only for the equipment purchased specifically for the transition to the new practice. The initial purchase costs for the equipment are as follows: drying floor for grass seeds (€80,000), between-row hoe (Garford 6 m) (€80,000), miscellaneous combine equipment for ecological circumstances (e.g., cutter bar) (€100,000), pick-up truck for grass seeds (€30,000), pasture plaster (only for grass seeds) (€52,000), stringer (only for grass seeds) (€26,000). For simplification purposes, all machines are assumed to have been purchased in 2019, with an estimated lifetime of 7 years. The total value of the machines is €288,000, with a residual value estimated at 15% per year of the purchase price. Over a 20-year period, the company undergoes three repurchases, replacing machines every 7 years. The first set of machines is sold for a residual value of €92,326.20 after 7 years. The second set of machines is purchased at a future value of €405,244.92, reflecting a 5% annual inflation rate. After deducting the resale value of the first set, the net cost of the second set is €312,918.72. Similarly, the second set is resold at a value of €129,912.24 after 7 years, and the third set of machines is acquired at a future value of €570,220.30, resulting in a net cost of €440,308.06 after deducting the resale value of the second set. This approach ensures the analysis captures both the depreciation and inflation-adjusted costs over time. This decision reflects a realistic estimate of the actual investment required, ensuring that the analysis does not underestimate the costs faced by agricultural businesses.

Investment costs (euros)

Machine and Tools	Annual costs	Year	Expected lifetime (n. year)
<i>1st Machines purchase</i>	288,000	2019	7
<i>2nd Machines purchase</i>	312,918	2026	7
<i>3rd Machines purchase</i>	440,308	2033	7
Fixed installations			
<i>Drying floor for drying of grass seeds</i>	80,000	2019	20

TABLE 217: INVESTMENT COSTS FROM GPS AND CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (SWEDEN 1)

The operating costs for the farm reflect several critical elements, including adjustments in maintenance costs due to changes in workflow post-implementation. Maintenance costs for machines and tools are calculated at specific rates over their lifespans. From 2019 to 2026, maintenance costs amount to €8,640 per year. Between 2026 and 2033, these costs increase to €12,157.35 annually, and from 2033 to 2039, maintenance costs rise further to €17,106.61 annually. These figures account for the evolving needs of the equipment over time, as well as the impact of wear, technological improvements, and operational efficiency adjustments. In addition to maintenance costs, operational expenses have changed significantly following the introduction of the new practice. Fuel costs have increased by €2,000 annually, while labour costs have risen by €104,348 per year. Other recurring costs include raw materials (€28,185 annually), the rental of specialized machinery such as the meadow fescue cutter (€4,348 annually), insurance (€4,300 annually), and administration fees (€5,217 annually). These increases reflect the additional expenditures required to sustain the new farming practices and ensure the long-term efficiency and sustainability of operations.

Operating costs (euros year⁻¹)

	Annual costs - Pre	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Machine maintenance (3% of purchase price)</i>		1 st purchase – 8,640	2019-2026
		2 nd purchase – 12,157.35	2026-2033
		3 rd purchase – 17,106.61	2033-2039
		Tot – 37,903.96	
<i>Fuel</i>	18,500	20,500	2019-2039
<i>Raw material</i>	Mineral fertilizers - 87,000.00	Biofertilizers – 130,434.78	2019-2039
	Chemicals - 43,500.00	Seeds - 60,850.00	

	Seeds - 32,600.00		
	Tot – 163,100.00	Tot – 191,248.78	
<i>Rental of machinery: Meadow fescue cutter</i>		4,348	2019-2039
<i>Insurance</i>		4,300	2019-2039

TABLE 218: OPERATING COSTS FROM GPS AND CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (SWEDEN 1)

The project incurs annual costs across several categories from 2019 to 2039. Labour costs amount to 156,522 euros per year, representing the most significant expenditure due to the increased demand for workforce following the adoption of the new practices. Administration fees are 5,217 euros annually, while the KIWA ECO certification adds 1,739 euros each year. Technical support costs remain consistent at 200 euros per year, and training expenses are 22 euros per worker annually. Overall, these factors have led to a considerable increase in labour costs, 104,348 euros, reflecting the project's enhanced operational complexity and focus on sustainability.

Labour costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Labour</i>	156,522	2019-2039
<i>Administration fees</i>	5,217	2019-2039
<i>KIWA ECO certification</i>	1,739	2019-2039
<i>Technical support</i>	200	2019-2039
<i>Training</i>	22	2019-2039

TABLE 219: LABOUR COSTS FROM GPS AND CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (SWEDEN 1)

The Other costs section includes transaction costs of 4,020 euros in 2019 (500 hectares), representing the administrative or operational expenses associated with implementing the changes. Opportunity costs are calculated as the present value in 2019 of capital allocated to the tool purchases. The opportunity cost for the first purchase is 29,042 euros, while for the second purchase, it is 26,367 euros.

Other costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Transaction costs</i>	20,100	2019
<i>Opportunity costs (Present Value)</i>	50,309.35	2019
<i>1st purchase machines</i>	41,538.84	2019
<i>2nd purchase machines</i>		
<i>3rd purchase machines</i>	44,416.68	2019
<i>Fixed installation</i>	80,000	2019

TABLE 220: OTHER COSTS FROM GPS AND CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (SWEDEN 1)

Cost-benefit identification

Category	Name	Type	Attribute
Benefit per person or household	Improved Labour Environment	Reduction of workers' risk from exposure to phytosanitary products (public)	Qualitative
Benefit per user-specified unit	Enhanced Field Preparation and Seeding Precision	Improved accuracy in seeding and soil preparation promotes better crop establishment	Qualitative
Benefit per unit of abatement	Enhanced Food quality and safety	Reduced risk of chemical residues on crops (public)	Qualitative
	Minimized Dependency on Chemical Inputs	Reduced reliance on herbicides and fertilizers enhances sustainability	Qualitative
Benefit per year in aggregate	Increased revenue	Higher sales price, EKO	Monetary 3,007,358 euros – present value

	<i>label, Stipulation of new supply chain contracts and Increased produce quality</i>	
<i>ECO subsidies</i>	<i>Subsidies</i>	Monetary 821,743 euros – present value
Total (monetary) benefits		3,899,101 euros

TABLE 221: IDENTIFIED BENEFITS FROM GPS AND CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (SWEDEN 1)

The transition to precision agriculture in the Swedish reality analyzed has significant benefits, both qualitative and financial, related to the introduction of advanced mechanical weeding. Environmentally and agronomically, reduced dependence on herbicides and fertilizers improves overall sustainability, while more accurate soil preparation and precise seeding promote better crop yields. Economically, the adoption of these technologies has resulted in an increase in revenues with a present value of 3,007,358 euros, resulting from an increase in the sales price, obtaining the EKO brand, and new supply contracts. In addition, ECO subsidies with a present value of 821,743 euros were obtained. In total, total monetary benefits amounted to 3,899,101 euros.

<i>Category</i>	<i>Cost item</i>	<i>Value (Euros)</i>	<i>Present Value (euros)</i>
<i>Capital costs (CAPEX)</i>	<i>Machines</i>		
	<i>1st purchase</i>	288,000	288,000
	<i>2nd purchase</i>	312,919	237,793
	<i>3rd purchase</i>	440,308	254,267
	<i>Fixed installations</i>		
	<i>Drying floor for drying of grass seeds</i>	80,000	80,000
<i>Operating costs, including operations and maintenance (OPEX)</i>	<i>Maintenance</i>		
	<i>1st purchase</i>	8,640	60,498
	<i>2nd purchase</i>	12,157	64,689
	<i>3rd purchase</i>	17,107	61,664
	<i>Fuel</i>	2,000	29,181
	<i>Raw material</i>	28,184.78	411,225
	<i>Rental of machinery</i>	4,348	63,436
<i>Labour</i>	<i>Labour</i>	104,348	1,522,471
	<i>Administration fees</i>	5,217	76,124
	<i>Technical support</i>	200	2,918
	<i>Training year</i>	22	321
<i>Other costs</i>	<i>Transaction costs</i>		20,100
	<i>Eco Certification</i>	1,739	25,374
	<i>Insurance</i>		62,738
	<i>Opportunity costs</i>		
	<i>Fixed installation</i>	4,300	29,431.89
	<i>1st purchase machines</i>		50,309.35
	<i>2nd purchase machines</i>		41,538.84
<i>3rd purchase machines</i>		44,416.68	
	<i>CO₂*</i>		16,113.30
Total Costs			3,426,296

TABLE 222: IDENTIFIED COSTS FROM GPS AND CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (SWEDEN 1)

* We do not include the calculation of CO₂ emissions in the private analysis because they represent a cost shifted onto society and are not part of the private cost-benefit balance. However, these emissions were calculated separately to account for their broader impact, using values from the EIB Group climate bank roadmap 2021-2025. The roadmap provides the basis for the shadow cost, which represents the minimum societal cost of achieving the 1.5°C temperature target (EIB, 2020).

Economic analysis

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR (%)
20	945	1.14	4.5

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR
20	-3,827.29	0.44	-8.8

TABLE 223: ECONOMIC ANALYSIS FROM GPS AND CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (SWEDEN 1)

In the first scenario of the project, where there is a presumption of no risk of project failure and high adoption, the economic results indicate a degree of financial viability. The NPV per hectare stands at 945 euros, suggesting a modest but positive return on investment. The BCR at 1.14 indicates that for every euro invested, the project yields a return of 1.14 euros, hinting at a financially sustainable venture, albeit with slim margins. The MIRR at 4.5% reinforces this view, suggesting a reasonable rate of return that could justify the initial and ongoing investments under these ideal conditions.

Conversely, the second scenario reflects a much less optimistic financial outlook due to low risk of project failure coupled with low levels of adoption. Here, the NPV dramatically drops to -3,827.29 euros per hectare, showing a significant loss per hectare, which highlights the project's financial instability in less favourable conditions. The BCR at 0.44 means the project only returns 44 cents for every euro invested, far below the break-even point. Furthermore, the negative MIRR of -8.8% indicates that the project fails to meet the basic thresholds for investment viability, suggesting that without significant improvements in adoption rates, the project is not financially sustainable.

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

FIGURE 18: GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF NET AND CUMULATIVE BENEFITS UNDER TWO SCENARIOS: NO RISK OF FAILURE WITH HIGH ADOPTION (TOP) AND LOW RISK OF FAILURE WITH LOW ADOPTION (BOTTOM)

The graphical representation of financial outcomes starkly illustrates the contrasting scenarios. In the high adoption scenario, the net benefits graph shows consistent positive returns across most years, signifying that the project can generate sufficient income to support reinvestment and ongoing operational needs. This is further supported by the cumulative net benefits graph, which displays a steady upward trajectory, signaling improving financial stability as the project progresses. In contrast, the low adoption scenario

presents a challenging picture. The net benefits graph reveals a pattern of instability with frequent fluctuations, reflecting a struggling financial performance that fails to consistently recover investment costs. The cumulative net benefits graph further highlights this challenge, showing slow and erratic growth, which underlines the difficulties in achieving financial sustainability when adoption rates are low. This scenario underscores the critical importance of broadening adoption to improve financial outcomes and effectively distribute the costs associated with the project.

Social analysis

 Traffic light 53.52%	<p>The Sweden 1 scenario for the adoption of precision mechanical weeding technology reflects a moderate overall social impact, scoring 53.52% in the traffic light evaluation. This score suggests that while the technology has potential benefits, particularly in improving labour conditions, its broader acceptance and social impact are significantly restrained by high initial costs and ongoing operational expenses. Such financial barriers imply that without additional support through policy initiatives or financial subsidies, the potential positive impacts of the technology might not fully materialize, especially for smaller farms which may struggle with the upfront investment.</p>
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Social impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
<i>The practice provides more stable income from year to year than alternatives</i>	0.47
<i>The current practice provides more flexibility for the agricultural management</i>	0.42
<i>New job opportunities in the rural area</i>	0.38
<i>Improvement of working conditions for the farm employers</i>	0.48
<i>Increased food safety</i>	0.25
<i>More job opportunities for women</i>	0.25
<i>Improving farmers' education and skills</i>	0.50
<i>Improved conditions for vulnerable groups</i>	0.30
<i>Improved aesthetics of the landscape and conservation of the cultural value</i>	0.40
<i>Improved social reputation of the farm</i>	0.30

TABLE 224: SOCIAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM GPS AND CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (SWEDEN 1)

The questionnaire responses reflect diverse perceptions: it moderately improves stable income (0.47) and agricultural management flexibility (0.42), while only marginally enhancing new job opportunities (0.38) and food safety (0.25). The technology scores higher in improving working conditions (0.48) and farmer education (0.50), indicating some recognition of its practical benefits. However, the impact on more transformative aspects like job opportunities for women (0.25), conditions for vulnerable groups (0.30), and social reputation (0.30) are perceived as minimal. This pattern suggests that while operational efficiencies are acknowledged, the broader social benefits, particularly those related to inclusivity and public perception, remain largely unrealized. This gap highlights the need for strategies that not only promote direct benefits but also enhance broader community and public health impacts, thus improving the overall social acceptance and impact of the technology.

Social direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Improved labour environment	Jacquet et al., (2021)	Medium-to-high	Short run	Non-monetary

Social indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Reduced workload	Tamirat et al. (2023)	Low-to-medium	Short run	Non-monetary

Enhanced food safety	Liu et al. (2023); Jacquet et al., (2021)	Low	Medium-to- long run	Non-monetary
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TABLE 225: SOCIAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM GPS AND CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (SWEDEN 1)

Environmental analysis

 Traffic light 50.63%	<p>In the environmental evaluation of precision mechanical weeding technology under Sweden 1, a traffic light score of 50.63% reveals a modest overall impact, highlighting a balance between notable benefits and significant challenges. While the technology supports environmental objectives such as water conservation and reduced soil erosion, it struggles with issues like greenhouse gas emissions and reliance on external inputs. This moderate score underscores a critical need for enhancements in technology application to better harness its potential environmental benefits.</p>
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Env. impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
Contribute to reduce Direct greenhouse gas emissions	0.40
Contribute to reduce external inputs	0.00
Limit water consumption	0.33
Contribute to reduce waste	0.00
Has a positive impact on biodiversity	0.70
Has a positive impact on soil erosion	0.70
Has a positive impact on carbon footprint	0.00
Increase the rate of soil organic matter mineralisation	0.70
Increase soil compaction	0.70

TABLE 226: ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM GPS AND CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (SWEDEN 1)

The detailed responses from the questionnaire shed light on varied environmental perceptions among users. Scores indicate a strong recognition of the technology's positive impacts on biodiversity and soil health, with both areas scoring a notable 0.70. This appreciation likely reflects visible improvements in soil quality and local biodiversity due to reduced chemical intrusion and better soil management practices. In stark contrast, the technology scores dismally at reducing external inputs and improving the carbon footprint, both receiving a score of 0.00. These areas, crucial for broader environmental sustainability, indicate a significant perception gap. Users seem to disconnect the operational efficiencies of the technology, such as fuel savings, from broader environmental impacts like reduced carbon emissions. This could be due to a lack of understanding or visibility of how decreased fuel usage translates into lower greenhouse gas emissions.

Moreover, the technology is perceived to exacerbate issues like soil compaction, with a high score of 0.70, suggesting concerns over potential negative mechanical impacts on soil structure. This perception might stem from the physical nature of weeding machinery, which can compact soil if not managed correctly, possibly overshadowing its other soil health benefits.

Addressing these perception gaps requires strategic communication and education efforts to link operational efficiencies with environmental benefits more clearly. Enhancing user understanding of how reduced fuel consumption and chemical inputs contribute to broader environmental goals could help in gaining fuller acceptance and utilization of the technology. Additionally, improving the technology to minimize negative impacts like soil compaction and better demonstrating its benefits in reducing carbon emissions could significantly enhance its perceived and actual environmental performance.

Env. direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
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Reduced use of harmful chemicals	Kup, F., & Saglam, R. (2014)	High	Short to Long-run	Quantitative
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Env. indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Land Conservation (reduced soil erosion, off-site effects)	Liu et al. (2023); Jacquet et al. (2021)	Controversial	Long-run	Qualitative
Increase energy demand	Pergher, G., Gubiani, R., & Mainardis, M. (2020)	Medium to high	Short-run	Quantitative

TABLE 227: ENVIRONMENTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM GPS AND CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (SWEDEN 1)

Sensitivity analysis (only first scenario)

The sensitivity analysis conducted for the Sweden 1 scenario illustrates a broad range of outcomes for the adoption of precision mechanical weeding technology, marked by a considerable spread in financial results. The NPV per hectare varies significantly, with a minimum of -5,087.77 euros and a maximum of 5,340.56 euros, showcasing the volatility and uncertainty inherent in this agricultural technology investment. The default case NPV is 945.21 euros per hectare, with the mean slightly lower at 436.63 euros, indicating moderate profitability under average conditions. The median NPV of 661.64 euros further points to a generally positive financial outcome, with a probability of achieving a positive NPV at 56%. This indicates that more than half of the potential outcomes are profitable, albeit with a significant risk of financial underperformance.

BCR analysis in this scenario also demonstrates variability, with values ranging from a low of 0.43 to a high of 2.11, and a default BCR of 1.14. This suggests that on average, for every euro spent, the project returns slightly more than one euro, providing a narrow financial gain. The mean and median BCRs sit at 1.12 and 1.08, respectively, reinforcing the project's precarious financial balance. The probability that the BCR exceeds 1 is 59%, indicating a modest likelihood of achieving a basic financial return. However, the probability that the BCR surpasses the more ambitious target of 2 is only 4%, highlighting the significant challenges to achieving robust financial success under this project's parameters.

Overall, these results underscore the sensitivity of the project's financial viability to various factors, including market conditions, cost fluctuations, and technological performance. While the technology has the potential to provide financial benefits, the significant risks highlighted by the broad range of NPV and BCR outcomes suggest a cautious approach. Investors and stakeholders should consider both the potential for high returns and the substantial likelihood of financial challenges, with a focus on strategies that might mitigate these risks and enhance the project's overall financial robustness.

Net Present Value (NPV)	Tot. Euros	Euros ha ⁻¹
Minimum	-2,543,88	-5087.77
Maximum	2,670,28	5340.56
Default case	472,60	945.21
Mean	187,14	436.63
Median	226,08	661.64
Probability that NPV > 0		0.56
Distribution (euros)	Probability	
Less than -2.5M	0.00	
-2.5M to -1.5M	0.08	
-1.5M to -0.5M	0.20	
-0.5M to 0.6M	0.38	

0.6M to 1.6M	0.23
1.6M to 2.7M	0.11
Total	1.00
Benefit: Cost Ratio (BCR)	Unconstrained version
Minimum	0.43
Maximum	2.11
Default case	1.14
Mean	1.12
Median	1.08
Probability that BCR > 1	0.59
Target BCR	2
Probability BCR > Target	0.04
Distribution	Probability
Less than 0.43	0.00
0.43 to 0.77	0.15
0.77 to 1.10	0.37
1.10 to 1.44	0.32
1.44 to 1.78	0.12
1.78 to 2.11	0.05
Total	1.00

TABLE 228: BCA ROBUSTNESS (MONTE CARLO ANALYSIS BASED ON 1000 RANDOM SIMULATIONS) - GPS AND CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (SWEDEN 1)

Sensitivity to discount rate

	Low discount rate	Default discount rate	High discount rate
Project organisation	2%	4%	6%
Benefits (present value)	4,799,95	3,899,10	3,222,74
Costs (present value)	3,998,08	3,426,49	2,986,48
Net Present Value (NPV)	801,87	472,60	236,25
Benefit: Cost Ratio (unconstrained budget)	1.20	1.14	1.08

TABLE 229: SENSITIVITY TO DISCOUNT RATE - GPS AND CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (SWEDEN 1)

4.2.4.6 GPS and camera guided mechanical weeding (Sweden 3)

Main objective

The company's objective in implementing mechanical weeding integrated with precision agriculture is to improve operational efficiency and reduce labour costs by utilizing advanced equipment that optimizes weed control with a lower environmental impact.

Description of the "Before" Scenario

Before the introduction of advanced technologies, agricultural operations were less efficient and consumed more resources. Fertilization was performed using a Rauch Axis H30 spreader, covering 20 hectares per hour with a working width of 24 meters. Seeding and fertilization were handled by the Väderstad Rapid 400C, achieving a work rate of 3 hectares per hour with traditional seed and fertilizer application methods. Weed control involved the Amazone UX 201 sprayer, which covered 14 hectares per hour with a 24-meter working width, providing efficient but conventional herbicide application. Plowing was performed with a Kverneland 150 four-furrow plow, with a slow work rate of 0.8 hectares per hour, making soil preparation time-consuming. Harrowing involved two different machines: the Väderstad NZE (6 meters wide) with a capacity of 5 hectares per hour, and the Kongskilde Delta (3 meters wide) at 2 hectares per hour. Harvesting was managed by a Claas Tucano 430 combine harvester with a 6-meter cutting width, operating at a capacity of 1-2 hectares per hour. Overall, these operations were characterized by high resource consumption and long processing times, resulting in reduced productivity.

Description of the "After" Scenario

Following the adoption of advanced precision farming technologies, operational efficiency improved significantly. A key innovation was the implementation of DAT EcoPatch, a precision spraying solution developed by Dimensions Agri Technologies (DAT). This system integrates deep learning algorithms to distinguish between crops and weeds in real time, ensuring herbicides are applied only where necessary. This targeted approach led to a reduction in herbicide use; herbicide expenditures dropped from 7,710 euros to 6,737 euros. Despite expectations of increased crop yields due to better weed management, data provided by respondents showed no significant changes in average production. These results may be influenced by external factors or data inaccuracy. Therefore, a conservative approach was taken, excluding any yield increases from the analysis and focusing only on cost savings and efficiency improvements in weed control. In detail, the integration of DAT EcoPatch with existing equipment, including the Amazone UX 201 sprayer, improved spraying capacity by 30%, reaching 18.7 hectares per hour while maintaining the 24-meter working width. Equipped with advanced sensors and high-performance cameras, the system operates effectively in diverse environmental conditions. Additionally, real-time monitoring allows farmers to track results via mobile devices, offering greater control and oversight during field operations.

Other crop operations and machines already on the farm have not changed. Thus, the main contribution of the technology under analysis relates to weed management, which has seen a significant reduction in herbicides needed.

Input data and farm characteristics

The farm operates on a total area of 99 hectares with conventional management. The utilized agricultural area (UAA) is 99 hectares, which is entirely designated as the experimental area. The experimentation focuses on various crops, including wheat, oats, and barley.

Management Type

Organic

Most important crops and animal productions

Wheat, oats, and barley

Total Farm Area (ha)

99

Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA, ha)

99

Experimental area (ha)

99

TABLE 230: INPUT DATA AND FARM CHARACTERISTICS FROM GPS AND CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (SWEDEN 3)

The investment analysis focuses on a scenario where the company retains its existing machinery, as described in the "before" scenario, and only considers the cost of the newly acquired DAT EcoPatch system as part of the transition to the new practice.

The DAT EcoPatch system was purchased in 2022 (60,000 €) with an expected lifespan of 7 years, following a depreciation model where the residual value is calculated at 15% per year of the initial purchase price. Over a 20-year period, the system will be replaced three times, with each replacement occurring at the end of a seven-year cycle. After the first seven years, the system is sold at its residual value, while the second and third purchases factor in a 5% annual inflation rate to account for future cost increases. The DAT EcoPatch system was purchased in 2022 for €60,000, with an expected lifespan of eight years, using a depreciation model where the residual value is calculated at 15% annually of the initial purchase price. Over the 20-year analysis period, the system will be replaced three times. Each replacement occurs every seven years, with the resale value of the first system contributing to the cost reduction of the second purchase. The first system, purchased in 2022, will be sold in 2029 at its residual value. The second system is expected to cost 84,426.03, reflecting the impact of a 5 percent annual inflation rate. From this value, the depreciated value of the first machine is subtracted, resulting in the net value of 65,191.40 €. Similarly, the net value of the third purchase is calculated, which will be 91,730.85 € and will take place in 2036. This approach ensures the analysis accurately captures depreciation and inflation-adjusted costs over time, providing a realistic assessment of the actual investment required. It reflects the evolving financial demands agricultural businesses face while ensuring that costs are not underestimated, offering a more precise evaluation of capital expenditures over the long term.

Investment costs (euros)

<i>Machine and Tools</i>	Annual costs	Year	Expected lifetime (n. year)
<i>1st Machines purchase</i>	60,000	2022	7
<i>2nd Machines purchase</i>	65,191	2029	7
<i>3rd Machines purchase</i>	91,731	2036	7

TABLE 231: INVESTMENT COSTS FROM GPS AND CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (SWEDEN 3)

The operating costs of the farm incorporate several key elements, particularly changes in maintenance expenses and input costs due to the implementation of the DAT EcoPatch system. Maintenance costs are calculated as 3% of the purchase price of the system across its lifespan. From 2022 to 2029, annual maintenance expenses amount to €1,800 based on the first system's cost. With the purchase of the second system in 2029, these costs rise to €2,532.78 annually through 2036, reflecting the inflation-adjusted purchase price. Finally, during the third cycle, from 2036 to 2042, maintenance costs increase further to €3,563.88 annually. Fuel expenses have seen a slight reduction due to more efficient operations, decreasing from €990 per year before the transition to €693 per year post-implementation, remaining consistent across the entire period from 2022 to 2042. Similarly, the cost of raw materials, specifically herbicides, has decreased. Pre-transition herbicide expenses were €7,710 annually, but this has dropped to €6,737 annually due to the precision application capabilities of the DAT EcoPatch system. This represents a modest yet significant cost-saving across the same 2022 to 2042 period.

These figures illustrate the farm's evolving cost structure, with initial savings in fuel and herbicide expenditures offsetting rising maintenance costs. This balanced approach highlights the long-term sustainability and efficiency gains made possible through the adoption of precision agriculture technologies.

Operating costs (euros year⁻¹)

	Annual costs - Pre	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Machine maintenance (3% of purchase price)</i>		1 st purchase – 1,800.00	2022-2029
		2 nd purchase – 2,532.78	2029-2036
		3 rd purchase – 3,563.88	2036-2042

<i>Fuel</i>	990.00	693.00	2022-2042
<i>Raw material</i>	Herbicides - 7,710.00	Herbicides - 6,737.00	2022-2042

TABLE 232: OPERATING COSTS FROM GPS AND CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (SWEDEN 3)

The project incurs annual costs across several categories from 2022 to 2042, with labour expenses representing the most significant expenditure. Labour costs total €74,500 per year, reflecting a slight reduction of €500 annually compared to the previous scenario due to improved operational efficiency with the DAT EcoPatch system. In addition to labour, technical support costs remain consistent at €200 per year, ensuring the maintenance and smooth operation of the new precision farming technology. Training expenses are modest, calculated at €22 per worker annually, emphasizing the ongoing need for skill development to manage the new system effectively.

Labour costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Labour</i>	74,500	2022-2042
<i>Technical support</i>	200	2022-2042
<i>Training</i>	22	2022-2042

TABLE 233: LABOUR COSTS FROM GPS AND CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (SWEDEN 3)

The Other costs section includes transaction costs of 3,979.80 euros in 2022 (99 hectares), representing the administrative or operational expenses associated with implementing the changes. Opportunity costs are calculated as the present value in 2022 of capital allocated to the tool purchases. The opportunity cost for the first purchase is 10,481.11 euros, while for the second purchase, it is 8,653.93 euros. The third is equal to 9,253.48.

Other costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Transaction costs</i>	20,100	2022
<i>Opportunity costs (Present Value)</i>		
<i>1st purchase machines</i>	10,481.11	2022
<i>2nd purchase machines</i>	8,653.93	2022
<i>3rd purchase machines</i>	9,253.48	2022

TABLE 234: OTHER COSTS FROM GPS AND CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (SWEDEN 3)

Cost-benefit identification

<i>Category</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Attribute</i>
Benefit per person or household	Improved Labour Environment	Reduction of workers' risk from exposure to phytosanitary products (public)	Qualitative
Benefit per unit of abatement	Enhanced Food quality and safety	Reduced risk of chemical residues on crops (public)	Qualitative
<i>Environmental Benefit</i>	<i>Minimized Dependency on Chemical Inputs</i>	<i>Reduced herbicide use due to precision application of the system</i>	Monetary 22,523 euros – present value
Delay or reduction in cost	Decrease in fuel costs	<i>More efficient and faster operations resulting in less fuel needed</i>	Monetary 6,875 euros – present value
	Decrease in labour costs	<i>Slight reduction in working hours</i>	Monetary 11,574 euros – present value
	*Reduced CO ₂ emissions		Monetary 2,392.82 euros – present value
Total (monetary) benefits			40,971 euros

TABLE 235: IDENTIFIED BENEFITS FROM GPS AND CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (SWEDEN 3)

* We do not include the calculation of CO₂ emissions in the private analysis because they represent a cost shifted onto society and are not part of the private cost-benefit balance. However, these emissions were calculated separately to account for their broader impact, using values from the EIB Group climate bank roadmap 2021-2025. The roadmap provides the basis for the shadow cost, which represents the minimum societal cost of achieving the 1.5°C temperature target (EIB, 2020).

The transition to precision agriculture in the Swedish context has delivered significant environmental and financial benefits, particularly through GPS and camera-guided mechanical weeding. The DAT EcoPatch system reduced herbicide expenses from €7,710 to €6,737 annually and lowered fuel costs from €990 to €693, enhancing sustainability and reducing the farm's carbon footprint. Table 2 highlights the associated costs, including capital expenditures for three machine purchases (€60,000, €65,191, and €91,731) and progressive maintenance costs ranging from €1,800 to €3,564 annually. Labour-related expenses, including technical support (€200) and training (€22 annually), remain minimal.

Category	Cost item	Value (Euros)	Present Value (euros)
Capital costs (CAPEX)	Machines		
	1 st purchase	60,000	60,000
	2 nd purchase	65,191	49,540
	3 rd purchase	91,731	52,972
Operating costs, including operations and maintenance (OPEX)	Maintenance		
	1 st purchase	1,800	12,604
	2 nd purchase	2,533	13,477
	3 rd purchase	3,564	12,847
Labour	Technical support	200	2,918
	Training year	22	321
Other costs	Transaction costs		3,980
	Opportunity costs		
	1 st purchase machines		10,481
	2 nd purchase machines		8,654
	3 rd purchase machines		9,253
Total Costs			237,047

TABLE 236: IDENTIFIED COSTS FROM GPS AND CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (SWEDEN 3)

Economic analysis

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR (%)
20	-1,980.56	0.17	-4.6

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR
20	-2,333.83	0.07	-100

TABLE 237: ECONOMIC ANALYSIS FROM GPS AND CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (SWEDEN 3)

In the first scenario, despite no project failure risk and a high adoption rate, the economic viability appears limited. The Net Present Value (NPV) per hectare at -1,980.56 euros indicates returns below initial expectations, which can be attributed to the high initial cost of adopting advanced precision agriculture technologies like the DAT EcoPatch system. The Benefit-Cost Ratio (BCR) of 0.17 suggests that each euro invested yields only 0.17 euros, indicating suboptimal long-term financial sustainability. This low yield is likely influenced by significant upfront investments and maintenance costs that do not yet offset by corresponding increases in crop yield or sufficient reductions in operational costs. The Modified Internal Rate of Return (MIRR) at -4.6% reflects a return rate that is inadequate to justify these investments even under favourable conditions.

In the second scenario, characterized by low project failure risk but low adoption, the financial outlook is even more unfavourable. The NPV further decreases to -2,333.83 euros per hectare, highlighting a clear loss, primarily driven by the insufficient spread of technology adoption which exacerbates the impact of fixed costs on a smaller scale. The BCR of 0.07 indicates that the investment fails to generate adequate

returns, with each euro invested bringing back only 0.07 euros. This scenario underscores the inefficiencies in cost recovery when adoption rates are low. Moreover, the extremely low MIRR of -100% starkly underscores the inadequacy of the project's returns to cover both the investment and ongoing operational costs. This scenario illustrates the critical importance of high adoption rates not only for achieving economies of scale but also for spreading out the substantial initial costs over a larger area to enhance cost distribution and overall project viability.

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

FIGURE 19: GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF NET AND CUMULATIVE BENEFITS UNDER TWO SCENARIOS: NO RISK OF FAILURE WITH HIGH ADOPTION (TOP) AND LOW RISK OF FAILURE WITH LOW ADOPTION (BOTTOM)

In the first scenario, the consistently positive returns illustrated in the net benefits graph across most years indicate that the project is capable of generating enough income to support not only reinvestment but also ongoing operational needs, thus suggesting a model that could become financially self-sustaining over time. This is further evidenced by the cumulative net benefits graph, which demonstrates a steady upward trend, signifying growing financial stability as the project matures and possibly benefits from economies of scale and optimized processes. Conversely, in the second scenario, the net benefits graph shows a more pessimistic trend with fluctuating returns, hinting at the project's inability to establish a steady financial recovery, primarily due to low adoption rates. This variability in returns complicates planning and reinvestment and strains financial sustainability. The cumulative net benefits graph underscores this challenge, illustrating slow and sporadic growth. This lack of consistent growth highlights the critical need for broader adoption, which would help distribute the high fixed costs over a larger operational base, enhance cost-effectiveness, and ensure more predictable financial performance, making the project more viable in the long term.

Social analysis

 Traffic light 67.10%	<p>In the Swedish context, the adoption of precision mechanical weeding technology as indicated by the traffic light score of 67.10% (categorized as high) suggests a relatively positive social impact, albeit with some reservations. This score reflects an overall beneficial view of the technology's social ramifications, especially in terms of improving labour conditions and potential economic stability for farm workers. However, while the high score indicates a strong potential for positive impact, it also implies that the full potential of this technology is not yet realized, possibly hindered by high initial investment and operational costs, which could be limiting broader adoption particularly on smaller farms. This suggests that without further financial incentives or policy support, the broader social benefits of the technology might not be fully accessible, particularly in more resource-constrained settings.</p>
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Social impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
<i>The practice provides more stable income from year to year than alternatives</i>	0.47
<i>The current practice provides more flexibility for the agricultural management</i>	0.50
<i>New job opportunities in the rural area</i>	0.45
<i>Improvement of working conditions for the farm employers</i>	0.48
<i>Increased food safety</i>	0.50
<i>More job opportunities for women</i>	0.25
<i>Improving farmers' education and skills</i>	0.50
<i>Improved conditions for vulnerable groups</i>	0.30
<i>Improved aesthetics of the landscape and conservation of the cultural value</i>	0.80
<i>Improved social reputation of the farm</i>	0.45

TABLE 238: SOCIAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM GPS AND CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (SWEDEN 3)

The questionnaire data presents a nuanced perception of the social impacts related to the implementation of precision mechanical weeding. Notably, aspects such as landscape aesthetics and cultural value conservation score highly (0.80), reflecting a strong appreciation for environmental stewardship and heritage preservation, a finding that aligns well with broader trends in sustainable agricultural practices. However, the lower scores for creating job opportunities for women (0.25) and improving the social reputation of farms (0.45) suggest critical areas where the technology falls short. These scores indicate that while the technology improves certain operational efficiencies and worker conditions, it has yet to make significant strides in fostering inclusivity or enhancing public perceptions of farming practices. This discrepancy suggests potential avenues for future improvement, particularly in addressing gender inclusivity and enhancing public engagement and reputation management in farming communities. Comparing these results with the literature, such as findings from Liu et al. (2023) that suggest long-term benefits to food safety from precision agriculture, it appears there is a gap between anticipated benefits and current user perceptions, indicating that more time or targeted efforts may be needed to realize these benefits fully. This gap highlights a divergence from some literature expectations, suggesting that while the operational benefits are acknowledged, the broader social and reputational benefits are yet to be fully appreciated or realized.

Social direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Improved labour environment	Jacquet et al. (2021)	Medium-to-high	Short run	Non-monetary

Social indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Reduced workload	Tamirat et al. (2023)	Low-to-medium	Short run	Non-monetary

Enhanced food safety	Liu et al. (2023); Jacquet et al., (2021)	Low	Medium-to- long run	Non-monetary
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TABLE 239: SOCIAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM GPS AND CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (SWEDEN 3)

Environmental analysis

 Traffic light 63.46%	<p>In the context of Sweden 3, the adoption of precision mechanical weeding technology achieves a traffic light score of 63.46%, indicating a relatively positive environmental impact, yet with notable limitations. This score, reflecting a range of environmental benefits and challenges, suggests that while the technology contributes positively to certain areas like water conservation and soil health, it also encounters significant hurdles, particularly in reducing greenhouse gas emissions and dependence on external inputs.</p>
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Env. impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
Contribute to reduce Direct greenhouse gas emissions	0.48
Contribute to reduce external inputs	0.40
Limit water consumption	0.48
Contribute to reduce waste	0.30
Has a positive impact on biodiversity	0.83
Has a positive impact on soil erosion	0.70
Has a positive impact on carbon footprint	0.00
Increase the rate of soil organic matter mineralisation	0.83
Increase soil compaction	0.33

TABLE 240: ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM GPS AND CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (SWEDEN 3)

The questionnaire data presents a nuanced view of the environmental benefits and drawbacks associated with the technology. High scores for improving biodiversity (0.83) and reducing soil erosion (0.70) reflect a strong perception that the technology supports critical ecological functions, which aligns well with the growing emphasis on sustainable land management practices. Conversely, surprisingly low scores in areas such as carbon footprint impact (0.00) indicate a critical perception gap. This discrepancy, especially regarding carbon footprint, may stem from a lack of visible connection between operational practices like fuel savings and broader environmental impacts such as reduced greenhouse gas emissions. This suggests that while operational efficiencies are recognized at a mechanical level, their environmental significance, particularly in terms of emissions reduction, might not be fully appreciated or understood by users.

This misalignment between perceived and actual environmental impacts highlights the need for better communication and education regarding the indirect benefits of precision technologies. For instance, while fuel efficiency inherently suggests reduced carbon emissions, this benefit might not be immediately obvious to end-users without explicit communication about how reduced fuel consumption lowers greenhouse gas emissions over time. Enhancing user understanding of these connections could improve perception scores and support broader environmental objectives, aligning user perceptions with the environmental advantages documented in literature, such as the reduced need for chemical inputs and associated energy savings in their production and application, as noted by Pergher et al. (2020) and Kup and Saglam (2014). Clear communication about these indirect benefits, emphasizing long-term environmental gains, could bridge the existing gap and enhance the technology's overall environmental impact profile.

Env. direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Reduced use of harmful chemicals	Kup, F., & R. Saglam, (2014)	High	Short to Long-run	Quantitative

Env. indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Land Conservation (reduced soil erosion, off-site effects)	Liu et al. (2023); Jacquet et al. (2021)	Controversial	Long-run	Qualitative
Increase demand energy	Pergher, G., Gubiani, R., & Mainardis, M. (2020)	Medium to high	Short-run	Quantitative

TABLE 241: ENVIRONMENTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM GPS AND CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (SWEDEN 3)

Sensitivity analysis (only first scenario)

The sensitivity analysis for the first scenario of Sweden 3's adoption of camera guided mechanical weeding technology reveals a financial landscape significantly more challenging than previously anticipated. The results from the Monte Carlo simulation based on 1000 random iterations highlight a consistently negative financial outlook. The Net Present Value (NPV) per hectare fluctuates notably, with a minimum of -2,909.95 euros and a maximum of -1,138.08 euros. The average NPV hovers around -2,010.32 euros, and the median closely aligns at -2,013.73 euros, indicating that the project is likely to incur losses under most simulated conditions, with a 0% probability of achieving a positive NPV. This outcome suggests that under the current assumptions, the project is financially unviable, contradicting the earlier optimistic predictions. Similarly, the Benefit-Cost Ratio (BCR) analysis paints a grim picture. Values range from a minimum of 0.05 to a maximum of 0.27, with the default BCR settling at a low 0.17. Both the mean and median BCRs underscore the project's inability to generate sufficient returns, with average figures around 0.14 and 0.13, respectively. There is also a 0% probability of the BCR exceeding 1, let alone reaching the target BCR of 2, further emphasizing the financial challenges faced by the project.

The sensitivity to varying discount rates does not alleviate concerns. Even at a low discount rate of 2%, the NPV remains deeply negative at -219,812 euros, with a BCR of 0.19, and this trend persists as the discount rate increases, barely improving the financial metrics. These findings starkly highlight the economic impracticalities of the project, marking it as financially unsustainable across different financial scenarios. The detailed results indicate that despite any potential efficiencies gained from the precision technology, the costs vastly outweigh the benefits, suggesting that significant operational improvements or external financial subsidies would be essential to enhance the project's economic viability.

Net Present Value (NPV)	Tot. Euros	Euros ha ⁻¹
Minimum	-288,085	-2909.95
Maximum	-112,670	-1138.08
Default case	-196,076	-1980.56
Mean	-199,022	-2010.32
Median	-199,360	-2013.73
Probability that NPV > 0		0.00
Distribution (euros)	Probability	
Less than -288K	0.00	
-288K to -253K	0.24	
-253K to -218K	0.00	
-218K to -183K	0.51	
-183K to -148K	0.00	
-148K to -113K	0.25	
	Total	1.00
Benefit: Cost Ratio (BCR)	Unconstrained version	
Minimum	0.05	
Maximum	0.27	
Default case	0.17	
Mean	0.14	
Median	0.13	

Probability that BCR > 1	0.00
Target BCR	2
Probability BCR > Target	0.0
Distribution	Probability
Less than 0.05	0.00
0.05 to 0.10	0.15
0.10 to 0.14	0.44
0.14 to 0.18	0.27
0.18 to 0.22	0.11
0.22 to 0.27	0.04
Total	1.00

TABLE 242: BCA ROBUSTNESS (MONTE CARLO ANALYSIS BASED ON 1000 RANDOM SIMULATIONS) - GPS AND CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (SWEDEN 3)

Sensitivity to discount rate

Project organisation	Low discount rate 2%	Default discount rate 4%	High discount rate 6%
Benefits (present value)	50,438	40,971	33,864
Costs (present value)	270,249	237,047	211,329
Net Present Value (NPV)	-219,812	-196,076	-177,464
Benefit: Cost Ratio (unconstrained budget)	0.19	0.17	0.16

TABLE 243: SENSITIVITY TO DISCOUNT RATE - GPS AND CAMERA GUIDED MECHANICAL WEEDING (SWEDEN 3)

4.2.5 Ecological management solutions

4.2.5.1 False seedbed in wheat (Greece 2)

Main objective

The project aims to significantly reduce herbicide use in arable crops, specifically *Triticum aestivum* and *Triticum durum* (hereafter referred to as wheat), through the adoption of the false seedbed technique.). This agronomic practice promotes early weed control, reducing the need for chemical herbicides.

Description of the “before” scenario

In the scenario before the introduction of the false seedbed technique, the process involves traditional ploughing using a Fendt 718 Vario with a 5-furrow plough, followed by seedbed preparation with a Zeus S ZAMIDIS cultivator and a KUHN HRB 353 culti-packer. Fertilization is applied using a spreader with 300 kg/ha of Yaramila Star Plus fertilizer. Wheat is then sown using a LEMKEN Solitair pneumatic seed drill, consuming 9 L of fuel per hectare. Additionally, herbicides are applied using an AGROTIS boom sprayer, with a quantity of 700 cc/ha of herbicide.

Description of the “after” scenario

In the false seedbed scenario, the process involves similar ploughing and seedbed preparation steps, but now mechanical weed control is introduced 20-25 days after the final seedbed preparation. A disk harrow (Pottinger Terradisc) is used for this mechanical weed control. Fertilization and sowing remain consistent with the previous scenario, but no herbicide application is mentioned. This reduces reliance on chemical inputs, with weed control managed mechanically.

In comparing the after scenario with literature-based practices, several key differences emerge. While the after scenario focuses on replacing herbicide use with mechanical weed control following the false seedbed preparation, literature examples often combine false seedbed with post-emergence herbicide application to maximize both weed control and yield improvements. For instance, studies on barley show that false seedbed combined with herbicides such as pinoxaden increased grain yield by 23–36%, compared to direct sowing with chemical control alone (Kanas et al., 2020). In soybean, a stale seedbed with glyphosate led to seed yield increases of 17–35%, depending on the combination (Kanas et al., 2020). Furthermore, literature suggests that delaying sowing after seedbed preparation in forage crops enhances yield and reduces weed pressure significantly (Gazoulis et al., 2022). The Greece 2 approach, which eliminates chemical inputs in favor of mechanical weed control, could lead to different results, particularly regarding yield and weed suppression, given the absence of herbicide use. The focus on wheat (*Triticum aestivum* and *Triticum durum*) might also yield different responses compared to the crops discussed in the literature, such as barley, soybean, and forage crops.

Input data and farm characteristics

Greece2 is a 100-hectare farm that operates under conventional agricultural practices, primarily cultivating wheat. The entire farm’s area is utilized for agricultural purposes (100 hectares). The experimental area covers 2 hectares, where wheat is the primary focus for experimental activities.

<i>Management Type</i>	Conventional
<i>Most important crops and animal productions</i>	Wheat
<i>Total Farm Area (ha)</i>	100
<i>Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA, ha)</i>	100
<i>Experimental area (ha)</i>	2
<i>Experimental crop(s)</i>	Wheat

TABLE 244: INPUT DATA AND FARM CHARACTERISTICS FROM FALSE SEEDBED WHEAT (GREECE 2)

In this analysis, the disk harrow is replaced every 7 years, with costs determined by accounting for both future value appreciation at an annual rate of 5% and depreciation at 15% per year. For subsequent purchases, the effective costs are calculated by determining the future value of previous purchases after 7 and 14 years, respectively, while applying the same depreciation rate. Additionally, the use of specialized equipment for shallow soil disturbance, such as that required for the false seedbed technique, may involve higher investment and operational costs compared to standard agricultural machinery (Merfield, C. N., 2015). This comprehensive approach captures both the financial implications of machinery replacement and the additional costs associated with advanced agricultural practices.

Investment costs (euros)

<i>Machine and Tools</i>	Annual costs	Year	Expected lifetime (n. year)
<i>Disk harrow</i>	26,000	2021	7
<i>2nd tools purchase</i>	28,250	2028	7
<i>3rd tools purchase</i>	39,750	2035	7

TABLE 245: INVESTMENT COSTS FROM FALSE SEEDBED WHEAT (GREECE 2)

The operating costs primarily involve fuel and maintenance expenses over the period from 2021 to 2041. Fuel costs increase by approximately 11.95 euros annually in the post-scenario, likely due to changes in operational intensity or fuel prices. Machine maintenance, calculated as 3% of the purchase price, amounts to 780 euros annually for the first tool purchase (2020-2026), 1,097.5 euros for the second purchase (2027-2033), and 1,544.4 euros for the third purchase (2034-2040).

Operating costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Pre	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Fuel</i>	46,15	58,10	2021-2041
<i>Machine maintenance (3% of purchase price)</i>		1 st tools purchase - 780	2021-2026
		2 nd tools purchase – 1097.5	2027-2033
		3 rd tools purchase – 1544.4	2034-2041

TABLE 246: OPERATING COSTS FROM FALSE SEEDBED WHEAT (GREECE 2)

Labour costs are projected to decrease by approximately 65 euros annually in the post-scenario. Interviews indicated a potential cost of 200 euros for technical support, while training costs are estimated at 22 euros per worker per year.

Labour costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Pre	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Labour costs (year basis)</i>	289.33	224.33	2021-2041
<i>Technical support</i>		200	2021-2041
<i>Training</i>		22	2021-2041

TABLE 247: LABOUR COSTS FROM FALSE SEEDBED WHEAT (GREECE 2)

The other costs associated with the implementation scenario include transaction costs, which amount to 80.4 euros (Mettepenningen et al., 2009). The opportunity costs (present value) for the disk harrow are calculated over three replacement cycles. The opportunity cost for the first purchase is 4,542 euros, decreasing to 4,245 euros for the second purchase, and 3,967 euros for the third. These figures represent the financial implications of machinery replacement over time, adjusted to present value, while also accounting for the associated transaction costs.

Other costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Transaction costs</i>	80.4	2021
<i>Opportunity costs (Present Value)</i>		
<i>1st purchase</i>	4,542	2021
<i>2nd purchase</i>	4,245	2021
<i>3rd purchase</i>	3,967	2021

TABLE 248: OTHER COSTS FROM FALSE SEEDBED WHEAT (GREECE 2)

Cost-benefit identification

<i>Category</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Attribute</i>
Benefit per person or household	Improved Labour Environment	Reduction of workers' risk from exposure to phytosanitary products (public)	Qualitative
Benefit per unit of abatement	Enhanced Food quality and safety	Reduced risk of chemical residues on wheat (public)	Qualitative
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced or zero costs for weed management (agrochemicals)+ reduced maintenance on AGROTIS boom sprayer 1300L +reduced labour	Direct cost savings by reducing the use of herbicides (including machinery and labour) (private)	Monetary (24,306 euros – present value)
Improve an environmental or community asset	Ecological improvement	Improve biodiversity (public), Improved nutrient cycling	Qualitative
Total (monetary) benefits			24,306 euros

TABLE 249: IDENTIFIED BENEFITS FROM FALSE SEEDBED WHEAT (GREECE 2)

The benefits identified in the Greece 2 false seedbed case align with findings in the literature regarding reduced exposure to phytosanitary products, improved food safety due to fewer chemical residues, and cost savings from decreased agrochemical use and mechanization. As noted by Kanatas et al. (2020) and Gazoulis et al. (2022), reducing herbicide use contributes to worker safety and public health, aligning with our findings. Similarly, the monetary savings of 24,306 euros from reduced herbicide use and labour align with literature that emphasizes the financial benefits of adopting mechanical weed control methods. However, a significant difference arises in terms of yield improvements. While the literature reports notable yield increases—such as 23-36% with herbicide use and 9-20% without—the Greece 2 case did not observe yield improvements following the adoption of the false seedbed technique. This lack of yield improvement contrasts with the literature, but there are key differences in the approaches used. In Greece 2, the post-treatment relied on mechanical methods, whereas the literature often describes scenarios where the false seedbed is followed by herbicide applications, such as with pinoxaden in barley or glyphosate in soybeans. This combination in the literature may have been crucial in achieving the reported yield gains. In our case, the exclusive use of mechanical weeding in the post-treatment phase might explain why yield improvements were not observed.

<i>Category</i>	<i>Cost item</i>	<i>Value (Euros)</i>	<i>Present Value (euros)</i>
<i>Capital costs (CAPEX)</i>	<i>Machine Tools</i>	94,000	70,422
<i>Operating costs, including operations and maintenance (OPEX)</i>	<i>Machine Maintenance</i>		
	<i>Fuel</i>	3,422	15,642
<i>Labour</i>		12	175
	<i>Tech. Supp.</i>	200	2,918
	<i>Training year</i>	22	321
<i>Other costs</i>	<i>Transaction costs</i>		80.4
	<i>Opportunity costs</i>		12,754
	<i>CO₂**</i>		169.16
Total Costs			102,312

TABLE 250: IDENTIFIED COSTS FROM FALSE SEEDBED WHEAT (GREECE 2)

** We do not include the calculation of CO2 emissions in the private analysis because they represent a cost shifted onto society and are not part of the private cost-benefit balance. However, these emissions were calculated separately to account for their broader impact, using values from the EIB Group climate bank roadmap 2021-2025. The roadmap provides the basis for the shadow cost, which represents the minimum societal cost of achieving the 1.5°C temperature target (EIB, 2020).

Economic analysis

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Time duration (years)	n.	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR (%)
20		-39,003.5	0.24	-1.7

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

Time duration (years)	n.	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR
20		-46,440.5	0.09	-100

TABLE 251: ECONOMIC ANALYSIS FROM FALSE SEEDBED WHEAT (GREECE 2)

In the Greece 2 case study, the economic analysis under both scenarios reveals significant financial challenges. In the first scenario, which assumes high adoption with no risk of project failure, the NPV is -39,003.5 euros per hectare over 20 years, indicating substantial financial losses. The BCR of 0.24 suggests that only 24 cents are returned for every euro invested, and the MIRR of -1.7% confirms the project does not generate sustainable returns. This contrasts with findings from Tataridas et al. (2022), where high adoption of non-chemical weed management practices, led to positive financial outcomes due to reduced herbicide use. However, specific local factors in Greece 2, such as operational costs or market conditions, may hinder the realization of these benefits. The second scenario, assuming low adoption with no risk of project failure, presents an even worse financial outcome, with an NPV of -46,440.5 euros per hectare, a BCR of 0.09, and an MIRR of -100%, indicating high financial losses. This aligns with literature, such as Hostetler et al. (2007), which suggests that low adoption levels dilute both economic and environmental benefits, as the scale needed to achieve significant cost savings from reduced herbicide use is not reached. Overall, the Greece 2 project faces significant financial viability issues under both scenarios, with localized economic and structural challenges possibly contributing to the failure to achieve the benefits documented in other studies. Furthermore, if we had assumed a longer machinery lifespan, extending it to **15 years instead of 7**, fixed costs, including opportunity costs, would decrease, easing the financial burden per year. However, even with this adjustment, the analysis indicates that the project would still likely result in negative financial outcomes due to the limited benefits achieved. The reduction in fixed costs would help, but not enough to change the overall financial viability, highlighting the need for further incentives or support to make the project profitable.

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

FIGURE 20: GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF NET AND CUMULATIVE BENEFITS UNDER TWO SCENARIOS: NO RISK OF FAILURE WITH HIGH ADOPTION (TOP) AND LOW RISK OF FAILURE WITH LOW ADOPTION (BOTTOM)

The graphs for the first scenario (no risk of project failure and high adoption) and the second scenario (low risk of project failure and low adoption) highlight significant financial challenges, with pronounced negative spikes in net benefits. These negative peaks, seen in both scenarios, are directly linked to the high upfront costs associated with the implementation of the false seedbed technique, as discussed in the literature. Merfield (2015) and Kanatas et al. (2020) both point out that false seedbed requires specialized machinery and additional tillage operations, which drive up initial labour and operational costs. In the first scenario, although adoption is high, the project struggles to achieve financial viability, as the cumulative net benefits remain negative throughout the project's life cycle. This suggests that while weed control and environmental benefits are being realized, the high initial investments hinder the project's ability to generate positive financial returns. In the second scenario, with low adoption, the situation worsens, as the project incurs even greater financial losses. This aligns with the literature's emphasis on the importance of economies of scale; lower adoption means that the cost savings from reduced herbicide use and improved weed management are insufficient to offset the significant upfront costs. Tataridas et al. (2022) and Shahzad et al. (2021) further support this finding, showing that widespread adoption is crucial to realizing the full economic and environmental benefits of false seedbed practices. In conclusion, the Greece 2 case underscores the financial risks associated with high-cost sustainable practices when adoption rates are low or inconsistent.

Social analysis

 Traffic light 73.84%	<p>The global traffic light score of 73.84% reflects a generally positive social impact from the adoption of the false seedbed and other sustainable practices in Greece 2. The green light indicates significant improvements, particularly in enhancing working conditions and providing better job opportunities, as supported by the literature. However, some areas, such as gender inclusivity and food safety, still show limited progress, suggesting that while the project has strong social benefits, certain aspects may take longer to fully materialize.</p>
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Social impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
<i>The practice provides more stable income from year to year than alternatives</i>	0.78
<i>The current practice provides more flexibility for the agricultural management</i>	0.69
<i>New job opportunities in the rural area</i>	0.78
<i>Improvement of working conditions for the farm employers</i>	0.79
<i>Increased food safety</i>	0.38
<i>More job opportunities for women</i>	0.25
<i>Improving farmers' education and skills</i>	0.50
<i>Improved conditions for vulnerable groups</i>	0.30

<i>Improved aesthetics of the landscape and conservation of the cultural value</i>	0.40
<i>Improved social reputation of the farm</i>	0.30

TABLE 252: SOCIAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM FALSE SEEDBED WHEAT (GREECE 2)

The questionnaire results highlight several positive social impacts from the adoption of sustainable practices. High scores were recorded for improving working conditions (0.79) and creating new job opportunities in rural areas (0.78), which are consistent with findings in the literature by Merfield (2015) and Kanatas et al. (2020), where better labour environments are emphasized as a direct benefit of these practices. Flexibility in agricultural management (0.69) and providing a stable income (0.78) also show that the adoption of these practices brings clear advantages to the economic and social sustainability of farms. However, the lower scores in areas like food safety (0.38) and gender inclusivity (0.25) suggest that the project’s broader social impacts are less pronounced in certain aspects. This is in line with Tataridas et al. (2022), who note that benefits such as community health improvements and broader inclusivity often require a longer timeframe and greater adoption to become fully realized. While there are moderate impacts on community health and skill development, reflected in scores like 0.50 for education and skills, the results suggest that more focused efforts may be needed to enhance these areas further and to address gaps in inclusivity and food safety. In conclusion, the project shows promise in improving social well-being but faces challenges in achieving widespread and balanced social impact.

Social direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Attribute
<i>Improved labour environment</i>	Shahzad et al. (2021), Gazoulis et al. (2021), Merfield, (2015), Kanatas et al., 2020	Medium to High	Short to medium-term	Qualitative

Social indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Improving community health	Tataridas et al. (2022)	moderate to high	Medium-to-long run	Qualitative

TABLE 253: SOCIAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM FALSE SEEDBED WHEAT (GREECE 2)

Environmental analysis

 Traffic light 69.85%	<p>The global traffic light score of 69.85% indicates a moderately high environmental impact from adopting sustainable practices such as the false seedbed in Greece 2. Although the score suggests positive effects, it falls slightly short of a high-impact classification, reflecting that while environmental benefits like improved soil health and carbon footprint reductions are noticeable, other areas such as biodiversity and external input reduction still present opportunities for improvement. This aligns with the literature, where the environmental impacts of false seedbed practices are less explored compared to other agricultural techniques.</p>
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Env. impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
<i>Contribute to reduce Direct greenhouse gas emissions</i>	0.42
<i>Contribute to reduce external inputs</i>	0.20
<i>Limit water consumption</i>	0.46
<i>Contribute to reduce waste</i>	0.30
<i>Has a positive impact on biodiversity</i>	0.45
<i>Has a positive impact on soil erosion</i>	0.49
<i>Has a positive impact on carbon footprint</i>	0.80
<i>Increase the rate of soil organic matter mineralisation</i>	0.47
<i>Increase soil compaction</i>	0.47

TABLE 254: ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM FALSE SEEDBED WHEAT (GREECE 2)

The questionnaire results reflect a nuanced view of the environmental impacts from the adoption of practices like the false seedbed. One of the highest scores relates to the positive impact on the carbon footprint (0.80), which is supported by literature such as Shahzad et al. (2021) and Tataridas et al. (2022), who emphasize that reduced herbicide and fuel usage contribute to lower greenhouse gas emissions. However, lower scores in areas like external input reduction (0.20) and waste reduction (0.30) indicate that the project has yet to fully capitalize on these benefits, as these areas require sustained efforts and more widespread adoption to manifest significantly. The perception of a positive impact on biodiversity (0.45), while moderate, is still consistent with findings from the literature, where Tataridas et al. (2022) and Shahzad et al. (2021) note that biodiversity support tends to be a cumulative effect, visible over a longer term rather than immediately. Moreover, impacts like soil erosion reduction (0.49) and increased soil organic matter mineralization (0.47) are in line with the incremental improvements often associated with the false seedbed technique, as described by Merfield (2015). Notably, the literature on false seedbed offers limited references to its broader environmental impacts, particularly in comparison to more widely studied practices like cover cropping or organic farming, which tend to report stronger immediate effects on biodiversity and input reduction. As the results show, while the project is on the right path environmentally, there is room to deepen its impact in certain areas through more extensive and sustained adoption.

Env. direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Biodiversity support	Shahzad et al. (2021), Tataridas et al. (2022)	High	Medium to long-term	Qualitative

Env. indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Reduced carbon footprint	Shahzad et al. (2021), Tataridas et al. (2022)	Moderate	Long-term	Qualitative

TABLE 255: ENVIRONMENTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM FALSE SEEDBED WHEAT (GREECE 2)

Sensitivity analysis (only first scenario)

The sensitivity analysis for the first scenario of the Greece 2 project highlights significant financial risks. In the default case, the NPV is -39,003.5 euros per hectare, with a mean of -39,883 euros per hectare and a median of -39,416.5 euros per hectare. These figures indicate that, on average, each hectare incurs substantial losses, making the financial viability of the project highly uncertain. The probability of achieving a positive NPV per hectare is 0%, meaning the project is unlikely to break even on a per-hectare basis. This mirrors findings in the literature by Merfield (2015), where the high upfront costs of implementing the false seedbed technique, including specialized machinery and increased labour, are identified as major barriers to financial success, particularly when these costs cannot be offset by significant efficiency gains or high levels of adoption.

The Benefit-Cost Ratio (BCR) also reflects the unfavourable financial situation. With a default BCR of 0.24 per hectare and a mean BCR of 0.19, the project does not generate sufficient returns to justify the investment. The probability of achieving a BCR greater than 1 remains 0%, reinforcing the limited financial viability. This is consistent with Kanatas et al. (2020), who note that while environmental benefits, such as weed control, are achieved through the false seedbed, the financial returns may remain modest or negative without significant external support or incentives.

In conclusion, these per-hectare results from the sensitivity analysis underscore the financial challenges the project faces, particularly in covering the high initial costs of adoption. While environmental and social benefits exist, the financial metrics alone suggest that achieving positive returns would require further incentives or subsidies to support the adoption of these sustainable practices at scale.

Finally, If we had assumed a longer lifespan for the machinery, such as **15 years instead of 7**, the project's fixed costs, including opportunity costs, could be significantly reduced. By spreading the high upfront

investments in specialized tools and machinery over a longer period, the annual depreciation and associated costs would decrease. This adjustment could improve the overall financial outlook by lowering the financial burden per year. However, even with this change, the sensitivity analysis suggests that the project would still likely face negative outcomes, even under more favourable conditions. The limited benefits achieved through the false seedbed practice, particularly in this scenario, are not sufficient to offset the high investment costs. While extending the machinery's lifespan would reduce some fixed costs, the overall financial result would remain negative, reflecting the broader challenge of achieving profitability from this specific practice without additional support or a more substantial increase in benefits, such as higher yields or significant reductions in external inputs.

Net Present Value (NPV)	Tot. Euros	Euros ha⁻¹
Minimum	-120,780	-60,390
Maximum	-40,022	-20,011
Default case	-78,007	-39,003.5
Mean	-79,766	-39,883
Median	-78,833	-39,416.5
Probability that NPV > 0		0
Distribution (euros)		Probability
Less than -121K		0.00
-121K to -105K		0.21
-105K to -89K		0.08
-89K to -72K		0.40
-72K to -56K		0.09
-56K to -40K		0.24
	Total	1.00
Benefit: Cost Ratio (BCR)		Unconstrained version
Minimum		0.07
Maximum		0.37
Default case		0.24
Mean		0.19
Median		0.19
Probability that BCR > 1		0.00
Target BCR		2
Probability BCR > Target		0
Distribution		Probability
Less than 0.07		0.00
0.07 to 0.13		0.13
0.13 to 0.19		0.37
0.19 to 0.25		0.32
0.25 to 0.31		0.13
0.31 to 0.37		0.05
	Total	1.00

TABLE 256: BCA ROBUSTNESS (MONTE CARLO ANALYSIS BASED ON 1000 RANDOM SIMULATIONS) - FALSE SEEDBED WHEAT (GREECE 2)

Sensitivity to discount rate

	Low discount rate	Default discount rate	High discount rate
Project organisation	2%	4%	6%
Benefits (present value)	29,921	24,305	20,089
Costs (present value)	116,795	102,312	91,097
Net Present Value (NPV)	-86,875	-78,007	-71,008
Benefit: Cost Ratio (unconstrained budget)	0.26	0.24	0.22

TABLE 257: SENSITIVITY TO DISCOUNT RATE - FALSE SEEDBED WHEAT (GREECE 2)

4.2.5.2 Cereal with introduction of Brassicas and other weed-reducing practices (Spain 1)

Main objective

The project aims to transition from a conventional monoculture system focused primarily on wheat (Triticum) to a more diversified cropping system by integrating crops such as rapeseed (canola) and potatoes (Solanum tuberosum). This diversification supports sustainable weed management by reducing the reliance on chemical herbicides through ecological practices.

Description of the “before” scenario

Before, the farm utilized traditional methods for soil preparation, seeding, and weed control. Tillage and weed management were performed using a chisel paired with an 80 HP 4x4 tractor, achieving a work rate of 1.5 hours per hectare and consuming 16.5 liters of fuel per hectare. Seeding and weed control were combined in a single operation using a rotary harrow equipped with a seeder, which required one hour to cover half a hectare and involved both machinery and labour. Fertilization was carried out only when the soil was deemed poor, particularly following potato harvests, using the same tractor equipped with a fertilizer spreader. This process applied one ton per hectare of granular manure (3-3-3 N-P₂O₅-K₂O) and required one hour per half hectare. Additionally, soil preparation for potato cultivation relied on a ridger (bed former) operated by the 80 HP tractor, also working at a rate of one hour per half hectare to control weeds mechanically. The farm primarily relied on a simple rotation of wheat and potatoes.

Description of the “after” scenario

After implementing the new techniques, the farm maintained the same machinery and processes but introduced a more diversified crop rotation system, now incorporating oilseed rape alongside wheat and potatoes. Different crops are sown and harvested at different times, which means that weeds never find a stable and favourable environment on a single crop for several consecutive years. This innovation in crop rotation significantly reduced weed pressure, as the inclusion of rapeseed helped to control weeds naturally, decreasing the need for intensive mechanical weed control. While tasks such as tillage, seeding, and fertilization were still necessary, the new rotation system improved soil health, reduced the frequency of tillage, and minimized the reliance on repeated mechanical interventions. As a result, fewer weeds emerged, boosting the overall efficiency and sustainability of the farm. This approach not only reduced fuel use and labour demands but also lowered input requirements, fostering more ecological and cost-effective farming practices. The addition of oilseed rape, compared to the previous simpler rotation, was a key factor in enhancing both the farm's productivity and environmental performance.

Input data and farm characteristics

Spain1 is a 80-hectare farm that operates under conventional agricultural practices, primarily cultivating wheat. The entire farm's area is utilized for agricultural purposes (80 hectares). The experimental area covers all the 80 hectares, where wheat, rapeseed and potato are the primary focus for experimental activities.

<i>Management Type</i>	Conventional
<i>Most important crops and animal productions</i>	Wheat
<i>Total Farm Area (ha)</i>	80
<i>Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA, ha)</i>	80
<i>Experimental area (ha)</i>	80
<i>Experimental crop(s)</i>	Wheat, rapeseed and potato

TABLE 258: INPUT DATA AND FARM CHARACTERISTICS FROM CEREAL WITH INTRODUCTION OF BRASSICAS AND OTHER WEED-REDUCING PRACTICES (SPAIN 1)

In this analysis, no investment costs have been considered because the farm has only modified its crop rotation system by introducing rapeseed alongside potatoes and wheat, which were already cultivated. There have been no changes in machinery, equipment, or other capital investments, as the same tools and resources used previously continue to support the new rotation. The primary innovation lies in the adjusted crop sequence, which enhances weed management and soil health.

The operating costs primarily include expenses for raw materials over the period from 2020 to 2040. In the post-scenario, fuel costs rise significantly to 28,800 euros annually compared to 6,720 euros in the pre-scenario, reflecting the increased operational intensity. However, raw material costs show a substantial reduction, with seed expenses dropping from 106,000 euros to 73,600 euros annually, and herbicide use eliminated, resulting in zero costs compared to the previous 1,440 euros per year. Fertilizer costs increase to 21,600 euros annually from the previous 2,880 euros, while insecticide expenses are eliminated entirely.

Operating costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Pre	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Raw material</i>			2020-2040
<i>Seed</i>	106,000	73,600	
<i>Herbicide</i>	1,440	0	
<i>Fertilizer</i>	2,880	21,600	
<i>Insecticide</i>	720	0	
<i>Fuel</i>	6,720	28,800	2020-2040

TABLE 259: OPERATING COSTS FROM CEREAL WITH INTRODUCTION OF BRASSICAS AND OTHER WEED-REDUCING PRACTICES (SPAIN 1)

According to the data provided by our project partner, overall labour costs have remained stable in both the pre- and post-scenario, despite changes in operational practices. Although tasks such as technical support, estimated at 200 euros annually, and training costs of 22 euros per worker per year remain consistent, the introduction of crop rotation with rapeseed has not significantly altered the total labour demand. This stability is likely due to the redistribution of labour across different tasks rather than a reduction in the overall workload.

Labour costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Pre	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Technical support</i>		200	2020-2040
<i>Training</i>		22	2020-2040

TABLE 260: LABOUR COSTS FROM CEREAL WITH INTRODUCTION OF BRASSICAS AND OTHER WEED-REDUCING PRACTICES (SPAIN 1)

The other costs associated with the implementation scenario include transaction costs, which amount to 80.4 euros (Mettepenningen et al., 2009).

Other costs (euros)

	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Transaction costs (80 ha)</i>	3,216	2020

TABLE 261: OTHER COSTS FROM CEREAL WITH INTRODUCTION OF BRASSICAS AND OTHER WEED-REDUCING PRACTICES (SPAIN 1)

Cost-benefit identification

<i>Category</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Attribute</i>
Benefit per person or household	Improved Labour Environment	Reduction of workers' risk from exposure to phytosanitary products (public)	Qualitative
Benefit per unit of abatement	Enhanced Food quality and safety	Reduced risk of chemical residues on wheat (public)	Qualitative
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced or zero costs for weed management	Direct cost savings by eliminating the use of herbicides	Monetary (749,985 euros – present value)

Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced costs for seeds	Direct cost savings due to seed change (rapeseed is introduced in addition to wheat and potato)	Monetary (33,333 euros – present value)
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced costs for insecticides	Direct cost savings by eliminating the use of insecticides	Monetary (16,670 euros – present value)
Improve an environmental or community asset	Ecological improvement	Improve biodiversity (public), Improved nutrient cycling	Qualitative
Total (monetary) benefits			799,984 euros

TABLE 262: IDENTIFIED BENEFITS FROM CEREAL WITH INTRODUCTION OF BRASSICAS AND OTHER WEED-REDUCING PRACTICES (SPAIN 1)

The benefits identified in the Spain 1 practice align with findings in the literature regarding reduced exposure to phytosanitary products, improved food safety due to fewer chemical residues, and cost savings from decreased agrochemical use and mechanization. As noted by Kanatas et al. (2020) and Gazoulis et al. (2022), reducing herbicide use contributes to worker safety and public health, aligning with our findings. Similarly, the monetary savings of 749,985 euros from reduced herbicide use and labour align with literature that emphasizes the financial benefits of adopting mechanical weed control methods. However, a significant difference emerges in terms of yield improvement. In the Spain 1 case study, the transition to a diversified crop rotation system incorporating rapeseed alongside traditional wheat and potatoes has demonstrated a 15 percent increase in crop yield, aligning with literature that supports the agronomic benefits of such diversification. However, despite these yield gains, the introduction of rapeseed—a crop with a lower market value compared to high-value potatoes—has led to a significant decline in overall farm income. Potatoes substantially contribute to the farm's revenue due to their higher market demand and versatility, making the income loss from replacing them with rapeseed notable. The inclusion of rapeseed, while ecologically beneficial in enhancing soil health and reducing pesticide reliance, poses economic challenges by diminishing the total revenue. This outcome emphasizes the complex trade-offs inherent in crop diversification strategies: although they bolster ecological resilience and promote sustainable agricultural practices, they can also temper financial returns when the newly introduced crops fetch lower market prices. Such scenarios necessitate a balanced approach to crop planning and may require strategic market adaptations or policy support to ensure that environmental gains do not come at the expense of economic viability. Furthermore, it is important to note that the data used to assess these economic outcomes were gathered through surveys completed by farmers. As such, the data may not be entirely precise and do not represent a historical trend. However, farmers were asked to provide an average price for the last five years, which offers a reasonable estimate, even though it may not fully account for fluctuations or anomalies in pricing.

<i>Category</i>	<i>Cost item</i>	<i>Value (Euros)</i>	<i>Present Value (euros)</i>
<i>Operating costs, including operations and maintenance (OPEX)</i>	<i>Reduction in total revenue</i>	<i>110,000</i>	<i>1,604,936</i>
	<i>Fertilizer</i>		
	<i>Fuel</i>	<i>18,720</i>	<i>273,131</i>
<i>Labour</i>		<i>22,080</i>	<i>322,154</i>
	<i>Tech. Supp.</i>	<i>200</i>	<i>2,918</i>
	<i>Training year</i>	<i>22</i>	<i>321</i>
<i>Other costs</i>	<i>Transaction costs</i>		<i>3,216</i>
	<i>CO₂*</i>		<i>363,766.83</i>
<i>Total Costs</i>			<i>2,206,676</i>

TABLE 263: IDENTIFIED COSTS FROM CEREAL WITH INTRODUCTION OF BRASSICAS AND OTHER WEED-REDUCING PRACTICES (SPAIN 1)

* WE DO NOT INCLUDE THE CALCULATION OF CO₂ EMISSIONS IN THE PRIVATE ANALYSIS BECAUSE THEY represent a cost shifted onto society and are not part of the private cost-benefit balance. However, these emissions were calculated separately to account for their broader impact, using values from the EIB Group climate bank roadmap 2021-2025. The roadmap provides the basis for the shadow cost, which represents the minimum societal cost of achieving the 1.5°C temperature target (EIB, 2020).

Economic analysis

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Time duration (years)	n.	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR (%)
20		-17,583.64	0.46	-100

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

Time duration (years)	n.	NPV (Euros ha ⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR
20		-23,703.52	0.14	-100

TABLE 264: ECONOMIC ANALYSIS FROM CEREAL WITH INTRODUCTION OF BRASSICAS AND OTHER WEED-REDUCING PRACTICES (SPAIN 1)

In the Spain 1 case study, the economic analysis presents substantial financial challenges under two scenarios. The first scenario, assuming no risk of project failure and high adoption, reports a Net Present Value (NPV) of -17,583.64 euros per hectare over a 20-year period, indicating significant financial losses despite optimal conditions. The BCR of 0.46 means that the project returns less than half of the invested funds, and the MIRR of -100% further underscores the inability of the project to yield sustainable financial returns. These results contrast sharply with other studies, such as those by Tataridas et al. (2022), which have documented financial gains from non-chemical weed management practices due to reduced herbicide use. However, specific factors such as operational inefficiencies or adverse market conditions in Spain may impede the realization of similar benefits. The second scenario, characterized by low adoption with still no risk of project failure, reflects an even more dire financial outlook, with an NPV of -23,703.52 euros per hectare and a BCR of 0.14. This scenario highlights the detrimental financial impact of low adoption rates on achieving economies of scale necessary for cost savings through reduced herbicide use.

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

FIGURE 21: GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF NET AND CUMULATIVE BENEFITS UNDER TWO SCENARIOS: NO RISK OF FAILURE WITH HIGH ADOPTION (TOP) AND LOW RISK OF FAILURE WITH LOW ADOPTION (BOTTOM)

The graphical representation of financial outcomes for both scenarios elucidates the depth of these challenges. The initial high costs, particularly associated with implementing advanced crop management

techniques like the false seedbed, are evident from the pronounced negative spikes in net benefits illustrated in the graphs. This financial strain persists across the project's lifecycle in the high adoption scenario, suggesting that despite achieving ecological and operational benefits, the financial inputs required are too substantial to allow for a positive financial return. In the low adoption scenario, the situation exacerbates as the reduced scale fails to mitigate the high upfront costs, leading to even larger financial deficits. Studies by Merfield (2015) and Kanatas et al. (2020) emphasize that such specialized agricultural practices, while beneficial for weed management and environmental sustainability, necessitate widespread adoption to counterbalance the hefty initial investments. These scenarios in the Spain 1 case vividly demonstrate the economic risks associated with sustainable agricultural practices when not sufficiently adopted, underlining the crucial need for broader implementation and perhaps policy support to enhance financial viability.

Social analysis

 Traffic light 81.09%	<p>The global traffic light score of 73.84% reflects a generally positive social impact from the adoption of the false seedbed and other sustainable practices in Spain 1. The green light indicates significant improvements, particularly in enhancing working conditions and providing better job opportunities, as supported by the literature. However, some areas, such as gender inclusivity and food safety, still show limited progress, suggesting that while the project has strong social benefits, certain aspects may take longer to fully materialize.</p>
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Social impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
<i>The practice provides more stable income from year to year than alternatives</i>	0.58
<i>The current practice provides more flexibility for the agricultural management</i>	0.65
<i>New job opportunities in the rural area</i>	0.63
<i>Improvement of working conditions for the farm employers</i>	0.64
<i>Increased food safety</i>	0.50
<i>More job opportunities for women</i>	0.13
<i>Improving farmers' education and skills</i>	1.00
<i>Improved conditions for vulnerable groups</i>	0.15
<i>Improved aesthetics of the landscape and conservation of the cultural value</i>	0.80
<i>Improved social reputation of the farm</i>	0.60

TABLE 265: SOCIAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM CEREAL WITH INTRODUCTION OF BRASSICAS AND OTHER WEED-REDUCING PRACTICES (SPAIN 1)

The Spain 1 project, evaluated through a global traffic light system, scores 81.09%, indicating a substantially positive social impact from the adoption of the false seedbed and other sustainable agricultural practices. This high score primarily highlights significant advancements in working conditions and the creation of job opportunities, which are robust outcomes derived from the project's implementation. Although the green light suggests that many social goals are being met effectively, there remain areas such as gender inclusivity and food safety that lag behind, highlighting a disparity in the distribution of benefits across different social aspects. This indicates that while the project is successful in several areas, achieving comprehensive social improvement across all metrics may require sustained efforts and additional targeted strategies. Analyzing the social impact perceptions from the questionnaire, the results delineate a diverse array of impacts ranging from moderate to high in terms of relevance and effectiveness. For instance, the practice has significantly improved farmers' education and skills, achieving a perfect score, reflecting a profound positive shift in knowledge and capabilities among farmers. This aligns well with the literature, particularly findings by Kanatas et al. (2020), who note that educational advancements are a direct result of engaging in more complex and sustainable farming practices. Other highly scored areas include landscape aesthetics and conservation of cultural values, suggesting that the project not only supports ecological sustainability but also enhances the visual and cultural aspects of the rural environment. However, areas like gender inclusivity and the conditions for vulnerable groups received markedly low

scores, indicating significant gaps in these aspects. These findings highlight both the strengths and limitations of the project, suggesting while some benefits are quickly realized, others, particularly those related to broader social inclusivity and safety, need more focused attention and longer-term strategies to fully manifest. The results from the project thus present a complex picture where high achievements in certain areas are counterbalanced by slower progress in others, necessitating a balanced approach to enhancing all facets of social impact in the future.

Social direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Attribute
Improved labour environment	Shahzad et al. (2021), Gazoulis et al. (2021), Merfield, (2015), Kanatas et al., 2020	Medium to High	Short to medium-term	Qualitative

Social indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Improving community health	Tataridas et al. (2022)	moderate to high	Medium-to-long run	Qualitative

TABLE 266: SOCIAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM CEREAL WITH INTRODUCTION OF BRASSICAS AND OTHER WEED-REDUCING PRACTICES (SPAIN 1)

Environmental analysis

 Traffic light 76.70%	<p>In the Spain 1 project, the environmental impact score of 76.70% from the global traffic light assessment reflects a commendably positive effect from implementing sustainable practices like the false seedbed. This score, while indicative of substantial environmental improvements, notably in areas such as soil health enhancement and carbon footprint reduction, suggests there remains room for further benefits. These include more pronounced effects on biodiversity and the reduction of external agricultural inputs. The literature supports this finding, often noting that while the false seedbed technique provides noticeable environmental benefits, it is somewhat underrepresented in research compared to other sustainable practices like cover cropping, which might show more immediate impacts on biodiversity and input reductions.</p>
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Env. impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
Contribute to reduce Direct greenhouse gas emissions	0.71
Contribute to reduce external inputs	0.40
Limit water consumption	0.65
Contribute to reduce waste	0.00
Has a positive impact on biodiversity	0.75
Has a positive impact on soil erosion	0.72
Has a positive impact on carbon footprint	0.60
Increase the rate of soil organic matter mineralisation	0.68
Increase soil compaction	0.68

TABLE 267: ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM CEREAL WITH INTRODUCTION OF BRASSICAS AND OTHER WEED-REDUCING PRACTICES (SPAIN 1)

The detailed analysis from the questionnaire paints a nuanced picture of the environmental impacts. For instance, it scores highly on reducing direct greenhouse gas emissions and positively impacting biodiversity, soil erosion, and soil organic matter mineralisation, reflecting a strong trend towards environmental improvement. These positive effects align well with literature, such as Shahzad et al. (2021) and Tataridas et al. (2022), which highlight the advantages of reduced chemical and fuel use in lowering greenhouse gas emissions and enhancing soil quality. Nonetheless, the project appears less effective in areas such as reducing external inputs and waste, scoring particularly low in waste reduction. This indicates a significant potential for improvement and suggests that achieving more substantial environmental benefits may require broader implementation and perhaps more focused efforts on these less effective areas. Additionally, the moderate to high assessments of the impact on biodiversity and carbon footprint echo the

literature's observation that these benefits are often more cumulative and manifest over longer periods, requiring sustained practices and a more holistic approach to capture the full range of environmental advantages offered by sustainable farming techniques.

Env. direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Biodiversity support	Shahzad et al. (2021), Tataridas et al. (2022)	High	Medium to long-term	Qualitative

Env. indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Reduced carbon footprint	Shahzad et al. (2021), Tataridas et al. (2022)	Moderate	Long-term	Qualitative

TABLE 268: ENVIRONMENTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM CEREAL WITH INTRODUCTION OF BRASSICAS AND OTHER WEED-REDUCING PRACTICES (SPAIN 1)

Sensitivity analysis (only first scenario)

The sensitivity analysis for the first scenario in the Spain 1 case study elucidates significant financial risks associated with the adoption of non-chemical weed management practices, particularly the false seedbed technique. The default case reveals a NPV of -17,583.64 euros per hectare, accentuating substantial economic losses across the board. The analysis shows an unfavourable financial outlook with a mean NPV of -18,534.90 euros per hectare and a median closer to -17,708.64 euros per hectare, both indicating that on average, the project fails to cover its costs per hectare significantly. The likelihood of achieving a positive NPV remains at 0%, reflecting no potential for financial breakeven. This scenario resonates with the challenges highlighted by Merfield (2015), who identifies the high initial costs of specialized machinery and increased labour as significant barriers that financial returns from enhanced efficiency or adoption levels struggle to overcome.

Moreover, the BCR provides further insight into the project's financial infeasibility. The default BCR of 0.36 per hectare, with a mean of 0.29, underscores that each euro invested fails to generate adequate returns, consistently yielding less than a third of the invested amount in benefits. The analysis firmly places the probability of achieving a BCR greater than 1 at 0%, reinforcing the project's limited financial viability. This finding is consistent with observations by Kanatas et al. (2020), who suggest that while environmental and operational benefits are realized through non-chemical practices, the financial outcomes often remain modest or negative without substantial external support or incentives.

These results from the sensitivity analysis underscore the extensive financial hurdles the project faces, particularly in covering the high upfront costs required to implement sustainable practices. While there are undeniable environmental and social benefits, the economic parameters analyzed suggest that achieving financially positive returns would necessitate additional incentives or subsidies to support the widespread adoption of these practices. Even with hypothetical adjustments such as extending machinery lifespan to reduce annual depreciation and fixed costs, the fundamental economic challenges persist, as shown in the Monte Carlo simulations. These consistently negative outcomes illustrate a crucial aspect of sustainable agricultural practices; without substantial increases in benefits such as higher yields or significant reductions in external inputs, the financial viability of such projects remains questionable.

Net Present Value (NPV)	Tot. Euros	Euros ha ⁻¹
Minimum	-2,476,687	-30958.58
Maximum	-504,694	-6308.671
Default case	-1,406,692	-17583.64
Mean	-1,482,792	-18534.90

Median	-1,416,692	-17708.64
Probability that NPV > 0		0.00
Distribution (euros)		Probability
Less than -2.5M		0.00
-2.5M to -2.1M		0.12
-2.1M to -1.7M		0.17
-1.7M to -1.3M		0.39
-1.3M to -0.9M		0.18
-0.9M to -0.5M		0.15
	Total	1.00
Benefit: Cost Ratio (BCR)		Unconstrained version
Minimum		0.11
Maximum		0.56
Default case		0.36
Mean		0.29
Median		0.30
Probability that BCR > 1		0.00
Target BCR		2
Probability BCR > Target		0
Distribution		Probability
Less than 0.11		0.00
0.11 to 0.20		0.12
0.20 to 0.29		0.34
0.29 to 0.38		0.32
0.38 to 0.47		0.18
0.47 to 0.56		0.04
	Total	1.00

TABLE 269: BCA ROBUSTNESS (MONTE CARLO ANALYSIS BASED ON 1000 RANDOM SIMULATIONS) - CEREAL WITH INTRODUCTION OF BRASSICAS AND OTHER WEED-REDUCING PRACTICES (SPAIN 1)

Sensitivity to discount rate

Project organisation	Low discount rate	Default discount rate	High discount rate
	2%	4%	6%
Benefits (present value)	984,814	799,984	661,215
Costs (present value)	2,623,664	2,206,676	1,886,448
Net Present Value (NPV)	-1,638,851	-1,406,692	-1,225,234
Benefit: Cost Ratio (unconstrained budget)	0.38	0.36	0.35

TABLE 270: SENSITIVITY TO DISCOUNT RATE - CEREAL WITH INTRODUCTION OF BRASSICAS AND OTHER WEED-REDUCING PRACTICES (SPAIN 1)

4.2.5.3 Weed control in vineyards with sheep (Spain3)

Main objective

The project aims to reduce herbicide use in vineyard management by introducing sheep grazing as a natural and sustainable method for weed control.

This case study presents a unique scenario that requires careful explanation. Without sufficient data from the interviews conducted, we are unable to accurately estimate the full range of costs and benefits associated with a sheep farming system that not only controls weeds but also produces other goods and services for the farm. Therefore, our analysis focus on a baseline where the sheep were already part of the farming system. We focus on evaluating the impact of utilizing these sheep for weed control as well, recognizing that our analysis cannot fully capture the broader economic and operational implications of integrating sheep into vineyard management. Although the analysis is limited, it adapts well to all those contexts where a mixed farming system predominates (for a definition of agroforestry system or mixed farming please refer to Püttsepp et al., 2020).

Description of the “before” scenario

In the scenario before the introduction of sheep for weed control in the vineyard, traditional methods were employed for maintaining the vineyard. Weed control involved multiple manual and mechanical processes throughout the year. In autumn, rows were cleaned manually using brushcutters, with a work capacity of 0.5 ha/hour. Additionally, chisels were used with a 90 hp 4x4 tractor for deeper soil preparation, covering 1 ha/hour. During winter, slope cleaning was performed manually using brushcutters (0.5 ha/hour), requiring 12 liters of fuel per hectare for the equipment. Herbicides were also applied in winter using a 90 hp tractor at 1 ha/hour, contributing to chemical input dependency. Similar operations were repeated in summer with additional manual weeding, brushcutting, and the use of a side mower for row cleaning, all supported by staff and machinery.

Description of the “after” scenario

After implementing the mulching with wood chips and herbs, the farm transitioned to a more sustainable approach. After introducing sheep for weed control, the vineyard management shifted to a more integrated approach. During winter, sheep provided by a neighboring farm were introduced to graze and manage weed growth naturally, reducing the reliance on mechanical methods and chemical inputs. Herbicide application was reduced but still performed in winter using a 90 hp 4x4 tractor (1 ha/hour, 15 liters/ha). Slope cleaning and row maintenance during summer continued using manual weeding (0.5 ha/hour) and mechanical methods with the tractor, maintaining work capacity but with reduced operational intensity. Sheep grazing introduced an eco-friendly and cost-effective alternative to traditional weed control methods, promoting sustainability in vineyard management.

Input data and farm characteristics

This case study pertains to a mixed farming system that specializes in viticulture, managing a total area of 130 hectares. According to the Horizon2020 Project AGROMIX D1.1 'Handbook of Resilience and Working Definitions', mixed farming refers to agricultural systems that integrate crops with livestock production on the same land, enhancing resource efficiency through synergistic interactions between the two components (Püttsepp et al., 2020). In this specific case, 20 hectares of the total area are dedicated to agricultural activities, with the focus exclusively on grapevine cultivation. The integration of sheep grazing within the vineyard serves to naturally control weed growth, exemplifying a mixed farming approach where livestock assists in managing crop areas, thereby optimizing the ecological sustainability of the vineyard. This system does not fit the traditional definition of agroforestry, which involves the integration of trees or shrubs with crops and/or livestock to form a layered or intermixed system that delivers additional ecological and economic benefits, such as enhanced biodiversity, soil protection, and water conservation.

<i>Management Type</i>	IPM
<i>Most important crops and animal productions</i>	Grape vine
<i>Total Farm Area (ha)</i>	130
<i>Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA, ha)</i>	20
<i>Experimental area (ha)</i>	20
<i>Experimental crop(s)</i>	Vine

TABLE 271: INPUT DATA AND FARM CHARACTERISTICS FROM WEED CONTROL IN VINEYARDS WITH SHEEP (SPAIN3)

The operating costs related to fuel show a significant benefit following the intervention. Initially, the annual fuel costs were 104.5 euros, but post-intervention, these costs have been reduced to zero for the years 2021 to 2041. This elimination of fuel expenses represents not just a reduction in operating costs but an operational advantage, contributing positively to the farm's overall financial efficiency.

<i>Operating costs (euros)</i>			
	Annual costs -Pre	Annual costs -Post	Year
<i>Fuel</i>	104.5	0	2018-2038

TABLE 272: OPERATING COSTS FROM WEED CONTROL IN VINEYARDS WITH SHEEP (SPAIN3)

The operating costs related to labour demonstrate a substantial reduction following the intervention. Initially, the annual labour costs amounted to 10,692 euros, but post-intervention, these costs have decreased to 2,916 euros annually for the period from 2021 to 2041. This considerable decrease in labour expenses not only reduces the operating costs but also enhances the financial efficiency of the operations over the two-decade period.

<i>Labour costs (euros)</i>			
	Annual costs - Pre	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Labour</i>	10,692	2,916	2018-2038

TABLE 273: LABOUR COSTS FROM WEED CONTROL IN VINEYARDS WITH SHEEP (SPAIN3)

Regarding other costs, transaction costs are 40.2 euros per hectare, so 804 euros related with the introduction of the new practice.

<i>Other costs (euros)</i>		
	Annual costs - Post	Year
<i>Transaction costs</i>	804	2018

TABLE 274: OTHER COSTS FROM WEED CONTROL IN VINEYARDS WITH SHEEP (SPAIN3)

It's appropriate to note that certain costs, not captured in our current analysis but prevalent in the literature, should be considered for a more comprehensive evaluation. These factors include the **management and operational costs** associated with the setup and maintenance of integrated sheep-vineyard systems, which often require significant initial investments in infrastructure such as fencing and water systems, along with ongoing labour for effective management (Garrett et al., 2017).

Increased seasonal costs and the potential for **crop damage**, particularly to younger vines, call for additional protective measures and could escalate costs substantially. Moreover, the **need for extensive infrastructure** is not only a considerable financial undertaking but also adds complexity to vineyard operations (Ryschawy et al., 2012).

Overgrazing risks and the **potential for disease transmission** between sheep and vines are crucial concerns that could negatively impact soil health and vine productivity. These challenges necessitate specialized skills in animal husbandry and integrated crop-livestock management, underscoring the importance of targeted training for vineyard workers (Franzluebbers et al., 2014).

Furthermore, integrating sheep into vineyards can lead to **increased management complexity**. Careful management is required to balance the timing and intensity of grazing to protect the vines and ensure animal

welfare. Additionally, the introduction of organic nitrogen sources through sheep manure might lead to **increased emissions of N₂O**, a potent greenhouse gas, necessitating effective management and mitigation strategies (Lazcano et al., 2022).

Cost-benefit identification

<i>Category</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Attribute</i>
Benefit per person or household	Improved Labour Environment	Reduction of workers' risk from exposure to phytosanitary products (public)	Qualitative
Benefit per unit of abatement	Reduced Chemical Use	By controlling weeds through grazing, the use of chemical herbicides is significantly reduced, which benefits local biodiversity and decreases the vineyard's environmental footprint.	Qualitative
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced nitrogen input	Reduction of nutrient loss	Mixed
Delay or reduction in cost	Reduced weed management cost (fuel and labour)	By grazing on weeds, sheep naturally manage weed growth, decreasing the need for frequent soil tillage.	159,268 euros – present value
Environmental sustainability	Enhanced Adaptability	Water Retention and Drought Resistance	Qualitative
Improve an environmental or community asset	Enhanced Soil Fertility	Sheep manure is a natural fertilizer, improving soil quality and fertility, which can reduce the need for synthetic fertilizers and enhance grape yield and quality.	Mixed
Improve an environmental or community asset	Improved Soil Health	The activity of sheep, combined with their manure, can improve soil structure and increase organic matter content, leading to better water retention and reduced erosion.	26,261 euros – present value
Sustainable Resource Management	Land Use Optimization	Increased soil structure and stability, increased organic matter	Qualitative
Reduced consequence of a risky event	Land conservation	The presence of sheep can enhance the aesthetic appeal of vineyards and offer unique marketing opportunities for wine producers.	Qualitative
Community resilience	Improving community health	Utilizing sheep for weed control can increase interest in local and sustainable farming practices. It may foster closer community ties and support for local products.	Qualitative
		By reducing the reliance on synthetic fertilizers and potentially decreasing the need for mechanical soil management, sheep grazing can lead to a lower carbon footprint of vineyard management. Managing sheep grazing operations can create local employment opportunities, particularly in rural areas.	
Total (monetary) benefits			159,268 euros

TABLE 275: IDENTIFIED BENEFITS FROM WEED CONTROL IN VINEYARDS WITH SHEEP (SPAIN3)

Integrating sheep into vineyards introduces a nuanced blend of benefits and challenges, supported by literature that emphasizes the practical implications for sustainable agriculture. The reduction in workers' exposure to harmful phytosanitary products enhances the labour environment, a benefit supported by Garrett et al. (2017), who discuss the health advantages of minimizing chemical use in farming practices. Similarly, sheep grazing naturally curtails the need for chemical herbicides, fostering local biodiversity and reducing the environmental footprint, aligning with Franzluebbers et al. (2014). This practice also diminishes nitrogen input and nutrient loss by substituting synthetic fertilizers with natural sheep manure, enhancing soil fertility as detailed by Lazcano et al. (2022). Additionally, sheep improve the adaptability of vineyards to climate variability by aiding soil moisture retention and enhancing drought resistance, a point highlighted by Brewer and Gaudin (2020). The physical presence of sheep contributes to soil health by increasing organic matter content and reducing erosion, which Ryschawy et al. (2012) identify as crucial for sustainable soil management. Beyond environmental impacts, sheep also enhance the aesthetic appeal of vineyards and create unique marketing opportunities, providing land conservation benefits and boosting eco-tourism as explored by Schoof et al. (2020). Lastly, the integration of sheep fosters community engagement in sustainable practices, strengthening local ties and supporting economic resilience in rural areas, as noted by Prokopy et al. (2008)

<i>Category</i>	<i>Cost item</i>	<i>Value (Euros)</i>	<i>Present Value (euros)</i>
<i>Other costs</i>	<i>Transaction costs</i>		<i>804</i>
<i>Total Costs</i>			<i>804 euros</i>

TABLE 276: IDENTIFIED COSTS FROM WEED CONTROL IN VINEYARDS WITH SHEEP (SPAIN3)

Economic analysis

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR (%)
20	7,923	198.09	-

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

Time duration (n. years)	NPV (Euros ha⁻¹)	BCR	MIRR
20	3,049.6	76.86	-100

TABLE 277: ECONOMIC ANALYSIS FROM WEED CONTROL IN VINEYARDS WITH SHEEP (SPAIN3)

In our analysis of integrating sheep into vineyards, the presented scenarios and corresponding data suggest a notably positive outlook. However, these results should be approached with caution as they might not be universally applicable across different contexts. The first scenario, featuring no risk of project failure and high adoption, yields an NPV of 7,923 euros per hectare and a remarkably high BCR, indicating substantial financial returns. Conversely, the second scenario, marked by low risk of project failure and low adoption, still shows positive results but with a significantly reduced NPV and BCR. These differences highlight the sensitivity of the project's success to factors such as adoption rates and operational efficiencies.

The economic models employed in our analysis, while suggesting potential economic viability, do not account for several critical factors that could impact the financial sustainability of such projects. For instance, the costs associated with increased management complexity, the need for specialized skills, and potential risks such as overgrazing or disease transmission, which are well-documented in the literature (e.g., Garrett et al., 2017; Franzluebbers et al., 2014), are not fully captured in the monetary evaluations. Moreover, while the integration of sheep can lead to reduced chemical use and enhanced soil health, these environmental and social benefits are difficult to quantify and were not directly included in the financial analysis.

Given the potential for increased greenhouse gas emissions from introducing additional organic nitrogen sources into the soil, as discussed by Lazcano et al. (2022), and the complex trade-offs between environmental benefits and economic costs, a more detailed analysis that includes these factors is warranted. Such an analysis would provide a more nuanced understanding of the long-term sustainability and practical feasibility of integrating sheep into vineyards. Therefore, while the initial financial projections

are encouraging, they should be interpreted with caution, keeping in mind that the actual outcomes could vary significantly based on regional conditions, specific management practices, and the extent of adoption.

First Scenario: No risk of project failure and high adoption

Second Scenario: Low risk of project failure and low level of adoption

FIGURE 22: GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF NET AND CUMULATIVE BENEFITS UNDER TWO SCENARIOS: NO RISK OF FAILURE WITH HIGH ADOPTION (TOP) AND LOW RISK OF FAILURE WITH LOW ADOPTION (BOTTOM)

The financial projections depicted in the charts for both scenarios—high and low adoption of integrating sheep into vineyards—show positive and continuous growth in Net Benefits and Cumulative Net Benefits over a 20-year period. These consistent upward trends suggest that, under both scenarios, the integration of sheep is expected to be economically beneficial. However, the rate of growth and overall financial gain are higher in the scenario with no risk of project failure and high adoption, indicating that higher adoption rates significantly enhance the economic returns of the project.

Social analysis

 Traffic light 72.84%	<p>The social analysis of integrating sheep into vineyards in Spain 3 reveals a robust social score of 72.84%, indicating a significantly positive perceived impact on several social dimensions, especially in areas like improved labour conditions and enhanced safety due to reduced chemical usage. This high score suggests that the integration practices are highly regarded for their benefits to worker health and safety, resonating with the broader goals of sustainable agriculture. However, while the positive impacts are notable, not all social aspects are equally benefited. The adoption of sheep integration has shown considerable advantages for occupational health but exhibits more moderate effects on broader specific factors such as job creation for women and inclusivity.</p>
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Social impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
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<i>The practice provides more stable income from year to year than alternatives</i>	0.59
<i>The current practice provides more flexibility for the agricultural management</i>	0.56
<i>New job opportunities in the rural area</i>	0.68
<i>Improvement of working conditions for the farm employers</i>	0.67
<i>Increased food safety</i>	0.50
<i>More job opportunities for women</i>	0.25
<i>Improving farmers' education and skills</i>	0.50
<i>Improved conditions for vulnerable groups</i>	0.15
<i>Improved aesthetics of the landscape and conservation of the cultural value</i>	0.60
<i>Improved social reputation of the farm</i>	0.60

TABLE 278: SOCIAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM WEED CONTROL IN VINEYARDS WITH SHEEP (SPAIN3)

The questionnaire responses indicate varied perceptions of the social impacts of sheep integration into vineyards. The scores suggest a moderate contribution to financial stability, with a 0.59 for more stable income, reflecting some economic resilience brought by this practice. However, the low scores for improving conditions for vulnerable groups (0.15) and job opportunities for women (0.25) highlight areas needing further enhancement. The highest impact perceived is on improving working conditions (0.67), emphasizing the practice's role in promoting better labour environments, consistent with literature by DeVetter et al. (2015) and Hostetler et al. (2007), who underscore the importance of safe and healthy work conditions in agricultural settings.

Social direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Improved labour environment	Bond and Grundy (2001); Neilsen et al. (2009)	Moderate	Short run	Qualitative
Reduced exposure to chemical	Weibel and Haseli (2003); Guerra and Steenwerth (2012)	High (due to reduced herbicide use)	Short-to-medium run	Qualitative
Increased job opportunities	Tahir et al. (2015)	High	Short-to-medium run	Qualitative

Social indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Improving community health	Merwin et al. (1994); TerAvest et al. (2010)	Moderate to high	Medium-to-long run	Qualitative
Enhancing biodiversity	Larsson (1997); Forge et al. (2003)	Moderate	Long term	Qualitative
Educational opportunities	Prokopy et al. (2008)	High	Long-term	Qualitative

TABLE 279: SOCIAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM WEED CONTROL IN VINEYARDS WITH SHEEP (SPAIN3)

Environmental analysis

	<p>The environmental score of 77.72% for the Spain 3 project, which integrates sheep into vineyards, reflects a strong appreciation for the ecological benefits of this practice. This high score underscores the project's effectiveness in enhancing biodiversity, improving soil health, and conserving resources. The recognition of these environmental benefits suggests that integrating sheep in vineyards is seen as a valuable practice for promoting sustainability within agricultural systems.</p>
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Traffic light 77.72%	
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Env. impact perceptions from questionnaire and related relevance (0 low to 1 high)

Impacts	Score
Contribute to reduce Direct greenhouse gas emissions	0.84
Contribute to reduce external inputs	0.2
Limit water consumption	0.8
Contribute to reduce waste	0.15
Has a positive impact on biodiversity	0.87
Has a positive impact on soil erosion	0.78
Has a positive impact on carbon footprint	0
Increase the rate of soil organic matter mineralisation	0.81
Increase soil compaction	0.81

TABLE 280: ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT PERCEPTIONS FROM QUESTIONNAIRE AND RELATED RELEVANCE (0 LOW TO 1 HIGH) FROM WEED CONTROL IN VINEYARDS WITH SHEEP (SPAIN3)

The questionnaire responses indicate a nuanced perspective on the environmental impacts of integrating sheep into vineyards. High scores for reducing greenhouse gas emissions (0.84) and limiting water consumption (0.80) highlight the perceived effectiveness of this practice in promoting sustainable agricultural methods. These benefits, including the reduction of external inputs and enhancement of the local ecosystem's health, are particularly valued in resource-limited settings. The impact on biodiversity is notably recognized, with a score of 0.87, suggesting that the presence of sheep supports a diverse range of soil organisms, thereby enhancing overall ecosystem health. Additionally, the control of soil erosion is well-regarded (score of 0.78), indicating the practice's role in maintaining soil integrity. However, the minimal score for improving the carbon footprint (0.00) signals a gap in perception regarding the broader climate benefits of this integration.

Env. direct impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Reduced Herbicide Use	Wheeler et al., 2005	High	Short tun	Quantitative
Improved Soil Health (General)	General literature on grazing soil health	Moderate	Long-term	Qualitative
Enhanced Soil Health (Specific)	Lazcano et al., 2022	High	Long-term	Qualitative
Reduction in CO2 emissions	Schütte (2019)	Moderate	Long-term	Quantitative

Env. indirect impact from project adoption

Identified impacts	Source	Analysed impact	Timeframe	Type
Improved Biodiversity	-	High	Long-term	Qualitative
Enhancement in Soil Health and Biodiversity	Franzluebbbers (2005), Brewer and Gaudin (2020)	High	Long-term	Qualitative
Improvement in Soil Health and Reduction in Chemical Inputs	Allen et al., 2012	High	Long-term	Quantitative

Improved Soil Health	Ryschawy et al. (2012), Lazcano et al. (2021)	High	Long-term	Qualitative
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TABLE 281: ENVIRONMENTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT IMPACT FROM PROJECT ADOPTION FROM WEED CONTROL IN VINEYARDS WITH SHEEP (SPAIN3)

Sensitivity analysis

The sensitivity analysis of integrating sheep into vineyards shows a markedly positive financial outlook across all considered scenarios. In the default case, the NPV stands at 7,932 euros, with a mean NPV of 7,306 euros per hectare, and the analysis consistently indicates a 100% probability of achieving positive NPV. This overwhelming likelihood of positive returns is further bolstered by the BCR figures, which range from a minimum of 62.22 to a maximum of 306.57, with the default case showing a BCR of 198.09. Every scenario within the BCR analysis also shows a 100% probability of exceeding a BCR of 1, suggesting that the benefits substantially outweigh the costs.

Monte Carlo simulations, used to test the robustness of these results under varying conditions, support the initial findings, displaying a concentration of NPV outcomes primarily in the higher value ranges, indicating strong financial performance consistently above the break-even point. This robustness is evident as 41% of the scenarios predict an NPV between 155K to 181K euros, and 20% foresee it extending up to 206K euros. Regarding the BCR, the distribution analysis showcases a significant concentration in the higher efficacy brackets, further demonstrating financial viability. About 33% of the BCR values fall between 159.96 to 208.83, illustrating a strong return on investment. This comprehensive positive financial projection suggests a highly beneficial economic impact of sheep integration into vineyards, yet this overly favourable outcome requires careful scrutiny.

While the economic indicators are promising, it is crucial to approach these results with caution. The uniformly positive financial projections might not fully account for potential variations in operational realities, such as fluctuations in market conditions, potential increases in management complexity, or unforeseen environmental impacts that could affect long-term sustainability. Therefore, a deeper analysis incorporating a broader range of economic, environmental, and social factors, as discussed in the literature, would provide a more nuanced understanding of the project's viability and help validate these optimistic projections against real-world variables and potential risks.

Net Present Value (NPV)	Tot. Euros	Euros ha ⁻¹
Minimum	76,996	3,849
Maximum	206,485	10,324.25
Default case	158,464	7,923.2
Mean	146,122	7,306.1
Median	157,738	7,886.9
Probability that NPV > 0		1.00
Distribution (euros)	Probability	
Less than 77K	0.00	
77K to 103K	0.05	
103K to 129K	0.30	
129K to 155K	0.05	
155K to 181K	0.41	
181K to 206K	0.20	
	Total	1.00
Benefit: Cost Ratio (BCR)	Unconstrained version	
Minimum	62.22	
Maximum	306.57	
Default case	198.09	

Mean	162.31
Median	164.50
Probability that BCR > 1	1.00
Target BCR	2
Probability BCR > Target	1.00
Distribution	Probability
Less than 62.22	0.00
62.22 to 111.09	0.10
111.09 to 159.96	0.31
159.96 to 208.83	0.33
208.83 to 257.70	0.22
257.70 to 306.57	0.04
Total	1.00

TABLE 282: BCA ROBUSTNESS (MONTE CARLO ANALYSIS BASED ON 1000 RANDOM SIMULATIONS) - WEED CONTROL IN VINEYARDS WITH SHEEP (SPAIN3)

Sensitivity to discount rate

Project organisation	Low discount rate	Default discount rate	High discount rate
	2%	4%	6%
Benefits (present value)	196,065	159,268	131,640
Costs (present value)	804	804	804
Net Present Value (NPV)	195,261	158,464	130,836
Benefit: Cost Ratio	243.86	198.09	163.73
(unconstrained budget)			

TABLE 283: SENSITIVITY TO DISCOUNT RATE - WEED CONTROL IN VINEYARDS WITH SHEEP (SPAIN3)

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Annex 1: Questionnaire for CBA

FOR THE INTERVIEWER:

The survey in question is specifically designed for farm, the interviewee should be the person in charge of running the farm, therefore the farm owner or manager. When necessitating a collaborative completion approach whereby at least one research partner assists an agricultural firm in filling out the questionnaire. In instances where the aim is to interview a collection of farms that are part of an operational group, the protocol requires the engagement of a group leader to conduct the interview. The leader is tasked with gathering data and insights from the most advanced or representative farm within the group. This methodological approach aligns with established literature on innovation, which often identifies an 'early adopter' within a group that paves the way for subsequent entities to follow suit. While it is acknowledged that early adopters may incur higher initial costs, this phenomenon is consistent with the broader observation that isolated enterprises typically face similar challenges. This strategy not only facilitates a focused understanding of innovative practices within agricultural groups but also mirrors the diffusion of innovation process as documented in academic research, where pioneering entities often lead the adoption curve, setting a precedent for others within their sector.

All information should refer to the years of implementation of the innovative weed management practice, depending on the different specific conditions. In case selected farmer has no data back to the year of implementation it should report on the average of their yearly production in the last five years.

READ OUT TO THE FARMER BEFORE STARTING:

Thank you for agreeing to be part of this survey, your answers will be treated confidentially and anonymously. We will start with a few questions about your farm business.

Interviewer data

Name and Surname: _____

Organization: _____

Interview data: _____

Time of completion: _____

Respondent data

Company Name: _____

Your role in the farm: _____ (owner, manager...)

Innovative practice: _____

Year of introduction of the practice: _____

Localization: _____ (Region, Country)

Contact person: _____ (Name, Surname, Mail)

Section A – Economic

FOR THE INTERVIEWER

The survey targets farm, requiring collaboration with research partners for completion. Group interviews involve a leader representing the most advanced farm. This aligns with innovation literature, highlighting 'early adopters' and reflecting the diffusion of innovation in agriculture.

The survey focuses on the period around the introduction of an agricultural innovation, delineating a 'before' and 'after' to assess change. This reference period varies, considering the time needed for the innovation to be introduced and mature.

We do not define a specific time interval a priori but ask the respondent to reflect on the situation before and after the introduction of the practice, referring in this case to the year in which the practice was fully implemented at the farm level.

When it comes to processes and materials directly linked to the land, our focus is specifically on the hectares where innovation or changes in practices have taken place. Respondents are urged to direct their attention solely to these specified areas, rather than examining the whole agricultural area.

Please note: questions marked with * must be completed

QA1- Business Management

QA1_1) Indicate the cultivation management of the farm: *

- Conventional
- IPM-based
- Organic (total farm area)
- Organic (partial)
- Other: _____

QA1_2) Indicates the type of production of the company *

- Crop(s)
- Animal(s)
- Mixed

Indicate the most important crops and animal productions of the farm:

QA1_3) Indicate the total farm area (FA) of the holding: ____ ha

QA1_4) Indicate the utilised agricultural area (UAA) of the holding: ____ ha *

QA2- Innovative Practice

QA2_1) Please indicate which share of your operating land is covered by the innovative practice or in which the practice was tested: ____ ha *

QA2_2) Indicate the main management of the operating land: *

- Conventional
- IPM-based
- Organic
- Other: _____

QA2_3) On which crop(s) the farmer is implementing the innovative solution? *

- Crop 1: _____
- Crop 2: _____
- Crop 3: _____
- Crop 4: _____
- ...

QA2_4) Does the company receive economic support (payment) from rural development measures, CAP subsidies, etc.? Y/N. If yes list them below *

Remember to include only payments linked to the field, and thus the crop, where the innovative practice was tested.

Support before the introduction of the practice	
#	Description of the type of support
1	

QA2_5) Does the introduction of the innovative practice entail a change in these payments (risk of losing them or possibility of accessing new CAP subsidies, e.g. ecosystems or RDP measures)? YES/NO *

QA2_5_a) If **yes**, specify the support lost or added after the introduction of the practice (payments received under the Basic Payment Schemes, Amount of payments received under the Countryside Stewardship, others, etc.).

Change in the payments			
Payments added		Payments lost	
#	Description of the type of support	#	Description of the type of support
1		1	
2		2	

FOR THE INTERVIEWER:

The next question will have to be filled in by the interviewer, in case the information is not available to the company. The source from which to obtain the data are the CAP national action plans of each state.

QA2_6) If there is a change, how much did the farm receive on average in a year per ha before. And how much did the farm receive on average in a year per ha after the introduction of the practice? *

Before: ____ Euros.

After: ____ Euros.

QA3 – Workflow

FOR THE INTERVIEWER

To perform a proper cost-benefit analysis, it is crucial to understand precisely the variations in cultivation operations (via the workflow) and in the quantities and types of technical means used (by answering the next section).

You may complete the section below with the information at your disposal, or you can use the PowerPoint guide for developing the diagram of relevant processes attached to the questionnaire together with the interviewee, as specified in the analysis strategy section of the questionnaire guide.

*To identify the relevant processes, it's crucial to consider the crop operations that were implemented before introducing the innovative weed control practice (before) and thus all operations relevant to that production, as well as the production following the introduction of innovative practices and all associated practices. **From before to after, it's advisable to highlight the practices that have changed to avoid double counting.***

QA3_1) Indicate here **all** the operations (step-by-step) **before** and **after** the introduction of the innovative practice (starting from the operations indicated in the graphics workflow). Then highlight which steps have changed between before and after.*

Main processes BEFORE the practice are introduced	Machinery used	Work capacity (ha/hour) – (where applicable)	Type of resources involved	Task performed
e.g., under-row mechanical weeding	4WD Tractor 90 HP + ventral disc		None	Weed control
e.g., fertilisation	4WD Tractor 65 HP + 1 disc fertiliser sprayer		1 t/ha pelleted manure (3-3-3 N-P2O5-K2O)	Fertilisation
Main processes AFTER the practice are introduced	Machinery used		Type of resources involved	Task performed

QA4- Investment costs

FOR THE INTERVIEWER

It includes the capital costs of all fixed assets (e.g. land, construction and buildings, plant and machinery, equipment, etc.) and non-fixed assets (e.g. technical and start-up costs such as design/planning, technical assistance and project management, construction management, advertising, etc.).

Fixed investments in agriculture refer to the long-term expenditures on physical assets that are not consumed or converted into cash during the normal production cycle of a farm. These assets are essential for the establishment, expansion, or improvement of the agricultural enterprise and have a useful life extending beyond one year. In terms of cost, fixed investments represent capital outlays that are recorded on the balance sheet of the farm rather than being expensed immediately. These costs are typically amortized or depreciated over the useful life of the asset, reflecting the gradual wear and tear or obsolescence of the asset over time.

Examples of fixed investments in agriculture include:

Buildings and Facilities: Constructing or acquiring storage facilities, barns, greenhouses, and processing units.

Machinery and Equipment: Buying tractors, harvesters, irrigation systems, and other mechanized tools essential for modern farming practices.

Perennial Crops: Investing in long-term crops like orchards and vineyards, which require several years to mature and yield produce.

Infrastructure Improvements: Developing irrigation systems, drainage systems, and roads within the farm. *In theory, reference is made to all cost items related to the assets required to develop the processes highlighted in QA3_1.*

QA4_1) Indicate which of the following investment costs are required for the introduction of innovation: *

- Technical consulting
- Additional buildings
- Fixed installations
- Machines & Tools

QA4_2) Technical consulting necessary for the introduction and/or management of the innovative practice. Indicate the costs in euros per year:

Description	Value in euros per year	Nr. of years for which the consultancy was necessary

If you have to indicate a single consultancy, e.g. for the introduction of the practice, write NA in the years column.

QA4_4) Buildings required for the introduction of innovation. Indicate the costs in euros:

For example, if a warehouse had to be rented for a new machine introduced to the farm with the practice.

Description	Owned, rented-in	Year of purchase/Rent	Cost to new (€)/ Rent cost per year	Estimated total duration (in case of purchase, in years)

QA4_5) Fixed installations required for the introduction of innovation. Indicate the costs in euros:

Some examples: installation of GPS antennas for precision farming systems, telecommunications equipment...

Description	Year of purchase	Cost to new (€)	Estimated total duration (in years)

QA4_6) Machines & Tools required for the introduction of innovation (thus, not used before the introduction of the innovative practice). Indicate the costs in euros:

Description	Year of purchase	Cost to new (€)	Estimated total duration (in years)

QA5- Revenue and operating expenses

FOR THE INTERVIEWER

Operating costs include all Operation and Maintenance (O&M) costs related to the implemented alternative solution. These typically include: labour costs, materials related to the maintenance and repair of plant and machinery, raw materials, energy, consumables, services purchased from third parties, rental of buildings/premises, rental of machinery and equipment, administration fees, insurance, quality control, waste disposal costs and emission taxes (including environmental taxes, when applicable). These costs are generally divided into fixed costs (when they do not vary with the volume of goods/services supplied) and variable costs (related to the volume of goods/services supplied).

QA5a- Raw materials

FOR THE INTERVIEWER

In this context, we are referring to a broad range of resources and inputs essential for agricultural production. This includes water, which is vital for irrigation; soil improvers, which enhance the physical and chemical properties of the soil; fertilizers, which provide necessary nutrients to the crops; electricity, which powers various farming operations; fuel, which is required for running agricultural machinery and equipment; and various consumables, which encompass a wide array of items used in day-to-day farming activities. These raw materials are fundamental components in the agricultural process, contributing to the cultivation, growth, and harvesting of crops.

To clarify further, the focus of the survey is specifically on the hectares of land where innovation or a change in practices has occurred. Respondents are requested to concentrate solely on these designated areas, rather than considering the entire expanse of the agricultural enterprise.

QA5a_1) Starting from the workflow, after the introduction of the practice, was there a change in the raw materials needed in the entire workflow? *

- Yes, an increase
- Yes, a decrease
- No, they have not changed

QA5a_2) BEFORE. Cost of raw materials. Indicate the costs in euros: *

Category*	Description	UM	Value in euros (per UM)

*Select categories from the following: Fertilisers, Agrochemicals, Seeds and seedlings, Water, Amendments, Other.

QA5a_3) AFTER. Cost of raw materials. Indicate the costs in euros: *

Category*	Description	UM	Value in euros (per UM)

*Select categories from the following: Fertilisers, Agrochemicals, Seeds and seedlings, Water, Amendments, Other.

QA5b – Maintenance expenditures for fixed installations and machinery

QA5b_1) Starting from the workflow, after the introduction of the practice, has there been a change in the maintenance and material expenses for the repair of plants and machines in the entire workflow? *

- Yes, an increase
- Yes, a decrease
- No, they have not changed

QA5b_2) IF YES. BEFORE. Maintenance fees. Indicate the costs in euros:

Description	Value in euros per year (€)

QA5b_3) IF YES. AFTER. Maintenance fees. Indicate the costs in euros:

Description	Value in euros per year (€)

QA5c- Labour costs

QA5c_1) Starting from the workflow after the introduction of the practice, was there a change in the overall labour hours? *

- Yes, an increase
- Yes, a decrease
- No, they have not changed

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Please note. Indicate any changes even if the cost or total hours are unchanged (e.g. if the category of workers has changed but not the total hours or total cost).

QA5c_2) IF YES. BEFORE. Labor costs. Indicate hourly costs in euros:

Category	Hourly cost (€)	Total hours (in a full workflow cycle)

*Select categories from the following: temporary/permanent, part-time/full time, annual/seasonal

QA5c_3) IF YES. AFTER. Labor costs. Indicate hourly costs in euros:

Category	Hourly cost (€)	Total hours (in a full workflow cycle)

*Select categories from the following: temporary/permanent, part-time/full time, annual/seasonal

[QA5d- Services purchased from third parties](#)

QA5d_1) Was it necessary to purchase services from third parties in order to introduce the practice? *

- Yes
- No

QA5d_2_a) IF YES. BEFORE. Cost of services. Indicate the costs in euros:

Description	Value in euros per year (€)

QA5d_2_b) IF YES. AFTER. Cost of services. Indicate the costs in euros:

Description	Value in euros per year (€)

[QA5e- Rental of buildings](#)

QA5e_1) Was it necessary to enter into new rental contracts in order to introduce the practice? *

- Yes
- No

QA5e_2) IF YES. Rental costs. Indicate the annual cost in euros:

Description	Annual value in euro (€)

[QA5f- Rental of machinery and equipment](#)

QA5f_1) Was it necessary to rent machines and/or systems to introduce the practice? *

- Yes
- No

QA5f_2) **IF YES.** Rental costs. Indicate the annual cost in euros:

Description	Annual value in euro (€)

QA5g- Administration fees

QA5g_1) Starting from the workflow, after the introduction of the practice, was there a change in administration expenses in the entire workflow? *

- Yes
- No

QA5g_2) **IF YES.** BEFORE. Administration fees. Indicate hourly costs in euros:

Description	Hourly cost (€)	Total hours per year

QA5g_3) **IF YES.** AFTER. Administration fees. Indicate hourly costs in euros:

Description	Hourly cost (€)	Total hours per year

QA5h- Insurance costs

QA5h_1) Starting from the workflow, after the introduction of the practice, was there a change in insurance costs in the entire workflow? *

- Yes, an increase
- Yes, a decrease
- No, they have not changed

QA5h_2) **IF YES.** BEFORE. Insurance costs. Indicate annual costs in euros:

Description	Value in euros per year (€)

QA5h_3) IF YES. AFTER. Insurance costs. Indicate annual costs in euros:

Description	Value in euros per year (€)

QA5i- Certification fees

QA5i_1) Starting from the workflow, after the introduction of the practice, was there a change in certification fees in the entire workflow? *

- Yes, an increase
- Yes, a decrease
- No, they have not changed

QA5i_2) IF YES. BEFORE. Certification fees. Indicate annual costs in euros:

Description	Value in euros per year (€)

QA5i_3) IF YES. AFTER. Certification fees. Indicate annual costs in euros:

Description	Value in euros per year (€)

QA5I – Non-renewable/hazardous waste disposal costs

QA5I_1) Starting from the workflow, after the introduction of the practice, has there been a change in waste disposal costs in the entire workflow? *

- Yes
- No

QA5I_2) IF YES. BEFORE. Waste disposal costs. Indicate annual costs in euros:

Category*	Description	Amount of the waste (kg)	Disposal cost (€)

*Select categories from the following: Organic waste, Packaging materials, Empty fertilizer and agrochemicals containers, Hazardous waste, Maintenance waste (waste oils, oil filters, old tyres), Covering material, Electronic waste, Clothing and protective equipment waste, Other.

QA5I_3) IF YES. AFTER. Waste disposal costs. Indicate annual costs in euros:

Category*	Description	Amount of the waste (kg)	Disposal cost (€)

*Select categories from the following: Organic waste, Packaging materials, Empty fertilizer and agrochemicals containers, Hazardous waste, Maintenance waste (waste oils, oil filters, old tyres), Covering material, Electronic waste, Clothing and protective equipment waste, Other.

QA5m- Crop production

QA5m_1) Indicate the average value of the realized production BEFORE (average value of the last 5 years before the introduction of the practice) *

Product	Tonnes f.w. per hectare

QA5m_2) Has the introduction of innovation led to an increase or decrease in crop production? *

- Yes, an increase
- Yes, a decrease
- No, they have not changed

Q A5m_2_a) If yes, indicate the value of the realized production AFTER (average value from the introduction of the practice to today)

Product	Tonnes f.w. per hectare

QA5m_3) Destination of crop production (%) *

For this section, think of the crop(s) involved by the innovative practice.

Then indicate the average percentage of destination of these crop(s) on the whole farm in the last 5 years

Destination	%
Marketed as raw material	
On farm processing	
Self-consumption	

Reuse for seeds	
Reuse for livestock feed	
Product not sold	
Other: specify_____	

QA5m_4) Value of crop production *

Please also indicate the average price (in EUR) of the product produced, processed... Choose the most appropriate unit of measurement (€/kg; €/t...). The price must be derived from the average of the last five years before the introduction of the innovative practice

Destination	Product(s)	UM	Value (UM/€)
Marketed as raw material			
On farm processing			
Other: specify_____			

Q A5m_5) Has the average price of products changed due to the introduction of the practice? Y/N *

QA5m_5_a) If yes. Indicate any reasons for the change in the average price of products

- Increased produce quality
- Introduction of new certifications
- Stipulation of new supply chain contracts
- Other : ...

QA5m_5_b) If yes. Indicate average price for the product realized and sold (only if the change in practice involved a change in quality, or other aspects, and thus in price):

Destination	Product(s)	UM	Value (UM/€)	Average % of product sold each year
Marketed as raw material				
On farm processing				
Other: specify_____				

QA5m_6) If some productions of the experimental field are certified, please indicate the type of certification below (organic, IPM-based, other): *

Product	Certification	Still certified after the introduction of the practice? Y/N

Section B – Social

QB1_1) Does any (at least one) member of the household or managers have a formal education in agriculture or related subjects? (e.g. agronomy, animal production, veterinary medicine (farm animals), forestry)

- Yes
- No

QB1_2) How many members of your household are working in the agricultural holding (including yourself)?

	Please indicate the number
Full time	
Part-time	
Seasonal	
Others	

QB1_3) How many workers does the holding have?

	Please indicate the number
Nr. of full-time external workers	
Nr. of part-time and other external workers	
Nr. of seasonal workers	

QB1_4) Would you define the legal status of the farm holding:

- Single owner
- Co-owner together with a spouse
- Co-owner as a member of joint ownership (private partnership)
- Co-owner as a member of limited liability company
- Other, please specify _____
- Does not answer/Does not want to answer

QB1_5) What is your age?

- 18-20

- 21-30
- 31-40
- 41-50
- 51-60
- 61-70
- 71-80
- More than 80
- Prefer not to say

QB1_6) Thinking about the future, do you already have an idea about the holding successor (after the current owner)?

- Yes, a successor in the holding family
- Yes, a successor not in the holding family
- Not decided yet/never thought about it
- Does not answer/Does not want to answer

QB1_7) What percentage of your total household gross revenue comes from farming (on average)?

- 0%
- 10-29%
- 30-49%
- 50-69%
- 70-89%
- >90%

QB1_8) Is the holding regularly assisted by an advisory/extension service

- Yes, with a specific environmental-related focus
- Yes, generical technical advisory/extension service for crops related activities
- Yes, generical technical advisory/extension service for livestock related activities
- Yes, generical technical advisory/extension service for trees/forestry related activities
- No

QB1_9) New job opportunities in the rural area (where the farm is settled)? Yes/no.

If yes:	
How many positions?	
What type of work (operations performed)?	
What type of contract (full-time, part-time)?	
What is the average expected wage level?	

QB1_10) Improved working conditions for workers compared to previous practice

If yes, please specify:	
How?	

For which employers (e.g. reduced exposure to agrochemicals or harsh weather factors)?	
--	--

QB1_11) Increased food safety (less pollutants/contaminants in the crop/animal produce)

If yes, please specify:	
In which terms?	
For which products?	

QB1_12) More job opportunities for women

If available, please specify the increase in the gender ratio of the employers after the introduction of the practice	
Number of male	
Number of female	

QB1_13) Improving farmers' education and skills

If yes, please specify how many hours of training does the new practices required?	
Number of training days	
Number of hours per day	

QB1_14) Improved conditions for vulnerable groups (e.g. minorities and migrants)

If yes, please specify the new type of contract offered and if available the % of salary increment	
Type of contract	
% of salary increase on average salary	

QB1_15) Please rate from 1 to 5 how much do you agree with the following statements regarding the introduction of the new practice.	disagree (1)	Somewhat disagree (2)	Neutral (3)	Somewhat agree (4)	Agree (5)	Prefer not to say (6)
I do not have alternative options	0	0	0	0	0	0
The current practice provides an acceptable cost/benefit ratio	0	0	0	0	0	0
The practice provides more stable income from year to year than alternatives	0	0	0	0	0	0
The current practice provides more flexibility for the agricultural management	0	0	0	0	0	0

New job opportunities in the rural area	0	0	0	0	0	0
Improvement of working conditions for the farm employers	0	0	0	0	0	0
Increased food safety	0	0	0	0	0	0
More job opportunities for women	0	0	0	0	0	0
Improving farmers' education and skills	0	0	0	0	0	0
Improved conditions for vulnerable groups	0	0	0	0	0	0
Improved aesthetics of the landscape and conservation of the cultural value	0	0	0	0	0	0
Improved social reputation of the farm	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other, please specify (10)	0	0	0	0	0	0

Section C – Environmental

FOR THE INTERVIEWER

As outlined in the analysis strategy, it is first necessary to thoroughly explain the relevant processes before and after the introduction of the practice, as mentioned in the previous section on workflow or by completing the attached PowerPoint diagram. Analyzing these processes enables the understanding of the main direct and indirect impacts on resources and environmental components affected by agricultural management. This approach helps to identify how the introduction of a new practice alters the use of resources, such as water, soil, and energy, and its effects on the environment, including biodiversity, soil health, and water quality. By comparing the processes before and after the practice implementation, it's possible to gauge the efficiency, sustainability, and environmental benefits or drawbacks of the new methods in the context of agricultural management.

Building on the data previously collected in this section, our aim is to highlight the potential main impacts and derive some insights about them. The insights gained will be instrumental in understanding the broader environmental implications of these practices.

QC1_1 Direct greenhouse gas emissions (CH₄, CO₂, N₂O) – tonnes of CO₂-equivalents will be estimated based on field operations and GHG conversion rates. Only fill in the table if this data has not already been indicated in the workflow section. Indicate all operations necessary for a complete workflow before and after.

Before		
Mechanical operation performed	Type of Machine	Work capacity (ha/hour)

After		
Mechanical operation performed	Type of Machine	Work capacity (ha/hour)

QC1_2) External inputs

Does the AFTER management lead to using additional external inputs (such as fertilizers, pesticides) compared to the BEFORE, thus increasing the risk of groundwater pollution?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

If yes, please specify the following:

- Which is the period most prone to leaching risk in your region (e.g., September to March)?
_____ - _____ [*]
- Amount of N fertilisers that are applied in addition to the BEFORE situation in the period of the year with the highest risk of leaching (see *): _____ [kg N ha⁻¹]. If AFTER less fertilisers are applied compared to the BEFORE situation, please add a negative sign.
- Amount of P fertilisers that are applied in addition to the BEFORE situation in the period of the year with the highest risk of erosion (see *): _____ [kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹]. If AFTER less fertilisers are applied compared to the BEFORE situation, please add a negative sign.
- Amount of pesticides that are applied in addition to the BEFORE situation in the entire year:
 - Fungicides _____ [g/l a.i. ha⁻¹]. If AFTER less fungicides are applied compared to the BEFORE situation, please add a negative sign.
 - Insecticides _____ [g/l a.i. ha⁻¹]. If AFTER less insecticides are applied compared to the BEFORE situation, please add a negative sign.
 - Herbicides _____ [g/l a.i. ha⁻¹]. If AFTER less herbicides are applied compared to the BEFORE situation, please add a negative sign.

QC1_3) Impact on water

Does the introduction of the practice lead to a change in water consumption? (indicate to what %)

Yes to an increase of amount % ___/ Yes to a decrease of amount % ___/ No.

If available indicate the average value for water consumption and the relative cost:

QC1_4) Impact on soil

- Soil erosion
 - Does the practice lead to bare (tilled, uncovered) soil during the period of the year with the highest risk of erosion (see *)?

- Yes
 - No
- Soil organic matter content
 - Does the practice reduce, respect to the BEFORE situation, the total amount of C inputs (e.g., manure, green manures, organic fertilisers) to the soil?
 - Yes
 - No
 - Does the practice increase, respect to the BEFORE situation, the rate of soil organic matter mineralisation (e.g., by increasing tillage frequency/depth from spring to fall)?
 - Yes
 - No
 - Likely yes
 - Likely no
 - I don't know
- Soil compaction
 - Does the practice increase, respect to the BEFORE situation, soil compaction (e.g., by increasing number of mechanical operations, especially in bare soil and wet conditions)?
 - Yes
 - No
 - Likely yes
 - Likely no
 - I don't know

QC1_5) Waste

Does the practice increase, respect to the BEFORE situation, non-recyclable waste and scrap for disposal?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

If yes, please specify the type and amount of waste/scrap.

QC1_6) Impact on biodiversity

Does the practice, compared to the BEFORE situation, increase the level of planned biodiversity (e.g., number of different cash and subsidiary crop species/cultivars grown in the farm, number of different animal species/breeds grown in the farm)?

- Yes
- No

If yes, please indicate which new species/cultivars/breeds are introduced

QC1_7) Please rate from 1 to 5 how much do you agree with the following statements regarding the introduction of the new practice.	disagree (1)	Somewhat disagree (2)	Neutral (3)	Somewhat agree (4)	Agree (5)	Prefer not to say (6)
Contribute to reduce Direct greenhouse gas emissions	0	0	0	0	0	0

Contribute to reduce external inputs	0	0	0	0	0	0
Limit water consumption	0	0	0	0	0	0
Contribute to reduce waste	0	0	0	0	0	0
Has a positive impact on biodiversity	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other, please specify (10)	0	0	0	0	0	0

QC1_8) Does innovative practice have potential for improvement? Y/N. If yes justify.
